

**An Exploration of Algerian English Language Teachers' and Learners'
Perspectives and Conceptions of Intercultural Communicative Competence: A
Case Study of Two Universities in Algeria.**

NAWAL OUCHENE

A thesis submitted In Partial Fulfilment for the Degree of Doctor of Philosophy

School of Education and Social Sciences

University of the West of Scotland

October 2023

Declaration

I, Nawal Ouchene, hereby declare and confirm that this thesis entitled, An Exploration of Algerian English Language Teachers' and Learners' Perspectives and Conceptions of Intercultural Communicative Competence: A Case Study of Two Universities in Algeria, is my own original work, except for citations and quotations which have been clearly stated and acknowledged. I also confirm that this work has not been previously submitted or presented for any other degree or qualification at the University of the West of Scotland, or any other institution.

Name: Nawal Ouchene

Date: 04th October 2023

Dedication

I wholeheartedly dedicate this thesis to:

The memory of my best and beloved friend, Khawla Keziz, who passed away before completing her PhD thesis. This work is for you. You forever live in my heart.

My precious husband, Mohammed, who has been the source of love, support, encouragement and patience for me throughout the entire journey. Your constant belief in me has strengthened my determination and inspired me to go beyond my limits.

My beloved family, my parents and siblings, whose unwavering support, love and prayers have been the source of inspiration and strength when my confidence waned. Thank you for your unconditional love.

My grandparents who have been my guiding stars, through their constant prayers and unconditional blessings. You instilled in me compassion and empathy.

My beloved nephew and nieces

My beloved in-laws

Acknowledgement

I start this acknowledgement with a profound gratitude to Allah, The Almighty, for His abundant blessings, guidance and strength that have carried me through this tough journey.

I want to express my gratitude to the Algerian Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research for funding my doctoral program. Their financial assistance has made it possible for me to pursue my PhD research in the UK, a dream that would not have been achievable without their support.

I also would like to thank my supervisory team Dr. Beth Cross and Dr. Catriona Oaks for their endless support and for their constructive feedback. A special thanks goes to Beth for her unwavering guidance, enduring patience and valuable feedback throughout my PhD journey. I also appreciate her understanding and flexibility in accommodating my personal circumstances. Without Beth's insightful feedback and constructive criticism, I would not have reached this point.

I want to convey my gratitude to all the participants who contributed to this study. Your willingness to share your perspectives, experiences and insights was invaluable and made this research possible.

Finally, I would like to express my genuine appreciation to my best friends, Hanan, Afaf, Amina, and Hadjer who shared this challenging and enriching international experience with me. Our shared experiences, sleepless nights, thoughtful discussions and unwavering support, especially during strange times of COVID-19, have been invaluable part of my journey. Your presence has made this journey more enriching and enjoyable.

Abstract

This study follows a constructivist approach to explore Algerian English language teachers' and learners' perspectives and conceptions of the notions of culture and intercultural communicative competence (ICC). It also endeavours to investigate participants' intercultural exposures and how these experiences influenced their ICC teaching practices in two universities chosen for this study referred to hereafter as East University and West University. The current body of literature on intercultural communication acknowledges the pressing requirement for a transformation in foreign language education. This shift entails moving away from the conventional teaching approaches, which emphasise the development of learners' communicative competence, to the integration of an intercultural approach. However, there is a noticeable gap in research in the MENA contexts, particularly Algeria, where the transition to an 'intercultural turn' remains unexplored.

To answer the four research questions of this study, I have conducted an exploratory mixed research approach, which involved both qualitative and quantitative methods. Semi-structured interviews were carried out with ten (n10) Algerian English language teachers to investigate their perspectives of culture and ICC and how their intercultural exposures influenced their teaching practices. Online questionnaires and focus group discussions were conducted with English language learners to investigate their English language learning experience as well as to explore their understanding of ICC. Two further interviews were conducted with members of the intercultural club that students took the initiative to create at West University. This club is called 'The Global Representatives of Culture' (The GRC). It aims to promote cultural diversity and intercultural awareness among learners. The empirical findings revealed that teachers and learners, from East University, conceptions and ways of teaching culture were mostly essentialist and nationalist, based on a communicative competence approach, which strives to make learners able to effectively communicate with native speakers of English. Therefore, their understanding of ICC was limited. However, teachers and learners, from West University, attitudes towards culture and ICC were shifted to an 'intercultural turn'. They frequently referred to the "five savoirs" to express their perspectives. They demonstrated that the primary objective of teaching English as a foreign language is to promote learners' intercultural awareness.

The findings also showed that members of the GRC shared positive attitudes about their experience of learning ICC at West University, and how this fostered their willingness and determination to create an open space for learners to interact, share experiences, and promote mutual understanding and respect. This initiative also sought to promote inclusivity and diversity among learners and to prepare them to act as citizens of the world.

Finally, this research aims to contribute to knowledge by raising teachers' and learners' awareness about the significance of integrating and developing ICC in language education in Algeria. It also provides valuable insights and practical implications to Algerian policy-makers to prioritise the teaching of ICC as a mandatory subject in Algerian Higher Education. Furthermore, it advocates for the importance of offering educators training that addresses ICC.

Table of Contents

Declaration	2
Dedication	3
Acknowledgement	4
Abstract	5
List of Tables	11
List of Figures	12
List of Abbreviations	13
Chapter One	14
Introduction	14
1.1 Personal Experience	14
1.2 Research aim and objectives.....	18
1.3 Research questions	19
1.4 Arabic, Tamazight, French and English- in Algeria.....	19
1.5 Researcher’s Positionality	22
1.6 Structure of the thesis.....	23
Chapter Two	26
Context of the Study	26
2.1 Introduction	26
2.2 Language Policy in the Algerian Educational System	27
2.2.1 The colonial phase (1830-1962)	27
2.2.2 Post-independence phase (1962 – 1993)	29
2.2.3 2000s-present phase	34
2.3 The Structure of the Educational System in Algeria.....	38
2.4 Educational Reforms in Algerian Higher Education.....	38
2.4.1 The Early Independence Reform	39
2.4.2 Higher Education Reform of 1971	39
2.4.3 The Third Reform of the LMD System	39
2.5 Concluding the chapter	41
Chapter Three	42
Literature Review	42
3.1 Introduction	42
3.2 Definitions of Culture	42
3.3 Aspects of Culture	45
3.4 The relationship between language and cultural	48
3.5 Approaches to Teaching Culture	50
3.5.1 The Traditional Approach	51
3.6 Intercultural Communicative Competence Approach (ICC) in Language Teaching.....	52
3.6.1 Communicative Competence	52
3.6.2 What is ICC	55
3.7 Bennett’s Model of Intercultural Sensitivity Development.....	56
3.8 Byram’s ICC Model	61
3.8.1 Attitudes (Savoir Être)	62
3.8.2 Knowledge (Savoirs)	63
3.8.3 Skills (Savoir Comprendre et Savoir Apprendre)	64
3.8.4 Critical cultural awareness (Savoir S’engager).....	64
3.9 The Importance of Teaching ICC	66

3.10 Practical Activities to Develop ICC in the Classroom	68
3.11 Intercultural Communicative Competence in Practice	70
3.11.1 Challenges and Issues	72
3.12 Critics of Byram’s ICC Model in FL Context	74
3.13 Empirical Studies on ICC.....	75
3.13.1 Research about culture and ICC conducted in Algeria	75
3.13.2 Other Contexts	76
3.14 Concluding chapter	78
Chapter Four.....	79
Research Methods and Methodology	79
4.1 Introduction	79
4.2 Philosophical assumptions and worldviews	79
4.2.1 Ontology	79
4.2.2 Epistemology	81
4.3 Research Design Framework.....	83
4.4 Sampling Techniques.....	86
4.5 Data collection procedures	88
4.5.1 Interviews	89
4.5.2 Questionnaires	91
4.5.3 Focus Group.....	92
4.6 Design of Research Tools.....	93
4.7 Data Analysis	96
4.7.1 Approaches to Qualitative Data Analysis	97
4.7.2 Thematic coding approach	99
4.8 Coding the Participants	102
4.9 Ethics	102
4.9.1 Informed consent	103
4.9.2 Anonymity and Confidentiality.....	105
4.10 Trustworthiness of the research	105
4.10.1 Credibility	105
4.10.1 Transferability.....	106
4.10.3 Dependability	107
4.10.4 Conformability.....	107
4.11 Concluding the chapter	108
Chapter Five.....	109
Algerian English Language Teachers’ Perceptions and Conceptions of Culture and ICC.....	109
5.1 Introduction	109
5.2 Teachers’ Perspectives of Culture	110
5.2.1 Teachers’ Definitions of Culture	111
5.2.2 The Importance of Teaching about Cultures in the Classroom	115
5.2.3 What Culture to Teach?.....	117
5.2.4 Interconnectedness of Language and Culture.....	119
5.2.5 Dissatisfaction of cultural content.....	119
5.2.6 Shaping or Threatening Student Identity	120
5.3 Teachers’ Attitudes and Conceptions of Intercultural Communicative Competence in Language Education	123
5.3.1 Teachers’ Conceptions of ICC	123
5.3.2 The Importance of the Inclusion of Intercultural Communicative Competence in English Language Teaching	125
5.3.3 Challenges of Teaching about ICC	128
5.3.4 Teachers’ Intercultural Exposures	131
5.3.5 Concluding the chapter (Summary of the Findings)	144
Chapter Six	146

English Language Learners’ Perspectives and Attitudes of culture and ICC in EFL Context.....	146
6.1 Introduction	146
6.2 Learners’ Questionnaire Analysis	147
6.3 Focus Group Discussions Analysis	163
6.3.1 Learners’ Perceptions of Their English Learning Experience in Algeria	163
6.4 Learners’ Perspectives of Culture.....	168
6.4.1 Learners’ Definitions of Culture.....	168
6.4.2 Learners’ Experience of Learning Culture.....	169
6.5 Learners’ Conceptions and Understanding of ICC.....	172
6.5.1 Passive Learning and Its Impact on Cultural Understanding	174
6.5.2 Learners’ Exposure to ICC at the West University	175
6.5.3 The Impact of ICC Education on Shaping Intercultural Attitudes and Deconstructing Stereotypes	177
6.5.4 The Role of Knowledge in Enhancing Intercultural Understanding and Tolerance	178
6.6 Learners’ Intercultural Lived Experience	179
6.7 The Creation of Intercultural Clubs	181
General Overview of the GRC.....	182
6.8 The GRC Members’ Perspectives of the Intercultural Club	182
6.8.1 Motivations for Joining the GRC.....	182
6.8.2 Impact of the GRC on Personal Development	183
6.8.3 Challenges of the Creation of Intercultural Clubs in Algeria.....	183
6.8.4 Mutual Intercultural Awareness and Sensitivity.....	185
6.8.5 Developing Cross-Cultural Awareness Through Immersive Intercultural Experiences.....	187
6.9 Unanticipated Findings.....	188
6.10 Concluding the Chapter.....	189
Chapter Seven.....	191
General Conclusion	191
7.1 Introduction	191
7.2 Summary of the Study.....	192
7.3 Answering the research questions of the study.....	192
7.3.1 Research Question 1.....	193
7.3.2. Research Question 2.....	195
7.3.3 Research Question 3.....	204
7.3.4 Research Question 4.....	207
7.4 Implications for Policy-Makers and Teachers.....	209
7.5 Limitations and Recommendations for Future Research	211
7.6 Contribution to the Study.....	212
7.7 Reflections.....	214
7.8 Concluding the study.....	215
References	217
APPENDICES.....	247
Appendix 1: Participants Consent Form	247
Appendix 2: Teachers Information Sheet	249
Appendix 3: Interview Protocol.....	252
Appendix 4: Learners Information Sheet – Questionnaire and focus group interviews –	255
Appendix 5: Students’ Questionnaire.....	258
Appendix 6: Focus Group Protocol	263
Appendix 7: Learners’ Educational Background.....	265
Appendix 8: Teachers’ Profile.....	266

Appendix 9: Data Analysis Process	267
Appendix 10: Thematic Analysis of the Study.....	268
Appendix 11: Learners' Thematic Network.....	269

List of Tables

Table 1: Demographic information of learner participants.....	147
Table 2: Number of the Learners according to their English Streams.....	148
Table 3: Learners' Years of Studying English Language.....	148
Table 4: Learners' Motives for choosing to learn English.....	149
Table 5: Distribution of Learners studying other foreign languages.	150
Table 6: Learners' Perceptions of the appropriate ways to improve their CC.	151
Table 7: Distribution of learners according to the most/least emphasised competence in EFL classroom.	152
Table 8: Learners' attitudes of Learning English as a Second Foreign Language.	153
Table 9: Learners' goals of learning English.	155
Table 10: Learners' definitions of culture.	156
Table 11: Learners' Definitions of the Notion ICC.....	157
Table 12: Learners' distributions according to their travelling experiences.	159

List of Figures

Figure 1 : Iceberg illustration of surface and deep culture (Patel et al., 2011)	45
Figure 2 : ICC Dimensions Byram (1997)	61
Figure 3 : Adopted from Maxwell (2013)	83
Figure 4 : An Exploratory Mixed Methods Research Design (Creswell, 2014).	85

List of Abbreviations

- AMHE:** Algerian Ministry of Higher Education
- CA:** Cultural Awareness
- CCA:** Critical Cultural Awareness
- ELT:** English Language Teaching
- EFL:** English as a Foreign Language
- FL:** Foreign Language
- FLL:** Foreign Language Learning
- ELF:** English as a Lingua Franca
- ENS:** Native Speakers of English
- FLT:** Foreign Language Teaching
- FLT&L:** Foreign Language Teaching and Learning
- IELT:** Intercultural English Language Teaching
- IC:** Intercultural Competence
- ICC:** Intercultural Communicative Competence
- ICT:** Information Communication Technology
- IS:** Intercultural Speaker
- LC:** Linguistic Competence
- L1:** First Language
- L2:** Second Language
- MENA:** Middle East and North Africa
- MSA:** Modern Standard Arabic
- SL:** Second Language

Chapter One

Introduction

1.1 Personal Experience

My interest in exploring Algerian English language teachers' and learners' perspectives and understanding of the notions of culture and intercultural communicative competence has originated from my background as an English language learner in Algeria for eleven years and my personal experience of being an international PhD student in the UK.

In Algeria, I was introduced to the English language at the age of eleven, particularly, when I started middle school; during this phase of my childhood, I developed a significant interest and passion towards this global language. Thus, my profound fascination with this language ultimately directed me to major in the field of English language teaching and learning.

I majored in English for five years in Algeria at the East University (chosen for this study), where I had my Bachelor's and Master's Degrees. After completing my studies, I believed that my level and skills in using the English language were adequate to communicate with great efficiency with native speakers of English and other individuals from different cultural backgrounds. Furthermore, as I was introduced to modules such as British and American civilisation, I used to believe that there was one single constant British culture that is shared by people living in the UK. However, my experience as an international student has changed all the aforementioned perspectives. My understanding of the notion of culture has been expanded and developed. I, for the first time, experienced a new lifestyle, new ways of speaking, new perspectives, and a completely different environment from the one I used to live in. I found myself in a multicultural environment that holds many different cultures and each culture has its uniqueness. These encounters illuminated my thinking to understand that there is no single culture and helped me to be aware of how cultures are different.

When I travelled to the UK, I was not aware of how to deal with a culture that was different from my own. I used to believe that mastering the four language skills (receptive and productive skills) is the primary objective of learning and speaking the language; this is what I was taught in Algeria. However, based on my personal experience, I can say that is not true. During my interaction with my friends who were from diverse cultures, I failed to go through several intercultural situations, despite my good command of the linguistic aspects of the

language. In other words, what people from diverse cultural contexts say may not necessarily align with what they mean. Sometimes the phrases and words these individuals utter during the conversation do not convey their literal meanings (the use of idiomatic expressions).

I have observed that some international students from diverse nationalities, including myself, who lack confidence in establishing connections with British individuals or those from different cultural backgrounds tend to stick to their own community where they feel comfortable and far from situations of being misinterpreted or judged. In addition, other individuals who travel to other countries feel uncomfortable sharing their culture, thus, they try to hide their own cultural norms and values and adopt the behaviours of the local people to assimilate and immerse in that culture. However, it has been agreed by many scholars in the field of IC and ICC that engaging effectively in cross-cultural and multilingual interactions does not necessitate the abandonment of one's own cultural values and identity and the assimilation into others (Smith, 1987). Intercultural communication entails the awareness of the differences and similarities that exist between different cultures to understand their influence on the communication process. The idea of incorporating ICC into the teaching of the English language underscores that learning English as a foreign (FL) or second language (SL) does not require adopting a particular single culture, but entails the embracement and appreciation of oneself culture and respect of cultural diversity. It also aims at bridging gaps and tensions by discovering and establishing connections to reach successful and effective communication (Alptekin, 2002).

No one can ignore that stepping out of someone's comfort zone is a challenging journey. This journey exposed me to the challenges, complexities, and opportunities that developed my critical insights into the cultural differences that coexist in a single situation. One of the cultural misunderstandings I experienced was about the way people greet each other. In Algeria, it is common for women to greet each other with kisses on the cheeks. It's a way to express joy, warmth, and affection. However, when I attempted to greet my friends from diverse cultures in the same manner, I noticed that they found it strange and sometimes uncomfortable. I understood that in their cultures physical contact is generally limited to a handshake or verbal greetings. This was among the incidents that enlightened my awareness about the need to adapt my behaviours and actions in different cultural contexts.

Navigating a foreign environment, both socially and academically, has illuminated and awakened my critical thinking towards the significance of integrating intercultural

communicative competence in the Algerian educational system to promote effective communication and foster mutual understanding among learners nationally and globally.

At the early stage of my Ph. D., I conducted informal professional conversations with Algerian English language teachers who majored in teaching English as a Foreign Language and have expertise in teaching subjects that address culture. These conversations were neither recorded nor used as data for this research.

These teachers volunteered to take part; they were affiliated with 10 different Algerian universities. I asked them two questions: how culture is addressed in the Algerian classroom; second question, how familiar they are with notions such as intercultural communication, intercultural sensitivity, intercultural competent speakers, and intercultural awareness? As expected, all teachers except one stated that the cultural content provided primarily addresses the surface or the visible culture. Most of them were not familiar with the notion of interculturality or other related concepts. Instead, they provided some insights about the pedagogical approaches of how to enable learners to effectively communicate. Furthermore, they narrowed the term of teaching about cultures to teaching the target culture, British/American civilizations, and literature. However, only one teacher from West University was aware of the notion of ICC; he demonstrated that ICC was introduced as a subject at the Department of English and it is considered as a fundamental objective to achieve in teaching English as FL in the West University.

I came to realise that the teaching approaches, pedagogical methods, and recourses used in Algeria do not adequately address the intricacy of the notion of culture. Rather, the emphasis was on developing the learners' linguistic and communicative competence to enable them to communicate in English. They also limited the intricacy of the notion of culture to one singular culture, the target culture. Importantly speaking, they address the visible aspects of the target culture in the classroom. I believe that this conventional approach is no longer sufficient for learners to understand and think critically in that language (Byram, 1988; Krasner, 1999), and they cannot cope in the globalized world we are living in. Learners in Algeria were taught and still to acquire communicative skills, however, these basic skills do not help them to overcome the challenges and tensions that might occur while communicating with people from different cultural backgrounds.

It was interesting that among these universities, only one university which I referred to in this research as the West University introduced ICC as a separate subject for learners who are

majoring in Language and Communication. Former learners at this university created an intercultural club, the Global Representatives of Cultures, to promote cultural diversity, cross-cultural understanding, and collaboration among learners from different cultural backgrounds.

The reason behind choosing the East and West University goes back to the fact that I used to be a student at the former university and I do not recall being exposed to ICC for five years of studying English. I chose the second university because of the integration of ICC at the English language department. I wanted to explore teachers' and learners' perspectives and attitudes of culture and ICC and to what extent these notions are embedded. In addition, I was curious to investigate the members of the GRC's experience of creating the intercultural club.

One of the most crucial objectives for teachers is to develop their learners' awareness about the challenges they may encounter when travelling to a society that is culturally different from their own, or when interacting with individuals from a diverse socio-cultural environment to reduce the effect of cultural shocks and tensions. It is worth stating that teachers themselves may encounter challenges in understanding the diversity and intricacy of cultures, this might lead them to prioritise the linguistic dimension of the language as is the case in Algeria. In my perspective, exploring teachers' and learners' perspectives and conceptions of culture and ICC, and how these notions are addressed in both universities is essential.

Although internet connectivity can facilitate the development of ICC, it is important to note that higher education in Algeria still lacks a strong technological foundation, and institutions frequently struggle to get access to advanced technology. Many institutions have challenges related to outdated technology, poor internet connectivity, and an inadequate supply of digital resources (Bouzidi, 2005 and Aoumeur, 2017). Even though there have been attempts to improve ICT infrastructure—especially through government initiatives meant to increase technological accessibility, the technological foundation remains weak. This aligns with Mansouri's (2019) study. She investigated Algerian teachers' and learners' perspectives on the use of web blogs in universities. In her findings, she believed that to facilitate the use of ICT in Algerian classrooms, it would be advisable to hire adequate experts to assess this initiative for quality assurance and allocate resources towards acquiring the necessary IT materials.

1.2 Research aim and objectives

According to Spencer-Oatey and Franklin (2009), intercultural communicative competence (ICC) has been a subject of investigation across various disciplines. Research has indicated that in teaching Foreign Languages (FL), there exist two different contexts that significantly help learners cultivate their ICC and foster skills of tolerance and respect towards cultural diversity; one of these contexts, as advocated by Derwin (2017), is experiential learning, which involves immersive experiences such as study abroad programs that provide learners with the opportunity to engage with foreign cultures and individuals from diverse cultural backgrounds. However, educational experience within the classroom setting is more challenging and demanding, as students learn about unfamiliar cultures within their familiar surroundings. The influence of teachers and the instructional resources they employ significantly shape students' level of cultural awareness and comprehension of cultural differences.

Teaching the English language as a foreign language (FL) or as a second language (SL) has been deemed a significant means of communication to attain the ultimate goal of effective intercultural communication with people from diverse socio-cultural backgrounds (Spencer-Oatey and Franklin, 2009; Baker, 2009a). Despite this, there has not been enough research done on Algerian English language teachers' levels of awareness when it comes to addressing ICC in the classroom. Teachers might have felt dissatisfied and returned to focusing on language structure (grammar, vocabulary, and phonology) due to the lack of suitable approaches and guidelines for teaching the intricate notion of culture (Byram and Fleming, 1998).

This research is a constructivist exploratory research that aims to explore how Algerian English language teachers and learners perceive culture, and how they relate the intricacy of this concept to their English teaching practices. It also sought to investigate and understand the teachers' and learners' perspectives and conceptions of intercultural communicative competence. This involves exploring their understanding of the notion of ICC and its dimensions (attitudes, knowledge, skills and critical cultural awareness) necessary for effective communication across different cultures. It also aimed to gain insights into how teachers' intercultural lived experiences shaped their understanding of ICC and influenced their teaching practices. Furthermore, this study endeavoured to explore how the model of

intercultural speaking clubs contributes to the development of intercultural communicative competence. This involves investigating the impact of such extracurricular activities on the development of learners' cultural awareness and intercultural sensitivity.

1.3 Research questions

In light of the aforementioned objectives, the following research questions are presented:

RQ1. How do Algerian English Language teachers perceive and understand the concept of culture and how it is placed in their English language teaching practices?

RQ2. What are Algerian English Language teachers' understandings and conceptions of intercultural communicative competence? How do their intercultural encounters influence their teaching practices?

RQ3. What are Master English learners' perceptions and attitudes of culture and intercultural communicative competence, and to what extent is ICC embedded in their English language learning?

RQ4. How does the model of intercultural speaking clubs contribute to the development of learners' ICC?

1.4 Arabic, Tamazight, French and English- in Algeria

Because of the different invasions that Algeria has been through, the current complex linguistic landscape is characterised by the coexistence of different languages such as Tamazight, Arabic, French, and English (Abdelhamid, 2002). The above-mentioned languages hold a distinct place in society, reflecting the country's rich multicultural and multilingual heritage (Serai, 2022).

Modern Standard Arabic (MSA) is the official and national language (Daoudi, 2018; Benrabah, 2013) of Algeria, it is deeply intertwined with the Algerian identity. It is used in formal contexts such as religious affairs, government affairs, official documents, media and education, while Algerian Arabic (Derja) serves as the everyday spoken language (colloquial dialect) among much of the population in everyday interactions. After independence in 1962, the Algerian authorities implemented the policy of Arabisation (monolingualism), which aimed at restoring and reinforcing Arabic as the primary national language of the country (Benrabah,

2007a). These attempts were to promote Algeria's Arab-Islamic identity, which had been suppressed during the colonial period (see Chapter 2).

Tamazight represents the Berber language and culture. It was recognised as a national and official language in Algeria in 2016 (Rouabah, 2022; Hamdan and Kessar, 2023). Tamazight was officially considered as a national language in Algeria in 2002, and later as an official language alongside Arabic in 2016 (Benrabah, 2013). This was added to the Algerian constitution as a kind of acknowledgement of the linguistic plurality and pluralism of Algeria (Benrabah, 2013). Tamazight is considered as the native language of the Indigenous people of North Africa such as Algeria, Morocco and Libya. In Algeria, it is mostly spoken by people living in the Kabylie and Aurès regions in addition to other Berber-speaking areas. It encompasses several dialects, including Kabyle, Chaoui, Tachelhit and others. Although Tamazight is partially included in education (optional); however, its incorporation is a significant recognition of Algeria's cultural and linguistic diversity and continuous endeavours to preserve and promote the Berber culture.

French was introduced to Algeria during the colonial period, which lasted from 1830 to 1962. Algeria lived under the Frenchification policy for 132 years, where the French language and culture were imposed at the expense of the national and native languages (Tamazight and Arabic) and cultures (Wardhaugh, 1987; Benrabah, 2005; 2007a). Thus, at that time, the French Language was recognised as the national and official language and Arabic and Tamazight as foreign languages (Maamri, 2009). After independence (1962), the Algerian government adopted the policy of Arabisation, aiming to regain the Algerian identity and foster the use of Modern Standard Arabic as the national and official language of the country (Benrabah, 2004). The Algerian authorities considered the Arabic language as the official language for all domains, and they regarded it as the language of civilisation (Gordon, 1978), disregarding the other spoken languages and neglecting the fact that Algeria is linguistically and culturally diverse (Benrabah, 2004; 2014; Maamri, 2009; Roux, 2017). However, this policy failed (Benrabah, 2007a; 2007b) (see Chapter 2 for more details). Due to the significant impact of French colonialism, French holds a powerful and prestigious status in Algeria and has a significant influence on the country's social history (Benrabah, 2007b; Benrabah, 2014), it is considered the first foreign language, and it is extensively used in administrations (official

documents, legal matters and international diplomacy), education and public life. French is taught as a first foreign language starting from the third year of primary school and it is used as the main language of instruction in scientific fields (medicine, mathematics, engineering and technology) in higher education (Sebti, 2001; Benrabah, 2007b).

The status of the English language in Algeria is evolving, particularly in higher education and international communication. Although English is not as prevalent as Tamazight, Arabic and French, it is being promoted in schools and universities as Algeria seeks to enhance its global connections. It aims to integrate into the global economy and to effectively engage with international communities (Benadla, 2013; Djebbari, 2016). Algerian language planners consider English as a language of modernity, prosperity and technology (Bouhadiba, 2006). They also believe that the promotion of the English language is essential because it has a dominant and powerful status in the world (Daoudi, 2018). Algerians advocated and called policy-makers to re-evaluate the status of the English language as a second foreign language instead of French, as they believed that French is not the language of science and technology (Benrabah, 2014) (see Chapter 2). However, English occupied a third position in the Algerian educational system after Arabic and French. It used to be introduced as a second foreign language in the first year of middle school and continued through secondary education. However, in recent years, there has been a notable shift towards promoting and strengthening the status of English, reflecting a national strategy which aims to diversify learners' linguistic repertoires. This shift was particularly evident when they introduced English in primary schools (starting from third grade) in 2022. Learning the English language has been promoted in Algeria through social media platforms (Belmihoub, 2015; 2018), recognising its significance in accessing global knowledge and conducting international research. Spaces like Facebook and YouTube provide Algerian youth with a unique opportunity to express themselves in English and become proficient language users (Belmihoub, 2018). However, the status of the English language in higher education remains limited primarily to students majoring in English language and literature. For students majoring in English, the language is not only the subject of study but also the medium of instruction. In Algeria, this major emphasises the development of students' linguistic competence and language proficiency as it is the case in this study. However, French continues to be the dominant language, as the language of instruction in most scientific,

medical and technical fields, and it is used in business and professional sectors (Maamri, 2009). To enhance and strengthen the status of English in Algeria, the Algerian government has provided opportunities for students to study abroad, particularly in English-speaking countries.

Algeria is considered a multilingual and multicultural country (Benrabah, 2004; Tulga, 2020). Algeria's multiculturalism is rooted in its long history of interaction with various ethnic groups, including the Berbers, who are recognised as the Indigenous population of Algeria, and the Arabs who immigrated to North Africa to spread Islam. In addition, the long-lasting presence of French colonialism in Algeria which lasted for 132 years, has resulted in the linguistic and cultural diversity remarked in present-day Algeria. The Algerians' diverse cultural backgrounds and their different linguistic repertoires make it paramount to foster and promote linguistic pluralism and cultural diversity in this country. According to Benrabah, "One possible way out is to give priority to a global societal project grounded on an ideology that favours pluralism in general and multilingualism in particular" (2004, p.75).

In the Algerian educational system, there is a growing emphasis on cultivating and fostering learners' multilingual competence because of its importance in this globalised world. Within this framework, English is gradually gaining significance, particularly in education, where it is seen as a means of opening new academic and professional horizons for Algerian students and scholars. While Arabic, Tamazight, and French continue to dominate the linguistic landscape.

1.5 Researcher's Positionality

Talking about the study in general, my status as a researcher is an insider who belongs to the Algerian context and is familiar with the educational context there. However, speaking of the two chosen contexts in this study (East and West University), my status as a researcher is characterised by an insider-outsider dynamic. I possess an insider status within the East region where I have resided most of my life, and the East University, where I completed my academic studies (Bachelor and Masters Degrees). Conversely, I hold an outsider position in relation to the West University, given my lack of prior experience there and preconceived notions about

the status of intercultural communicative competence (ICC) at that institution. This dual positionality as an insider-outsider informs my research approach.

Being an insider facilitated effective communication and trust-building with participants, thereby enhancing the depth of the data collected. Being an outsider helped me to explore new insights without being subject to any preconceived notions. My insider-outsider positionality contributes a nuanced perspective, enriching the research findings and fostering a more comprehensive understanding of ICC in Algerian Higher Education.

Despite my insider status, I maintained awareness of my position and engaged in reflexivity to minimise potential biases. This reflective practice involved continuously examining my background, experiences, and perspectives. To further ensure the reliability of the findings, I employed triangulation methods, integrating interviews, questionnaires, and focus groups. This approach allowed me to address the phenomenon of ICC from diverse perspectives, including those of teachers, Algerian learners, Malian learners, and members of the intercultural club (GRC).

1.6 Structure of the thesis

This thesis is divided into seven chapters. The first chapter is an introductory chapter where I illustrate how my personal experience, as an international student in the UK, was the main factor in developing the current research. Additionally, I have explained the informal professional conversations I conducted with Algerian English language teachers, from different Algerian universities. The research objectives, research questions and positionality and background of the researcher were also addressed in this chapter.

The second chapter describes the context of the study. It provides a historical overview of the Algerian educational system, where I demonstrated how French colonialism significantly impacted the Algerian educational system and the Algerian language situation. The second chapter also highlights the language policy in the Algerian education system from 1830 to the present day, the educational reforms, and the discrepancies and challenges of the LMD system applied in Algerian higher education (Licence, Master, Doctorate).

The third chapter provides a critical review of the literature where I presented various definitions of the notion of culture and its relation to English language teaching in FL context.

Then, I demonstrated the transition from the traditional approach (linguistic and communicative) to an intercultural approach in the domain of English language teaching, as well as, I provided a concise overview of how the notion of intercultural communicative competence emerged, and how the concept of Intercultural Speaker is defined. The third chapter also reviewed and presented Byram's Intercultural Communicative Competence model (1997), one of the most widely utilised in EFL teaching and learning. Critics and challenges of implementing this model in a context like Algeria are presented.

The fourth chapter presents the ontological, epistemological, and methodological stances of the researcher. It also provides the research design, sampling techniques, methods of data collection, and the procedures for analysing the gathered data. This chapter additionally outlines the participant recruitment and data collection procedures, through conducting semi-structured interviews with Algerian English Language teachers and the members of the intercultural club, as well as, online questionnaires and focus groups with learners of English from the East and West University. Additionally, it offers a comprehensive elucidation of the sequential steps involved in transcribing, thematising, interpreting, and presenting the research findings. Ethical considerations and criteria for evaluating trustworthiness in this research such as credibility, transferability, conformability, and dependability were addressed.

The fifth and sixth chapters present the findings and interpretations of the data collected through semi-structured interviews, questionnaires, and focus group discussions, as well as, relating them to the existing reviewed literature.

Chapter Five presents the findings that address the first and second research questions. which are related to teachers' perceptions of culture and ICC and how their intercultural lived experience fostered their understanding of ICC.

Chapter six answers the two other remaining research questions which are related to English language learners' attitudes towards their English language learning experience and their understanding of culture and interculturality. Additionally, the GRC's perspectives of creating an intercultural club are discussed.

Finally, chapter seven provides a summary of the study. I have answered the four-research questions through the participants' voices. My contribution to knowledge, implications to Algerian policy-makers, and educators, limitations that I encountered during the data

collection process, and recommendations for future research are discussed in this chapter. At the end of the thesis, a list of references and appendices are provided.

Chapter Two

Context of the Study

2.1 Introduction

Algeria, in Arabic Al Jazair; in Berber Dzayer; in French L'Algérie. It is a sovereign state in North Africa on the Mediterranean coast. It is officially The People's Democratic Republic of Algeria, and its capital is Algiers (Benrabah, 2005). Algeria, along with Tunisia and Morocco, is one of the three North African/ Maghrebi nations. It holds the position of being the largest country in Africa, boasting a population exceeding 41 million, and ranks as the tenth largest globally (Benrabah, 2005). Modern Standard Arabic (MSA) is recognized as Algeria's official and national language. Despite this, the country has a diverse linguistic landscape, featuring two distinct language-speaking ethnic groups: the Berbers and the Arabs. The Berbers are the indigenous inhabitants of North Africa. According to Benrabah (2005), both languages, Tamazight and Arabic, have influenced and borrowed from each other.

In this research, investigating Algerian English Language teachers and Master learners' perspectives of culture and the significance of integrating intercultural communicative competence in foreign language education becomes particularly crucial in a culturally diverse context like Algeria.

Algeria has been always considered as a place of disruption and confusion; this refers to the long colonial history it witnessed starting from 1830. However, after gaining its independence on the 5th of July 1962 from the French colonizer, the situation of confusion and complexity has not steadied and different political ideologies still vie within the Algerian society in general and within the Algerian educational system in particular. Algeria witnessed the heaviest colonial impact in comparison with the other Arab countries that were under European rule (Sharkey, 2012).

France invaded Algeria in 1830 and declared Algeria not to be only a colony but an extension land of France itself (Clancy-Smith, 1997; Smith 2006). Additionally, the French occupation in Algeria sought not only economic exploitation and political domination but implicitly aimed at suppressing the Algerian cultural identity and remoulding the Algerian society according to the French lines (Maamri, 2009). The impact of this policy remained even after the Algerian

independence in 1962 and was apparent through the Algerian dual language system which is deemed as a coloniser's legacy (Benrabah, 2013).

2.2 Language Policy in the Algerian Educational System

Language policy and language planning (LPLP) are very sensitive subjects to be studied in Algeria, this goes back to its unrivalled history in the Arabic-speaking world; Algeria was the only country that lived under the Frenchification policy (French assimilation) for 132 years (Benrabah, 2005). After the Algerian independence in 1962, Gordon noted that Algeria's future will continue to be a compelling case study for both Orientalists and those focused on development and modernization (Gordon, 1966). From the pre-independence to pro-independence periods, language has been a sensitive serious issue entangled with politics, as accurately stated by Berger "the most severe problem of Algeria in its present and troubled state" (2002, p.8). Therefore, the complexity of language policy placed Algeria apart from the rest of the Arab world and makes it in particular a pedagogical and instructive example for language education policy and planning fields (Benrabah, 2007a).

Language and Education have been always used as effective tools to fulfil the central power's political aims and goals. Schools in Algeria were considered a vehicle to linguistically and culturally dominate the population (Benrabah, 2013). After independence, the historical development of Algeria encompassed three significant periods. Each phase had a considerable impact on language implementation policies. The first one was identified by the French colonial occupation's rules where the French language was imposed in schools and considered as an official language in Algeria. The second phase, which lasted from 1960 to 1990, was marked with the nationalism transition where Arabic was progressively enforced by the Algerian government to be the official language. The third phase started in the early 2000s, and it was characterised by the free economic market which reduced the emphasis on the Arabisation policies (Benbarah, 2007). During the third period, the Algerian authorities came across a dispute over the reform of the rehabilitation of the Algerian schooling system. In other words, the Algerian polity acknowledged that the Algerian education has failed (Benrabah, 2007a).

2.2.1 The colonial phase (1830-1962)

The endeavours of France to dominate and control Algerians through the assimilation policy were demonstrated in the field of education (Heggo, 1973). France imposed the French

language and culture at the expense of the Algerian native languages (Algerian Arabic, Tamazight); it sought to the hegemony of the French culture and its educational norms over the other native languages and cultures (Wardhaugh, 1987). In the same vein, during the colonial phase, France's educational project aimed at attaining what they called civilising mission (Murphy, 1977; Benrabah, 2004; 2005; 2007; 2013; 2014; Le Roux, 2017), the process to change the Algerian language and culture and to assimilate Algerians through the French lines (Djité, 1992; Murphy, 1977). Therefore, the French language, at that time, was classified as the national and official language (Murphy, 1977), and the Arabic language as a foreign language (Maamri, 2009). The use of Arabic in Algerian schools and formal administrative documents was prohibited and forbidden. Therefore, the status of Arabic was diminished and marginalised (Ennaji, 1991; Ezzaki and Wagner; 1991). The French language superseded the Arab educational norms and sought to maintain Algerian subordination through the change of different structural policies of education in Algeria (Heggo, 1973). A French supporter, Jules Ferry, who had a lasting impact on French schooling policy in Algeria (Maamri, 2009), stated that France is a superior civilised race and Algeria is species descended from a backward race, and they are responsible for the task of civilising the inferior races (Maamri, 2009). Ferry considered the school as the most effectual and pacific vehicle to transform society and evoke the notion of civilising schools through the teaching of the French language and culture to the people of Algeria. This created a new whole re-structuration to Algerian education according to the French trajectory and the obliteration of the Arabic and Islamic roots in order to create a generation free from culture and religion, a generation that is easy to manipulate. The French conquest considered Islam as a barrier and impediment to the Frenchification of the Algerian people. Hence, France enforced the French language as a dominant language and dislodged all the local languages (Maamri, 2009).

French provided a free, secular, and mandatory education for Algerians who formerly relied on sending their children to Arabic Quranic schools in order to learn reading and writing. The French coloniser refused to allocate any funds for the Quranic schools, however, more than five times was spent on schools of European learners (Maamri, 2009). Many Quranic schools were closed because they were left without income. Therefore, a very small percentage, less than five percent of Algerian children attended French schools. In 1917, only boys were allowed to attend schools. Later, this policy changed, and education was limited only to those children who lived three kilometres from public schools, which were allocated to Algerians

only (Benrabah, 2013). Algerian parents rejected the idea of sending their children to French schools; they viewed French education as a threat to Islam. Henceforth, they preferred for their children to stay illiterate in order to preserve their cultural and religious identity (Saad, 1992). The French coloniser created three types of schools in order to encourage Algerians to attend French institutions. The first type of school is identical to those schools in metropolitan France. The second type is an Arabic school under the surveillance of the coloniser, and the third one is a bilingual school French-Arabic school where both languages are used for instruction (Benrabah, 2013).

Although Algerians fought not to send their children to schools offered by the French coloniser, in 1920, some of them surrendered and had no option but to accept the French schooling system. Their opposition and cultural resistance lessened. Surprisingly, they started to demand extra hours of teaching in French (Heggoy, 1984, cited in Benrabah, 2005).

The French assimilation earnestly backfired. The feeling of being marginalised and deprived of their rights and heritage led the Algerian population to revolt violently against the French coloniser for the sake of preserving Islam, culture, identity, and the local languages. Therefore, a prominent group of scholars (Jamaat Al-Ulema) reacted violently against France after the closure of the Quranic schools. The establishment of this conservative movement was under the leadership of Ben Badis; its aim was to instil Islamic principles and protect the Algerian Arabic identity in the whole generation and evolve self-consciousness (Maamri, 2009). After the foundation of this association, many free private schools were established throughout the country and only Arabic was provided to educate the Algerian population.

2.2.2 Post-independence phase (1962 – 1993)

After the independence of Algeria, the Algerian government (1962-1965) opted for a new language policy that preferred monolingualism (Arabisation policy) and denied the fact that Algeria is recognised as a multilingual and multicultural country (Benrabah, 2005). The Algerian authorities considered Arabic as the language of literature and civilisation (Gordon, 1978). The implementation of the Arabisation policy was authoritarian and there was no endeavour to attain unanimity about this sensitive issue (Benrabah, 2004). In other words, there was a total ignorance of the Algerians' linguistic and cultural diversity (Berber and Arabs).

The Algerian authorities emphasised that the first institution to be Arabised was the educational system, and this was the crucial aim for the educated religious-conservative movement, Ulema, when they were offered a high position in the Ministry of Education in July 1965 (Benrabah, 2004). The imposition of the Arabisation policy was to dominate and transform the country by creating a new society that needs to learn thinking in Arabic. To justify this perspective, the new Minister of Education added the expression of “new Algeria” and “new Algerians” (Benrabah, 2004, p.67), and talked about the necessity of creating an Arabised generation that think in Arabic. In the same vein, the religio-conservative movement sought first to Arabise the populations’ minds and hearts and second the native language of Algeria (Tamazight) (Benrabah,2004; 2007b; 2013; 2014). The Frenchification ideology, which underestimated and suppressed classical Arabic later turned this language to be the language of liberation and civilisation (Djite, 1992; Gordon, 1978). The position of this language was further valued by its link to Islam as justified by Gordon “Islam and the Arabic language were effective forces of resistance against the attempt of the colonial regime to depersonalise Algeria” (Gordon, 1966, quoted in Benrabah, 2007a, p.229). When the French coloniser flew to their mainland in 1962, Algeria was linguistically a pluralistic country. This goes back to its heritage and to the cultural influences witnessed from Berber, Phoenician, Romans, Vandals, Byzantine, Jewish, and Ottoman Empire. The main languages were Algerian Arabic, Tamazight (in different varieties), and French language. Although Algeria is linguistically and culturally diverse, the Arabisation policy disregarded the status of the other spoken languages in Algeria and reinforced the Arabic language as the official and national language of the country (Benrabah, 2004; 2014; Maamri, 2009; Roux, 2017).

In 1962, Ahmed Ben Bella the new president of independent Algeria instigated the policy of Arabisation in the educational system (Grandguillaume, 2004; Benrabah, 2007a). Therefore, the status of the French language progressively diminished, and Arabic teaching was mandatory in all subjects and all levels during the period 1963-1964 (Bennoune, 2000). The French language turned out to be the main aim of Arabisation (Lewis, 2004). In 1963, the hours devoted to teaching the Arabic language were robustly increased to 10 hours at all levels. Furthermore, the first grade of the primary school was fully Arabised, and all religious and civic subjects were later added to the programme (Grandguillaume, 2004). The Algerian authorities constantly viewed the native languages, Algerian Arabic (dialect) and Tamazight, as small languages, faulty, an unorganised and unsophisticated. The implementation of this

policy in Algeria confronted real challenges and obstacles because the Algerian authorities didn't take into account any of the changes left by French imperialism, including the immense increase of the pupils who are enrolled in the primary cycle, in addition, to the unavailability of competent teaching personnel and that was due to the mass number of educators who had left Algeria by July 1962 (Bennoune, 2000). Henceforth, the illiteracy rate increased among Algerians (Bennoune, 2000). To solve this issue, the Algerian government hired 1,000 Egyptian educators who were positioned as Arabic language instructors. These teachers were not qualified for teaching because their main interest was "in the ideological indoctrination of the students than in teaching" (Saad, 1992, p.60). These group of teachers were members of the Muslim fraternity and neglected the Algerian cultural identity and social reality (Sarter and Sefta, 1992). In their teaching, they relied on outdated pedagogy (memorisation, recitation, and physical punishment), which later proved to be inconvenient and unsuitable (Grandguillaume, 2004). Furthermore, their spoken Egyptian Arabic was not comprehensible to Algerians in general and Berbers in particular (Benrabah, 2007a).

The second president of the new Algeria was Hoauri Boumediene who led the military coup in 1965. During his presidency, the policy of Arabisation was greatly reinforced and gained great attention. In 1967, the Algerian Minister of Education enforced a total Arabisation of the first two primary grades and this imposition was coupled with the poor quality of the Algerian education. Hence, many parents delayed their children's school registration until the third year when the French language was introduced (Saad, 1992). The Algerian parents' opposition to sending their children to schools until the third grade is a sturdy signal to the linguistic dominance and Arabisation policy. The Minister of the National Ministry of Education, primary and secondary, Ahmed Taleb Ibrahimi, made a declaration during a government session that the Arabisation policy would not work but they still need to apply it (Grandguillaume, 2004).

After independence, The Algerian educational structure was inherited from the colonial period, which comprised three levels. Primary school; consisted of five years. The second level is the middle school was composed of four years. The last grade was secondary school that consisted of three years. In 1976, a new reform was introduced as the Fundamental school in the educational schooling system. This reform indicated the incorporation of both primary and middle grades to be nine successive years and the dominant language of instruction for

all subjects was standard classical Arabic except for foreign languages (Assous, 1985; Saad, 1992).

Mostefa Lacheraf was appointed as the Minister of primary and secondary education in 1977. The Arabisation process signalled a pause in Boumediene's presidency (Grandguillaume, 2004), and the fundamental school was suspended by the Minister Lacheraf. In addition, all supporters of Arabisation were dismissed from the Ministry, and teacher training in the French language was reintroduced. The Minister introduced robust forms of bilingualism in both primary and secondary schools and he promoted the use of the French language as a medium to teach scientific subjects such as math and biology. Mostafa Lacheraf was an advocator of bilingualism and sought to gradually decrease Arabisation. However, his endeavours didn't see the light, he resigned after the death of President Boumediene in 1978. The new Minister of Primary and Secondary Education, Cherif Kharroubi, was appointed in March 1979 after the resignation of Mostafa Lacheraf. He is an Arabist Kabyle who supported the monolingualism system and he was despised by his fellow Kabyle because he refused to speak his mother tongue (Tamazight) (Roberts, 2003). His first decision was to continue the Arabisation policy of all the educational sectors (Daoudi, 2018), and consider Arabic as the dominant language for all curriculum subjects. Cherif Kharroubi's second decision was to reinstate the reform of the Fundamental School and enforce teaching religious instruction at all levels (Tefiani, 1984). The ministry personnel turned the Arabisation policy into an Islamisation process (Benrabah, 1999). The minister of education postponed French until Grade four and introduced English as a second compulsory foreign language in Grade eight. At the beginning of the 1990s proponents of Arabisation put the Minister of Education under pressure to postpone the teaching of the French language in the Fundamental school. Nevertheless, the minister ignored the lobbyist's claims and instead, he qualified English to replace French (Laib, 1993). In 1993, primary school children in fourth grade were given the opportunity to choose between French and English as the first compulsory foreign language (Bennoune, 2000). However, the language competition ended up favouring French because the number of pupils who favoured English was inconsiderable (Nadia, 2011). In addition, other parents obliged their children to choose French over English (Nadia, 2011). This can refer back to two factors. Firstly, during that period, English was a relatively new language for parents and was perceived as having a low social value within the Algerian context. Consequently, parents may have believed that their children would not have

opportunities to use English in their social lives. Secondly, the remaining influence of French may have played a significant role, as it was already being used at the time and appeared to be the only language with potential future utility. According to Miliani (2001), the introduction of the English language in primary schools was deemed unsuccessful due to its political aims rather than being driven by educational considerations. In other words, its implementation aimed to eradicate the impact of French colonisation.

The opposition to the Arabisation policy came first from the Berber-speaking minority (Kabylis). They viewed this policy as a threat to the Berber culture and identity (Maamri, 2009). The Berber's anger swiftly turned out against the Algerian authorities and they formed two main Berber parties: the Socialist Forces Front (FFS) and the Rally for Culture and Democracy (RCD). The ideologies and tides formed by the former parties were all opposed to the Arabisation policy. However, the Kabyle department from the FFS pointed to the significance of preserving the teaching of the French language because it is the language of science and technological development and the language of civilised people (Maamri, 2009), but it was not more valued than the local languages. On the other hand, the RCD vigorously demanded support from francophone elites. Their demand indicated the maintenance of the French language as an essential language of the state alongside Arabic and Tamazight. According to the Kabylis Francophones, French was the language of progress and civilisation. Different series of riots and manifestations were led by Kabylis, against the Algerian authorities, after the cancellation of Mouloud Mammeri's lecture about ancient Tamazight poetry, which was to be taught at the University of Tizi Ouzou (capital of the Berber region of Kabylia). This made the Kabylis very angry, and they were on strike for a month to make their language and culture recognised and not marginalised. The strike resulted in many injuries, arrests, and the deterioration of the country. The Berber riots and violent demonstrations such as the Berber Spring, were considered the first factors behind the destabilisation of the Algerian regime and announced a revolution to end the socialist system of the country to political liberation (Benrabah, 2007a). Furthermore, the Berber language was adopted by Berberphones as a passive means of resistance. Tamazight-speaking parents forced their children to speak Tamazight and French and banned them from the use of Arabic (Kahlouche, 2004). They encouraged them to deliberately speak Tamazight and French in Cafes, restaurants, and different administrative sectors. In 1988, Berberophones actively requested political and cultural liberalisation under the ideological steering of The Berber

Cultural Movement (in French MCB). This was the only way to guarantee their linguistic and cultural rights and identity in democratic Algeria. They also sought the recognition of their language as an official language and rejected the Arabisation policy of the educational system because of its de-Frenchifying aims.

Notwithstanding, most Kabylisians confirmed the fact that Algerian authority could not offer Algerian citizens justice and equality (not only for Kabylisians but throughout the whole country). The newly elected president, Abdelaziz Bouteflika, aimed to create a room for tolerance, acceptance, openness, and respect for cultural differences; which is an ideal framework for democracy (Benrabah, 2007a).

In terms of English language teaching, two main events were marked. The first was the establishment of a General Inspectorate of English, and the second was when the Algerian Ministry of Education decided to Algerianise the Algerian textbooks of English in both cycles (Middle and Secondary school textbooks) (Mize, 1978). To compensate for the lack of teachers, the Ministry of Education hired immigrants from all over the world. Teachers of primary schools were offered positions without any formal training. However, teachers of middle school had to do a one-year formal training at the Institutes of Education, and secondary teachers were asked to do a three-year teaching degree which is called Licence d'Enseignement (Bachelor Degree) (Bellalam, 2012).

2.2.3 2000s-present phase

The issue of languages in the Algerian educational system has been a serious matter since 2000 (Benrabah, 2007a). The question of whether they should continue to monolingualism or move to bilingualism (French and Arabic) was raised. This debate reached its climax in 2002 when the Arabo-Islamists (the opponents of the monolingual Arabisation policy) issued a new Fatwa objecting to Modernist perspectives (francophone members of the population and the elite, who aimed at the implementation of Arabo-French bilingualism) (Abdelhai, 2001). This fatwa viewed supporters of bilingualism as the “enemies of Islam and the Arabic language” and the advocates of westernised Algeria (Djamel, 2001, quoted in Benrabah, 2007a, p.227). Hence, The Algerian educational system has been always seen as an ill-starred system. Mohammed Boudiaf, a previous president, viewed the educational system as doomed and lacking value to the Algerian population (Benrabah, 2007a; 2013). Abdelaziz Bouteflika

also referred to the educational system as 'doomed schooling system' and criticised its standards for reaching an unacceptable level (Benrabah, 2007a, p.228; 2013).

Abdelaziz Bouteflika was the newly elected president of Algeria. He established a new reform for the Algerian Education System called the "National Commission for the Reform of the Educational System" (also known as GNRSE in French). The GNRSE was established in 2000, it aimed at the reinforcement of the French language as the first compulsory foreign language in grade two (6-7 years old) instead of grade four (8-9 years old). Furthermore, the GNRSE stated that all scientific disciplines to be taught in French instead of Arabic in Secondary Schools (Sebti, 2001). There were other aims that Bouteflika's government Reform committed itself to achieve. For instance, promoting the Algerian educational Framework capacities, and refining the qualities of education and youth training. This reform urged also the revision of all school cycles, the renovation of Algerian textbooks and curriculum, the provision of various teacher training in Arabic and French, and the encouragement of introducing ICT in schools and universities. English has secured a prominent position as an international language in Algeria, enabling it to align the country with developed countries (Benadla, 2013; Djebbari, 2016). The Algerian central power aspired to create a multilingual and multiliteracy polity that boosts the students' achievement and to transform from a weak bilingual education where - French is taught as a subject- to a robust form of multilingual education which includes three languages Arabic, French, and English.

Bouteflika acknowledged publicly that Algeria is multicultural. His frequent use of the French language created confusion among advocators of monolingual policy (Benrabah, 2013). Bouteflika stated that "for Algeria, I will speak French, Spanish, and English, and, if necessary, Hebrew" (Benrabah, 2013, p.76). He further added that "it is unthinkable to...spend ten years studying pure science in Arabic when it would only take one year in English" (Benrabah, 2013, p.75). The president's perspective towards other languages appeared to implicitly acknowledge the failure of the Arabisation policy, especially in teaching scientific disciplines and promoting multilingualism. In all his public speeches, the president adopted bilingual fluency in Arabic and French; he was known as the ideal epitome of a bilingual Algerian citizen (Daoudi, 2018; Benrabah, 2013).

Benrabah (2004; 2013) advocated a 'bottom-up' approach to language education and planning, which was deemed to be more suitable for a multilingual context, like Algeria. This approach was later adopted by the Algerian Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific

Research in 2019, where they conducted an online survey about replacing French with English and considering it as the language of instruction. More than 90% of respondents expressed positive attitudes towards this decision. Subsequently, a second online survey was conducted to examine people's views and perspectives on the most effective approaches to implementing English. This decision was approved by many, and seen as a significant step towards de-Frenchification and a more globalised Algeria.

There were three main motives, which made the Algerian central power shift from monolingualism to multilingualism (Arabic, French, and English). Firstly, the 11th of September 2001 event put the Algerian authorities under strong pressure from the Western world to establish new educational reforms as part of the Global War against Terror (Karmani, 2005, cited in Benrabah, 2007a). Secondly, the transition to an economic market and internationalisation that was enforced by the economic reforms necessitated a reassessment of the monolingual educational system. Lastly, there were socio-political motives, which called for democratisation and linguistic minority rights (Benrabah, 2005).

The last two motives changed the political and economic policy of the Algerian government to be more politically and economically liberal and open towards other countries (Bellalem, 2012). The government's first mission was to open the Algerian economic market to other countries, particularly the UK and the USA. Henceforth, Algeria witnessed an increase in investments from America and Great Britain due to its gas and oil revenues (Bouhadiba, 2006).

The economic market led Algeria to opt for different political and economic reforms. Politically, a new policy of political pluralism was adopted. Economically, the reforms involved the reinforcement of private businesses and investments, where many investors were encouraged to import from China and Dubai (Bellalem, 2012). The second economic reform was to promote the tourism sector in Algeria, which could offer potential positions for those who have a good command of foreign languages. Therefore, the development of foreign languages, French and English, was a crucial condition to meet the economic targets.

In this respect, the educational reforms that were implemented in the educational system adopted globalisation and aimed to meet 21st-century educational requirements. Therefore, in 2004, the English language was given a prestigious status and reconsidered by Algerian youth as the language of prosperity and success (Bouhadiba, 2006). At that time, Algerian learners of English developed an interest in listening to American and British folksongs,

watching movies, and getting access to British Council activities, which helped them to develop their English language (Belmihoub, 2012). The learners' aim of learning English was not only for professional purposes but also to learn and explore the culture of that language (Bouhadiba, 2006). Furthermore, the spread of the English language in Algeria can be related to the extensive recruitment of teachers from different parts of the world (Pakistan, India, the UK, and the US), which assisted the learners to be motivated to gain a better cultural understanding of the differences between Algerian and other international cultures (Bouhadiba, 2006). Subsequently, many Algerian learners preferred to choose English as a major subject at university (Benrabah, 2014). In other words, Algerians' perspectives towards the French language have remarkably shifted. They believed that French is not the language of science, technology, and civilisation, calling policy-makers to re-evaluate the status of English by identifying it as a Second Foreign Language (SFL) while downgrading the status of French to a Foreign Language (FL). The rise of technology platforms and social media has provided Algerian teachers and learners with the opportunity to propagate the use of English (Mami, 2013; Belmihoub, 2015). Additionally, The US embassy and the British Council in Algeria have played a crucial role in encouraging and promoting English learning and usage, offering both teachers and learners of English with short abroad programs (Belmihoub, 2015). Miliani (2001) indicated that:

In a situation where the French language has lost much of its ground in the sociocultural and educational environments of the country, the introduction of English is being heralded as the magic solution to all possible ills-including economic, technological and education ones (2001, p.13).

In 2000, twenty-nine European countries gathered in Bologna and established what is called the Bologna Agreement. The agreement aimed at the unification of efforts to face internal and external challenges, to increase diversification in higher education, and to promote mobility. In 2004-2005, the Bologna Declaration was introduced in Algeria in higher education by adopting what is called the LMD system (License, Master, and Doctorate). Algeria subscribed to the principles and rules of the Bologna Process to improve the quality of higher education and to make it compatible with the global system in general and with the European system in particular. In part, the intention was to create more space for learners' ambitions and to encourage mobility (Mami, 2013). The philosophy of teaching under the new

educational architecture (LMD system) stipulated the continual improvement of educators and the reinforcement of teacher's training using Information and Communication Technology (ICT) to create an effective and successful learning environment (Mami, 2013).

2.3 The Structure of the Educational System in Algeria

The educational system in Algeria is composed of two ministerial departments (Gustin, 2007, 2008). The Ministry of National Education (it is in charge of Primary Education, Lower Secondary Education, Middle School, and Secondary Education). During the first stages, learners are introduced to Arabic, French, and English respectively (the learning of Tamazight is introduced in some cities). The Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research (it is in charge of Higher Education). In university, most scientific streams are taught in French, leading to a transformation in the status of French from being a Second Language (SL) to becoming the primary language of instruction.

As the focus of this research is on higher education in Algeria, the study sheds light on the educational system and reforms that have been applied in Algerian Higher Education after independence.

2.4 Educational Reforms in Algerian Higher Education

Higher education plays a significant role in the development of any society. It is considered the cornerstone of any development drive of the country because it disseminates knowledge through research findings, promotes creativity and improvement, and reinforces wellbeing and citizenship (Benouar, 2013). Within this context, Algeria adopted an open education policy, which permits and provides education for all categories of society. The educational system is free of charge in all educational public sectors, and the Algerian state takes full responsibility for providing all the services for students such as accommodation, grants, and transportation (Mohamed and Brahim, 2010). Furthermore, all students who pass their final secondary examination (Baccalaureate) are promptly offered a seat at the university. Achieving all these goal strategies has given the state great responsibilities to ensure a successful continuity of projects that can accommodate a great number of students arriving at university each year. Thus, Algerian Higher Education relied on applying massification policies that favoured quantity over quality.

2.4.1 The Early Independence Reform

The first reform extends from the Algerian independence in 1962 until 1971. In this phase, the Algerian Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research was established in Algiers, which was assigned the task of supervising and promoting Algerian Higher Education. The effect of French colonialism remained in this period. The educational structure and policy were carried through three main phases: the first stage was composed of three years of study towards a post-Baccalaureate certificate; the second phase was composed of one year long and the students who passed were awarded what is called in French Diplôme d'Études; the third phase where the student can get a Doctorat de Troisième Cycle and then a Doctorat D'État.

2.4.2 Higher Education Reform of 1971

The Algerian University at this stage has witnessed different transformations:

- Reconstruction of the educational system of Algerian higher education in all aspects (its construction, the way it operates, and its philosophy of education) (Lakehal, 2008). This Reform of higher education entails three major goals: democratisation, Arabisation, and Algerianisation. After the independence of Algeria, the Algerian authorities assured to algerianise the educational system. They used education as a vehicle to implant Algerian pride and prejudice in the students' identity (Benrabah, 2013).
- Offering training to a huge number of individuals at a lower cost.
- A large increase in the number of enrolments.
- Extension in the number of the Algerian university networks (from one University to fifty-five higher education establishments which includes thirteen universities, and sixteen high schools) (Djeflat,1992).

2.4.3 The Third Reform of the LMD System

The last decade viewed an enormous quantitative evolution of higher education in Algeria. There was tremendous growth in its infrastructure in terms of material and human. This growth in quantity was followed by a series of problems and issues that led to a gradual deterioration of the teaching and learning quality at the Algerian university level. Furthermore, there was a clear contradiction between social and market demands and what the Algerian university produced. This fact justified the malfunctioning of the Algerian classical system (former system) that was implemented in Algerian Higher Education since

independence. The former system includes four years of Bachelor's, two years in Magister, and at least four years of Doctorate system. The objectives of the former system did not respond to the challenges imposed by the changing situation of economic and politics of the Algerian society in particular and within the European countries in general. The changing situation led the government of Algeria and policymakers to re-think the educational system of Algeria and introduce a new advanced system that responds to the socioeconomic mutations, environmental and technological needs, and contributes to the development of the country. Algeria adopted a ready-made European system that is known as the LMD system (licence-Master-Doctorate) in 2004/2005. This system aimed to enhance the quality of the Algerian Higher Education and promote multiple diverse trainings and linking them with economic and social sectors.

The implementation of the new educational system encountered great pressure, it was indispensable and urgent to change the Algerian educational system to cope with the expectations of the 21st century and with the global trend of higher education (Benadla, 2013; Djebbari, 2016).

The LMD system was adopted by the Algerian authorities to change the Algerian educational structure from institutes into faculties following the French educational structure and to improve the quality of education (Mohamed and Brahim, 2010). However, EFL teachers still facing challenges in implementing this new system. Many researchers in the field of education have deemed this reform as inadequate in the context of Algeria. Several drawbacks of the LMD system in Algeria have been demonstrated by Metatla (2016):

- The focus on massification policies prioritised quantity over quality, resulting in a lack of proper mechanisms for ensuring quality. Consequently, students were more inclined to prioritise obtaining degrees rather than acquiring the necessary skills for their future careers.
- Algerian Higher Education Institutions lacked autonomy as government policies managed higher education, leaving limited decision-making power to the institutions themselves.
- While Europe introduced the LMD system to improve the quality of education and to foster mutual identity, Algeria predominantly focused on adopting an identical vision similar to that of more developed countries, rather than developing an innovative program that corresponds with Algeria's socio-economic profile.

- Lack of resources, training, and the complete absence of technology (Bouhadiba, 2013) were all challenges that contributed significantly to hindering the integration of intercultural communicative competence in EFL higher education in Algeria.

2.5 Concluding the chapter

This chapter provides comprehensive historical events that were essential in shaping the Algerian educational system. It also demonstrates the complexities of the language situation in Algeria, which went through three phases, colonial, post-colonial and contemporary Algeria. The first phase examines the Algerian educational system under the Frenchification policy (1830-1962). The second phase covers the period from 1962 to 1993, characterised by the implementation of the Arabisation policy (monolingualism). The third phase coincided with the emergence of a free global economic market, which required the use of English, during which the Algerian authorities acknowledged the failure of the Arabisation policy and the educational system in general (Benrabah, 2007a). It also provides insights into the new educational reform (LMD) that was applied in Algerian Higher Education in 2003 to improve the quality of teaching and learning. However, the implementation of this reform was inefficient within the Algerian context.

Chapter Three

Literature Review

3.1 Introduction

This study explores Algerian English language teachers' and learners' perspectives and conceptions of culture and intercultural communicative competence (ICC) in the East and West Universities in Algeria. It also investigates the Global Representative of Culture members' experiences and perceptions of establishing an intercultural club at West University, and how it promotes ICC in language education.

In the previous chapter, a brief historical background about Algeria and its educational system during the colonial and postcolonial eras was provided. This chapter provides the theoretical foundation of the present research by critically reviewing the relevant literature. It also presents a comprehensive summary of the previous studies conducted by other scholars in the realm of interculturality. This chapter is divided into three main sections. Given the significance of the notion of culture in this study, it is essential to first provide clear definitions and understandings of the concept of culture, its aspects, and its interconnectedness with language. The position of culture in FLT and L and the shift from the traditional approach (cultural turn) of imparting general cultural knowledge to intercultural language teaching approaches (intercultural turn) is discussed in this chapter. The second section delves into the historical background of intercultural communicative competence, where the notion of ICC and its dimensions are introduced. The third section provides a comprehensive discussion about ICC in practice. This chapter ends by providing a comprehensive review of recent empirical studies on the significance of teaching and learning ICC in various contexts, including the Algerian context and other contexts.

3.2 Definitions of Culture

The task of defining culture has proven to be complex and challenging for several scholars and researchers across various academic disciplines (Williams, 1983; Banks, 2002; Kramsch 2003; Eagleton, 2016). Despite the difficulties, numerous attempts have been made, and continue to be made to develop a comprehensive definition and gain a deeper understanding of this intricate concept. Numerous scholars recognised the need to establish a comprehensive definition. Therefore, they have categorised culture into two different types:

the big culture “big C”, and the small culture “little c” (Chastain, 1976, p.338; Dodd, 1998; Doyé, 1999; Peterson, 2004; Lee, 2009; Kramersch, 2013; Kun, 2013). The former was correlated with a broad understanding and knowledge of art, history, and literature. Holliday (2019) referred to them as “cultural artefacts” (p.5). These aspects are linked to "our culture" or national culture, although they may differ among smaller subgroups within a particular community and can be shared and learned across various cultural contexts (p.5).

According to Kramersch (2012), capital C is considered a traditional approach to language teaching. Furthermore, big C can be defined as the culture that encompasses factual information and statistics associated with various aspects of a particular society, including arts, history, geography, education, festivals, traditions, and customs (Weaver, 1986; Triandis, 1989; Dodd, 1998). This definition of culture is considered a conventional essentialist structural and generalised perspective in which cultures were identified based on nations and cultural differences. However, this perspective is no longer considered acceptable and lacks validity in many nations due to the increasing multiculturalism and cultural diversity seen in numerous countries (Jandt, 2013). In this sense, the term culture encompasses various entities such as nationalities, regions, and countries, and it may extend beyond the multiple regions and nations. Thus, the definition and the usage of the notion of culture may vary depending on the context. Several scholars argue against perceiving culture as solely factual information about a particular nation or using it as a synonym for a country (Barili and Byram, 2021), which is transmitted through language (Bennett, 2004; Byram, 2006; Kramersch, 2008). They stated that adopting such perspective may potentially cultivate essentialist and culturalist perspectives in the fields of research and education. However, little c refers to the everyday aspects of life, it encompasses all elements that constitute a comprehensive way of life. According to Lee (2009), this particular type of culture represents the invisible and deeper aspects of a specific culture, including different attitudes, beliefs, behaviours, and assumptions. Small “c” encompasses various elements such as viewpoints, perceptions, tastes, preferences, clothing styles, body posture, and gestures (Peterson, 2004). In other words, the little “c” culture has gained a significant relevance since the 80’s. It encompasses all aspects of people’s ways of life, including behaviours, eating habits, language use, and beliefs (Kramersch, 2012). Additionally, the individual’s beliefs, actions, and social interactions contribute to their self-identification through specific patterns of behaviours, attitudes, and traditions that are passed and transmitted through generations (Kun, 2013). In this study, I

look at the concept of culture from an anthropological perspective due to the interlinked relationship between language and culture, which has gained significant attention in the field of cultural anthropology (Risager, 2006). This perspective aligns with a strong connection with constructivist ideology by adopting an anti-essentialist perspective of culture, which views culture as an ongoing and dynamic process of re-creation that prevails through the continuous reshaping and renewal of social activities. In the same sense, culture is characterised as a dynamic entity that is in constant change and development (Spisak, 2009; Baker, 2009a; Byram, 2003). Elsen and St John (2007) demonstrated that if culture is viewed as a dynamic process of creating meaning in teaching foreign languages, the intercultural English language teachers' competence would involve navigating complex and unpredictable processes that contribute to promoting a deeper understanding and awareness of diverse perspectives (Witte, 2011).

Despite the numerous definitions of culture, it is crucial for teachers of FL to encourage learners to engage in cultural discussions (Frank, 2013). For instance, students can be guided through activities that enable them to reflect on aspects related to their native culture, such as how people think, perceive, make, and do things. According to Frank (2013), the key dimensions that students can be guided through are:

- What behaviours reflect our cultures?
- What influences our cultures?
- What is unique and different about our cultures?
- What are the values that shape our cultures?
- How does understanding cultures facilitate human co-existence?
- What symbols are prevalent in our culture?

Enabling students to engage in discussions on different topics about cultures within the classroom, encouraging them to consider their own culture, and establishing connections between diverse cultures. Creating an environment that promotes intercultural understanding can be achieved by allowing students to construct and share their own understanding of the notion of culture instead of passively feeding them a pile of information about specific nations or teaching them facts about grammar and history (Byram, 2008; Frank, 2013).

3.3 Aspects of Culture

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Figure 1 : Iceberg illustration of surface and deep culture (Patel et al., 2011)

Huebener (1965) suggested that culture can be understood through various lenses. The sociological aspect of culture encompasses aspects such as geography, civilizations, and economics. Additionally, the artistic dimension of culture encompasses diverse forms of expression, including music and art. The last dimension pertains to the anthropological orientation of culture, including many facets of human behavioural patterns, including conventions, daily life routines, quality of living, religion, and language.

The capital C culture or the surface culture represents the visible aspects of culture that distinguish one particular group from the other (Holliday, 2013; Kramsch, 2013; Holtzman and Sharpe, 2014). This perspective of culture is limited and bounded as it fails to include the values, beliefs, and attitudes of other cultures. On the other hand, the small c culture or subjective culture, according to Triandis (1989), offers a broader understanding, referring to the way of life, the ways of thinking, habits, values, and beliefs of a particular nation. In contrast to the big C culture, small c culture encompasses invisible and intangible elements of culture that lie at a deeper level. Little c culture, in fact, is more comprehensive and larger than capital C culture, as one can possess extensive knowledge about a particular culture, but still lack the ability to effectively communicate with its members. In a similar vein, Dodd (1998) presented a framework for understanding culture, dividing it into three main categories: the inner core which involves values, identity, beliefs, and attitudes; the

intermediate layer which encompasses the cultural practices, such as art, rituals, communication; and the outer layer which covers broader cultural systems of education, politics, religion, family and other different aspects, which describe a specific culture. Although Dodd's (1998) categorisation seems comprehensive, I argue that the significance of religion can differ among diverse cultural groups. Al-Omari (2015) presented an angle that perceives culture within a group as an amalgamation of two key elements: behaviours and attitudes. Behaviours tackle the query of "what is happening", while attitudes explain the motivations driving these behaviours. Educating students about both aspects of culture can be perplexing and demanding in the foreign language (FL) classroom. As a result, educators frequently choose to emphasise components of big C culture, asserting that teaching small c culture poses difficulties and challenges.

To provide a clear understanding of both tangible and intangible aspects of culture, Hall (1976) developed a conceptual framework that aimed at enhancing students' comprehension of the elements of culture. The analogy coined by Hall (1976) is commonly referred to as the "cultural iceberg". This analogy drew a comparison between the notions of culture and iceberg. This analogy has been employed to assist individuals who are transitioning into a new cultural environment to distinguish between the visible elements of culture (referred to as the tip of the iceberg) and the largest portion of culture which remains less invisible and unseen, such as the behavioural patterns of a specific culture (referred to as the submerged part of the iceberg). As it is demonstrated in the iceberg, visible and invisible facets of culture are interconnected, with the invisible component forming the foundation. These definitions are crucial as they suggest that successful intercultural communication hinges on recognising the numerous invisible factors that influence communication behaviour. According to Dignen and Chamberlain (2009), it is crucial to be aware of the invisible aspects of culture to prevent them from unexpectedly emerging and causing tensions and misunderstandings. The contemporary understanding of culture portrays it as a dynamic and ever-evolving concept, consistently being reshaped. Although culture has always been subject to change, the speed of transformation has amplified owing to heightened interactions between individuals from diverse cultural backgrounds, facilitated by technological progress, immigration, information exchange, and other related elements (Bruner, 1997; Byram, 2003; Baker, 2009a; Spisak, 2009). In today's interconnected globalised world, where the delineations of national cultures

are gradually fading and cultural experiences seem to merge, a reassessment of the concept of culture holds immense importance. Based on the existing literature, it is suggested that culture is something that unites and divides people, and its definition significantly depends on its context. A definition that holds meaning and validity in one context can vary across different contexts. Culture can be regarded as a power that unifies people and brings them together, simultaneously it necessitates interactions due to the existence of diverse cultures. Through culture, individuals share common ideas, customs, values, and beliefs that shape their identities. Culture at its core is socially constructed and crafted by humans for specific purposes, within particular contexts and times. People acquire culture through their interactions and engagements with others and their surroundings.

In the current globalised era, classifying or categorising the notion of culture separately and as a detached entity from other cultures is considered to be illogical and inconsistent, as we frequently observe the amalgamation of different cultural traits and features, which gives birth to hybrid cultures (Al Mawoda, 2011). As a result, individuals may belong to different associations that can be considered as cultures. For example, in addition to being affiliated with a particular nationality or ethnic culture, people's identities are collectively influenced and classified by variables such as gender, race, socioeconomic status, academic achievement, and other diverse aspects. To conduct a comprehensive investigation of intercultural communication skills, it is important to get a thorough comprehension and understanding of all facets of culture. Hence, the present study adopts a comprehensive definition of culture proposed by Spencer-Oatey and Franklin (2009), including the previously discussed definitions of culture. Culture is shown as a conceptual framework that manifests via several forms of patterns, some of which are more explicit and visible than others. They also stressed that culture is intricately linked to social groupings, however, it is important to note that no two individuals within the same group share identical cultural qualities. In academic discourse, culture is commonly understood as a term that is socially produced, and acquired via social interactions and communication. It has a significant role in shaping individuals' behaviours and their perceptions of others' behaviours.

3.4 The relationship between language and cultural

The relationship between culture and language has been extensively recognised in the literature of Foreign Language Teaching (FLT) during the past few decades. The nature of this relationship continues to be a subject of debate. Several scholars, such as Kramsch (1993), Byram (1991, 1997), Risager (2006, 2007), and Liddicoat and Scarino (2013), have emphasised the need to integrate culture into the field of foreign language teaching and learning (FLT and L). The prevailing perspective believes that language is an integral component of culture, as it serves as a medium through which culture is socially formed, transmitted, and expressed (Brown, 1986, 2014; Byram, 1991, 1997; Kramsch, 1993, 2011, 2015; Risager, 2006; Baker, 2012). Language, communication patterns and behaviours are strongly affected by the cultural contexts in which the individuals exist. The primary mode of interaction occurs through language (Seelye, 1988). Nevertheless, it is important to note that speaking the same language does not necessarily imply sharing the same culture.

Sapir (1921) argued that individuals who share the same language may be affiliated with distinct cultural groups. For example, there might be significant variations in cultural practises between the MENA (Middle East and North Africa) countries or English-speaking nations, despite the commonality of an official language (Arabic for the former and English for the latter). The linkage between cultural awareness and national cultures, regardless of whether they are native or foreign, has seen criticism, notably when considering the English Language, given its global status as a lingua franca (LF) (Baker, 2012). This study explores the intricate relationship between language and culture in the context of teaching English as a Foreign Language, based on participants' perspectives from the East and West Universities. Language serves as both a cultural practice and a mechanism for the construction of culture. Thus, the acquisition of a second or a foreign language involves individuals gaining access to the cultural practices associated with that particular language. According to Kayman (2004) and Fanon (1967), the process of acquiring language proficiency involves the assimilation and adoption the cultural norms and values, as the language one speaks often mirrors and reflects certain cultural attributes of a social group. However, Jandt (2013) criticised this viewpoint, suggesting that within a society, diverse sub-cultures can coexist with different values, norms, and behavioural regulations despite sharing a common language (Baker, 2012; Jandt, 2013).

It was important to study the link between language and culture in depth because of its importance in analysing intercultural dialogue and its role in teaching and learning English as a Foreign Language (FLT and L). What is also crucial and relevant to my study is the recognition that cultures differ whether these differences are within societies or across international boundaries, these disparities can impact the quality of communication. All facets of culture can be observed in human interactions during communication. Effective communication between diverse cultures can be challenging if individuals are unaware of the cultural differences, or fail to recognise the potential existence of such differences, as well as lacks strategies to navigate between them. Here are some examples of cultural misunderstandings I encountered. There were situations where I had the necessary linguistic skills to communicate, but I lacked awareness of the cultural differences.

I recall encountering several cultural misunderstandings while working on a project with an Indian friend. During our discussion, I noticed he was nodding repeatedly as I shared my thoughts. In my culture, nodding is a sign of agreement; therefore, I assumed we shared the same understandings and viewpoints. However, later I realised that in Indian culture, a nod indicates that the person is attentively listening but not necessarily agreeing. Unawareness of such cultural differences might cause misinterpretation, leading to cultural misunderstandings.

Another incident that caused cultural confusion was related to hospitality. In my culture, hospitality is paramount. When guests visit, it is normal to offer food or drinks multiple times to make sure the guests are not shy to eat or drink. I hosted a small gathering at my place in the UK and offered food several times to my guests, who were mostly from different cultural backgrounds. I was surprised that some of them seemed uncomfortable and kept politely declining. I later realised that repeated offers might be perceived as insistence or pressure, whereas I was simply trying to be a good host by Algerian standards. At first, not being aware of such cultural differences led to some awkward moments where I felt my hospitality was not being appreciated. However, later when I started developing intercultural attitudes towards different cultures, I realised that what is accepted in my culture is not necessarily accepted in other cultures. These experiences and many others emphasised the importance of developing intercultural understanding and respecting different cultural norms.

Developing communicative competence (mastering language skills) alone is insufficient for navigating intercultural interactions.

3.5 Approaches to Teaching Culture

Investigating the approaches and ways of teaching culture in the East and West Universities in Algeria is crucial to be examined in this research study. I am going to explore Algerian English language teachers and learners' perspectives and conceptions about how they approach culture in FLT and L context, as this can provide insights into their inclinations towards intercultural English language pedagogy. Therefore, understanding the various approaches used in teaching English within the language curriculum and shedding light on the pedagogical approaches of teaching culture is fundamental.

In the scope of this study, the first pertinent approach is Liddicoat and Kollner's (2012) categorisation of two directions of teaching culture. The first can be referred to as cultural orientation or traditional approach, which emphasises the knowledge of culture as an external subject to be taught to students and treated as a separate subject. The second tendency advocates for an "intercultural language teaching approach" (Liddicoat and Scarino, 2013, p.8). This approach emphasises transformational interaction and the cultivation of intercultural identity via encounters with various cultures. This involves exploring, questioning, and reshaping "the boundaries between the self and the other" (Liddicoat and Kollner, 2012, p. 79). The integration of an intercultural lens within the context of English as a Foreign Language does not undermine the value of the knowledge and practices that have been emphasised in the teaching of culture over many years. Contrary to teachers' perceptions, moving towards intercultural language teaching entails the implementation of an intercultural teaching approach while still incorporating communicative activities that can be modified to facilitate the development of intercultural awareness (Corbett, 2003). Therefore, within the Algerian context, it is essential for teachers to acknowledge that their preference for the teaching of communicative competence may serve as a beneficial basis for the development of intercultural education in Algeria.

Crozet et al., (1999) have identified two approaches to teaching culture in language education: the traditional paradigm and the intercultural teaching paradigm. Remarkably,

Liddicoat and Scarino (2013) have proposed a revised and expanded traditional approach to culture as a “national attribute” (p.18). However, one notable limitation of this paradigm is its reductionist and oversimplified perspective on culture that may result in reinforcing stereotypes and prejudices. In other words, culture is perceived as a simplified and unchallenged concept, reduced to a particular political and national geography (Liddicoat and Scarino, 2013). Consequently, this perspective promotes a positivist and narrow understanding of culture, which restricts learners' opportunities for critical thinking and developing the necessary intercultural skills that are required for promoting intercultural understanding.

3.5.1 The Traditional Approach

The primary focus of the traditional paradigm is on literature as a revered artifact representing a particular society. The notion of cultural competence in foreign language education is commonly understood as the mastery of a specific body of literature “canon literature” (Crozet et al., 1999; Liddicoat and Scarino, 2013, p. 19). This perspective is based on the belief that students acquire knowledge about old civilisations and the art of literature associated with the target culture primarily through reading (Flewellling, 1993). However, it remains uncertain whether the study of culture under this traditional paradigm was primarily aimed at an educated upper class, capable of understanding the complex details of literary works and participating in in-depth discussions of fiction and non-fiction narratives. This approach might have restricted the effectiveness of culture and language teaching and learning to specific audiences, focusing solely on the tip of the iceberg or the capital C elements of culture. In practice, the traditional paradigm of teaching language and culture failed to consider the diverse backgrounds and practices of learners in relation to the external world, where there are variations in language and cultural practises (Hall, 2012). Rather, the emphasis was on conveying factual knowledge about individuals who belong to the target culture. Importantly, this perspective aligns with the cognitive view of culture, perceiving culture as a reservoir of information that individuals hold about a particular society (Kramersch, 1993; Byram, 1997; Fenner, 2008; Scarino, 2010; Kiss, 2018). This approach has been criticised by several scholars.

3.6 Intercultural Communicative Competence Approach (ICC) in Language Teaching

3.6.1 Communicative Competence

Researchers and educators became aware of the necessity of effective communication, leading to the occurrence of pragmatic reform later in the 20th century. This reform brought about a significant change in the objective of foreign language teaching (FLT), shifting the emphasis from linguistic competence (LC) to placing greater importance on communicative competence (CC). Educators realised that there is a difference between being able to construct grammatically accurate sentences in a particular language and the ability to implement them in real-life scenarios (Doyé, 1999). Communicative competence (CC) was first presented by Hymes (1972), who provided a definition that encompasses the understanding of grammatical principles as well as the proper use of language within certain contextual settings. The introduction of CC can be viewed as a response to Chomsky's theory of linguistic competence (Chomsky, 1965; 1957). As Hymes (1972) argued acquiring a second language involves more than just acquiring linguistic competence, which refers to the mastery of grammatical rules. It also involves the development of the ability to use the language appropriately and effectively within a cultural context (Byram, 1988). Essentially, CC stressed the significance of sociocultural knowledge, asserting that it exceeds linguistic proficiency, and pertains to the understanding of the optimal timing, location, and interlocutors for effective communication (Brown, 2007). Canale and Swain (1980) expanded upon Hymes's (1972) conceptual framework by presenting a model of communicative competence that encompasses four distinct components: grammatical competence, sociolinguistic competence, strategic competence, and discourse competence. First, grammatical competence involves having a grasp of the language's structure, encompassing grammar, vocabulary, and phonology. It is alternatively referred to as linguistic competence in accordance with Van Ek (1986).

Second, sociolinguistic competence refers to an individual's understanding of the sociocultural norms and regulations in specific contexts. To elaborate, this competence encompasses the examination of how language is appropriately used in various contexts. It represents an individual's ability to adjust their speech to suit the specific context in which they are communicating (Brown, 2007). Third, strategic competence involves knowledge of communication strategies to effectively handle communication breakdowns. It specifically

pertains to the individual's ability to navigate challenges in recalling a term, expression, or particular grammatical structure (Canale and Swain, 1980). Fourth, discourse competence, on the other hand, focuses on the organization of phrases, sentences, and words to establish coherent communication and various linguistic expressions. The process entails the skill to integrate grammatical structures and semantic interpretations in order to generate coherent oral or written compositions (Canale and Swain, 1980). According to Brown (2007), discourse competence refers to the ability to establish coherence between phrases, generating a coherent and meaningful whole from individual utterances. Van Ek (1986) made an important contribution to the area of foreign language teaching and learning (FLT and L) by emphasising the importance of communicative competence (CC) as a fundamental concept in the development of communicative language education. The dominant approach in foreign language education for the past three decades has been communicative competence, which is currently employed by most educators and learners as evidenced by the prevalent use of textbooks that adhere to this methodology (Aguilar, 2009). However, Hymes's conception of communicative competence (1972) has been subject to critique and investigation by other academics with differing perspectives throughout the years.

According to Spencer-Oatey and Frankin (2009), there exists a close relationship between Hymes's notion of communicative competence and the concept of appropriateness. They noted that within the realm of foreign language instruction, there has been a tendency to assess appropriateness by using native speakers of the target language as the benchmark. However, this viewpoint has faced recent criticism from scholars such as Spencer-Oatey and Franklin (2009), Byram (1997), and Alptekin (2002). They argue that regarding the native speaker as the ultimate model is unrealistic and, at times, undesirable for language learners. This is because a significant number of English speakers globally do not have English as their first language (Savignon, 2009). In contemporary intercultural exchanges, it is common for native speakers to be absent or for both participants to possess distinct social identities. Consequently, the manner in which these individuals engage with each other deviates from the usual dynamics observed in conversations involving individuals of the same nationality and language (Spencer-Oatey and Frankin, 2009). According to Alptekin (2002), the conventional paradigm of communicative competence, which heavily relies on the competency of native speakers, is no longer appropriate or sufficient for acquiring and using

an international language in intercultural settings. In a similar vein, Byram (1997) and Van Ek (1986) raised concerns over Hymes' (1972) limited consideration of the cultural dimension in communication, as his analysis primarily centred on the examination of social interactions within a certain social group. According to Alptekin (2002), the traditional approach of CC, which heavily relies on native speaker skills, is no longer sufficient for acquiring and using a global language in intercultural settings. According to Byram (1997) and Van Ek (1986), Hymes' analysis of social interaction and communication within a specific social group, employing a single language, failed to consider the influence of culture on communication. However, misunderstandings and misinterpretations often arise not only from the shortage of language skills but also from cultural differences. Therefore, Van Ek (1986) expanded the communicative competence concept to introduce two additional components: social competence and sociocultural competence. Social competence refers to an individual's capacity and willingness to engage in interpersonal interactions. It covers having the necessary skills, motivation, attitude, autonomy, tolerance, and the ability to navigate in various contexts (Aguilar, 2009). Sociocultural competence, on the other hand, refers to having an awareness of the sociocultural milieu within which each language is embedded and serves as a reference frame for its speakers. It involves understanding and using reference forms that may differ significantly from those of the foreign language learner. This sociocultural knowledge covers various aspects of everyday life, historical, social, taboos, and behavioural norms (Reid, 2014). As a result, there has been a reassessment of the significance of culture within the context of foreign language instruction, recognising its central role in learners' acquisition of communicative competence.

According to Moore (1996), the concept of culture has been traditionally perceived as providing learners with contextual basic knowledge about the countries of the target culture, focusing on tangible and visible elements such as food, festivals, and other physical aspects of culture. However, there has been a gradual shift in focus from the surface culture, as previously discussed, towards a more profound examination of the concepts, principles, and actions that are collectively embraced by individuals within a given community or social collective. Several researchers, including Byram (1997) and Graddol (2006), have expressed criticism towards Van Ek's conceptualisation of communicative competence, arguing that it

does not adequately account for the scenario when two individuals who are not native speakers engage in communication in a context that is unfamiliar to them.

Byram et al (2013) asserted that the traditional emphasis on sociolinguistic appropriateness and politeness is insufficient and inadequate due to globalization, new technologies, and refugee migration. This statement posits that the notion of intercultural communicative competence poses a challenge to the dominant assumption of native speaker norms in the field of CC as discussed by Spencer-Oatey and Franklin (2009) and Byram (2006). The use of NS as a learning model is viewed as impractical and occasionally undesirable for learners because, in the current global context, English serves as a means for individuals from various linguistic and cultural backgrounds, whose native language is not English, to engage in communication and negotiate meaning (Sakuragi, 2008).

3.6.2 What is ICC

The notion of intercultural communicative competence expands upon the concept of communicative competence, placing particular focus on its implementation within the context of foreign language instruction (Byram, 1997). According to Baker (2015), there are instances where ICC and IC are used interchangeably, however, this particular interpretation dismisses intercultural interactions that include a second or even a third language, as well as the vital role of language as a mediator in communication (Fantini, 2012; Baker, 2015).

In line with Hismanoglu's (2011) perspective, ICC pertains to the comprehension of cultural variations in communication across distinct speech communities, along with the skills to decode and effectively navigate these distinctions. According to Guilherme (2000), the concept of intercultural communicative competence (ICC) refers to an individual's ability to engage in successful interactions with others from diverse cultural backgrounds. That is to say, Intercultural competence (ICC) encompasses an individual's awareness of diverse beliefs and behaviours shown by others, as well as their ability to effectively navigate these dissimilarities without bias or judgment. In the same vein, Reid (2015) demonstrated that respect and understanding of cultures is paramount in today's globalised world as it enables individuals to deconstruct stereotypes and eradicate discrimination among people from diverse cultural backgrounds. The role of ICC in English language education is to provide both

educators and students with the necessary skills to comprehend and engage in successful and culturally sensitive communication with individuals of diverse cultural backgrounds.

As ICC is the core of this research, I define it as the ability to successfully engage in communication and interpersonal exchanges with individuals who have different cultural backgrounds. This definition aligns with Byram's (1997) definition of ICC, he defined it as "the ability to communicate and interact across cultural boundaries" (p.7) This definition proposed by Byram (1997) occupies a prominent and significant position within the field of ICC and serves as the fundamental basis for the present study. Although Byram's work has been extended, this definition remains fundamental as it suits the objectives of this study. I believe, that in the current era of globalisation, language education should put the development of learners' intercultural communicative competence at the top of the list (Byram, 1997; Sercu, 2006; Baker, 2011) to prepare them for successful intercultural interactions.

Byram's (1997) work initially had a considerable influence on language classrooms globally. Nevertheless, the definition of ICC has been expanded by Byram et al (2002), who viewed it as "the ability to ensure a shared understanding by people of different social identities, and the ability to interact with people as complex human beings with multiple identities and their individuality" (p.10). They acknowledged the importance of understanding the diverse cultural values and beliefs of individuals from different cultures to effectively engage with them, emphasising the need for sensitivity to foster mutual understanding (Byram et al., 2002).

3.7 Bennett's Model of Intercultural Sensitivity Development

The Developmental Model of Intercultural Sensitivity (DMIS), created by Milton J. Bennett (1993), explains how people understand and interact with different cultures. It's based on the idea that our experiences are shaped by how we perceive the world. The model outlines six stages that individuals go through as they become more culturally aware and competent. The first stage, Denial, involves a lack of recognition and unawareness of cultural differences. Second, in Defence, individuals acknowledge cultural differences but view them as negative or bad. In the Minimisation stage, people believe that all cultures are similar, downplaying or disregarding significant differences. The Acceptance stage is where individuals begin to appreciate and understand cultural differences. In the Adaptation stage, people can adjust

their behaviour and communication to interact effectively in different cultural contexts. This model helps explain the progression toward greater intercultural competence. Finally, the integration stage is where individuals embrace and integrate cultural differences into their interactions and processes (Bennett, 1986; 1993; 2004; Landis et al., 2004; Bennett and Hammer, 2017; Paige et al., 2003; Barron and Dasli, 2010).

- **Denial**

During the Denial stage of the Developmental Model of Intercultural Sensitivity (DMIS), individuals frequently exhibit a lack of awareness or refusal to acknowledge cultural distinctions. They may perceive others solely as foreigners or minorities without comprehending the intricacies of many cultures. They possess a more intricate perception of their own culture, which leads them to perceive themselves as more authentic than others. This might result in apathy or even animosity towards intercultural interactions. Within organisations, Denial can manifest as a lack of rules or procedures aimed at effectively managing cultural diversity. When individuals are suddenly confronted with cultural disparities, such as through immigration or a shifting workforce, they may initially encounter difficulties. However, as time progresses, they might gradually develop a more refined and detailed perception of others. This transformation can occur either through interpersonal engagements or by the acknowledgement of variety by organisations, such as providing materials in different languages or incorporating varied imagery in their publications (Bennett, 1986; Landis et al., 2004; Bennett and Hammer, 2017; Paige et al., 2003; Barron and Dasli, 2010).

- **Defence**

After surpassing the stage of Denial, individuals move to the Defence stage, during which they acknowledge differences in culture but perceive them through a lens of us vs. them. Other individuals are currently more noticeable, but they are frequently perceived and judged based on preconceived notions and generalisations. During this phase, individuals may engage in cultural criticism and develop a sense of cultural superiority, perceiving their own culture as superior to others. Reversal is a form of Defence in which individuals idealise a different culture and perceive their own as being inferior. Within organisations, Defence can manifest itself through rhetoric that praises the superiority of its own culture or through actions rooted

on stereotypes. The conflict in this stage arises from perceiving cultural differences as a danger, which might result in the separation or exclusion of some groups. Resolving Defence entails prioritising shared values and can be achieved in organisations through team-building activities that highlight interdependence and acknowledge individual differences as variations (Bennett, 1986; 1993; Landis et al., 2004; Bennett and Hammer, 2017; Paige et al., 2003; Barron and Dasli, 2010).

- **Minimisation**

In the Minimisation stage, individuals begin to diminish the significance of cultural distinctions and instead prioritise what they perceive as commonalities. Oftentimes, individuals tend to presume that their own experiences and values are universally shared. This results in a perception of tolerance, where differences are regarded as minor variations from universal human patterns. Nevertheless, this method has the potential to obscure underlying cultural disparities and challenges, both at the individual and organisational levels. Within organisations, this could entail excessively prioritising equal opportunity while disregarding persistent cultural biases. When individuals or institutions are compelled to address substantial cultural disparities, it can lead to unease or even a regression to the previous phase of defence. Resolving this issue requires carefully considering and managing the acknowledgement of both commonalities and distinctions while promoting both unity and diversity (Bennett, 1986; Landis et al., 2004; Bennett and Hammer, 2017; Paige et al., 2003; Barron and Dasli, 2010).

- **Acceptance**

During the Acceptance stage, individuals acknowledge that cultural differences are similarly complex as their own cultural norms. They acknowledge the existence of these differences, even if they are not necessarily in agreement with them. Contrary to previous stages, their judgements do not rely on making comparisons solely within the context of their own culture. Individuals at this phase have curiosity towards diverse cultures and possess desire to acquire further knowledge. However, they may encounter difficulties in completely adjusting their conduct within varying cultural environments. While organisations may prioritise the promotion of "diversity and inclusion," they have not yet made intercultural sensitivity a crucial aspect of leadership. The challenge at hand is establishing a delicate balance between respecting cultural variations and making ethical evaluations, all while avoiding the trap of

ethnocentric reasoning (Bennett, 1986; Landis et al., 2004; Bennett,2004; Bennett and Hammer, 2017; Paige et al., 2003; Barron and Dasli, 2010).

- **Adaptation**

Addressing moral issues enables adaptation to cultural variations. This entails the cognitive process of perspective-taking or empathy, wherein an individual can imaginatively simulate and understand the world from the perspective of another culture. This enables individuals to behave in a manner that is considered suitable within the specific cultural context. Biculturalism, like bilingualism, demonstrates this ability, resulting in proficient adaptation to diverse cultural environments. At this stage, organisations develop adaptable policies that effectively accommodate many cultures without imposing their own. The challenge in Adaptation is in the process of keeping authenticity. When individuals can navigate through several cultural situations, it prompts the inquiry of where their authentic identity resides. The solution entails broadening the notion of identity to be more dynamic and adaptable. For organisations, adaptation entails the genuine incorporation of both global and local diversity into their processes (Bennett, 1986; Landis et al., 2004; Bennett,2004; Bennett and Hammer, 2017; Paige et al., 2003; Barron and Dasli, 2010).

- **Integration**

Resolving the issue of authentic identity allows cultural differences to be smoothly integrated into communication. In this integrated state, communication can move between different cultural contexts, enabling effective intercultural communication. Personally, Integration feels like being in a flexible, in-between state, where one's sense of self includes shifting between different cultural perspectives. This ability can help build cultural bridges and facilitate advanced cross-cultural mediation. Organizations at this stage support creating "third-culture" approaches, where multicultural teams adapt to each other, leading to innovative solutions that add value (Bennett, 1986; Bennett and Hammer, 2017; Paige et al., 2003; Barron and Dasli, 2010).

Bennett's Developmental Model of Intercultural Sensitivity (DMIS) is closely connected to the cognitive, emotional, and behavioural aspects that are crucial for the development of intercultural competence. "Cognitive skills" involve cultural self-awareness, cultural general awareness, culture-specific awareness, and interaction analysis; "affective skills" encompass various cognitive and emotional abilities, such as curiosity, motivation, openness, and

flexibility; “behavioural skills” comprise interpersonal competencies, including relationship-building, active listening, problem-solving (2011, p.3).

The DMIS delineates a sequential progression consisting of six stages—Denial, Defence, Minimisation, Acceptance, Adaptation, and Integration—that elucidate individuals' perceptions and reactions to cultural differences (Bennett, 1986; 1993; 2004; 2011). As individuals progress through these stages, the cognitive aspect of intercultural competence undergoes substantial development (Bennett, 2011). During the initial phases, such as Denial and Defence, awareness of cultural differences is narrowed or negative. Some individuals may lack understanding of cultural differences or reject the reality that cultural diversity exists. However, when individuals progress to the phases of Minimisation, Acceptance and Adaptation, their cognitive comprehension improves. They start to acknowledge, value and appreciate the complexity of cultural differences, including their awareness of their own cultural biases. At these stages, individuals develop the knowledge and understanding of cultural differences, norms and values. They also develop the ability to thoroughly analyse, interpret, compare and comprehend differences that exist within different cultures (Bennett, 2011).

The affective aspect also evolves during the stages of DMIS. During the Defence stage, individuals may first experience unpleasant or negative emotions, such as fear or animosity, anxiety, and uncertainty when they encounter cultural differences. This emotional resistance frequently results in adopting a defensive position, where one's own culture is regarded as superior (the only right one) or inferior. As individuals go through various stages, notably reaching the level of Acceptance, Adaptation and integration, their emotional reactions shift from defensive modes to empathy, curiosity, and openness. Individuals at these stages experience an increased sense of comfort and positivity when interacting with individuals from different cultures. They also build the emotional flexibility and empathetic understanding necessary to properly navigate cultural diversity (Bennett, 2011).

The behavioural dimension necessitates the skills to effectively act and communicate across cultural barriers, and this ability also develops through DMIS stages. In the beginning, individuals may display inflexible, culturally specific behaviours that cannot be adjusted to fit other cultural situations. As individuals progress to the latter stages, such as Adaptation and Integration, their behaviour becomes more flexible and suitable in various cultural contexts (Bennett, 1993; 2004; Landis et al., 2004; Paige et al., 2003). The behavioural dimension

requires the practical application of both cognitive knowledge and affective attitudes in real-world interactions. Individuals acquire the ability to adapt their communication style, behaviour, and interactions to conform to the cultural standards of the individuals they are engaging with. This ensures that their behaviour is respectful and efficient in diverse cultural contexts (Bennett, 2011).

In my research, I have used four stages of DMIS, Denial, Defence, Minimisation and Acceptance to analyse participants from the East and West Universities' intercultural exposures to different cultures in different contexts. Teachers from the East University and some from the West University lacked awareness of cultural differences, which led them to encounter cultural shock. Given the short duration of the participants' exposure to diverse cultures, I did not focus on the last stages of the Model of Intercultural Sensitivity Development (Adaptation and Integration), as participants did not have the opportunity to fully adapt and integrate with the other cultures. In this research, Byram's model of Intercultural Communicative Competence (Byram, 1997) was employed as the main theoretical framework because of its relevance in the context of language education and communication. This model aligns more closely with the objectives of my research, which seeks to explore how intercultural communicative competence can be developed and promoted in language learning settings (classroom).

3.8 Byram's ICC Model

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Figure 2: ICC Dimensions Byram (1997)

The dimensions demonstrated in the aforementioned figure depict various intersecting elements of intercultural communicative competence (ICC) that are of great importance for educators and learners in the contemporary globalised world. In the present study, I am not going to focus on communicative competence, as it is the main objective to reach in teaching English as a foreign language in Algeria. In line with Byram's suggestion, our learners should be exposed to ICC dimensions. In other words, the model of intercultural communicative competence comprises four primary dimensions, namely attitudes, knowledge, skills, and critical cultural awareness/political education. In the following section, I explicate these ICC components developed by Byram (1997, 2006).

3.8.1 Attitudes (Savoir Être)

The first dimension of attitudes covers various aspects such as curiosity and openness, together with a willingness to set aside preconceived assumptions about other cultures and beliefs about one's own culture (Byram, 1997; Spencer-Oatey and Franklin, 2009; Byram, 2006). This could involve an eagerness and clarity to postpone scepticism "about other cultures and belief about one's own culture" (Byram, 1997, p.50). It is described by Byram (1997) as "the ability to decentre" (p.34). These attitudes significantly influence individuals' interactions with people from diverse cultures as they generally tend to shape their expectations (Guirdham, 2005). The expectations may arise due to issues such as cultural prejudice and stereotypes. Guirdham (2005) demonstrated that stereotypes are formed gradually through our culture and they are stored in our minds through the accumulation of information over time. Negative stereotypes generate negative expectations, which lead to a negative interpretation of the behaviours of people from different cultures. Therefore, the significance of attitude in Byram's model lies in its recognition as the primary determinant. This recognition stems from the understanding that developing the necessary attitudes towards oneself and other cultures represents the most difficult and demanding part of the pursuit of effective intercultural engagements (Sharifian, 2010; 2012). An intercultural competent speaker should not judge people based on their pre-existing stereotypes, refrain from making generalisations, and maintain an open mindset towards cultural differences. Within the framework of Foreign Language Teaching (FLT), learners can possess unfavourable attitudes towards other cultures that are presented to them. In such instances, it becomes the duty of the instructors to effectively handle and rectify any misunderstandings and

misconceptions that may emerge among the students within the classroom setting (Byram, 2003).

3.8.2 Knowledge (Savoirs)

The dimension of knowledge, referred to as *savoirs*, has two distinct categories that may be delineated within the context of intercultural dialogue. The first category relates to the cultures and social groups of both cultural groups, often gained through social interactions. The second category refers to the knowledge of cultural norms, values, beliefs, practices, and systems. This knowledge requires an understanding and awareness of the processes via which social identities are obtained and the manner in which individuals from various cultural backgrounds are perceived (Byram, 1997; 2006). Byram (2020) redefined this dimension by involving the importance of how other individuals from other cultural backgrounds view and perceive us, and our knowledge about other people's worldviews. It is also crucial to emphasise that other people could be living within or beyond our national boundaries. Redefining knowledge from acquiring knowledge about a specific country to reflect and gain insights on the context and the dynamic of communication is crucial when it comes to intercultural citizenship (Barili and Byram, 2021; Byram, 2020). In other words, *savoirs* entail understanding oneself and others by being aware of the rules governing individual and social communication. Furthermore, cultural knowledge is not bound to fixed or factual information, but also includes an understanding of the dynamic nature of cultures, recognizing that they evolve and change over time. It involves being aware of cultural variations within a single culture and across different cultural groups. This awareness allows individuals to navigate successfully in intercultural communication with a more open and flexible mindset. According to Byram "knowledge about social groups and their cultures in one's own country, and similar knowledge of the interlocutor's country on the one hand, and similar knowledge of the processes and interaction at individual and societal levels, on the other hand" (Byram, 1997, p.35). I agree with Byram's perspective that the second category of knowledge holds greater significance for successful intercultural communication, as emphasized by Hofstede et al (2010) "Awareness is where it all starts" (p.419). Similarly, Sercu et al. (2005) asserted that learning culture-specific knowledge about a particular group is not sufficient. Therefore, it is important to display mindfulness towards potential cultural disparities in the context of intercultural communication. In addition to possessing culture-

specific information, intercultural competent individuals need to acquire a certain level of culture-general knowledge, which enables them to engage with several different cultures.

3.8.3 Skills (Savoir Comprendre et Savoir Apprendre)

Skills are categorised into two groups, both competencies enable individuals to navigate and interact effectively in culturally diverse contexts. The first category refers to the skills of interpreting and relating (*savoir comprendre*) while the second is skills of discovery and interaction (*savoir apprendre/faire*). The first skill involves the ability to independently learn, understand, interpret, and analyse documents, events, and practices from a different culture and explain and “relate them to documents or events from one’s own culture” (Byram, 1997, p.33). It entails the capacity to explain, analyse, and establish connections between events and texts from other different cultures to one’s own culture. The acquisition of these skills serves as a basis for the development of the second set of skills (skills of discovery and interaction) that are crucial for intercultural citizenship (Barili and Byram, 2021; Byram, 2020).

The skills of discovery and interaction emphasise the acquisition of “new knowledge of culture and cultural practices” (Byram, 1997, p. 98). It also necessitates the ability to use that knowledge in a direct intercultural interaction (Byram, 1997; Barili and Byram, 2021). Furthermore, it enables individuals to identify important aspects in a foreign context. This becomes increasingly complex in scenarios where the cultures involved have little or no commonality. Moreover, Byram (1997) indicates that the skills of discovery and interaction can function independently or in combination with interpreting and relating skills. These skills in the intercultural communicative competence model align with theories of autonomous learning and reflect the need for individuals to continuously learn, develop, and adapt their skills in response to the changing and expanding global world.

3.8.4 Critical cultural awareness (Savoir S’engager)

Critical cultural awareness/ political education (CCA) refers to the ability to critically evaluate and analyse using explicit and systematic criteria of reasoning, perspectives, practices, applications, and values in one’s own culture and other cultures (Byram, 1997; 2000; 2008; 2020; Hismanoglu, 2011). The four ICC dimensions previously discussed “attitudes, knowledge, skills of interpreting and relating, and skills of discovery and interaction”, can be

learned and acquired through experiences, personal reflections and professional training, even without the teacher's involvement (Byram, 1997, p. 33; Byram, 2012, p.7). Byram (1997; 2006; 2008; 2009; 2012; 2020) viewed CCA as essential and the core component of intercultural communicative competence (ICC), "it ensures that language teaching has an educational function" (2009, p. 325). According to Breeze (2017) the significance of "developing CCA in order to build effective intercultural relationships is undisputed in today's globalised world" (p.38). Furthermore, Byram (1997) has made significant contributions to the field of interculturality, affirming that it is crucial to integrate CCA in language education and to consider it as a fundamental objective to reach. S'engager entails "interacting vigorously and critically with knowledge and experience" (Byram,1997, p.90), and involves politics in the pedagogy and acquisition of languages. It fosters sensitivity, understanding, and mutual respect among people from diverse cultures. The development of CCA helps learners to take "action in the world" through social engagement (Barili and Byram, 2021, p.7).

Byram (1997) introduced the concept of CCA to emphasise the need to adopt a critical and analytical stance towards culture, both one's own and others, which implies the recognition of diverse cultural perspectives, and transcends the limitations of mono-culturalism and ethnocentrism. Byram (2000; 2011) highlighted the interconnectedness between cultural awareness and critical cultural awareness in the context of intercultural communicative competence. CA is a pedagogical approach that is characterised by its focus on developing knowledge, skills, and abilities that provide an in-depth understanding of the interconnected nature of language and culture (Byram, 1997; Guilherme, 2002; Risager, 2004). Moreover, CA refers to the conscious awareness of the significant role of culture in language education and communication (Baker, 2012). CA awareness equates with the knowledge acquired through the linguistic and communicative teaching and learning approaches. These approaches aim at familiarising students with the cultural aspects of the nation whose language is being taught within the educational setting (Byram, 2000; 2012).

According to Risager (2004), reflexivity is considered a fundamental dimension in CA because it enables individuals to shift from ethnocentrism to relativity. On the other hand, CCA argues that being aware of language and culture is not sufficient, rather, it is crucial to understand the sociological and psychological interplay between the two (Byram, 2012). Therefore,

understanding the significance of CCA in language education provides language teachers with valuable prospects to cultivate critical thinking skills in their students, fostering an awareness of the interconnectedness between classroom instruction and practical, real-life situations (Nugent and Catalano, 2015). CCA entails an awareness of the essential values and assumptions that shape our notions of right or wrong (Byram and Masuhara, 2013). Awareness is more profound and lasting compared to knowledge, which can be forgotten once learned as stated by Fantini (2018), “Knowledge can be forgotten, but once one is aware, it is difficult to become unaware” (p.36). Furthermore, the concept of awareness primarily pertains to the individual's comprehension of their own existence in relation to the surrounding environment and all other individuals (Fantini, 2012; 2018). In a similar vein, Croucher (2017) asserts that the state of being aware necessitates a shift from passive acceptance of knowledge to actively seeking and interrogating what lies beneath the surface.

This evaluative aspect of CCA distinguishes it from the other four *savoirs*, particularly attitudes (Byram, 1997). Breeze (2017) asserts that it is crucial for individuals to develop CCA to be able to establish successful intercultural connections and relationships with people from diverse cultures in today's globalised world. The primary objective of integrating intercultural dimensions in language education is not simply teaching factual knowledge about a specific foreign country. Instead, the aim is to facilitate students' understanding of the dynamics of intercultural communication, the role of social identities in various communication, the influence of personal opinions on the quality of communication, and the importance of gaining knowledge about the individuals they interact with (Byram et al., 2002).

3.9 The Importance of Teaching ICC

English language classroom in Algeria brings students from different cultural backgrounds together, for instance, students from Mali, Syria, and Palestine and other Algerians from diverse sub-cultures. These individuals have different cultural values, traditions, and beliefs, which play a significant role in shaping their identities. Due to these cultural differences, the inclusion and the acquisition of intercultural communicative competence is crucial because it equips learners with the necessary intercultural attitudes, knowledge, skills, and critical-cultural awareness to engage effectively and successfully in communication with not only their fellow Algerians, but also with other learners from diverse linguistic and cultural

backgrounds. According to Huang and Kou (2012), fostering ICC enables learners to develop, grow, and maintain positive attitudes towards diverse cultures, in addition, it promotes appreciation and respect for cultural variations. Ntuli (2012) stated that our actions and behaviours during interactions with other people from different cultures are largely influenced by our cultural values and backgrounds. Therefore, the development of ICC is essential to mitigate potential misunderstandings and other intercultural conflicts and tensions that may occur during intercultural interactions. As advocated by Pulverness (2000), teaching the language without culture makes the language empty of meaning. Therefore, teachers should strive to create culturally meaningful content for language teaching, considering the learners' existing knowledge about cultures and what they themselves can contribute in terms of cultural understanding. With this as a foundation, teachers can effectively collaborate with individuals from different cultural backgrounds. This collaboration aims to foster the integration of intercultural competence across the curriculum (Wagner et al., 2019).

When ICC is regarded as a significant objective to be promoted in the fields of ELT and FLT and L, the focal concerns revolve around how and what teachers can do to enable learners to acquire and develop ICC dimensions. Therefore, learners' development of ICC dimensions is determined by teachers' knowledge and awareness of ICC, and the approaches and methods employed to foster its development within the classroom context. In this case, teachers' awareness and critical understanding of ICC is crucial to effectively expose their learners to this competence (Barili and Byram, 2021). Furthermore, the acquisition of intercultural dimensions, attitudes, knowledge, and skills can greatly help teachers and learners in the classroom setting. For teachers, acquiring the knowledge dimension enables them to design various activities that integrate diverse cultures that learners might bring to the classroom, it also fosters an inclusive learning environment where every learner feels welcomed and valued. Furthermore, the incorporation of learners' languages and cultures into English language learning is likely to minimise the feelings of isolation experienced by some learners and foster their perception of English as a medium to express and share their everyday experiences with other learners who are culturally different. Additionally, if teachers are aware of their learners' cultures and beliefs, it inevitably reduces the stereotypes and creates a positive inclusive classroom atmosphere for everyone involved (Bishop, 2005).

In the context of globalisation, communication through the English language entails individuals from diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds. Therefore, it is crucial to have an understanding and awareness of different cultural contexts and communicative criteria to successfully engage and interact with different cultures (Baker, 2012). To engage in effective intercultural interactions with individuals who speak English around the world as well as to foster a deeper comprehension of their perspectives. The development of Intercultural Communicative Competence (ICC) attitudes and skills is essential for successful intercultural interaction. According to Garcia and Biscu (2005), the development of intercultural skills enables learners to effectively analyse, understand, and compare different cultures and relate them to their own culture. This ability not only enhances their engagement in the learning process but also provides them with a broader understanding of diverse cultures. By embracing an inclusive learning pedagogy, the intercultural communicative approach fosters a sense of unity and cooperation among all learners and emphasises the importance of accepting and appreciating different cultural backgrounds.

3.10 Practical Activities to Develop ICC in the Classroom

The ability to effectively communicate across different cultures has become a crucial skill in today's globalised world, particularly in education (teaching and learning). Intercultural Communicative Competence (ICC) goes beyond mastering linguistic competence and communicative competence (grammar, vocabulary and phonology), it involves understanding and navigating the cultural contexts in which language is used (Byram,1988; Baker 2009a). Developing intercultural communicative competence (ICC) is important for English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learners to successfully communicate in varied contexts. This necessitates a comprehensive strategy that combines cultural awareness, intercultural attitudes, sensitivity, and practical linguistic abilities. The following are some practical activities which are designed to improve and promote intercultural communicative competence (ICC) inside the classroom:

- *Comparing and Contrasting Cultures*

Integrating cultural comparison activities into teaching English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classroom is an effective method for fostering the development of intercultural communicative competence (ICC) among students (Byram, 1997,2008). These activities entail

conducting research and delivering presentations on diverse cultural practices, including holidays, cuisine, family dynamics, and educational systems, from both the student's national cultures and other different cultures such as English-speaking cultures. Through investigating these subjects, students themselves may recognise commonalities and distinctions among other cultures, thus developing a more profound sense of intercultural awareness and understanding. Byram (2008) believed that it is paramount for language teachers to encourage active participation in the classroom and let students explore things on their own through critical reflection, rather than just passively giving them facts about grammar or history (Byram, 2008). Furthermore, designing textbooks that address different cultures is crucial for fostering cultural awareness and intercultural competence among learners. These textbooks play a vital role in exposing students to diverse perspectives and helping them understand and appreciate cultural differences. The teaching goal isn't to get learners to adopt or embrace the values and beliefs of others' cultures. Instead, it's for them to be aware of the assumptions they make when they use language, either their own or the target language, to discuss and understand that other culture (Byram,2008). This would enhance language proficiency and foster critical thinking skills as students challenge their own cultural stereotypes and assumptions.

Activities of discovery and interactions

Byram suggested different activities to improve intercultural skills of discovery and interactions such as virtual encounters, emails and interviews. These activities offer students the opportunity to acquire new knowledge and operate skills and attitudes in real-life interactions (Byram,1997; Barili and Byram,2021). They provide a direct way for students to engage with different cultures while practising their language skills. Students can get insights into cultural differences, attitudes, and communication styles by conducting interviews with native English speakers or individuals from diverse cultural backgrounds. This practice promotes active listening and reflection on one's cultural presumptions. Additionally, it offers students a chance to utilise their language abilities in a practical setting, thereby improving their proficiency in both language and cross-cultural understanding. This interaction helps students develop a global perspective and reinforces the idea that English is a medium of communication across cultures.

- *Role-playing scenarios*

Another activity that might develop learners' intercultural attitudes as referred to by Byram (1997) is role-playing scenarios which offer learners practical ways to participate in different cultures and improve their abilities to effectively engage in intercultural interactions. This activity entails assigning students roles where they have to navigate cultural misunderstandings and tensions or social circumstances involving communication with individuals from different cultural backgrounds. For instance, one student plays the role of a Japanese culture, while another student plays a visitor from his/her own culture who is unfamiliar with the other's customs and beliefs. These simulations allow students to cultivate empathy and develop curiosity and openness towards other cultures. Developing these skills helps students eradicate preconceptions and stereotypes about other cultures and beliefs about one's own culture (Byram,1997; Spencer-Otaey and Franklin, 2009).

- *Authentic Materials*

Byram (1997) suggested the use of authentic materials such as film, songs, news articles, newspapers, and podcasts to develop what he refers to as knowledge (savoirs). Teaching English using authentic materials is important to expose students to real-world language use and different cultural contexts. These resources enable students to encounter various dialects, accents, and social conventions.

3.11 Intercultural Communicative Competence in Practice

Teaching a second or a foreign language entail connecting learners to a culturally diverse world (Sercu,2005). To effectively interact with individuals from diverse cultural backgrounds, it is important for learners to initially acknowledge and comprehend their own cultural values, beliefs, norms, and traditions (Newton, et al., 2010; Huang, 2014). ELT and FLT practices should focus on developing learners' intercultural communicative competence to enable them to become proficient "intercultural speakers" or "mediators" between different cultures (Byram et al., 2002, p.9). Fostering learners' consciousness of their own cultural background enables them to interpret, analyse and understand various cultural perspectives. In order to facilitate the integration of intercultural communicative competence in the classroom, it is crucial for teachers themselves to be aware of the concept and to display positive attitudes

towards learners' different cultures, in doing so, learners will acquire knowledge and awareness from their teachers, thus learners' ICC will be developed and promoted. According to Nault (2006), an essential role for teachers is to act as cultural mediators, facilitating the exploration of learners' cultural ideas, values and practises. This process enables learners to establish connections between their reflections and the comprehension of many cultures. Scholars (Holliday, 2009; Sybing, 2011) have emphasised the importance of educators establishing an inclusive educational setting that develops the abilities of acceptance, appreciation, and respect among students, enabling them to acquire knowledge from one another and cherish their own cultural values and norms. When learners' national cultures are integrated into English language teaching and learning (Holliday, 2009; Sybing, 2011), it offers learners the chance to engage in critical analysis of their own culture as well as other diverse cultures, promoting mutual tolerance and understanding. Therefore, teachers play a significant role in facilitating the development of ICC in the classroom. However, for teachers to effectively equip learners with ICC attitudes, skills, and knowledge, it is essential for them to get appropriate training to strengthen their own comprehension and awareness of ICC, as well as its practical application within the educational setting. This study proposes that the aim of English language teaching in Algeria should be to foster awareness of both teachers and learners about their own culture and other different cultures to enable them to successfully interact in both local and global contexts, and to help them avoid misunderstandings and stereotypes (Holliday et al., 2004).

According to Byram (2002), it is suggested that educators should integrate global subjects and themes into language teaching to enhance learners' comprehension of the global landscape and cultivate their consciousness to advocate social justice, equity, equality, and human rights. The aim is to promote tolerance and foster a sense of responsibility among individuals and society as a whole. This will encourage learners to actively engage in addressing local challenges, develop an interest in societal matters, promote sustainable development, demonstrate empathy towards those experiencing difficult circumstances, and comprehend the underlying causes and impacts of global issues (Byram et al., 2002).

The conventional approach of teaching and learning in language classrooms, guided by teachers, provides limited opportunities for developing practical abilities and skills necessary for real-life engagements. The integration of intercultural communicative competence attempts to provide learners with the necessary skills to engage in appropriate and efficient

communication in real situations in a foreign language. In a foreign language context, ICC can be fostered through activities that focus on behaviours and speech patterns. For instance, addressing various stereotypes and prejudices, suitable choices for engaging topics, expressing criticism and complaints, understanding personal space boundaries, tolerating others' values, and respecting others' attitudes.

3.11.1 Challenges and Issues

In recent years, the teaching of culture has been recognised as an essential element in the realm of foreign language education. In essence, it is vital for both educators and learners to understand the interconnectedness between language acquisition and cultural understanding. However, in many EFL classroom settings, like Algeria, culture is theoretically more feasible than in practice. Integrating culture and intercultural communicative competence poses a more intricate challenge as it requires going beyond general language skills and factual knowledge. Numerous factors might hinder the implementation of ICC, certain factors within this context can be effectively managed, whereas others present challenges that are more arduous to address. The literature indicates that EFL teachers encounter various challenges when teaching culture, which often leads to either limited cultural coverage such as teaching about the surface-level culture or completely neglecting it (Sercu, 2005). One issue that teachers may face is dealing with overcrowded curricula and textbooks, where they may not have the opportunity to tackle cultural content in the classroom. The instruction of cultural aspects necessitates a considerable amount of time. Consequently, some educators perceive themselves as unable to adequately dedicate time to the teaching of foreign language cultures due to the extensive curriculum designed to enhance learners' linguistic abilities. According to many teachers, the teaching of culture can be addressed later after enabling learners to master the basic language structure (basic grammar and vocabulary knowledge) and communicative competence to enable learners to understand and receive cultural knowledge, and to interact with NS of English. However, this later often never comes for most of the learners. Moreover, the lack of internet access can indeed be considered a significant challenge that hinders the implementation of ICC in EFL classrooms, which is the case in Algeria (Bouzidi, 2005; Aoumeur, 2017). In today's globalised world, the internet plays a vital role in facilitating intercultural communication and promoting global connections with people from diverse cultures (Nault, 2006). Without internet access,

learners may have limited exposure to authentic cultural recourses and opportunities to engage with individuals from diverse cultures.

Another serious challenge of integrating ICC is that teachers are convinced that they do not have sufficient knowledge about teaching culture (Gonen and Saglam, 2012), and they lack awareness when it comes to the notion of interculturality. Therefore, they feel hesitant and afraid of introducing such concepts to their students, they believe that their primary responsibility is bound to teach their learners about factual information and language structure (Gonen and Saglam, 2012). The third challenge is threatening students' national identity. Byram (2008) argues that in educational settings where the foreign language (FL) maintains considerable importance, learners may acquire the tendency to abandon their national or ethnic identities in favour of imitating the dominant values and behaviours of the culture being taught inside the classroom. In a context like Algeria, the French language is commonly seen as the language associated with those of sophisticated cultural backgrounds and is considered prestigious in comparison to Arabic (Standard Arabic, Derja, and Tamazight), and even English (second foreign language) is considered as the language of the educated class. These perspectives go back to the fact that Algeria has been colonised for over 132 years by France. Therefore, Algerian policymakers and teachers are trying to instil the Algerian national identity and culture by depicting it in the Algerian textbooks of English, and not considering ICC as an objective to promote.

The last challenge is the absence of appropriate and suitable training for teachers to teach culture and interculturality. Teachers may lack enough training or have inadequate strategies and approaches for addressing diverse cultural issues or ICC language teaching (Risager, 2007). Hence, educators fail to effectively assess cross-cultural competencies in the classroom. They also fail to develop their learners' attitudes towards different cultures. Byram and Kramersch (2008) outlined that teachers often fear stereotypes associated with the target culture, as well as they worry about students' ability to understand and interpret what they read and how they engage in various interactions. Therefore, the ways teachers approach culture and ICC in the FL classrooms, and their awareness of the deep complexities of both notions significantly influence the degree to which students develop intercultural awareness and critical cultural awareness.

3.12 Critics of Byram's ICC Model in FL Context

Byram's model of intercultural communicative competence (ICC) has garnered significant attention and implementation in language education; however, it was not without criticism. Byram's model has been criticised because of its individualistic nature and its potential limitations in addressing collective and societal dimensions of intercultural competence. It highlights the need to incorporate socio-cultural and political contexts into the understanding of ICC (Hoff, 2014). In other words, Hoff (2014) warns against how Byram's intercultural encounters may lead to an overly dominant perspective that neglects the needs and expectations of the Other. In such a scenario, Hoff (2014) argues that the relationship between the Self and the Other could become imbalanced, favouring power and dynamics over equality. According to Hoff (2014), Byram's model seems to suggest a passive and uncritical process of socialization and lacks a true meaning of intercultural dialogue. In a similar vein, various misunderstandings arise from "the absence of the interlocutor" in most of the definitions of intercultural communicative competence and IC (Ruben, 1989, p.234), which makes it primarily monological and individualistic. The existing definitions of ICC commonly focus on the individual possessing the competence (the user of the competence), overlooking the impact of the interlocutor and the contextual factors on the dynamic interactions. In reality, any individual can act as an intercultural competent speaker, but may still face challenges due to the interlocutor's lack of motivation or intercultural attitudes, negative intentions, or limited language skills. Therefore, the incorporation of these acts of co-construction of discourses and interactions is deemed crucial in the definitions of IC and ICC (Dervin, 2010). Ogay (2000) pinpointed the significance of using the term "intercultural dynamics" instead of "competence" to capture the shared responsibility and engagement of both parties in intercultural interactions (Ogay, 2000, p.53). Furthermore, challenges arise when it comes to assessing and evaluating ICC dimensions of Byram's model, as the assessment of such complex attitudes and skills remains subjective and challenging. Byram (1997) viewed that openness to others and critical self-awareness are fundamental values in education. However, the real challenge lies in proving, testing, and trusting the individual's genuine belief in these values (Dervin, 2010). As a result, attempting to assess the *savoir être* aspects is impractical and impossible (Dervin, 2010). Despite the critics, Byram's model

continues to be influential in shaping the field of intercultural communication and language education.

3.13 Empirical Studies on ICC

3.13.1 Research about culture and ICC conducted in Algeria

In her study, Rabehi (2021) conducted a qualitative interpretative study to examine the representation of culture in the recently introduced English as a Foreign Language (EFL) textbook for middle school pupils in Algeria. The study's findings indicated that the new textbook mostly embraces a nationalist and essentialist perspective in its depiction of the concept of culture. This approach limits the promotion of ICC among learners, as the cultural representations mainly revolve around Algerian cultures and fail to address other cultures, thus, failing to foster learners' critical cultural awareness (CCA). The study also showed that EFL teaching in Algeria maintains a focus on developing linguistic and communicative proficiency. Additionally, cultural education in EFL classrooms is significantly impacted by religion, cultural identity, and several other aspects. Consequently, she believed that the primary aim of the new Algerian textbook of EFL is to help learners understand their culture solely and to introduce Algeria to the world.

The study conducted by Ait-Aissa and Said (2012) focused on evaluating the Intercultural Communicative Competence (ICC) in an Algerian high school EFL textbook called 'New Prospects'. The researchers employed a quantitative content analysis approach and used two checklists (Cortazzi and Jin, 1999; Lee, 2009) as criteria for the assessment of ICC. The researchers found that the textbook prioritises aspects of the surface culture C, focusing on the broader aspects of culture rather than addressing ICC. They also found that the textbook places a significant emphasis on the non-target culture, providing overloaded information and features related to the learners' own cultures. In other words, the representation of the non-target culture outweighed the representation of the target culture. Overall, the study suggested that the textbook's approach to culture teaching in the Algerian EFL context did not adequately promote the development of ICC. It highlighted the need for a more balanced representation of cultures and a stronger focus on developing learners' critical cultural awareness.

The study conducted by Messekher (2014) focused on investigating the representation of culture in English as a Foreign language textbook used in the First-Generation Programme (FGP). Her study carried out two stages, the first stage entailed the analysis of the content analysis of four Algerian English textbooks, whereas, the second stage involved interviews with Algerian teachers to gather their perceptions and attitudes of how culture is integrated in their teaching practices. The findings revealed that culture was perceived as a significant component of the textbook, with substantial representations through texts and images. However, the cultural content primarily encompassed factual knowledge about the United States, the United Kingdom, and Algeria.

3.13.2 Other Contexts

Intercultural communicative competence has been the subject of several researches. Shin et al., (2011) researched the cultural content presented in the most widely distributed English language teaching textbooks. The results indicated that the majority of the English textbooks mostly reflect the cultures of the Inner Circle Countries, namely the US and the UK. The focus of the cultural content primarily revolved around factual information, particularly related to tourism and the big C aspects of culture. Thus, learners' opportunities to engage in critical discussions and understand deep-level aspects of culture (values, behaviours, and practices), as well as reflect on their own cultures were overlooked. I contend that the representation of cultures from the outer circle countries, where English serves as a medium of educational instruction, should also be integrated. This inclusion is crucial as it validates the significance of local cultures in the context of English language use.

Sasani (2018) investigated non-native teachers' perspectives and attitudes of culture and its relation to English language teaching. Furthermore, she explored their conceptions of IC. Her study involved nine non-native ESOL teachers from various language centres in the UK. The findings revealed that these teachers held different attitudes towards the notion of culture, they viewed it as "transferable facts, modes of thoughts, skills, and beliefs" (Sasani, 2018, p.118). Teachers have additionally acknowledged several obstacles that students may face when interacting with people from different cultural backgrounds, particularly related to the effects of globalisation and glocalisation. The findings showed that these non-native teachers generally had positive attitudes towards the concept of IC. However, they expressed their

confusion and uncertainty about the appropriate and systematic approaches to integrating IC and ICC into their teaching. They also outlined the challenges and issues they might encounter while teaching ICC, such as the limited time assigned for cultural teaching, students' level and interest, and lack of resources and authentic tools in language teaching.

The study conducted by Pena-Dix (2018) endeavoured to explore the intercultural communicative competence of Colombian English language teachers in the Colombian public sector. He carried out a qualitative exploratory study which sought to explore Colombian teachers' conceptions and attitudes of culture and interculturality. The findings of the study revealed that Colombian teachers had positive attitudes towards intercultural communicative competence in ELT. However, the predominant methods adopted by these teachers while addressing culture tended to be essentialist and nationalist, following communicative language teaching methodologies. He concluded that despite the efforts that were made to incorporate the Intercultural English Language Teaching Approach, teachers' profiles did not fully align with the desired expectations in terms of intercultural savours for IELTS.

Salem (2013) conducted research aiming to incorporate an intercultural approach in the Intensive English Program (IEP) at a university in Lebanon where English is employed as the primary medium of instruction. Her primary objective was to enhance Lebanese learners' intercultural communicative competence and to help them deconstruct stereotypes and otherizations. The findings of her study demonstrated that adopting an intercultural perspective in English language teaching can lead to several outcomes: developing learners' intercultural communicative competence, fostering language proficiency, enabling them to engage in discussions on sensitive topics without causing tensions or conflicts and creating an active and motivated environment in the classroom. She highlighted that although the findings are specific to a particular context (Lebanon), teachers and textbook designers might be encouraged to reconsider their teaching practices and shift their objectives to foster intercultural competence, which enables students to avoid biases and otherizations and prepare them for intercultural interactions with people of different cultural backgrounds.

Studies conducted in the Algerian context (Rabehi, 2021; Messekher, 2014) and MENA contexts indicate that the Arab context in general and Algerian in particular is still in the early

stages of integrating ICC, with the lack of specialised intercultural communication teachers, lack of teachers training programs and limited implementation of ICC in language education.

3.14 Concluding chapter

This chapter presents a comprehensive analysis of the existing literature that addresses the concepts within the field of interculturality. Given the intricate nature and the importance of the notion of culture, the first objective of the chapter was to provide different perspectives and understanding of this concept and demonstrates its connections to language. The transition from the conventional method of teaching culture, known as the cultural turn, to the intercultural approach is addressed. This chapter provides definitions to different concepts of Intercultural Communicative Competence and its dimensions. Furthermore, it demonstrates the necessity of integrating ICC in classroom settings. Finally, Challenges, critics of Byram's model and ICC in practice are also discussed in this chapter.

Chapter Four

Research Methods and Methodology

4.1 Introduction

This study aims to explore Algerian English Language teachers' and learners' perspectives and conceptions of culture and intercultural communicative competence (ICC) in EFL in higher education. The preceding chapter provided comprehensive insights into the notion of culture and its inextricable relationship with language. It also presented a historical overview of the notion of ICC and, its dimensions, its significance in teaching and learning foreign languages, and the challenges encountered by teachers when implementing ICC in the classroom in the Algerian context. This chapter presents the methodological approach and methods underpinning this study. For this purpose, it starts with an explanation of the researcher's ontological and epistemological viewpoints, and how the choice of the research questions played a pivotal role in shaping the study's research design. Furthermore, justifications for opting for triangulation methods and an interpretive paradigm for this study are provided. It also provides the research design, sampling techniques, and data collection instruments, in addition to the procedures and approaches used to analyse the data collected. Moreover, ethical considerations and criteria used for evaluating the trustworthiness of the study are discussed in this chapter.

4.2 Philosophical assumptions and worldviews

The philosophical assumptions of the research embrace different stances: ontological, epistemological, methodological and axiological which inform the research philosophy.

4.2.1 Ontology

The philosophical assumptions address the researcher's beliefs about the nature of reality, in a more philosophical way, it refers to the study of our existence and the substantial nature of reality. In the same vein, it addresses the "study of being", and it seeks to answer these questions: what exists? What is true? How can we sort existing things? (Kilam, 2013, p. 7; Crotty, 1988, p.10). This illustrates that the focus of ontology is on individuals' beliefs and the influence of these beliefs on their perception and interpretation of the surrounding world. According to Blaikie (2010), ontology in social science studies is related to the understanding of both objective and subjective knowledge. More clearly, the realist position (objective)

contends that reality exists regardless of the researcher, and it is completely independent of him/her (Guba and Lincoln, 1994; Hatch, 2002; Cohen et al, 2011; Bryman, 2012; Hammond and Wellington, 2013; Kilam, 2013). This assumption considers reality as singular and tangible and the real world is built independently from our knowledge as observers.

This philosophical worldview (objective) is also called the scientific method, which refers to the power of science and rational thought to understand and manipulate the world (Fisher and Buglear, 2010). Furthermore, it is an approach to generating knowledge through conducting research, which focuses on the natural sciences model. The data are collected using structured observation, closed-ended questionnaires, and experiments (Finch, 1985). Positivism is underpinned by the belief that research should be as objective as possible, the researcher does not have little or almost no impact on the outcome of research results (Robson, 2011). Positivists believe that the world is external and there is a single objective reality to all research phenomena regardless of the investigator's attitudes or perspectives (Hudson and Ozanne, 1988). However, the subjectivist ontology claims that there is no fixed reality, but the world is socially constructed (Richards, 2003; Creswell et al, 2003). It suggests that one plays a part in how the social environment is seen, and as a result, reality may vary depending on how it is perceived. Similarly, Burrell and Morgan (1979) argue that reality is a multiple-constructed and contextualised entity through individuals' experiences in the world they live in. From this perspective, the understanding of reality can vary among individuals or groups due to the unique nature of their experiences. This prompts the researcher or the observer to explore the variety and complexity of perspectives. In a nutshell, ontology is associated with the central question of whether social entities are perceived as objective (positivism) or subjective (constructivism) (Bryman, 2012).

Shifting from didactics of languages field to cultural studies was not an easy decision to take because of the need to develop critical thinking skills and make arguments for every step the researcher takes in his/her journey. For instance, looking at intercultural communicative competence as a variable in my study, I would say that it is a very complex concept that even experts in the field did not agree upon one static definition. At this stage, after conducting the literature review, I ended up shaping a good understanding of the field from different perspectives. I also ended up believing that gathering quantitative data solely is not enough to explore the participants' perspectives of intercultural communicative competence in

Algerian EFL classrooms. Therefore, this approach is inappropriate for social research as the researcher is completely separated from what is being researched.

This research explored Algerian English Language teachers' and learners' perspectives, intercultural lived experiences, and their understandings of intercultural communicative competence in the EFL context. Furthermore, it sought to investigate the members' attitudes toward creating the cultural club at West University, illustrating the importance of this initiative in developing learners' ICC. Therefore, the constructivism approach was adopted to investigate and explore the participants' perspectives of ICC.

4.2.2 Epistemology

Epistemology is the second philosophical assumption defined by Burrell and Morgan (1979). It addresses the nature and form of knowledge and how it can be acquired or learned by other human beings (Guba, 1990; Cohen et al., 2011). In addition, Crotty (1998) defined epistemology as a way of understanding and describing how we know what we know. Epistemology examines the relationship between the researcher and knowledge under inquiry (Killam, 2013). Killam (2013) considered two main questions in the epistemological assumptions: How knowledge is acquired? How do we know what we know?

Like ontology, there are two distinctions to be made. First, knowledge about the world can be possibly acquired with no interferences or interventions. Cohen et al (2011) viewed knowledge as hard, realistic, and objective demanding the researcher to act as an observer solely. This implies objectivity as everyone observes things in the same way (Cohen et al., 2011). Second, knowledge is never objective but rather subjective and influenced by the reality constructed by society. In other words, knowledge is multiple, internal, and dependent on the researcher through their research with those being under study (Guba and Lincoln, 1994; Hatch, 2002; Cohen et al., 2011; Kilam, 2013). The researcher minimises the distance or the "objective separateness" between him/herself and those being researched (Guba and Lincoln, 1988, p. 94). Moreover, subjective evidence is based on individuals' views through their subjective experiences to know what they know. In a nutshell, foundationalists would take the former stance (the naturalistic model of science) known as positivism (quantitative approach) to the research, while the anti-foundationalists would employ the anti-positivist or interpretive (qualitative approach) to research (Cohen et al., 2011; Bryman, 2015).

As Crotty (1998) stated ontology refers to what kind of world we are researching or exploring along with the nature of existence and the structure of reality.

The interpretive stance tends to understand the world as it is from the subjective experience of individuals. It uses meaning not measurement-oriented methodologies such as interviews, participant observations, and focus groups, that rely on the subjective relationship between the researcher and participants. The interpretive paradigm is based on observations and interpretations, hence to observe is to collect information and data about a particular event or phenomenon, while to interpret is to make meaning from the information you gathered by drawing assumptions and inferences or making judgments about whether there is a match between the information and some patterns already gathered (Aikenhead, 1997).

Having given the aforementioned definitions of ontology and epistemology, it is now worth outlining my ontological and epistemological stances in this study.

My research study takes an ontological stance of social constructivism, which is necessary to understand the social world of meaning. As a novice researcher myself, I presume that the world I am investigating is a world populated by human beings, who have multiple thoughts, views, attitudes, interpretations, and meanings. My investigation of this world is demonstrated by the use of different research methods of the interpretive paradigm such as the use of interviews, focus groups, and open-ended questionnaires to interpret and explore the Algerian English Language teachers' and learners' perspectives, experiences, attitudes, and understandings of intercultural communicative competence in EFL context. In addition, to investigate the members' perceptions and experiences of creating the intercultural club (The Global Representative of Cultures) in the West University. Therefore, the epistemological stance adopted in this study is interpretivism (subjectivism). By conducting this research, I am seeking to find answers to questions like how intercultural communicative competence is perceived by the participants and how it is addressed in their teaching practices in Algerian Higher Education. The construction of meaning is conducted within a social context and this is shown in the interviews and focus group discussions. These perspectives are not tended to be valid; so, the study is an invitation for reinterpretation or replication.

4.3 Research Design Framework

Figure 3: Adopted from Maxwell (2013)

A research design is concerned with transforming the research questions into projects (Robson, 2011). In reviewing the literature on research methodology, there are several research design models suggested by many scholars. Each design has interrelated and balanced components. Creswell (2014) believes that research design gives the researcher a specific orientation or direction for research procedures. Other scholars used other terminology such as strategy or inquiry but they all refer to the same concept (Denzin and Lincoln, 2011; Robson, 2011; Creswell, 2014).

Creswell (2003) defined mixed methods as methods which involve the combination of both qualitative and quantitative approaches in a single research study. The data are collected and analysed sequentially, where there is a sense of priority. It also requires the integration of data at one or more stages in the research process (Creswell et al., 2003). With the development of mixed methods, different classifications emerged according to the researcher's views and preferences; and choice can be affected by limited factors. Scholars in mixed research methods described these typologies of how to integrate and mix methods in a single study according to the theoretical drive (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004; Creswell and Clark, 2007; Teddlie and Tashakkori, 2003; Creswell, 2014). However, Maxwell (2012) and Robson (2011) suggested that they have limitations in terms of research approach, where they explained different interrelated components like in the interactive model suggested by Maxwell (2012), which consists of five components. These components are the goal, conceptual framework, research questions, methods, and validity (Maxwell, 2012). He stated

in his model that research questions are the heart or the hub of the whole process as they have a clear relationship with the other components in the design. These components are not different from many other research design models (LeCompte et al., 1993; Miles and Huberman, 1994; Robson, 2011). Maxwell's (2012) model is based on the way the relationship between the components is conceptualised. In other words, the different parts of the design are closely connected with each component rather than being in a linear or cyclic sequence. Research questions are the centre of the model in which they connect directly with the goals and should be grounded with previous knowledge about the research topic under investigation (Maxwell, 2012). The decision of the conceptual framework of the study depends on the goals and research questions. This interactive model is followed in my research because of its flexibility and elasticity with qualitative research. Maxwell (2012) used the term "rubber band" as a metaphorical image to portray his model, where the components can stretch and bend to some extent (p.5).

The use of multiple methods in collecting information is very common in qualitative research, and it is usually called mixed-methods research (Maxwell, 2012). In addition, Johnson and Onwuegbuzie (2004) described mixed method research as "the class of research where the researcher mixes or combines quantitative and qualitative research techniques, methods, approaches, concepts or language into a single study" (p.17). Following mixed methods to answer the research questions raised in this research study is beneficial for several reasons: it enables the use of different methods and instruments to tackle multiple realities in a single study. Secondly, it is a way where one database could be used to check the validity of the other database (Creswell, 2014). Thirdly, one database could be constructed on the other database. Therefore, the use of multiple methods is recommended in many research studies on intercultural competence. This enables the research to gain deep understandings and insights into meaning constructed through the participants' experiences and also to investigate their views about teaching and learning intercultural communicative competence in EFL classrooms through collecting qualitative and quantitative data. Creswell outlines three "mixed methods design" (Creswell, 2014, p.15). Firstly, convergent parallel mixed methods are a form of mixed methods design in which the researcher amalgamates and converges both quantitative and qualitative data to give an inclusive image of the research problem. The researcher collects both quantitative and qualitative data at the same time and then compares the information collected in the interpretation phase. Secondly, the explanatory

sequential mixed method is a kind of method in which the investigator collects the quantitative data, analyses and explains the findings then builds on the results to explain them in a detailed way with qualitative findings. It is called explanatory because the initial data gathered are explained further with qualitative data and it is called sequential because the quantitative stage is followed up by the qualitative phase. In this strategy, the weight is given to quantitative data, and the mixing occurs when the primary quantitative results inform the secondary qualitative data collection (Creswell, 2009). This form of research can be useful especially when unanticipated results arise from quantitative data, in this vein, the qualitative data collected can be used to investigate and examine these surprising results in a detailed way. Thirdly, the exploratory-sequential mixed method design reversed the sequence of the explanatory-sequential design. The research starts with the qualitative phase, exploring the participants' views, followed by a second stage of quantitative data collection and analysis that builds on the results of the first phase (Creswell, 2009). Weight, is placed on the first phase and the data collected are mixed between qualitative and quantitative data. In the first phase of this research, the data was collected concurrently through conducting semi-structured interviews with teachers and online questionnaires with English language learners. However, the second exploratory phase was carried out sequentially. This involved conducting two focus group discussions, one at the East and one at the West University with English language learners, as well as interviews with the GRC members. The purpose of the online questionnaires was to prepare learners to participate in the focus group discussions.

Figure 4: "An Exploratory Mixed Methods Research Design"

4.4 Sampling Techniques

The complexity of the phenomenon under investigation requires the implementation of different types of sampling techniques within the anticipation to effectively generate a sample that provides rich data to answer the research questions (Teddlie and Yu, 2007). The combination of different sampling techniques in a single research study can be advantageous in structuring a robust research design (Kemper et al., 2003).

The participants who took part in this study are Algerian English language teachers and Master's Degree learners from two Algerian universities (East and West), in addition to two members of the intercultural club (The Global Representative of Cultures), which was established in the West University. After passing my upgrade and receiving my ethical approval from the University of the West of Scotland Ethical Committee, I travelled to Algeria for data collection. A purposive sampling technique was employed to identify and recruit participants for this study. Robinson (2014) referred to it as purposeful sampling, it is a non-probability sampling technique used in research to select specific individuals based on predominated criteria or characteristics. This technique is non-statistical and it is mostly used in qualitative research and case studies. In this method, the researchers handpick participants who have enough knowledge and desired qualities that are relevant to the research objectives (Marshall, 1996; Cohen et al, 2011). Pattons (1990) states that "the logic and power of purposive sampling lies in selecting information-rich cases for study in depth" (quoted in Kemper et al., 2003, p.279). This sampling strategy involves selecting "certain cases or units" based on the researcher's specific purpose rather than randomly (Tashakkori and Teddlie, 2003, p.713).

Convenience sampling is a type of non-probability (purposive) sampling, where individuals from the target population are readily and easily accessible, and they are willing to participate in the research at any given time (Cohen et al., 2011). Therefore, it was adopted in this study to gain access to some participants to take part in the online questionnaire, those who were ready and available to participate in this study.

Snowballing sampling, which is a type of purposive sampling, was also employed in this study. Before travelling to Algeria, I contacted the heads of the English language departments at the

East and West University via email and sent them the information sheet. I got a response only from the head of the department of the East University, where she gave me the approval to conduct my study. It is worth noting that I used to be among the elites in that university and the head of the department used to teach me. However, I did not get any response from the second setting. Therefore, I had to use a snowballing technique to get access to more teachers and learners (Walliman, 2011; Goodman, 2011). I contacted a friend who was doing his master's degree in English at the West University and I asked for his help to connect me to teachers and learners from the West University. He provided me with teachers' emails and Facebook, particularly those who were experienced in teaching intercultural communicative competence to Language and Communication Streams. Furthermore, I created a Facebook page and added him as an administrator of the page to be able to invite his colleagues to join the page and take part in the online questionnaires and focus group discussions. I named the page 'The Significance of Promoting Intercultural Communicative Competence among Learners'. I provided an overview of myself as a researcher and the university I am studying at, which helped establish a connection with the participants. Additionally, I explained the rationale and aims of the study in detail. By sharing this background information, I was able to build trust with the participants, making them feel more comfortable and confident in engaging with the research process.

Notwithstanding, there is no clear rule of the size of the sample. Qualitative researchers argue that the primary objective of qualitative research is to get deeper understandings and insights into the educational and social practices, that are prevalent in a particular context (Onwuegbuzie and Leech, 2007; Cohen et al., 2011). A small sample is purposefully sought to attain a theoretical sample instead of representative. In other words, the criterion of the participants' selection is more crucial and central than the number of participants (Wilmot, 2005). In many cases, purposive sampling is designed to get access to people who are knowledgeable and have in-depth knowledge about particular issues (Cohen et al, 2011). Therefore, it was significant to choose Algerian English language teachers, who are qualified and have expertise in teaching subjects, which address the notions of culture and ICC in the East and West University in Algeria. It was also crucial that both Algerian and Malian Master English language learners to take part in the focus group discussions as this research aims to explore teachers' and learners' perspectives of intercultural communicative competence and

to investigate their intercultural communication with people from different cultural backgrounds. Furthermore, conducting interviews with members of the intercultural club was important to understand how this approach would help in the development of learners' ICC. The goal of purposive sampling is to ensure that the selected participants can provide valuable insights and knowledge about the research under investigation. The number of participants who took part in the semi-structured interviews in this study were ten (n10) Algerian English language teachers from both universities, in addition, sixty (n60) participants (learners) took part in the online questionnaires. Moreover, twelve (n12) participants (learners) (n6 from each university) participated in the focus group discussions. Finally, two (n2) participants who were former students at the West University and who were members of the intercultural club, participated in the interviews.

My justification for choosing two Algerian universities, East and West, as the case of this study was because I used to be a student at the former university, I am aware of the university system (modules, students' number in a class, materials used, and the complete absence of intercultural communicative competence teaching practices). In addition, in May 2017, I conducted online informal professional conversations with differently located Algerian Universities to gain insights into how culture is addressed in the courses, and to what extent ICC is integrated and considered as an objective. Most of the English departments were focusing on the big C culture, in other words, teaching about old civilisations and literature of the target culture. Their aim of teaching was to enable learners to communicate as natives.

What I found different within the West University was the fact that intercultural communicative competence was introduced to Master students as a separate module in the language and Communication Stream. I was aware of this information through an informal phone call with a former student, who used to study at the West University and is a co-founder of the intercultural club 'The Global Representative of Cultures'.

4.5 Data collection procedures

It is essential to choose different methods for data collection to obtain the required data to answer the research questions in this study. This is based on the nature of data needed to be collected, who are the participants, the research questions, and under what conditions

(Robson, 2011). In this study, I applied mixed research methods, where I conducted semi-structured interviews, questionnaires, and focus groups with Algerian English language teachers, learners, and members of the intercultural club to explore their perspectives and understandings of culture and intercultural communicative competence in the East and West Universities in Algeria.

4.5.1 Interviews

Interviews are needed in my research project to gain profound insightful views about the concepts of culture, intercultural competence, and intercultural communicative competence in EFL classrooms. The interview is defined as a conversational practice in which knowledge is produced through the interaction between an interviewer and an interviewee or group of interviewees (Brinkmann, 2014). Brinkmann and Kvale (2018) argued that if you desire to comprehend individuals' perception of their environment and existence, why not engage in conversation with them? They identified two contrasting stances using the metaphor of the interviewer as a miner or traveller. The miner metaphor views the interview as an interaction, which requires the participants' pre-existing knowledge or views. This view takes place within the positivist and post-positivist model, which sees knowledge as a buried metal, and the interviewer who detects the valuable metal and digs nuggets of knowledge out of topics (Kvale and Brinkman, 2009). Their second metaphor sees truth as something which does not exist in the interview with both the interviewer and interviewee actively participating and interpreting in the process. The interviewer is an active player in the development of data, and the interview is a transformative method, this fits generally with the constructivist research model

The interviewer-traveller walks along with inhabitants, asking questions and encouraging them to tell their own stories of their lived world...The journey may not only lead to new knowledge, the traveller may change as well. The journey might instigate a process of reflection that leads the traveller to new ways of self-understanding (Kvale and Brinkmann, 2009, p, 48).

Interviews are one of the major approaches in collecting data in qualitative research, in any interview conversation, the researcher asks about and listens to the interviewees, expressing their perspectives and views about the way they live. The researcher learns about their experiences, feelings, emotions, and hopes and the world they lived in. Therefore, an

interview is an inter-view, where knowledge is constructed in the interaction between the interviewer and interviewee (Kvale, 1996). In the same vein, He defined an interview as an inter-change of views that occurs between two people or a group of people on a subject of common interest and considers the interdependence of human interaction as a central of knowledge construction (Kvale, 1996).

Knowledge is produced between participants (Liang, 1967); thus, an interview cannot be only regarded as either objective or subjective, but rather intersubjective (Kvale, 1996). In addition, Kitwood (1977) classified three different conceptions of an interview. The first conception deals with an interview as a possible vehicle to collect and transfer pure valid data. If the interviewer perfectly does his job, by setting up questions in a reasonable way and the interviewee gives truthful and honest answers, valid data may be obtained.

The second conception is to admit that an interview has an absolute bias, which can be controlled by the interviewer. According to Kitwood (1977), “each participant in an interview will define the situation in a particular way. This fact can be best handled by building controls into the research design”, by having, for instance, a set of interviewers with different biases (Kitwood, 1977, p. 166). The third conception of the interview is that it is seen as a casual relaxed conversation with an individual who requires sharing different characteristics of his/her lived experiences. The focal point of this is not based on the method to deal with the bias, but rather on the theory of daily life that takes into consideration the pertinent facets of interviews such as perceptions, understanding, role-playing, and stereotyping. Interviews enable the interviewer and interviewee to interact about their views and understanding of the world they live in (Cohen et al.,2000).

Three different types of interviews can be implemented in social sciences research (May, 2011). Each type has its own objective, focus, and research question. Firstly, the structured interview is when the researcher uses closed-ended questions. In other words, the interviewer has pre-arranged questions, with fixed wording and it is commonly asked in the same order. The researcher writes down all the questions in a standardised way before conducting the interview. Therefore, this type of interview is more like a question-answer session than a conversation about the research phenomena. Secondly, the unstructured interview or non-standardised, ethnographic interview, contradicts the above, in that the flexibility and the questions are widely common and open. The interviewer has a general area

of interest but allows the conversation to develop, this area and this type can be completely informal (Robson, 2002). In this regard, Bryman (2008) argued that the interviewer could ask a single question and the interviewee has the option concerning the extent he/she responds. Interventions and interruptions on the part of the interviewer are kept to a minimum. Therefore, this would prepare a very relaxed atmosphere for the interviewees. Thirdly, the semi-structured interview is a mixture of the two types aforementioned, where the interviewer has predetermined questions, but there is flexibility in how and when the questions are asked to facilitate the flow of the conversation. The questions' wording and their order can be modified according to the interviewer's perception of what seems suitable (Robson, 2002). Additional questions can be asked and some may have not been expected at the beginning of the interviews. Additionally, the interviewer gives the interviewee the chance to elaborate and probe specific issues and views through open-ended questions.

I believe that a semi-structured interview is the most valuable and appropriate tool for conducting this research study since the interview is controlled by the interviewer at the same time the interviewee has the flexibility to guide and direct the interview. Teachers were individually interviewed and the interviews were carried out in Algeria through face-to-face interaction to enable the informants to express themselves openly and flexibly. Another significant reason for choosing this type of interview is its flexible nature of giving the researcher the chance to add and change the order and structure of the questions depending on the flow of the conversation and interaction (Wellington, 2015).

4.5.2 Questionnaires

It is stated by Robson (2011) that questionnaires are very common and widely used in social research for collecting data from and about people (Robson, 2011). The questionnaire should translate the research objectives into specific questions. These questions are designed to look for facts, opinions, attitudes, and beliefs of respondents (Nachmias et al., 1992). The primary aim of using questionnaires in this research project is to set the profile of English language learners' perspectives of their English learning experience and to look to what extent they are aware of the notions of culture and ICC in the East and West University. Furthermore, the questionnaires in this study are considered as a preparation for Master's Degree learners of English to take part in the focus group discussions. I conducted online questionnaires with sixty (n60) learners in total from both universities (East and West).

There are two types of questions, which were used in questionnaires, closed-ended and open-ended questions. In closed-ended questions, respondents are offered multiple answers and they are asked to choose one of the choices that most closely represent their views. These types of questions are considered as easy to ask and easy to answer because they require no writing by the respondents (Nachmias et al.,1992). While open-ended questions are not followed by a list of choices, thus the respondents are required to supply answers by expressing their views and perspectives about the research under inquiry.

4.5.3 Focus Group

The generic term ‘focus groups’ generates a process, which is very different from in-depth interviews. Data are generated by the interaction between a group of participants (Ritchie and Lewis, 2003). Therefore, a focus group is not a collection of individual interviews with questions directed solely by the interviewer. It is better outlined as a group interview. They are synergistic (Stewart and Shamdasi, 1990) in the sense that a group of people works and interacts together. This interaction is used to generate data and rich insights (Morgan, 1997). Ritchie and Lewis (2003) stated that spontaneity is considered a key feature of focus groups, the views and perspectives come from the same social context the participants share. For example, while responding to each other, participants feel more comfortable and reveal their own frame of knowledge on the topic under study. The language they use during the interaction, the arguments they give, and their general understanding of the topic are displayed spontaneously. All the data that emerges from the group interaction is provided through the active interaction of the participants, but the researcher is less influenced by the discussion. Krueger and Casey (2000) described focus groups as a tool that “presents a more natural environment than that of the individual Interview because participants are influencing and influenced by others just as they are in real life” (Kreuger and Casey, 2000, quoted in Ritchie and Lewis, 2003, p.171).

This data collection method should be well-organised in a suitable setting and bring the participants together to discuss a specific given theme or issue where the interaction with the group will lead to outcomes (Smithson, 2000; Hydén and Bulow, 2003). The participants present their opinions, and experiences and listen, and reflect on what has been said. They are allowed to ask questions to each other, seek clarifications, comment on what they have heard, and prompt others to explain more (Ritchie and Lewis, 2003).

Focus groups give the researcher the chance to see how ideas and views emerge in a more naturalistic setting. These ideas are shaped through conversation, individual identity, and shared meanings, which are a paramount part of the way we perceive, explore, and experience the world around us (Bloor et al.,2001).

As far as this study is concerned, two focus groups were conducted with English Master learners (six (n6) from the East University and six (n6) from the West University). Both sessions were separately carried out in the East and West campuses. Each session took one hour, and it involved learners from different cultural backgrounds (Malian learners and Algerian learners with diverse sub-cultures). I made sure that Malian learners take part in this study to explore their experiences of learning and living in different linguistic and cultural environments, as well as to demonstrate the necessity of the integration of intercultural communicative competence in Algerian Higher Education, as it gathers students from diverse cultural backgrounds. It was significant to conduct focus groups to gather learners from different cultures. By doing this, I gave the participants the power to speak out and use their own voices while being stimulated by others' comments and thoughts. The participants were able to express their views about their experience of majoring in English in Algeria and to what extent ICC is embedded in the Algerian context.

4.6 Design of Research Tools

The research employed a combination of semi-structured interviews, online questionnaires, and focus groups to explore the teaching and learning of intercultural communicative competence (ICC) in Algerian Higher Education.

- **Interviews**

Semi-structured interviews were chosen for their flexibility and depth, allowing a detailed exploration of teachers' conceptualisations and understanding of culture and ICC. The interview protocol was carefully structured to answer the first, the second and the fourth research questions. It comprises three sections; the first set of questions served as warming-up questions to gain insights into participants' experiences of teaching English as a Foreign Language in the chosen contexts, such as how long they have been teaching English and what languages they use in the classroom. These initial questions provided an overview to understand the participants' backgrounds. The focus of this study was not on the first set of

questions as this research aims to explore how teachers perceive notions of culture and intercultural communicative competence (ICC).

The second set of questions addressed the participants' perspectives and understanding of the notion of culture, how it is embedded in the course and how important it is for teachers to promote cultural diversity in the classroom. This aligns with the first research question: How do Algerian English Language teachers perceive and understand the concept of culture and how it is placed in their English language teaching practices?

The third set of questions aimed to explore participants' perceptions of intercultural communicative competence and how important it is for them to develop learners' intercultural attitudes, skills, knowledge and critical cultural awareness. Furthermore, it aimed to explore the participants' intercultural lived experiences and how their exposure to different cultures influenced their teaching practices in Algeria.

The fourth set of questions addressed teacher training. Participants were asked if they had attended any training related to ICC or other relevant concepts, and what kind of ICC training they think is paramount to be provided by policymakers.

The interview ended with participants reflecting on Byram's model of ICC, and sharing valuable and rich insights about their intercultural encounters and understanding of ICC. This effectively answered the second research question of this study: what are Algerian English Language teachers' understandings and conceptions of intercultural communicative competence? How do their intercultural encounters influence their teaching practices?

The Semi-structured interviews were also conducted with two members of the intercultural club (The Global Representative of Cultures) to gain a deeper understanding of their perceptions of the notion of interculturality and its role in the establishment of this club. This addressed the fourth research question of this study: how does the model of intercultural speaking clubs contribute to the development of ICC?

- **Online questionnaire**

The online questionnaires consisted of 14 items divided into three main sections. The first section collected demographic information about the participants (learners), including their nationality, age, speciality, years of study, and motives for majoring in English. Additionally, It addressed the learners' perspectives on the effective methods for achieving language proficiency. This section aimed to gain a general background about the participants (learners),

providing a foundation for interpreting their responses in the second section. In general, this section addressed learners' perspectives of their English learning experience in the East and West universities. This set of questions helped me to be more aware of the diverse cultures that exist in the classroom. The second section of the questionnaire focused on examining learners' attitudes toward language skills and competencies developed in the classroom as well as their goals of majoring in English. It also tackled their understanding of the notion of culture. The third section comprises a mix of closed and open-ended questions designed to capture and explore the participants' (learners) perceptions of intercultural communicative competence and their exposure to different cultures. This section (open-ended questions) aimed to provide deeper insights into how learners understand and navigate cultural diversity within and outside the classroom. The online questionnaire addressed learners' perspectives of their English learning experience and their understanding of the notions of culture and ICC. The questionnaire provided valuable data to answer the third research question.

- **Focus group discussions**

The focus group protocol was divided into two sections. The first section examined learners' experience of learning English, their understanding of culture, and the importance they place on developing cultural and intercultural awareness. This exploration was intended to uncover the learners' foundational knowledge and attitudes towards culture. The second section of the protocol addressed learners' perspectives and conceptualisations of ICC. It sought to investigate how learners define and perceive ICC, along with their practical experiences of intercultural interactions. This section was crucial for understanding the learners' deeper cognitive and affective responses to cultural diversity and their ability to effectively navigate intercultural encounters in their academic and social lives.

The data that emerged from the online questionnaires and focus group discussions that were conducted in the East and West Universities answered the third research question of this study: what are Master English learners' perceptions and attitudes of culture and intercultural communicative competence, and what extent ICC is embedded in their English learning?

While the online questionnaire provided valuable insights, the focus group discussions allowed for a deeper exploration of the phenomenon under investigation. I conducted focus group discussions with learners from both universities to underpin and gain a more comprehensive understanding of the learners' perspectives and experiences. Although the

questionnaire was useful in gathering initial data, the focus group discussions were crucial in obtaining more nuanced and in-depth information, enriching the study's findings.

The combination of quantitative data from the questionnaires and qualitative insights from the interviews and focus groups offered a rich and comprehensive understanding of teachers' and learners' perspectives.

This study provides new insights and valuable perspectives into a context (Algeria) that is unexplored in the literature by exploring an under-researched phenomenon (ICC) within the Algerian context, therefore, it provides a detailed understanding of ICC in the field of language education. It also adds to the literature by demonstrating the need to re-evaluate the outdated English language teaching approaches and methods in Algeria.

The study's findings align with existing research on the significance of integrating intercultural dimensions into language education (Byram, 1997). By linking the design of each instrument to the relevant research questions, the study was able to address its objectives and provide useful insights into the field of intercultural education.

4.7 Data Analysis

The analysis of the data collected follows the same sequence of the research design adopted for the present research study. After collecting data, according to Bloomberg and Volpe, the next stage is "to manage, organise, and make sense of all of the separate pieces of accumulated information" (Bloomberg and Volpe, 2012, p.134).

Qualitative data analysis encompasses "organising, accounting for and explaining the data" (Cohen et al., 2011, p. 537). In short, it is to make data sound logical and intelligible concerning the participants' themes, categories and situations under investigation. Cohen et al (2011) stated that qualitative research quickly complies with massive amounts of data, which, in turn, requires an analysis to reduce and minimise the issue of overloaded data, by picking out only the most relevant data. Huberman and Saldana (2013) added an interactive process for analysing, it comprises three streams:

Data reduction: this stage takes place regularly throughout the analysis. In the early stages, it occurs through editing, segmenting, and summarising the data. The middle stage takes place through coding and memoing accompanied by activities such as coming up with themes, clusters and, patterns to transform the hundred pages of interviews and focus group transcripts into a one-page matrix, it is also called condensing the data. The final stage

happens through conceptualising and explaining the abstract data. Thus, in my research project, it is essential to pick the most important data among the raw data that answers the research questions. It is worth mentioning that the main purpose of data reduction at this stage is to reduce the data without the loss of significant information.

Data display: because qualitative data is enormous and bulky, it is very important to display data by organising, compressing, and assembling it. Miles and Huberman (1994) considered it as a fundamental stage and overwhelmingly, used the phrase 'you know what you display'. Therefore, the validation of qualitative data can be achieved through the data the researcher opted to display.

Drawing and verifying conclusion: the main purpose of data reduction and data display is to facilitate drawing conclusions. The stages of drawing and verifying conclusions are likely to follow or take place at the same time as the reduction and display stages. Thus, conclusions can be noted early in the analysis, but they may remain vague, unclear, and ill-formed at this stage. They are not completed until all the data are in and have been analysed. This stage aims to merge what has been done so far into a comprehensible, meaningful, and coherent picture of the data. The three stages overall are intertwined and synchronous throughout the data analysis, the first two stages remain basically on the operation of coding and memoing. These later are the two fundamental operations that keep the analysis going in qualitative research.

According to Cohen et al (2011), there is no single or valid tendency to analyse and present qualitative data. Thus, the researcher should adhere to the issue of fitness for purpose, where there are multiple interpretations to be built and supplied to fit the purpose of the qualitative research study under investigation. Further, this process is a "reiterative" back-and-forth process (Teddlie and Tashakkori, 2009, p.251); as the researcher notes thoughts, reflections, and memos (Cohen et al, 2011).

4.7.1 Approaches to Qualitative Data Analysis

Trochim (2006) categorises two comprehensive modes of reasoning. The inductive and deductive approaches. He views inductive reasoning as the process of moving from the specific to the general, while the deductive approach involves starting with the general and ending with the specific. In other words, the inductive approach focuses on developing new theories, conceptual frameworks, and conclusions through the generation of data from the

field (Trochim and Donnelly, 2006). According to Creswell and Plano Clark (2007), the inductive mode is when the researcher employs a "bottom-up" approach, using participants' perspectives, attitudes, and experiences to develop a range of themes, and new categories, and construct an interconnected theory (p.23). Conversely, researchers conducting a deductive approach commence with an existing theory, previous research findings, or a hypothesis and then test its validity using observation and other instruments. In this approach, themes do not emerge from the gathered data; instead, they emerge from existing theories, models, and a pre-set of research questions (Given, 2008). The deductive researcher employs a "top-down" approach, progressing from theory to hypotheses to data to either enhance or challenge the theory (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2007, p.23). Arguments that are concerned with individuals' perspectives, views, and experiences are more effectively expressed inductively, whereas arguments based on established laws, and rules, are better expressed deductively. Various scholars have advocated for the inductive approach, such as Glaser and Strauss (1967, p.3), who deem it "the best approach" for systematically generating theories from analysing data in social research. After that, the researcher can ensure that the theory aligns and functions effectively. The implementation of the inductive technique allows researchers to establish the compatibility of a particular theory with a particular empirical context ensuring its comprehensibility to a broad audience.

My study is exploratory and interpretive in nature, which indicates my inclination towards an inductive approach. This inclination is evident in the nature of my research questions, research design, and my chosen data collection methods. My approach involves conducting interviews with Algerian English language teachers and the GRC members of the intercultural club. Questionnaires and focus groups with learners of English in two differently located universities in Algeria, were carried out, aiming to delve into their attitudes and experiences rather than solely relying on data extracted from existing literature and established theories. Nevertheless, it is crucial to acknowledge that despite starting my fieldwork after reviewing the literature, the existing body of knowledge undeniably influenced and supported me throughout both the data collection and the data analysis phases. Essentially, a researcher's theoretical foundation contributes to forming their perspectives and attitudes (Charmaz, 1996), making it an integral aspect that cannot be disregarded. Strauss and Corbin (1998) acknowledge this point as a limitation of the inductive approach, highlighting that even

though researchers may seek to adopt an inductive methodology, they usually begin with some level of theoretical understanding.

During the coding process and while constructing themes, I realised that various perspectives and ideas shared by my participants had already been explored in previous studies. Moreover, I noted that while coding the data, I could establish connections to the literature I had previously reviewed. For instance, I identified a direct link between the dimensions of Byram's (1997) model of intercultural communicative competence and participants' attitudes towards the teaching and learning of ICC in the EFL context. However, this does not imply that I approached my study deductively. When I started collecting my data, I aimed to collect participants' perspectives of culture and ICC and how these notions are addressed in the classroom. I also sought to explore the GRC's perspectives and experiences of creating an intercultural club at the West University. Most of the participants from the West University evoked works of various scholars such as Byram (1997), Bennett (1993), and Deardorff (2006) and they expressed how crucial it is to integrate ICC into the curricula. Their perspectives and awareness of ICC were based on existing literature. Therefore, my study was conducted through a combination of both inductive and deductive approaches.

4.7.2 Thematic coding approach

- This generic approach does not have to be linked with a specific theoretical framework.
- All or part of the data are classified, coded, and labelled according to the researcher's potential interest.
- Codes under the same label are grouped as a theme.
- Codes and themes that emerge from the data can be organised following deductive or inductive thematic analysis by reviewing the data or linking it to the existing literature or research questions (Robson, 2011).

The thematic coding approach is the method of analysis employed in the present study. Firstly, its flexibility can be used with all types of qualitative data. Secondly, it equips the researcher with means to summarise key features of huge amounts of qualitative data, it is not bounded to a particular level of interpretation and can be applied in different disciplines (Robson, 2011). Last but not least, this approach can be used either as a realist or as a constructivist method. Realism can report the experiences and meanings, it depicts the real

world of the participants. Constructivism, explores and examines how realities and experiences are the effects of a variety of discourses operating within society.

- **Codes and Coding**

Coding is an essential strategy of any qualitative data analysis (Robson, 2011). A code refers simply to a name or a label that the researcher gives to a text that comprises an idea (Cohen et al., 2011). Kerlinger (1970) defines coding as the translation of respondent answers to particular categories for analysis. In the same vein, codes are also called tags, names, or labels, hence, code is the process of putting codes or tags on a piece of information. This data can be words, phrases, or large chunks of information. The purpose of using labels is to give meaning to the data, it also enables summarising the data by grouping it under themes. The coding process involves comparing new chunks of data with previous ones. Therefore, similar chunks will be tagged with the same code, and this process is referred to as a “constant comparison analysis” (Robson, 2011, p.474). After the coding stage, it comes grouping the initial codes into smaller units of themes. Theme is not clearly defined; it typically captures something related to the research questions. According to Miles and Huberman (1984), there are two levels of coding; first and second-level coding. First-level coding refers to the process of attaching labels to groups of words, this level of coding is also referred to as descriptive coding, which involves little or no inferences beyond the data itself. This level is an essential starting point for analysing the data; it enables the researcher to get a feel of the data; summarises the segments of the information obtained; and supplies the researcher with a basis for later higher-order coding. Later codes can be in a more interpretive manner that involves degrees of inferences beyond the data. Thus, the second level of coding requires grouping the initial codes into smaller and meaningful numbers of themes (Robson, 2011).

- **Coding Process**

Thematic analysis was employed to identify themes and patterns within the data. Firstly, the interviews and focus groups were transcribed through careful and repeated listening to the records. After the transcription, the data was imported into NVivo, which served as a valuable tool for organising, managing, and analysing qualitative data. NVivo is used to analyse the data generated from the interviews and learners’ focus groups, as this computer software is considered by Robson (2011) as the most preferable software for qualitative data analysis. As stated by Robson (2011), NVivo in this study helped to handle huge amounts of raw data

quickly, provided one systematised storage system for all the stored data, and provided easy and quick access to the coded material. It made it easy to display the results in different manners and helped to analyse commonalities, differences, and relationships between the coded units (Robson, 2011).

The first step after the transcription process was the familiarisation with data through repeatedly reading the transcripts to gain a comprehensive understanding of the content.

The initial stage of analysis started by identifying initial codes for essential sections and texts in the interviews and focus group discussions. Each of the significant passages was assigned an initial code that encapsulated its idea. Passages about the same subject were allocated the same codes. Many initial codes were generated from the interviews such as "Culture as everything", "Culture as defined by national boundaries", "Culture as a behaviour", and "Culture as fluid and dynamic entity". These initial codes were then grouped into broader categories or themes (organisational themes) based on similarities and patterns observed in the data (Attride-Stirling, 2001). For instance, the above-indicated initial codes were grouped under one organisational theme, which is "Teachers' definitions of culture". Both "ICC as an art of embracing diversity" and "ICC as a communicative competence" as initial codes were also grouped under "Teachers' conceptions of ICC" as an organisational theme. Concerning the focus group discussions, initial codes such as "English and French status in Algeria" and "Learners' expectations versus reality" were classified under "English learning experience in Algeria" as a global theme (Attride-Stirling, 2001).

Finally, the generated organisational themes in both interviews and focus group discussions were also consolidated under global themes, providing a comprehensive and structured representation of the multi-layered data.

In my research, themes emerged through a combination of deductive and inductive reasoning (Soiferman, 2010). Deductive reasoning guided the initial identification of themes based on established theories and literature in intercultural communication and language education. For example, I have anticipated themes related to cultural awareness, language proficiency, and intercultural communicative competence based on the model proposed by Byram (1997). My research also incorporated inductive reasoning, allowing new themes to emerge from the data itself. As I engaged with the rich qualitative data collected from interviews and focus group discussions, I remained open to unexpected patterns and insights that may not have been captured by pre-existing theories alone. For example, the role of intercultural speaking

clubs in promoting cross-cultural understanding among students emerged through the participants' narratives at the West University.

4.8 Coding the Participants

In the focus group discussions and questionnaires, each learner (L) participant was assigned a unique code that integrated both the initial of their university origins (E or W) and a numerical identifier. For instance, participants from the East University were labelled as EL followed by a numerical distinction such as "EL1" and "EL2" while participants from the West University were assigned codes consisting of letters followed by alphabets such as "WLA" and "WLB".

Teachers from both universities were assigned codes (Teacher) followed by alphabets for the East University and numbers for the West University such as "Teacher A" and "Teacher 1".

Additionally, the members of the intercultural club were assigned codes using the initials of the club (The Global Representatives of Culture) followed by numerical identifiers. For example, GRC1 and GRC2

This coding system allowed for the easy categorisation of participants according to their universities. Moreover, it contributed to participant anonymity, safeguarding their identities as promised in the consent forms (Robson, 2011).

4.9 Ethics

The term ethics refers to "the philosophy that addresses questions about morality" (Wiles, 2013, p.197). He demonstrated that the concepts "ethics and morals" are used interchangeably (p.197). Researchers in the social science field argued that ethical dilemmas are context-specific by which the basis to make an ethical decision in social science research is to include adherence to participants' rights, high respect for all the participants, and a commitment to knowledge by preserving the participants' rights to know that they will take part in your research before conducting the research. There is a slight difference between notions of ethics and morals. Ethics, generally, refer to a set of principles to what the researcher ought to do. However, morals usually refer to a particular act, whether this act is coordinated with right or wrong, good or bad. Ethics in research is important as long as the research undertaken has to deal with people's behaviours or observations of their interactions. Hence, ethics preserve the participants' rights and provide them with respect, trust, and safety.

In conducting any social research, the researcher should take into consideration the ethical issues at an early stage of the research process (Robson, 2011). Importantly speaking, these forms of ethical issues could stem from the nature of the research study itself including the contextual framework of the research, procedures of data collection, the nature of the participants, and the way of reporting, analysing, and interpreting the collected data (Cohen et al., 2011).

In this study, EFL Algerian teachers and Master learners willingly participated in this research. They were all provided with an information sheet that explained in detail the rationale of the study, as well as they were given a consent form to fill out and sign before the data collection phase. Participation in the present study was voluntary, and the participants were free to withdraw at any stage they wanted. This research project followed four ethical principles or codes which are respect, competence, responsibility, and integrity (British Psychological Society, 2009).

- **Respect:** by taking into consideration the dignity and value of the participants including their rights, preserving their confidentiality, and signing the consent form.
- **Competence:** by being aware of my ongoing professional development and maintaining my role as a researcher in the most appropriate way. Using my knowledge, experience, and skills to guide the research.
- **Responsibility:** by taking the whole responsibility that my participants are safe, not causing them any kind of harm, deceiving them, or forcing them to participate.
- **Integrity:** by considering clarity, fairness, honesty, and clarity in my communication with the respondents and fostering integrity in all aspects of data collection.

4.9.1 Informed consent

Informed consent involves ensuring that research participants are fully aware of the research and their expected involvement in it (Daniels, 2008). In my study, participation was voluntary, and participants were informed of their right to withdraw at any time they wanted or to refuse to answer any question they felt uncomfortable about (Christians, 2005). One of the principles of informed consent outlines the researcher's responsibility to elucidate to the participants the various aspects of the research clearly and comprehensively. These explanations involve who is conducting the research; the study's nature; the study's rationale and objectives; the potential role of the participants; how the participants' rights are

preserved; how the data is gathered and how it will be disseminated (Piper and Simons, 2005; Walliman, 2005; Wiles, 2013; Webster et al., 2014).

Informed consent is defined by Diener and Crandall (1978) as “the procedures in which individuals choose whether to participate in an investigation after being informed of facts that would be likely to influence their decisions” (quoted in Cohen et al., 2011, p.78). This definition comprises four components: competence, voluntarism, full information, and comprehension. Competence refers to the responsibility of mature individuals, who can make correct decisions when they are given the information sheet and consent form. Researchers must ensure not to engage with individuals who are incapable of making this decision; voluntarism involves applying the essence of informed consent and guaranteeing that participants are free to take part in the research. Furthermore, the researcher should ensure that the physical, social, and psychological well-being of the participants is not affected by any means during the research. The relationship between the research participants should be based on mutual respect and trust; full information entails that the consent is fully informed, though it is sometimes impossible for researchers in practice to inform participants of everything because the researchers themselves do not know everything about the investigation especially on the fieldwork. Comprehension indicates that subjects fully comprehend the nature of the research under investigation even if the procedures are complicated. The participants should ensure that they are fully aware of the situation they are putting themselves into (Cohen et al., 2011).

In this regard, the researcher is responsible for providing the research participants with a full detailed information sheet about the research project and making sure that they all understand what taking part in research might entail (Wiles, 2013).

In this study, informed consent forms were sent to English language teachers and members of intercultural clubs via email. However, for Master English language learners, I posted the consent forms and information sheet on the Facebook page I created to gather the learners from the East and West universities. Sending informed consent forms before starting the data collection was to allow the informants to have sufficient time to read and decide whether to take part in my study or not. On the day of the interviews and focus groups, participants were allowed to ask any questions they had about the research study or their roles.

4.9.2 Anonymity and Confidentiality

When engaging in the process of analysing qualitative data, which encompasses transcription of the data, the analysis process itself, and presenting findings and excerpts from the data, the ethical considerations regarding anonymity and confidentiality become paramount (Flick, 2007). Ensuring confidentiality throughout the research process, and respecting and valuing the privacy of the participants who participated in the study (Piper and Simons, 2005), were deemed vital concerns in my research. The core of anonymity is that the data gathered should in no way reveal the participants' identity as it is regarded as a significant ethical practice in ethical research boards (Robson, 2011). The participants are therefore considered anonymous in the research. By preserving confidentiality and anonymity in my study, participants felt empowered to speak openly and had the option to withhold publication of any material they deemed potentially harmful, although this situation did not arise in the context of this study, as verified through the member-checking process.

4.10 Trustworthiness of the research

According to Seale (1999), trustworthiness is considered a fundamental criterion for assessing the quality of qualitative research. Its alternatives in quantitative research are reliability and validity (Flick, 2007; Bryman, 2016). While positivists often question the trustworthiness of qualitative research, some methodologists highlight how qualitative researchers can incorporate measures to address trustworthiness concerns (Shenton, 2004). Lincoln and Guba (1985) suggest four criteria that should be taken into account when conducting a qualitative study: credibility, transferability, dependability, and conformability (Guba and Lincoln, 1985). Each of these elements has corresponding criteria within the realm of quantitative research: internal validity, external validity, reliability, and objectivity, respectively (Miller, 2008). In the following sections, I discuss each of these criteria in detail.

4.10.1 Credibility

Qualitative researchers view reality as multidimensional, and constantly evolving (Merriam, 2009). Therefore, it is their responsibility to ensure that their findings align appropriately with this complex reality (Merriam, 1998; Shenton, 2004). Wellington (2015) defines credibility as the degree to which a document is sincere and unbiased. According to Lincoln and Guba (1985), credibility in qualitative research is achieved when the researcher's interpretation of the collected data aligns with the participants' constructed realities. Similarly, Robson (2002)

asserts that providing comprehensive information about the data collection methods, in addition to the researchers' rationale and their justification of choosing a particular research design supports the credibility of the findings. To achieve credibility in my study, triangulation approach was employed through conducting semi-structured interviews, focus group discussions and online questionnaires with diverse categories of participants (teachers, Algerian learners, Malian learners, and GRC members). The inclusion of diverse individuals in the sample enriched the research process by facilitating an in-depth investigation of the research topic using multiple viewpoints. Additionally, the study used consent form that elucidated the aim and objectives of the research. The consent form provided information about the researcher's credentials and ensured the privacy of data and the anonymity of participants.

I sought guidance from my supervisor, she reviewed the sections where I illustrated the methods and research design selected for this. Additionally, I sent her the transcription and the themes I extracted and asked her to review and confirm the accuracy of the information. I also sent the transcription to some of the participants to ensure that their perspectives were recorded correctly.

4.10.1 Transferability

Transferability in qualitative research refers to the extent to which the findings, conclusions, and insights derived from a study conducted in a specific context can be applied or transferred to other similar contexts or settings (Tashakkori and Teddlie, 2003). Unlike generalizability in quantitative research, which aims to apply findings to a larger population, transferability in qualitative research focuses on the potential applicability of the results to different situations or settings. It involves considering whether the findings are relevant and meaningful beyond the immediate context of the study and whether they can inform and enrich understanding in other similar contexts. This study was conducted in Algeria with Algerian English Language teachers, Master English learners (Algerian and Malian), and members of the cultural club. The concept of transferability revolves around where the findings of this study can be applicable in a different context of teaching and learning English as a Foreign Language in higher education. However, this task can be challenging due to the small sample of this research. The purpose of conducting this research was not to make generalisations, but rather to gain a comprehensive and detailed understanding of how English Language teachers and

learners perceive the notion of ICC and how it is addressed in the classroom, and how the creation of intercultural club helps in promoting inclusivity in education.

Patton (2002) highlights that transferability entails the idea that the findings of a particular research can be contextualised and fundamental in the setting where the research was conducted. Importantly speaking, in qualitative studies, it is often not possible to transfer the findings to a different setting at different times because qualitative researchers tend to reach findings that might be valid within a particular time and a particular setting (Lincoln and Guba, 1985).

4.10.3 Dependability

Dependability in qualitative research refers to the stability and consistency of the entire research process, deciding about the conceptual framework, choosing the methods, the process of collecting the data and interpreting the findings. Therefore, the researcher should be accurate and diligent when conducting the research. A crucial aspect of ensuring dependability in my study is providing adequate justification for the selection of participants, the timing, and the setting of conducting interviews and focus groups. The more consistent the research process is, the more reliable the findings become. Furthermore, achieving dependability involves documenting the whole research process including ethical procedures, the methods used to collect the data, steps of analysing data in detail so that they can be easily accessed, replicated, or verified by other researchers (Lincoln and Guba, 1985; Creswell and Miller, 2000; Bryman, 2016). In this study, I have consistently saved all the documents in hard and electronic formats. Additionally, I have thoroughly explained and justified all the choices made throughout the research.

4.10.4 Conformability

Conformability refers to the researcher's ability to maintain objectivity and ensure that their theoretical inclinations and personal values do not unduly impact the study under investigation (Bryman, 2012). It is important to acknowledge that achieving complete objectivity in my research is challenging and might be impossible. However, I made my best effort to minimise the influence of my personal opinions and perspectives during the process of conducting interviews, and focus groups, and during the analysis of the data to accurately present the participants' voices (Bryman, 2012). To assure conformability, I employed a triangulation approach, I also engaged in member checking, a process of sending interviews

and focus group transcripts to the participants to check how accurately their perspectives were recorded (Lincoln and Guba, 1985; Lunsford, 2009). However, I was not able to do the member checking with all participants because of their unavailability. As an alternative, I sought assistance from my supervisor who read my findings, evaluated the data analysis, and provided valuable feedback. Having external perspectives proved to be immensely beneficial in validating the accuracy and trustworthiness of my interpretations. Confirmability can be attained by maintaining self-awareness of one's own perspectives, emotions, actions, and reactions in relation to the experiences and behaviours of participants (Miles and Huberman, 1994, Shenton, 2004). Thus, being aware of my position in this research (insider-outsider) is significant in reducing bias.

4.11 Concluding the chapter

In this chapter, I presented the ontological (constructivism), epistemological (interpretivism) and methodological stances that guided my research to gain rich insights and understandings of how Algerian English language teachers and learners perceive culture and intercultural communicative competence in teaching and learning English as a Foreign Language in Algerian higher education context. This chapter elucidates how the adopted methodological choices guided me to explore in detail the intercultural club members' perspectives on how this club contributes to the development of learners' ICC. Furthermore, the chapter demonstrated the justification for the methodological procedures, the choice of mixed research methods, the sampling techniques, the data collection instruments and data analysis. I explained the sampling techniques used to recruit participants in this research study, following this, I justified the choice of semi-structured interviews, questionnaires, and focus group discussions. The ethical issues that might be encountered while conducting this study were also addressed in this chapter.

Chapter Five

Algerian English Language Teachers' Perceptions and Conceptions of Culture and ICC

5.1 Introduction

I used Creswell's exploratory research design to answer the four research questions raised in the present research study. After getting the consent forms signed, the data collection phase took place in Algeria at two different Algerian Universities (East and West), and it was carried out over two months from April to June 2018. Two phases were carried out: the first qualitative phase involved collecting semi-structured interviews and online questionnaires. The participants who took part in the semi-structured interviews were twelve (n12) in total. Ten (n10) Algerian English language teachers, five (n5) from the East University and five (n5) from the West University in Algeria. The online questionnaires were carried out with English language learners from both universities. The second phase of the data collection consisted of two focus group discussions with Master learners of English from both universities researched. Furthermore, the two other interviews left were conducted with two (n2) Algerian members, alumnus students, of the intercultural club which was established at the West University. The semi-structured interviews are designed to bring out a vivid picture of the informant's lived experiences and understanding of the research phenomena (Mack et al., 2005).

I would argue that semi-structured interviews conducted in the first phase of the research were the most suitable type of interview because of their flexibility in following up on emerging questions and their ability to give the interviewee enough space and time to discuss certain issues (Dörnyei, 2007). I opted for this type of interview because it allowed me to ask the participants the same questions but not compulsory in the same sequence, order, or wording. It also allowed me to add some questions and comments, which were necessarily required in this research to let the interview flow naturally in a seamlessly connected way. Carrying out twelve semi-structured interviews aided me in gaining participants' information about their perspectives of intercultural communicative competence and the intercultural experiences they encountered abroad.

The interviews were transcribed in a secured software Nvivo12 provided by the West of Scotland University and the data was analysed and interpreted after repeated readings to outline the basic, organisational, and global themes (Sterling, 2001), and to identify the similarities and discrepancies in the participants' attitudes and perceptions.

In this chapter, I present the research findings about Algerian English language teachers' perceptions and beliefs about the implementation and the teaching of culture in EFL classrooms. The chapter also demonstrates their understanding of ICC and how its dimensions are embedded in their teaching practices. Moreover, Algerian English language teachers' intercultural lived experiences and how such experiences promoted their awareness of ICC are addressed and discussed in this chapter. These findings answer the first and the second research questions of this study: 1. How do Algerian English Language teachers perceive and understand the concept of culture and how it is placed in their English language teaching practices? and 2. What are Algerian English Language teachers' understandings and conceptions of intercultural communicative competence? How does their intercultural lived experience foster their ICC teaching practices?

Semi-structured interviews analyses

During the transcription phase, my focus was not on the questions I used in the interview appointments, but it was on close listening to the responses and categorising themes on how interviewees think, view and perceive the world reality. After transcribing and recurrent reading of the data, I grouped the participants' perceptions into global meaningful units. I generated for each meaningful unit a meaningful brief phrase, which covers different basic themes that will be illustrated in the following section (Sterling, 2001).

Numbers will be used to identify participants from West University; however, letters will be used to refer to participants from East University to preserve their anonymity as promised in the consent forms.

5.2 Teachers' Perspectives of Culture

All participants in this research are teaching English as a Foreign Language (EFL) in two different Algerian universities (East and West). Participants from the West University are teaching English to students whose speciality is Language and Communication. This speciality encompasses the subject of intercultural communicative competence (ICC). While

participants from East University are teaching English to students whose major is Didactics of Languages and Foreign Cultures.

As it was mentioned before culture is the most paramount concept in this research study; therefore, exploring the participants' perceptions and definitions of the term culture was crucial and significant. At first, most of the participants from both universities found defining the concept of culture challenging, maybe due to the complexity of the term itself (Kramsch, 2003). However, some participants from the East University viewed culture as something tangible, observable and obtainable from the society (Hall, 1976; Moore, 1996). During the interview, in many ways, their definitions of culture were either describing and listing the aspects of culture, which were related to their national culture, in most cases, these concepts were related to capital C culture (Peterson, 2004; Lee, 2009), as it is demonstrated in this quotation "culture is my traditions, my language, my values, my beliefs, my customs and taboos" (Teacher E). This perception of culture seems to identify the cultural groups that individuals belong to, rather than understanding their beliefs, behaviours and actions (Yuen, 2011; Canale, 2016), which aligns with the big C aspects of culture.

Another group of participants viewed culture as something complex, nondefinable, and dynamic (Witte and Harden, 2011). As it is stated by Teacher 2, from West University, "It is very difficult to define culture because the meaning of the concept escapes certain limitations, certain boundaries, and certain approaches. I believe culture is all about being different" Teacher 2.

It is interesting to mention that Teacher B from the East University asked me from which perspective she is supposed to define the concept of culture, as someone who never travelled abroad or as an Algerian who lived abroad. According to Teacher B, the way people perceive the concept of culture differs from a person who has never experienced another culture but his/her own, and a person who travelled/lived abroad. In the following section, in detail, I present and discuss the salient participants' conceptions and definitions of the concept of culture.

5.2.1 Teachers' Definitions of Culture

5.2.1.1 Culture as a whole and everything

There was a prevalent tendency among the majority of teachers from East University and some teachers from West University to characterise the concept of culture as "all" or

“everything” (Cuzzort, 1969), to illustrate that culture is everything that people do, have, think and behave as members of society. This is demonstrated by Teacher 4 who stated that “Culture is everything! we have beliefs, traditions, literature, arts even your way of seeing things, your way of doing things” Teacher 4. Another teacher from the East University viewed it as “everything, culture is a sum of many things, it’s a way we speak, how we live, how we behave, how we deal with people.... everything I would say in a word” Teacher D. I asked the participants to further explain what “everything” means. Their perceptions turned into an essentialist structural definition, which is associated with fixed and static aspects of culture that are shared by members of the same society. This first perception of culture as “everything” (Horton and Hunt, 1984), or as an enumerative list was common among teachers from the East University except one, who viewed culture as a complex entity that should be lived and experienced and should not be limited to words. This was posited by Teacher A, “I think that culture is something one should live rather than just explain”.

Some other participants from the West University shared the same perspective of culture as “everything”. Some participants, particularly, from the first site (East University) tend to list the salient features of culture instead of defining it, it was sometimes perceived as a shortcut to bypass the intricacy and multidimensionality of the concept of culture (Risager, 2007). In this regard, teachers’ understanding of the notion of culture seemed to underestimate its complexity (Nieto, 2002).

5.2.1.2 Culture as defined by national boundaries

In accordance with the first perception, which portrayed culture as “everything”, another common definition was shared among Algerian English language teachers from both sites (East and West University) was that culture is a “way of life” of a particular community or geographical region. They also tended to state an enumerative list, which encompasses all the different aspects of culture such as traditions, language, identity, customs, religion, behaviours, and lifestyle of a group of people, who live in a particular geographical region and share different aspects of life. Teacher D reported that culture is “a way of life with your people, with yourself, and it is about traditions, behaviours and customs”.

Only one participant (Teacher 5) from the West University viewed culture as a way of life that is related to people of the same nation stating that “culture is a way of life of people who share the same principles, norms, religion, and language”. The first and the second

perceptions of culture seem to favour an essentialist-generalised view of culture (Elsen and St. John, 2007). Hence, culture is perceived by some participants as a static, unchangeable phenomenon that is related to a particular nation (Algerian culture, French culture). In this regard, culture is perceived as something that can be customised based on the geographical and national boundaries of a particular nation. This perspective aligns with an essentialist view of culture (Holliday, 2010; Baker, 2015).

5.2.1.3 Culture as a way for language mastery

Some teachers from the East University demonstrated the interlinked relationship between the target language (English) and the target culture (British). When I asked **Teacher C** to share her perspective of what is culture, she did not provide a clear definition, instead, she referred to the target culture (British culture) she teaches in the classroom.

Culture refers to the big C culture, there are two modules that deal with that. We have American and British literature, and we have culture and civilisation of the language. British and American civilisation these are separate modules, and they aim to teach about the target culture to master the language (**Teacher C**).

It is intriguing to state that **Teacher C** did define the concept of culture, but instead, she listed the modules which address the target culture in the classroom at the East University. This may go back to her lack of associating a clear definition to the concept and limiting it to the target culture. Moreover, she demonstrated the significance of teaching the target culture (the big C culture) such as teaching learners about old British civilisations and history to help them master the English language. In addition, she remarkably perceived the small c culture as a way of life of native speakers of English. However, according to her, tackling the small c culture is not mandatory in the curriculum and it is not considered a significant aim in teaching English as a FL in the classroom at the East University. She (**Teacher C**) stated that “when it comes to the small c culture of native speakers, it’s up to the teacher’s preferences, if he wants to include it in his curriculum or not”. Additionally, **Teacher D** perceived culture as a tool for expanding students’ vocabulary and enhancing their pronunciation skills. He believed that incorporating cultural elements into lessons, students are exposed to new words and expressions “learning the target culture helps students to enlarge their vocabulary”. This perspective makes it clear that teachers from the East University view culture as an add-on to foster the teaching of English language (Luk,2012). It can be also considered as a finished

product (British literature/civilisation) resulting in neglecting the dynamic nature of the notion of culture, and potentially leading to the formation of essentialist understandings of culture (Liddicoat and Scarino, 2013; Baker, 2015).

5.2.1.4 Culture as a behaviour

Among all participants, two viewed the concept culture as a “behaviour of people”. Thus, they believed that culture shows and dictates on the individual how to behave and react on everything. As it is demonstrated, in the following quotation, by participant from the East University, “culture is everything, it’s the way we speak, how we behave and how we deal with people” **Teacher D**. Another participant from the West University agreed that “culture is a way of seeing things, a way of doing things, and language is part of culture too” **Teacher 4**. As these above-mentioned definitions of culture appear to be tangible, visible, and accessible to a specific group of people, as it is opposed to many other aspects of culture, it can be understood that these aspects can be learned and acquired from society. Furthermore, these perceptions are considered to be under the category of essentialist-generalised definition of culture (Holiday, 2010; Baker, 2015).

5.2.1.5 Culture as a dynamic entity

Most of the participants from the West University agreed on the fact that culture is a complex and undefinable term that cannot be limited to a particular fixed definition (Witte and Harden, 2011). **Teacher 1** and **Teacher 2** emphasised that the definition of the notion of culture cannot be limited neither to the features of big C culture or the small c culture, nor to the lifestyle, traditions, and norms of a particular community, but as something dynamic, evolving, and complex that words cannot describe.

It’s not easy to define culture. You cannot limit culture to the big C and the small c. You cannot limit culture to the triangle approach. You can never limit it to these notions, culture is much more um it’s not just traditions, lifestyle, and the way you dress, it is fluid, It’s the way you are, the way of perceiving yourself, and the way you perceive the other (**Teacher 1**).

Teacher 1 viewed culture as a “way” of perceiving and understanding one’s self and the other. Likewise, **Teacher 2** demonstrated that he made several researches in order to understand and locate the term culture with a perception. According to him, culture escapes many limitations and boundaries of the traditions, values, and customs of a particular community. It is rather about “being different, flexible, welcoming and caring about the other”. **Teacher**

2's perception of the term culture was not based on the old conventional definitions, but he associated his understanding of the notion of culture with the ICC conceptions. It is worth elucidating that this teacher's demonstrated his teaching expertise at the beginning of the interview to show the researcher that he is familiar with the ICC concept and its dimensions. This teacher was aware of using dimensions of intercultural competence to define the notion of culture. His definition is associated with anti-essentialist views and understandings of culture (Elsen and St. John, 2007). Teacher 1 and Teacher 2 perceived culture as complex, fluid, and dynamic (Witte and Harden, 2011). Therefore, they set aside the traditional and conventional definitions of culture and constructed more constructivist understandings of the concept (Baldwin et al., 2006).

5.2.1.6 Culture as a cognitive lens

Some participants from the West University related the concept of culture to the inner and mental features of people, who share the same culture like values, beliefs, and norms. More interestingly, they viewed the individual's ways of thinking and ways of perceiving the self and the world as components of culture. This can mean that they view culture as something that can be empirically observed through attitudes and conceptions. Teacher 3 stated that "it is about thoughts, the way you perceive yourself and the other, and the way others perceive you. It's the way you are with your people and the way you are with others". This sub-theme exemplifies the small "c" culture or the sociocultural knowledge.

Unlike the perceptions of teachers from the East University, teachers from the West University demonstrated a shift towards the formation of anti-essentialist views of culture, that have a strong foundation in constructivist thinking, which recognised the robustly complex and dynamic nature of the notion of culture. In other words, their appraisals appeared to consciously set apart all the conventional definitions by shedding light on the essence of the ICC and its components.

5.2.2 The Importance of Teaching about Cultures in the Classroom

This theme discusses teachers' perspectives on the significance of teaching culture and its crucial role in English Language Teaching (ELT). All participants without exception asserted that exposing students to other cultures is paramount and essential. Most of the participants from West University elucidate that they don't focus or opt for one particular culture to teach about, but they address multiple cultures starting with the students' national culture as it is

explained by Teacher 1 and Teacher 2. Teacher 1 stated, “There is no particular culture, we speak about cross-cultural and intercultural competence as notions; so, we do not focus on the target culture in our classroom”. Teacher 2 reported, “I am not a teacher who imposes certain cultures, I leave the cultures to talk about themselves and represent themselves in the classroom”. In addition, all participants from the same university emphasised the significance of teaching about the students’ national culture. Teacher 5 stated that “all the cultures are embedded, starting with the learners’ own culture. So, if you want to teach your students about other cultures, you need first of all to make them aware of their own culture”.

It is intriguing to state that Teacher 1 focused on the significance of teaching about notions of interculturality such as culture, cross-cultures, intercultural competence, and ICC. To teach these concepts in EFL classrooms, she outlined an approach that she uses in her teaching. It is called “The personalisation approach”. This approach focuses on teaching diverse cultures through fostering the learners’ national culture. In other words, it is fundamental to raise the learners’ awareness of their national culture. She stated that “the best way to approach teaching about other cultures is through the personalisation approach, like trying to teach other cultures through the learners’ own culture”.

Starting the process of learning by providing a familiar environment to the learner might make the transition to a new foreign one easier because it helps learners to relate to their own culture and make connections (Kramsch, 1993; Mahmud, 2019). Therefore, learners can make similarities and contrasts between situations that are familiar to them and others which are unfamiliar.

Importantly another key perception was provided by Teacher 3, she stated that teaching about other cultures entails experiencing that particular culture. In a more detailed way, Teacher 3 believes that broadening and developing her students’ intercultural awareness is a challenging task for her and for any teacher because students cannot afford to travel abroad and experience a different culture. Therefore, she tries to make the course vivid by narrating her traveling experiences to students. In other words, this participant viewed that teaching about other cultures is significant and should be taught through real-life experiences as it is exemplified in the following quotation:

I tell them about my own experience and at the same time I ask them about theirs, but you know usually they do not travel. So, they expect me to tell them about my own experiences and they are quite amazed to learn about culture this way (Teacher 3).

Correspondingly to participants' views from the West University, most of the participants from the East University confirmed that tackling the target culture, particularly in their teaching is the primary goal of teaching because it helps to develop learners' language skills. It can be stated that the majority of teachers from the East University bounded their understanding of the complexity of cultures to the target culture (British/American). This view was presented by Teacher B in the following quotation, "About Britain! Yes, I always speak about, for example, if I had to give an example, I wouldn't only base myself in Algeria. I will teach the target culture" Teacher C also stated that "culture refers to the big C culture, there are two modules that deal with the teaching of culture, American and British civilisations and literature". This finding can be linked to Byram et al (2001) and Roberts et al (2001) who demonstrated that cultural awareness (CA) is considered a teaching approach, which predominantly focuses on preparing learners of English to interact with native speakers of English (ENS). Although the CA model promotes the notion of an intercultural speaker, it predominantly focuses on the British and American cultures, which should be part of the cultural content because they are considered dominant cultures in the teaching of EFL (Byram, 1997).

By the same token, Teacher B, Teacher C, Teacher D, and Teacher E associated teaching about other cultures with teaching about the target culture. More elaborately, they believed that because they teach English as FL, they have to exclusively teach about the target culture, specifically that either of Britain or America.

Talking about teaching culture, Teacher D explained the bounded relationship between language and culture "We cannot really separate them, it is like the two faces of the same coin, oh yeah!". However, in practice, they tend to teach culture as a single separate entity. In other words, the teaching of the target culture aims to foster the learners' cultural awareness and develop their language proficiency.

5.2.3 What Culture to Teach?

Participants from both universities were asked what culture they teach in EFL classrooms in Algeria. Despite their agreement on the inseparability of language and culture teaching and their recognition of its significance in EFL education, the participants' perspectives (from both the East and West University) on which cultures to include in their courses were varied.

Accordingly, two interesting perspectives can be identified. Firstly, the target culture and the national culture (Algerian culture). Secondly, other cultures engaged in the process of the development of the learners' ICC.

The first view was shared by most of the participants from the East University. It states that the target culture should be predominantly involved in the English language teaching to help learners master the target language and widen their vocabulary. **Teacher C** reported that "if you want to make learners master the language you need to make them learn its culture". Adding to that, **Teacher D** stated that "through learning culture, learners enlarge their vocabulary whether they feel it or not". Some participants from the East University further highlighted the importance of the inclusion of the students' local culture along with the target language. **Teacher A** stated, "Let's say juxtaposition of trying to do dichotomies between one's national culture and the target cultures is very important". Several scholars argue that the process of language learning goes beyond the mere acquisition of linguistic, communicative and cultural knowledge (Byram, 1997; Byram et al., 2023; Holliday et al., 2004; Corbett, 2003). It involves active engagement with cultural practices, beliefs, and attitudes that shape different cultures. Therefore, the integration of language and culture should be a fundamental aspect of English Language Teaching (ELT). On the other hand, the second view was shared among participants from the West University in which they did not opt for a particular culture to teach, however, different cultures are included in the classroom. **Teacher 2** and **Teacher 1**, for example, stated they do not impose a single culture, but they involve diverse cultures in one course. The participants did not confine their courses just to the teaching of one particular culture (target culture). Rather, they expressed a preference for developing the learners' intercultural awareness towards different cultures, with the ultimate goal of promoting the necessary intercultural skills for effective intercultural interactions. Moreover, they outlined the significance of incorporating the learners' national culture in their teaching practices, enabling them to embrace their own culture and make them engage in critical analysis by drawing comparisons and recognising the similarities and differences between their own culture and other various cultures. This approach of teaching through comparisons proves to be beneficial and intellectually stimulating, particularly for young learners who are not familiar with some aspects of their own culture. Nevertheless, Canale (2016) indicated that the approach of comparing learners' national culture with other cultures eventually leads to the formation of stereotypical generalisations. Hence, comparisons can

be beneficial in fostering intercultural communicative competence (ICC), but they must be accompanied by additional activities which allow learners to understand, respect and empathise with others' perspectives from foreign cultures (Sercu et al., 2005). Furthermore, learners need to engage in self-reflection to gain a deeper understanding of their own cultural perspectives as well as foreign ones.

5.2.4 Interconnectedness of Language and Culture

Most participants from both universities referred to the interlinked relationship between language and culture in which language cannot be separated from culture, and language cannot be taught without culture (Byram, 2006; Hall, 2002; Holliday et al., 2004; Kramsch 1993, 2008; Jiang, 2000; Risager, 2006). This can be in line with Jiang (2000), who provided a metaphor of the mirror to depict the inextricable relationship between language and culture "Language is the mirror of culture", in a way people view culture through its language (p.328). As opposed to participants' views from the West University, the inclusion of cultures in the EFL course does not entail the target culture solely, the views of participants from the East University focused on tackling the target culture for language proficiency purposes. In other words, it can be stated that culture teaching is considered an add-on to foster language teaching at East University (Luk,2012). However, **Teacher A** from East University conveyed that it is significant to do a juxtaposition between the students' national culture and the target culture because, if not, the students would never know to what extent they are different/similar to each other. He (**Teacher A**) argued that "It's impossible for anyone who has never had a chance to really appreciate British culture, American culture to fully be let's say critical". As a researcher, it is interesting to state that most of the participants' perspectives from East University were limited to identifying the relationship between the English language and the target culture, unlike the participants from West University.

5.2.5 Dissatisfaction of cultural content

Teacher A from the East University conveyed his dissatisfaction with the curriculum offered by the Algerian Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research (AMHESR), specifically highlighting that the content course primarily consists of theoretical concepts with limited opportunities for practical application. Regarding this matter, **Teacher A** expressed "Headlines that we are asked to follow, you will find that most of them are theoretical explanations of what is culture, what composed culture, what is cultural competence".

5.2.6 Shaping or Threatening Student Identity

Two participants from West University initially expressed concerns about the potential negative impact of teaching different cultures on learners' national identity. However, **Teacher 1** confidently presented a counterargument by highlighting the benefits of promoting ICC in education as a remedy to such issues and challenges. According to **Teacher 1**, learners' awareness of their cultural identity and their ability to approach and understand other cultures neutrally is essential for successfully understanding and respecting of different cultures without compromising their own national identity and culture. It is important to state that the same participant initially had doubts about exposing her learners to different cultures, suggesting that it might pose a threat on the learners' social identity. However, she immediately shifted her perspective, asserting that learners' exposure to other cultures does not necessarily lead to letting go of their identity. Instead, she argued that if learners happen to change their thinking or modify some of their practices, it is not because they abandoned their culture, but rather due to the re-evaluation of the preconceived stereotypes they held about other cultures. This perception aligns with what Byram refers to as "savoirs" (knowing how) and "savoir comprendre" (skills of interpreting and relating) in his ICC model (Byram, 1997,p.73).

The only supposed harm is their social identity, but I do not really think it's threatening the students' identity. To change some of their practices not because to let go of their identity, no because when comparing and contrasting you just feel that this is stereotypical (**Teacher 1**)

Additionally, **Teacher 2** proposed a solution to tackle the issue identity threat. He advocated for the development of learners' intercultural awareness and intercultural communicative competence as a remedy for such concerns. According to him, if teachers could promote learners' intercultural awareness regarding their own culture and other cultures, they would be equipped with the knowledge and skills to compare and contrast the commonalities and disparities that exist between cultures. They would be able to effectively mediate between cultural differences. Moreover, **Teacher 2** asserted that acquiring knowledge about diverse cultures does not imply disregarding or rejecting one's own culture. Rather, it fosters an appreciation for one's self-culture and promotes the qualities of flexibility, tolerance, and acceptance towards other cultural differences. He stressed that achieving these outcomes necessitates the development of learners' ICC.

I do emphasise the fact that what is called an identity is at stake, but there is a remedy for this kind of problem which is the development of intercultural awareness. A learner who develops an intercultural awareness, will be able to find commonalities and differences and bridge between them. When we talk about Byram's model of ICC, I always prioritise intercultural awareness. I always believe that learning about other cultures is not at all refusing your culture or just disregarding it. However, if learners do not develop what we call intercultural awareness, they can have problems of identity loss (Teacher 2)

In a related vein, other participants from the same university demonstrated that the primary objective of teaching English as a Foreign Language (EFL) is to foster the development of students' intercultural communicative competence (ICC). For instance, Teacher 4 emphasised the significance of promoting "savoir s'engager" (critical cultural awareness) among her learners. This particular skill enables learners to reflect and recognise their own culture, not in terms of its perfection or superiority, but rather in the context of its divergence from other cultures (Byram et al., 2023). Additionally, Teacher 4 emphasised the importance of "savoir être" (attitudes), highlighting the need to instil in learners a fundamental sense of objectivity when engaging with other cultures. She also indicated that learners initially tend to possess a sense of superiority towards their own culture, perceiving it as the epitome of correctness and superiority. This belief leads them to regard other cultures as inferior. Therefore, Teacher 4 stated that her mission is to develop learners' intercultural attitudes and objectivity, encouraging them to suspend stereotypes and dispel any disbelief they may hold about other cultures.

It is noteworthy to mention that all participants from West University focused on offering a remedy for potential identity loss by advocating for the development of students' ICC. They disagreed with the idea that teaching about other cultures might threaten Algerian learners' identity. Instead, they emphasised the importance of equipping students with the necessary intercultural skills to navigate cultural diversity and foster mutual understanding.

On the other hand, participants from East University shared perspectives that teaching about other cultures, specifically the target culture, has a negative impact on learners' social identity. Teacher B argued that learners' values and identity can be influenced if they lack awareness of their own culture and the differences that exist in the target culture. In such cases, learners may feel overwhelmed or inferior when compared to the target culture. Consequently, Teacher B highlighted that learners may start questioning themselves,

pondering why they should engage with a culture that is not their own. This teacher stated that it would be beneficial if students were aware of the advantages of learning about the target culture to master the language. As a researcher, it can be inferred that this participant's understanding of other cultures is primarily limited to the target culture and their aim of teaching is predominantly focused on language acquisition and proficiency. This perspective is exemplified by **Teacher B** in the following quotation, "It depends on the student's awareness himself, if he can take advantage of the target culture to master the language, that's going to be great". Furthermore, other participants from the East University demonstrated that teaching about the target culture has a definitive impact on learners' attitudes towards their national culture. **Teacher D** illustrated this by exemplifying the use of an American movie as authentic material to expose learners to the target culture. While acknowledging the benefits of using authentic materials to teach the English language, such as expanding vocabulary and developing language skills. **Teacher D** stated the drawbacks. He highlighted the potential conflict arising from scenes in movies that contradict learners' cultural values, thereby influencing their moral beliefs. Furthermore, **Teacher D** reported that even the way the characters in movies wear can influence learners' behaviour and physical appearances, potentially leading to an uncritical imitation of others. He emphasised the importance of respecting the values and principles prevalent in Algerian society, suggesting that students' learning experiences should expose them to culturally appropriate content.

The participant from East University displayed a defensive and protective tone, reflecting a firm belief in protecting his own culture and that of the learners. His perspective exhibited an authoritative stance. He used some terms like "bad" and "wrong" to describe some cultural aspects of other cultures, this indicates the presence of negative stereotypes and believing that his culture is the only correct and best one.

Most of the participants from East University shared the belief that the students' national culture is threatened by the target culture, particularly if students lack awareness of their own cultural background. In such cases, there is a concern that students may let go of their values and beliefs. However, teachers from the West university demonstrated that the development of the learners' ICC is the way to understand, embrace and appreciate oneself and others' cultures.

5.3 Teachers' Attitudes and Conceptions of Intercultural Communicative Competence in Language Education

This section presents Algerian English language teachers' conceptions and perspectives of intercultural communicative competence and its dimensions. The findings of this section address the second research question, which seeks to understand how Algerian English language teachers perceive ICC and to what extent it is embedded in their pedagogical practices in Algeria. Additionally, this section explores teachers' personal intercultural lived experiences and examines how such experiences contribute to the development of ICC.

5.3.1 Teachers' Conceptions of ICC

Several questions were assigned to draw out certain data about participants' understandings of the notion of ICC. At the beginning of this section, I asked participants if they were familiar with the notion of intercultural communicative competence. All five participants from West University indicated that they were familiar with the concept and its dimensions. All of them without exception evoked Byram's ICC model (1997) and other IC models in their definitions. Additionally, they demonstrated that they have been teaching it as a separate subject to master students of English, whose major is language and Communication at the West University. They also believed that it is paramount to integrate controversial topics into language education because it helps learners develop compassion, respect, and flexibility towards their culture and others (Byram et al., 2023).

5.3.1.1 ICC as Art of Embracing Diversity

Most of the participants from West University perceived ICC as an art that embraces diversity, an art of welcoming differences, and the ability to mediate between different understandings in different intercultural settings. While defining it, they occasionally referred to it as intercultural awareness (IA), intercultural competence (IC), and intercultural skills. The utilisation of these diverse terms by the participants suggested that they viewed the notion of ICC in different ways. Furthermore, participants from West University conceptions tended to address communication between cultures, flexibility, tolerance, acceptance, and openness. This perspective is illustrated by **Teacher 2**, who stated, "For me, Intercultural communicative competence is all about tolerance, understanding, flexibility, and welcoming the differences of cultures". He underpinned his perception by referring to scholars like Byram, Deardorff and Fantini, who emphasised the significance of tolerance, understanding, and embracing

diversity. By invoking the contributions of these ICC pioneers, the participant showed his familiarity with the concept of ICC and demonstrated an awareness of the field of interculturality. It is interesting to observe that **Teacher 1** drew attention to the difference between IC and ICC concepts. She viewed IC as “the knowledge you possess about different cultures including yours” whereas ICC as the “ability to use that knowledge to communicate cross-culturally because knowing does not mean being good communicators”. In the same vein, the other three participants referred to ICC as the ability to interact and behave adequately and properly in different intercultural settings.

The inclusion of intercultural perspectives has emerged as a crucial element in the reinvigoration of language teaching and learning across various settings. Language teachers play a significant role in facilitating this transformative process, as highlighted by scholars such as Dervin and Gross (2016), Guilherme (2002), Risager (2007), and Sercu et al. (2005). This is explained in the following excerpt:

The teachers need to have intercultural skills as Byram’s divided them, um, I think even the teacher needs to have these skills developed first of all. His way of thinking or his way of perceiving things should be based on openness and tolerance (**Teacher 4**).

These perspectives demonstrate the necessary skills and competencies that should be promoted within the intercultural English language teaching context. In this essence, these competencies and attitudes encompass aspects of respect, tolerance, flexibility, and openness, extending beyond the communicative competence teaching approach (Byram et al., 2023). Moreover, some participants from the West University highlighted the significance of incorporating the learners’ local culture into the learning process, enabling them to engage in meaningful comparisons and contrasts between cultures.

5.3.1.2 ICC as Communicative Competence

The same question was raised to participants from the East University. One participant expressed confusion when I asked her to define ICC. She provided a hesitant and indecisive response stating that ICC is “the way people interact”. Subsequently, she (**Teacher B**) asked me to define it for her maybe to check if she answered correctly or not, “You tell me, what is it?”. This shows that this participant believed in the existence of one fixed and correct definition. Her initial reaction and confusion imply a lack of familiarity with the notion of ICC, possibly indicating that it was her first time hearing the concept. **Teacher D** from the East

University defined it as “The ability to know about one’s culture and interact with native speakers of English”. Others preferred to list what they teach. Subjects and courses which address intercultural education and intercultural communicative competence (ICC) do not appear to hold explicit visibility within the educational context at the East University. This finding becomes evident when examining the definitions provided by participants from East University, as their understanding of the concept itself was lacking clarity, with none of them addressing any of the ICC dimensions in their perceptions. Notably, there was an absence of awareness towards intercultural attitudes, knowledge, skills and critical cultural awareness (Byram, 1997; 2020). Instead, the teaching of English focus seemed to be primarily on preparing learners to interact with native speakers (NS) of English. Baker (2009b) viewed the native speaker approach as an inappropriate and ill approach to English language teaching. He argued that English nowadays is used as lingua Franca, which is used as a means of communication amongst individuals who have different first languages from the language being used in interaction. These individuals have different “linguacultures” (p.569).

It is noteworthy that none of the participants mentioned ICC or the development of its components as a teaching objective in their teaching practices. This highlights a significant gap in the participants’ awareness and integration of ICC in their teaching approaches. Therefore, there may be a need to promote a deeper understanding of ICC and its essential components among educators at East University to enhance intercultural education and foster more comprehensive intercultural communicative competence among teachers and learners.

This finding can be lined with Byram’s (1997,2006), Fantini’s (2005) perceptions. They believed that to meet the needs of students in today’s globalised world, the primary objective of Intercultural Language Teaching (ICLT) should extend beyond communicative competence (CC). While CC encompasses linguistic competence and the ability to communicate effectively with native speakers, it is suggested that ICLT should also aim to develop learners’ ICC. ICC emphasises the integration of language, culture, and various cultural dimensions such as knowledge, skills, attitudes, and critical cultural awareness (Byram, 1997, 2006).

5.3.2 The Importance of the Inclusion of Intercultural Communicative Competence in English Language Teaching

Participants from both universities were asked why they consider teaching about other cultures essential in English language teaching classrooms. Their perceptions of this matter

were varied. Some of these perceptions focused on boosting students' critical cultural awareness (*savoir s'engager*) and their reflection on language learning, aiding in deconstructing the students' stereotypes and promoting flexibility, tolerance, and respect between cultures that are included in the learning process.

To demonstrate the significance of ICC in English language teaching, all participants from both universities agreed on the importance of developing students' critical cultural awareness in language learning. The following excerpts demonstrate this:

For me, a teacher should be a mediator in the sense that I think our learners have the potential to develop their critical thinking, but a teacher has a kind of duty, or a kind of role to develop such as critical thinking in his students (Teacher 2).

It's important for students to have a critical position, and to have a critical perspective towards their own culture and towards other cultures. So, this is what Byram adds as a fifth component "*savoir s'engager*", which raises the critical cultural awareness of the students and aids them not to take things for granted (Teacher 4).

As previously mentioned, all participants from West University demonstrated their familiarity with the notion of intercultural communicative competence (ICC) and its dimensions right from the beginning of the interview. Their perceptions align with Byram's (1997) component of critical cultural awareness (CCA), which emphasises the ability to critically evaluate and engage in diverse intercultural conversations. In contrast, participants from the East University acknowledged the importance of promoting ICC in the classroom; however, it has not yet been introduced in their teaching practices. They demonstrate that fostering learners' CCA is essential because it enables them to critically compare and contrast their own national culture with the target culture. Again, the focus here is on the target culture.

Second, participants from the West University pointed out the cruciality of deconstructing stereotypes their students may build towards other cultures through developing their students' ICC. Teacher 3 expressed:

Sometimes students think that, of course, they have that kind of sentimental feeling of superiority. They think that their culture is number one, it's the best one and they usually are biased viewing the other as an inferior culture etc. Part of our mission is to develop this kind of critical cultural awareness and objectivity in them and forget about subjectivity (Teacher 3).

Teacher 5 supported the above perspective. She stated, “I pursue my students to not judge other cultures’ values. They should understand the differences without saying it’s right or wrong. There is no right or wrong culture”.

These two perceptions represent the first ICC component “attitudes” where Byram (1997) persists on the importance of developing the learner’s curiosity and openness towards diverse cultures and suspending their beliefs that their culture is the only correct culture (p.34). On the other hand, none of the participants from the East University demonstrated the importance of avoiding stereotypes, which students may have. Some of them confirmed that they themselves hold negative stereotypes about some beliefs and values exist in other cultures. Teacher D stated, “I need to make things like, you know, filtering what is good and what is bad for students to understand about other cultures”.

The third perception which highlighted that ICC contributes to the development of flexibility, tolerance, and respect between diverse cultures involved in the classroom was shared among participants from the West University. This is explained as follows:

Those who develop intercultural communicative competence are going to have the ability to filter, mediate, understand and bridge between different understandings, and these individuals can develop what is called flexibility, tolerance, openness and respect (Teacher 2).

According to Murphy-Lejeune (2003), the concept of openness encompasses multiple dimensions, including curiosity, tolerance, and flexibility. She further identified these qualities as fundamental characteristics based on her own research findings regarding the students' experiences with intercultural encounters. In a similar vein, Fantini (2000) provides a definition of intercultural competence (ICC) which encompasses various aspects, such as flexibility, patience, openness, interest, curiosity, empathy, and tolerance for cultural ambiguities. These qualities contribute to the development of learners’ ICC to critically evaluate the differences and deconstruct stereotypes and prejudice towards cultures of different backgrounds. Furthermore, it enables them to observe, compare, and perceive the world with new perspectives (Barany, 2016).

5.3.3 Challenges of Teaching about ICC

According to participants, the implementation of the ICC model is challenging in the EFL context. Firstly, it remains primarily a theoretical framework, encompassing abstract aspects that cannot be easily taught but rather experienced in real life.

Most of the participants demonstrated that the inclusion of intercultural communicative competence (ICC) in the teaching of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classroom poses several challenges. These challenges arise from various factors, including the nature of ICC itself, the learning environment, and the limitations within the educational system.

ICC involves understanding and navigating cultural differences, which are complex and multifaceted. However, some aspects of ICC, such as attitudes of curiosity and openness are abstract and difficult to teach directly. They are best learned through experiential and immersive intercultural encounters, which may be challenging to replicate in the classroom setting. Teachers expressed perspectives in the following remarks:

This is a theoretical model. You have to take into consideration the practical obstacles in teaching because there are dimensions that are not teachable. It is not possible to transfer them to your learners (Teacher A).

You need to take learners from their seats straight to the plane because they have to live the new culture, and that's why it is a must to have a teacher who has travelled to be able to transmit their intercultural encounters (Teacher 3).

Limited exposure to different cultures In the EFL context (cultural homogeneity), students often have limited exposure to diverse cultures, which hinders their development of ICC. Without any exposure or frequent interaction with individuals from other cultures, students may struggle to grasp the cultural nuances and develop a deep understanding towards others' cultures. This aligns with Teacher C's perspective, she reported that they cannot create a multicultural environment in the classroom as the majority of students are from the same cultural background, limiting opportunities for intercultural interaction. According to her, this homogeneity hinders the development of ICC as students may have limited exposure to diverse cultural perspectives and encounters. She expressed:

No, we cannot have this because in Algeria we are all from the same culture and we can't have a multicultural environment, we are all homogenous we belong to the same culture, so we don't have foreign students (Teacher C).

However, **Teacher 1** from the West University indicated that Algeria is a multilingual and multicultural country that holds diverse cultures (Beraba,2004). She believed that integrating Algerian sub-cultures in teaching is an effective way to improve and foster students' ICC. She expressed "Algeria is a very rich country in terms of dialects and cultures; so, I can use these differences". Furthermore, **Teacher 4** demonstrated that she can create a multicultural environment as there are students from Mali and other students from different sub-cultures in Algeria.

Lack of authentic resources and the absence of network in laboratories: EFL classrooms lack the necessary teaching authentic resources, and network in laboratories that facilitate interactive and communicative language learning. Laboratories provide opportunities for students to engage in authentic intercultural activities, such as arranging Skype calls with individuals from different cultural backgrounds, and sending/receiving emails. The absence of such facilities limits the students' exposure to authentic intercultural communication.

Classroom size and engagement: In overcrowded or large classrooms, it becomes challenging for all students to actively participate in intercultural activities and discussions. Limited interaction opportunities may impede the development of ICC, as students may not have enough chances to practice and engage with diverse perspectives. **Teacher A** stated:

Teaching ICC is only feasible if we are provided with enough authentic tools and recourses because you need at least a language laboratory equipped with a network. You will need enough time, you will need small-sized classrooms of ten to fifteen students maximum, you will need also to receive external help, where you can take learners to places so they meet foreigners, interact with them, and apply what they have learnt. if you have these resources provided, I guess you can promote learners' ICC, and it's going to be fruitful (**Teacher A**).

A specific section of the interview protocol was dedicated to exploring participants' perspectives on attending any training which addresses ICC in English language teaching. All participants unanimously from both universities highlighted that they had not attended any training specifically addressing intercultural communicative competence in Algeria. In other words, there was no pre-service on culture or intercultural awareness that was provided by the Algerian Ministry of Higher Education and Social Sciences. Instead, participants from West University stated that their understanding of interculturality was promoted primarily through research and through their intercultural lived experiences where they encountered diverse cultures. Participants were also asked about their perceptions of the usefulness of pre-service

training on ICC, considering its recent emergence as a subject of study in Algeria. This question aimed to investigate the participants' willingness to enhance their knowledge and incorporate ICC into their teaching practices. All participants expressed strong interest in attending such training, acknowledging its significance and usefulness for EFL teachers. **Teacher 3** posited that although she had never attended training on ICC, she had the opportunity to participate in numerous international conferences where cross-culturality was a major theme. She regarded these conferences as preparatory sessions that highlighted the concept of ICC, its dimensions, and teaching techniques and strategies. Furthermore, the majority of participants agreed that the Algerian Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research should prioritise the availability of exchange programs for both teachers and students. They believed that such programs would provide valuable opportunities for practical immersion in other cultures, allowing both learners and teachers to be exposed to new cultures. Conversely, some participants from East University emphasised the importance of offering training by English NS. This perception is bounding the notion of ICC to the target culture. Lack of training can be aligned with the finding of a study conducted in Finland, which focused on pre-service teachers and sought to provide initial insights into the extent to which cultural issues were emphasised in language teachers' initial training (Larzén-Östermark, 2009). The study's findings indicated that cultural aspects in language teaching had not been adequately addressed in teacher training programs. One of the key factors contributing to this was the lack of intercultural dimensions in practice.

Teachers may face challenges in effectively incorporating ICC into their teaching practices due to limited training and professional development opportunities. Without proper training on ICC pedagogy and strategies, teachers may struggle to design and implement intercultural activities that effectively promote students' intercultural competence.

I will tell you something the intercultural communicative competence in Algeria or our universities is very new, and that's why I have not seen to my knowledge any training about ICC at the level in Algeria (**Teacher 4**).

Teachers from the East University believed in the existence of one single culture that is shared by people of the same nation. This perspective is aligned with the essentialist structuralist view of culture. Therefore, it indicates that their understanding of ICC is limited. However, teachers from the West University demonstrated that Algeria is a rich country that

encompasses diverse sub-cultures that can be taught to develop learners' intercultural attitudes. Some of them included Malian culture to be taught to create an inclusive learning environment. Indeed, teaching ICC in Algeria is challenging; however, it is crucial for EFL educators and policymakers to prioritise the integration of ICC into the curriculum, to provide professional development opportunities for teachers, and to seek innovative approaches that create authentic intercultural experiences within the classroom.

5.3.4 Teachers' Intercultural Exposures

5.3.4.1 Enriching Journeys in Different Intercultural Contexts

Exploring teachers' perspectives on their interactions with people from various cultural backgrounds is crucial to understanding how these experiences enrich their intercultural attitudes and cultural sensitivity. All teachers in this study reported having different and enriching intercultural lived experiences which contributed to the development of their awareness and understanding of other cultures. These experiences allowed them to deepen their intercultural awareness in various ways, shaping their perspectives and enhancing their ability to engage successfully in several intercultural dialogues. The diversity of these lived experiences positively influenced their professional and personal growth.

Teacher 1 reported that her first intercultural experience was in London, where she travelled to attend an English language course at a private school to improve her communication skills. She elucidated that the classroom she used to study in had an intercultural environment where different cultures existed (Korean, Spanish, French and Italian cultures, etc). In her first experience, she had the identity of an international student who left her country for learning purposes, where she had the chance to be directly exposed to different cultures. Teacher 1 reported another intercultural exposure where she taught cross-cultural subjects in London to students from diverse cultural backgrounds (Japan, Switzerland, France and other nationalities). She described this experience as 'enriching and enlightening' as teaching individuals from diverse cultures has provided her with deeper insights into their cultures. This experience helped her to observe, appreciate and respect the differences between peoples' perspectives (Byram,1997), recognising that there are distinct cultures across the globe. Teacher 1 expressed that despite all these differences, she and the other people she

interacted with were able to find common ground, reinforcing the belief that the uniqueness of each culture is what connects people.

Teacher 2 also stated that he has visited Spain, Turkey, and England. During the interview, he focused on his intercultural encounter with his Indian friend, who provided him with insights and perspectives about various aspects of Indian culture. It is worth mentioning that Teacher 2 mentioned at the beginning of the interview that his field of research is language education and intercultural communication. His awareness of intercultural communicative competence (Byram,1997;2006;2008) allowed him to effectively communicate across different cultures and enriched his understanding of the complexities involved in such interactions. In addition, Teacher 3 had different enriching intercultural exposures where she encountered several cultural shocks.

The intercultural lived experience of Teacher 4 differed significantly from the previous experiences. She demonstrated her intercultural experience in Jordan, where Jordanians share the same language (Modern Standard Arabic) and religion (Islam) but have different cultural practices. Teacher 4 travelled to Jordan to pursue her postgraduate studies, which allowed her to encounter different cultures and interact with people who spoke various dialects. This exposure to a different culture broadened her horizons and deepened her understanding of other cultures.

Teacher 4's experience in Jordan proved to be fruitful and enriching on personal, academic, and social levels. Unlike the other participants, Teacher 3 intercultural exposure was for a long duration, three years, in Jordan to pursue her studies. It was interesting that she did not encounter any conflicts or misunderstandings which can be attributed to the shared religion and language between the host culture and her own culture. However, as reported by Sapir (1921) sharing the same language does not necessarily imply sharing the same culture. It is possible for individuals who speak the same language to belong to different cultural groups (Sapir,1921). For instance, in the MENA region (Middle East and North Africa) or English-speaking countries, cultural practices can vary across different regions despite the common official language. Linking cultural awareness solely to national cultures, both native and foreign, has faced criticism, particularly when the language under consideration is English, given its global use as a lingua franca (Baker, 2012).

Teacher 5's intercultural experiences were in France and Saudi Arabia. Similar to Teacher 2, the interviewee affirmed that her awareness and familiarity with interculturality in general

and with the ICC dimensions (attitudes, knowledge, skills and critical cultural awareness) (Byram,1997;2006;2008), in particular, helped her in handling unusual situations such as cultural misunderstandings and effectively navigating intercultural communications with people from diverse cultural contexts. Furthermore, she highlighted that her experiences abroad greatly contributed to her personal and professional development, particularly in developing tolerance, understanding, and openness. These intercultural dimensions were crucial to successfully interact with different cultural practices and perspectives (Byram,1997). Teacher 5 also indicated that these intercultural lived experiences enabled her to navigate cultural differences with empathy and sensitivity.

It was interesting that most of the teachers from the East University had difficulty understanding the question about describing their intercultural lived experiences. As a result, I had to reformulate the question to "Have you ever travelled or experienced a different culture?" This indicates that the participants from East University are not familiar with concepts such as intercultural lived experiences, intercultural encounters, and interculturality more broadly as shown in this quote, "I don't really get this point" Teacher C

Teacher A from the East University indicated that he had several intercultural lived experiences in France, England, Spain and Germany. He pointed out that he met new people from different cultural backgrounds and experienced different food tastes, clothes, weather, language, religion and many other things. Among his various travels, he reported that his intercultural exposure in England was different. It changed his perspectives and influenced his English language teaching approach at the East University.

Teacher B's intercultural lived experience was mainly in Great Britain. She demonstrated that she lived in Cardiff for ten years where she got the chance to be trained and taught by native speakers of English during her Masters and PhD journeys. She reported that she had a rich experience where she interacted with individuals from diverse cultures. These people welcomed her and showed openness and flexibility towards her cultural differences with genuine interest and respect. Similar to Teacher 1, Teacher B believed that the development of intercultural communicative competence (ICC) is most effectively achieved through direct cultural immersion. According to her, authentic exposure to diverse cultures was crucial in deepening her understanding and enhancing her ability to communicate across cultural boundaries. Additionally, Teacher C, Teacher D, and Teacher E highlighted different aspects of their intercultural lived experiences. Teacher C reported that her understanding and

accepting new cultures were difficult, particularly in multicultural settings like London. Teacher D experienced diverse cultures in Dubai. He stated that he engaged in different intercultural exchanges via social media platforms like Instagram and Twitter where he interacted with both native English speakers and non-native speakers from various countries. Teacher E pointed out that he encountered challenges with cultural nuances and misunderstandings but gradually adapted by learning more about the cultural contexts of those he interacted.

5.3.4.2 Cultural Misunderstandings

Participants in this study were asked if they encountered any cultural clashes during their intercultural experiences. Although Teacher 1 reported previously that she did not face any challenges in terms of language use during her communication with others, she revealed that there were some cultural clashes. She referred to these clashes as “unusual situations”, where people she met were not familiar with her culture and religion. She stated that she looked for the commonalities exist in her culture and others’ cultures to be able to navigate intercultural dialogues (Minimisation Stage) (Bennett, 1993; 2004).

Teacher 2 also demonstrated the challenges he encountered during his intercultural lived experience, particularly related to communication. In the initial weeks of his stay, he struggled to understand many words used by his Indian friend, as his way of speaking English was significantly different from the English he was accustomed to. Teacher 2 expressed that he did not experience a cultural clash, he emphasised the importance of staying connected to one’s own identity while also respecting and tolerating the cultures and perspectives of others. By maintaining a balance between knowing and embracing his cultural identity, and being open to diverse viewpoints, he was able to avoid potential tensions and conflicts and navigate intercultural interactions. This perspective aligns with Bennet’s (2011) notion of intercultural competence, where she highlighted the necessity of knowing and being aware of one’s own cultural identity as a foundation for developing intercultural attitudes, knowledge and skills to understand and appreciate other cultures. Bennett (1993) demonstrated in her model of intercultural sensitivity development that moving from an ethnocentric worldview (where one’s own culture is central) to an ethnorelative perspective (where cultures are seen as equally valid) requires individuals to first become aware of their own cultures and identities. It is also significant to state that both Byram’s (1997,2006) and

Bennett's (1993) models emphasise the importance of self-awareness in developing intercultural competence. Self-awareness (cognitive skill) is critical in shifting from a mindset that views cultural differences as threatening or inferior to one that appreciates and adapts to these differences.

Teacher 3 shared multiple intercultural experiences from her visits to France, Germany, and Prague. Her first intercultural encounter took place in France, where she experienced multiple cultural shocks. Initially, she was unaware of the differences between her own culture and French culture (Denial Stage), relying on her cultural background (Algerian culture) during her interactions with French people (Bennett, 1986;1993; Landis et al., 2004). However, she soon discovered that certain words or actions she opted for were not accepted in the French culture. She provided a concrete example of offering her seat to an elderly French man on a bus but he refused to sit. Teacher 3 stated that she left her seat because he was old and vulnerable. The man perceived her gesture as rude and reacted negatively leading to a misunderstanding, and leaving Teacher 3 feeling frustrated and confused. This incident caused a cultural shock for her, highlighting the importance of understanding cultural differences. At the beginning she viewed the man's behaviour as not acceptable and disrespectful (Defence Stage). As a researcher coming from the same background, leaving a seat for elderly people in the Algerian culture is a sign of respect.

Teacher 3 also recounted another unusual incident about a British woman visiting Algeria, particularly the West University. Every morning, Teacher 3 asked the English woman if she had slept well, which was not a common practice in the British culture. Therefore, the English woman questioned the repetitive question, finding it strange: "Why are you asking me this question, It's quite strange!". Teacher 3's intercultural experiences can be linked to her lack of intercultural dimensions provided in Byram's model of Intercultural Communicative Competence (1997,2006). According to Byram, successful intercultural communication requires a combination of attitudes, knowledge, skills, and critical cultural awareness. In Teacher 3's case, her initial reliance on Algerian cultural norms—such as asking the British woman if she slept well—demonstrates that she lacks knowledge, as she was unaware of the differing social expectations in that culture which led to a cultural misunderstanding. Bennett (1993) referred to this as denial stage (unawareness of cultural differences). This dimension (knowledge) involves understanding the cultural practices, products, and perspectives of

other cultures. Despite this challenge, Teacher 3's willingness to engage with a different culture reflects an attitude of curiosity and openness (Byram,1997; Bennet,2011).

These situations made Teacher 3 aware of her limited knowledge of intercultural communicative competence (ICC). She recognised that what is acceptable in Algeria may not be acceptable in other parts of the world (Acceptance of cultural differences). Teacher 4 and Teacher 5 reported that they did not encounter challenges in communication or experience a cultural clash while interacting with different cultures.

Teacher A demonstrated that there were some challenges that hindered his communication with people in the UK during his intercultural experience. He stated that some individuals he met with did not have the curiosity and openness (Byram,1997;2002;2006) to learn about his culture (Algerian). He described their reactions as judgmental, particularly when it comes to physical appearance and certain sensitive topics. According to Teacher A, these individuals seemed more critical than open-minded, reacting strongly to discussions on specific and sensitive issues, leading to unsuccessful interaction. This aligns with Ruben (1989) concept "the absence of the interlocutor" (p.234) which makes the interaction primarily monological and individualistic. Dervin (2010) supported this perspective by indicating that an individual can act as an intercultural competent speaker but may still encounter cultural misunderstandings and face communication challenges due to the interlocutor's lack of intercultural attitudes or interest in knowing about the other's culture. In other words, reaching successful intercultural interaction requires both parties to have intercultural attitudes. However, Teacher A reported that he met with other individuals who were more inclined to listen rather than speak, showing a genuine interest in understanding his viewpoints and culture. Therefore, the participant (Teacher A) urged the importance of mutual tolerance and respect for effective intercultural interactions. Teacher A stated that meeting and interacting with people who do not share the same culture is crucial because the more the individual travels the more his/her horizons are widened and the more tolerant, open, and flexible they will be. Teacher C claimed that she witnessed various intercultural experiences in England and France. She expressed that the first thing she worked on while being there was to have that mindset of not belonging neither to the lifestyle nor to the culture there. Yet she developed an adapted to the new environment (Bennett,1993). She also stated that she adjusted her perspectives and behaviours to be flexible towards people from different cultures (adaptation stage) (Bennett, 1993; 2004). Despite her ability to adapt,

she stated that she encountered several challenges in communication. Her challenge was similar to **Teacher 2**, from the West university, where they both mentioned that academic English is completely different from real-life English. She expressed, “Real-life English is different from classroom English”. Furthermore, she stated that her intercultural experience assisted her to reflect upon her English use in her teaching practices. She reported that she did not realise that her communication skills were missing until she got into direct contact with native speakers of English. Notably, Teacher C placed significant emphasis on how her intercultural exposure influenced her communicative competence rather than focusing on how her intercultural attitudes were fostered. While she acknowledged the importance of adapting to new cultural environments, her primary concern seemed to revolve around the practical challenges of language use, particularly the differences between academic English and real-life English spoken by native speakers. In addition, Teacher D faced some challenges while communicating with people from different backgrounds. He pointed out how tricky it is to fall into the trap of misunderstanding in the middle of the conversation. Teacher E stated that his communication between cultures used to be influenced by his own culture and societal norms. He used to believe that his culture is superior and best one (Defence Stage). He stated that he used to interpret and respond based on his cultural background, without fully considering the cultural context of the other person. Therefore, he encountered several cultural misunderstandings. This perspective can be linked to the early stages of Bennett’s model of Intercultural Sensitivity Development (the denial and defence stages) (Bennett,2004). Teacher E’s reliance on using his own cultural norms to interpret and interact with other people from different cultures suggests that he might be interacting from a position of defence, where he might perceive his own culture as right and superior or as a reference. This can lead to misunderstandings and tensions.

5.3.4.3 Benefits of Intercultural Exposure in Promoting Intercultural Awareness

Teachers from both East and West Universities reported that their intercultural experiences promoted their cultural and intercultural awareness. These exposures allowed them to gain a deeper understanding of diverse cultural practices, values, and communication styles. It also enabled them to navigate different intercultural misunderstandings.

Teacher 1 addressed that she did not face challenges in communicating with foreigners because they were gathered in a formal setting where academic English was spoken inside

the classroom. Yet she pointed out that she was cautious observing and noting that people she interacted with had different ways of interactions. Therefore, she tried her best to pay attention to her words before uttering them and also looked for the appropriate ways to express her ideas. In addition, the interviewee indicated that she was already aware that there are some phrases and body language that exist in one culture that might be offensive in other cultures. She mentioned that she was given a teaching brochure by the institution in London to teach with. This brochure was mainly to make the teacher trainees aware not to mention “any examples that might be culturally sensitive or offensive to the other”.

It is interesting to mention that this participant declared that culture cannot be fully conveyed through documents and books. She emphasised the importance of experiential learning, which involves immersive experiences such as exchange programmes which give learners the opportunity to explore and interact with different cultures (Dervin,2017). Although such cultural exposures are limited for Algerian learners, Teacher 1 reported that she uses her own intercultural experiences in the ICC course to develop her students' awareness and enrich their understanding and appreciation of cultural diversity. In the interview, **Teacher 1** affirmed that her intercultural experiences in London promoted her flexibility, openness, and curiosity (Byram,1997,2006,2008) to know more about other people's beliefs, values, and behaviours. Additionally, she stated that through these intercultural encounters in London, she could recognise and value commonalities and differences that exist between different cultures. In addition, she developed the art of appreciating, tolerating and respecting different cultural practices. She expressed:

It was amazing to notice, appreciate and respect the differences between cultures, and to be able to find some commonalities and differences between these cultures. I do believe that all cultures of the world have to meet somewhere. These experiences made me feel more tolerant, more open and flexible towards others' cultures. It enriched my perspective and my knowledge. (**Teacher 1**)

Teacher 1's feelings about her intercultural lived experience were described as “reborn” because when she stepped out of her comfort zone, she explored and valued the cultural differences around her. Her way of perceiving things has changed.

Despite the challenges the participants encountered, Teacher 2 demonstrated a welcoming and flexible attitude toward cultural differences. He also articulated the importance of

preserving one's own cultural identity, in which he explained that identity attachment involves staying true to one's own values and sense of belonging. Furthermore, understanding what is unique and different about one's own culture (Frank,2013) and respecting others' cultures and identities is crucial. By maintaining this balance, individuals can appreciate their cultural background, while also developing a deeper understanding and empathy for different cultural practices. This approach makes individuals able to navigate and appreciate the richness of global diversity without losing a sense of self. This is called by Liddicoat and Scarino (2013) intercultural awareness which is reached through exploring, questioning, and redefining boundaries between the self and others (Liddicoat and Scarino, 2013).

Teacher 2 acknowledged that his Indian friend and himself occasionally encountered misunderstandings, but due to their awareness and understanding of Intercultural Communicative Competence (ICC), they were able to overcome these obstacles and overcome any misinterpretations rooted in their cultural backgrounds. Teacher 2's reflections align with his initial interview responses, where he expressed an awareness and familiarity with ICC. He emphasised his ability to mediate and bridge cultural gaps, consistently advising his students to adopt positive attitudes towards diversity.

Teacher 2 further supported Teacher 1's perspective about the excitement of meeting people from different cultures while travelling, highlighting the interconnected relationship between the self and the other. He stated that the self is completed through interactions with others. In other words, cultural identities are not fixed but fluid, and interactions with other cultures can reshape one's understanding of his/her own culture as well as his/her perception of others (Liddicoat and Scarino,2013). Additionally, he shared insights from his travels within Algeria, describing it as a multicultural country where even people who share the same language and religion may have distinct cultures. Teacher 2 argued that these differences should be respected and accepted, underscoring the importance of intercultural competence in navigating both international and intra-cultural interactions.

Teacher 3 and Teacher 4 stated that their intercultural exposures led them to understand and appreciate their culture. In addition, they indicated that their intercultural attitudes were promoted. Teacher 3 articulated that these lived experiences were of great help in teaching intercultural communication courses, as students are interested in real-life experiences.

Teacher 3 reported that the incidents she encountered provided her with an opportunity to develop skills of discovery and interaction (Byram,1997,2006), as it encouraged her to seek

out and learn more about different cultural contexts. She also stated that this experience developed her critical cultural awareness, a key component in Byram's model (1997), where she began to critically reflect on the differences between her own culture and other cultures, understanding that what is considered respectful in one culture may not be perceived the same way in another.

Teacher 5 indicated that she did not face any challenge or a cultural clash in France due to her familiarity with the French language and culture. In addition, her attitudes towards others were based on her understanding and appreciation of the differences. The participant further elucidated in her interview that there was no kind of clash because she didn't feel that people were imposing their way of thinking or the way of living on her, they respected the way she was. She interestingly referred to a Qur'anic verse to explain her point of view as: "لَكُمْ دِينُكُمْ وَلِيَ دِينِ"; English: "For you is your religion, and for me is my religion" Surah al-Kafirun (109:6). This participant here preferred to switch to Arabic to explain herself as she wished. The interviewee quoted a Quranic verse to show that her religion persuades her to respect and tolerate cultural and religious differences. She drew on religion as a metaphor because of its strong resonance. Teacher 5 demonstrated the significant role of knowledge as a foundation in fostering intercultural awareness, stating: "You first need to develop knowledge because without knowledge we cannot say that we have an intercultural awareness". However, this perspective contradicts Bennett's views, she argued that acquiring knowledge or learning certain behavioural skills from another culture is insufficient if one does not know how to use them appropriately within that culture context. Bennett (1997) introduced the concept of the "fluent fool" to describe individuals who, despite being knowledgeable in a foreign culture, fail to grasp the deeper cultural nuances and therefore struggle to apply their knowledge in a meaningful way Bennett (1997; p16). She stressed that the development of components of knowledge and skills should be accompanied by acceptance and adaptation, allowing individuals to navigate cultural differences (Bennett, 2004). Teacher 5 further elucidated that knowledge can be acquired through real-life experiences (short sojourns) as well as through research. Teacher A, Teacher B and Teacher C noted that their engagement with people from different cultural backgrounds broadened their horizons and enabled them to be more tolerant and open towards others' cultural practices and perspectives. They stated that the diverse viewpoints they encountered enriched their understanding, allowing them to view and understand cultures from multiple angles. However, it is important to remark that

Teacher B focused on comparing the English she uses in her teaching practices and the English used by native speakers of English.

Teacher D pointed out that he developed empathetic intelligence through intercultural immersion. He explained that he started putting himself in others' shoes when dealing with a culture different from his own. Referring to empathetic intelligence here means that the participant demonstrated self-discipline by setting aside preconceptions and biases from his cultural background (Byram, 1997) and fully engaging with the perspectives and experiences of others. Teacher E indicated that he met with people from different nationalities. He stated that each culture is unique in its features. What Teacher E found exciting about travelling was meeting different cultures and being exposed to how people perceive and view the world differently. The respondent indicated that this experience helped him to break the ethnocentric attitude he used to have. This aligns with the model of intercultural sensitivity development (Bennett, 2004). He indicated that in his first encounter with individuals from diverse cultures, he had ethnocentric thinking in viewing and evaluating other cultures according to the preconceptions he held in his culture. However, after his intercultural experiences, he learned how to challenge these stereotypes. The interviewee reported that different incidents he witnessed in the host country raised his intercultural awareness.

5.3.4.4 Sharing and Embracing Cultural Identity Through Intercultural Dialogue - introducing Algeria to the world-

Teacher 3 shared a positive experience with an individual from different cultures who showed a genuine interest in the Algerian language, culture, and lifestyle. This person was interested to know about teacher 3's background and engaged in conversations to learn more about Algeria. Teacher 3 found this intercultural exchange both enjoyable and enriching, as it deepened her understanding of her own culture while providing an opportunity to introduce and promote Algerian cultures to others. Reflecting on the experience, she remarked, "It's a nice experience when you go abroad to publicise your country because sometimes you realise it's unknown to the world." Additionally, Teacher 1 stated that, after several intercultural interactions, her non-Algerian friends gained an understanding of the Algerian culture and they were eager to know about her traditions and religion. She asserted that these experiences taught her and her friends the importance of being flexible, tolerant, and open to learning about other cultures. According to her, these interactions not only broadened

their perspectives but also fostered mutual respect and understanding across cultural boundaries. Furthermore, Teacher A shared that some of the people he interacted with were keen to know about his culture. Most of the teachers from the East and West Universities demonstrated that these intercultural exposures provided them with the opportunity to introduce various aspects of their culture to the world, including their traditions, values, beliefs, and social norms. They stated that these intercultural exposures allowed them to reflect and understand their cultural identity in broader contexts and fostered their respect and appreciation of different cultures.

5.3.4.5 Intercultural Encounters' Impact on Teaching Practices

Intercultural exposures have developed the participants' appreciation of their own culture and promote tolerance and understanding towards other cultures. The direct interaction with different cultures enriched their perspectives, making their knowledge more comprehensive and nuanced. It was interesting that Teacher 1 believed that cultural understanding cannot be fully captured through documentaries or books alone; instead, it requires direct engagement with communities from different cultural backgrounds. According to her, these exposures have profoundly influenced her teaching practices by providing concrete, real-life examples of other cultures, which they now incorporate into her lectures. She reported that these vivid examples, drawn from personal interactions with people from diverse backgrounds, offer students a more authentic and relatable understanding of different cultures, making the lessons far more impactful and interesting than generalized or theoretical examples. Additionally, Teacher 2 indicated that these intercultural exposures contributed to the development of his Intercultural communicative competence (ICC) and it also enabled him to transmit this knowledge to his learners in the intercultural communicative competence course at West University. In the classroom, Teacher 2 addressed the Indian culture as an ICC course and encouraged his students to share their knowledge about it. Most of their responses were centred around Indian dancing and music, which they had seen on TV and social media platforms. However, he disagreed with their perceptions and utilised the knowledge he gained from his Indian friend to challenge their stereotypes and broaden their understanding towards the Indian culture.

These encounters also developed Teacher 3's intercultural awareness and influenced her teaching practices. Initially, her teaching focused primarily on developing learners' linguistic

and communicative competence. However, after experiencing misunderstandings in several intercultural settings, she shifted her teaching objectives to integrate intercultural communicative competence (ICC). Teacher 3 demonstrated that her intercultural experiences were crucial in helping her convey the importance of ICC to her students, who are more interested in practical, real-life experiences than in theoretical or factual knowledge about cultures. This perspective is confirmed by Byram and Kramsch (2008), who reported that students prefer and, in fact, provide higher interest to language teachers who promote dynamic engagement in their lectures and create opportunities for students to independently explore concepts, rather than just feeding them with factual information about grammar or the history of other civilisations.

Teacher 3 stated that she used the cultural shocks she experienced as a course to prepare students for similar scenarios and enable them to bridge and mediate between cultural differences.

On the other hand, most of the teachers from the East University did not demonstrate how these intercultural exposures influenced their teaching practices. Only Teacher C expressed that her experience helped her to reflect on her English language use. She stated that her communicative skills were improved during her interaction with native speakers of English. Therefore, she reported that her main objective of teaching is to develop students' communicative competence to communicate with native speakers of English. This perspective has been greatly criticised by Byram (2013) and Alptekin (2002) who believed that the traditional teaching approaches of CC which heavily emphasise the model of native speaker is impractical and no longer sufficient for acquiring global language in intercultural contexts.

Teachers from West University, in contrast, believed that true communicative competence extends beyond linguistic accuracy and fluency to have the ability to navigate cultural differences in communication (Byram,1997). This broader perspective incorporates the understanding that effective communication in a globalized world requires sensitivity to cultural contexts, which is essential for students to function successfully in diverse environments. Overall, Intercultural lived experiences are considered a valuable resource and an educational approach to develop learners' intercultural attitudes in a more dynamic and impactful way.

5.3.5 Concluding the chapter (Summary of the Findings)

This chapter presents the findings regarding the conceptions and beliefs of Algerian English language teachers concerning the teaching of language and culture in the teaching of English as an FL. It also sought to explore their perspectives of ICC and to what extent ICC dimensions are embedded in the classroom in the East and West Universities in Algeria. Furthermore, it investigated the teachers' different intercultural encounters and how their experiences promoted their intercultural awareness, and how it influenced their teaching practices. The chapter aimed to answer the first and the second research questions of this study, which address the teachers' conceptions and beliefs about language and culture teaching, and their perspectives of ICC in teaching English.

The findings revealed that Algerian English language teachers hold diverse definitions of culture, ranging from traditional and structural definitions to more constructivist perspectives although the latter are more common in the West University. The teachers expressed their willingness to teach culture and acknowledged its fundamental role in English language teaching and learning. However, teaching culture in practice at the East University was assigned a minor role in the classroom, where they implicitly tackle the target culture. Previous studies indicated that the teaching of culture often lacked seriousness (Guilherme, 2002). In addition, the findings displayed that teachers from the East University tend to teach culture as an add-on to foster learners' language proficiency. However, teachers from the West University shared an anti-essentialist perspective of culture, they viewed culture as complex, dynamic and fluid. This research finding aligned with the literature, suggesting that culture and language cannot be separated (Kramsch, 1993, 2009; Risager, 1998, 2007; Byram, 1997, 2011). Findings displayed that the ICC understanding of teachers from East University was limited and bound to the target culture. They sometimes provided unclear definitions and occasionally referred to ICC as CC. However, teachers from the West University were aware and familiar with ICC, relating it to cultural understanding, intercultural awareness, intercultural dialogues, and intercultural tolerance towards different cultures. Teachers from the West University demonstrated the importance of incorporating intercultural training in Algeria for language teachers.

Although most of the teachers from the East University had intercultural encounters with people of different cultural backgrounds, their perspectives of ICC are still limited to the target

culture. Their major aim of teaching was to prepare learners to acquire and speak like native speakers of English. However, the intercultural lived experiences of teachers from the West University were based on understanding cultural differences, developing intercultural awareness, and introducing those experiences to their learners in the ICC course.

Chapter Six

English Language Learners' Perspectives and Attitudes of culture and ICC in EFL Context

6.1 Introduction

The main aim of the second phase was to collect Master learners' perspectives and understandings of the notions of culture and intercultural communication. The online questionnaires (see Appendix E) were conducted with sixty (n60) learners (participants) and it was in English for two reasons. First, the participants, who were invited to engage in the survey were learners who had majored in the English language for four years. Their English language was good enough that it enabled them to understand and provide answers to all the questions addressed in the online questionnaires. Second, the language of instruction for teaching culture and ICC is English. Therefore, it is likely that they are more conversant about this topic in English rather than Arabic. A fifteen-item questionnaire was submitted through an online questionnaire format and not a paper form mainly to ensure confidentiality and to allow learner participants to respond in a setting they feel secure and comfortable in. The questionnaires mostly comprised closed-ended questions to help learners supply straightforward answers and prepare them to take part in the focus group interviews. However, a few open-ended questions were included to address learners' self-comprehension and attitudes toward the notion of ICC.

The answers to the questions which are quantified are presented in tables. The figures in the table, on the whole, represent the number of learners who responded with this answer and the sum represents the total number of respondents. However, in some cases, learners had the option to give several responses to the same question; therefore, the sum might exceed the number of participants. The data from the questionnaire and the focus group discussions are presented and discussed through the lens of the following research question:

- What are Master English learners' perceptions and attitudes of culture and intercultural communicative competence, and to what extent ICC is embedded in their English learning?

6.2 Learners' Questionnaire Analysis

		Total
Age	20-25	50
	26-32	10
Gender	Male	19
	Female	41
Nationality	Malian	5
	Algerian	55

Table 1: Demographic information of learner participants

Question1: Learners' Age

The first question addresses the age category of learners who took part in the questionnaires. As shown in the overhead table, the majority of participants for this study are young adult Algerian and Malian learners whose ages ranged between (22-25).

Question 2: Learners' Gender

The majority of participants in the questionnaires are females (n41) which largely exceeds the number of male participants (n19). In order to preserve the same gender balance in both focus group discussions and questionnaires, more females were recruited to the focus group interviews than males.

Question 3: Learners Nationality

This question sought to find out the learners' nationality. It was significant to explore if the Algerian classroom is a cross-cultural setting. The question revealed that the majority of learners are from Algeria, and a very small number of five (n5) learners are from Mali (two (n2) at the East and three (n3) at the West). Malian learners left their home and travelled to Algeria for the sake of pursuing their postgraduate studies. It was enriching for the present study to include learners from different cultures in order to investigate their international learning experience and to shed light on their intercultural interactions in the focus groups interviews.

Question 4: Learners' English Speciality

Subject	Participants	
Didactics of Language and Foreign Cultures	East	43
Language and Communication	West	16
Prefer not say	1	

Total	60
-------	----

Table 2: Number of the Learners according to their English Streams

This fourth item illustrates the learners' academic courses in Algeria. A small number of sixteen (n16) learners from the West University specialised in Language and Communication while the vast majority of respondents were learners from the East University of Algeria whose speciality is Didactics of Languages and Foreign Cultures.

From my investigation of both sites, the difference between the aforementioned specialities is that the former addresses language and culture from communicative and intercultural perspectives. The latter, although its name indicates that teaching foreign cultures is promoted; however, it focuses on the structural aspects of the language. this speciality addresses the superficial aspects of culture (big C culture) which view culture as a bounded body of knowledge rather than living social practices. Only one learner preferred not to identify his subject course, yet he stated that he is doing a master's degree at the East University.

Question 5: Years of Studying English

Years of studying English	Participants
1-4	3
5-8	5
9-12	42
13+	10
Total	60

Table 3: Learners' Years of Studying English Language

This item examines the period of learning the English language since learners' middle school phase. It is noticed that 42 out of 60 learners stated that they have been studying English for (9-12) years. Other ten (n10) learners showed that they studied English for more than 13 years as it is shown in the table above. However, a small number of five (n5) learners intended to count only the university phase of studying the English language and this period was for five years (3 years Bachelor plus 2 years Masters).

Question 6: Please rate the three most important primary reasons for choosing to learn English at university.

Motives of Choosing the English language	Participants	
	West	East
Personal Interest	15	40
To know more about Foreign Cultures	2	10
To Teach EFL in Algeria	12	21
To study in a foreign country	9	42
University Requirement	5	13
Sitting for Language tests as IELTS	0	6

Table 4: Learners' Motives for choosing to learn English.

In this item learners were not asked to be restricted to tick one option; they were rather asked to choose three options according to the degree of importance behind their rationale of studying English as a major subject at university.

As was explained previously, most of the participants who took part in the completion of the questionnaires studied English for more than twelve years. The table overhead represents what were the most three important motives that drove the participants to choose English as a major subject at the university level. Most of the respondents (15 from the West and 40 from the East) opted for personal interest as the main motive.

The second large proportion to this question (12 from the West and 21 from the East University) is allocated to the learners' willingness to teach EFL in Algeria after graduation. The third category chosen was to pursue their postgraduate studies abroad. At the other end of the spectrum, the least category was assigned for university requirements and sitting for an IELTS test as motives behind choosing the English language.

Question 7: Languages studied other than English.

Languages other than English	Participants	
	West	East
French and Arabic	16	22
Spanish	8	2
Korean	2	0

German	0	2
Turkish and Russian	0	1

Table 5: Distribution of Learners studying other foreign languages.

This question was raised to find out what other languages English learners are learning. It can be figured out from the table above that a large proportion of the population stated that they are learning French and Arabic in both settings. This category was chosen by the majority because Arabic is the official language, and French is the first foreign language in Algeria. The focus on the French language was because, as mentioned in the contextual chapter of this study, is the language of administration, technology and science in Algeria. It has a substantial impact on the Algerians' identity in particular and on the Algerian educational system in general. In addition, eight (n8) learners out of sixteen (n16) from the West indicated that they learn Spanish as an additional language to their repertoire. On the other hand, only two (n2) out of forty-four (n44) participants from the East University showed their interest in learning Spanish. This may be because Spanish is taught as an optional subject to learners who specialise in the Language and Communication stream at the West University but not in the East. The least nominated category is allocated to learners who learn Turkish and Russian.

Question 8: To what extent these methods are good for increasing the practical use of English (CC)?

Statements	SA		A		N		D		SD	
	W	E	W	E	W	E	W	E	W	E
Attending practical courses such as how to make successful English conversations.	6	23	8	18	0	2	2	1	0	0
Memorising vocabulary and well-formed utterances to use during interactions.	1	11	0	30	5	2	10	0	0	1
Learning about more about grammatical rules.	0	10	4	31	1	1	12	1	0	1
Joining language study groups.	0	21	13	13	2	4	1	5	0	1
Reading short stories and novels.	4	29	11	11	0	1	0	3	1	0
Listening to English songs.	2	18	11	14	3	7	0	5	1	0
Watching English series or movies.	4	27	12	13	0	1	0	2	0	1

Table 6: Learners' Perceptions of the appropriate ways to improve their CC.

This item sought to understand the efficient methods of teaching students to use English properly, as well as strategies to develop different cultural attitudes.

Firstly, the majority of learners from both settings (14(88%) from the West and 41(93%) from the East) robustly agreed that the attendance of practical courses would assist students to communicate effectively. However, a very small proportion 3(5%) of respondents expressed their disagreement about the first strategy.

Secondly, 41(93%) learners from the East expressed their agreement about the strategy of memorisation of vocabulary and other well-formed statements as a good factor to enhance their communicative competence. However, only 1(6%) learner from the West University agreed with it. Likewise, in the third statement, the same number of learners from the East 41(93%) stressed that learning the grammatical rules of language can be deemed as a prominent factor in helping them improve their language skills. On the other hand, only 4(25%) respondents from the West agreed. It is noticeable that there is a huge difference between learners' perspectives of the West and the East universities.

It is marked that the vast majority of learners from the East 34(77%) indicated in their responses that learning the language in group discussions is a useful approach, where learners get the chance to freely discuss their points of view in a comfortable and open setting with their fellows. 13(81%) participants from the West also agreed about the usefulness of group discussion activities. This viewpoint is discussed in depth in teachers' interviews and perceptions of the GRC members at the West University.

Section 2: Language and Culture

Question 9: To what extent these competencies are taught/emphasised in the classroom?

Components taught in the classroom	SE		Slightly		OE		NE	
	W	E	W	E	W	E	W	E
Linguistic competence	11	19	2	13	3	9	0	3
Academic English resources relevant to your speciality	9	15	5	18	1	9	1	2
Communicative competence/ Fluency +Intercultural CC	11	9	1	16	2	13	2	6
Understanding a range of cultural practices	10	8	2	18	3	10	1	8
Gaining awareness about cultural differences	9	16	5	13	1	9	1	6

Skills of comparing and contrasting in relation to the Algerian culture	9	17	3	10	3	7	1	10
Ways of interaction with foreigners	10	8	2	18	3	9	1	9

Table 7: Distribution of learners according to the most/least emphasised competence in EFL classroom.

The table above indicates to what extent the aforementioned listed components are emphasised in the Algerian classroom. This item was designed using a scale of strongly emphasised, slightly emphasised, occasionally part of the classroom, and lastly not a component in the classroom. Seven statements were given, and teaching about linguistic competence took the lion's share in both settings. 11(69%) learners from the West strongly asserted that this competence is crucial and significant. However, 19(43%) learners from the East University indicated that the main element addressed in all subjects was linguistic competence. However, 13(81%) learners from the East University reported that this component is slightly emphasised.

Furthermore, only 5(31%) responses stated that other academic resources, which are relevant to the learners' speciality were slightly emphasised at the University of the West. On the other hand, 18 (41%) participants from the East ticked the same option. Very few numbers of them denied that all that they are exposed to, is relevant to their speciality.

The third component as shown in this table is the communicative competence and ICC. It can be noticed that the number of responses who strongly emphasised from the West University is 11 (69%).

Eleven respondents, who majored in the Language and Communication speciality, indicated that communicative competence and ICC is the primary aim of teaching English as a foreign language in the West University. This answer will be further explained in the students' focus group interview analysis. However, 69% of the answers allocated to slightly and occasionally part of the classroom, were answered from learners from the East of Algeria.

Overall, linguistic competence is much more emphasised in both settings, whereas communication and ICC are also strongly emphasised in the West but not in the East.

The following three statements were about understanding and gaining awareness of cultural practices, and comparing and contrasting skills development. It can be seen that the vast majority of learners from the West claimed that these competencies are strongly emphasised

in their courses at the West University. In contrast, a very small proportion of 6% claimed that these skills are not addressed. On the other hand, 20% of the participants from the East showed that these aspects of understanding and gaining different cultural activities were not tackled in the classroom.

The last one was about the ways of interaction, 18 (41%) learners from the East answered that this method is partially emphasised. On the other hand, the 10 (63%) answers from the West revealed that ways and strategies of interaction with foreigners are highly emphasised by their teachers in the EFL classroom. Only 6% from the West disagreed. However, 20% from the East chose to answer that ways of interaction are not included in their course.

Question 10: Please indicate to what extent do you agree/disagree with the following statements.

Statements	S		A		N		D		SD	
	W	E	W	E	W	E	W	E	W	E
Learning language skills solely facilitates the learning process	6	26	4	12	3	2	1	3	2	1
Learning about the target culture solely facilitates the learning process	1	10	7	20	1	5	5	6	2	3
Learning the language skills in conjunction with the target culture	5	26	11	13	0	4	0	1	0	0
How foreigners behave enables you to develop your communicative skills	10	32	4	12	2	0	0	0	0	0
Learning about different cultural subjects makes the learning more interesting	6	24	10	12	0	5	0	1	0	2
Keeping an open mind is an important subject	7	27	6	13	3	0	0	4	0	0
Being exposed to different cultural elements, I developed a positive attitude	3	13	10	19	2	9	1	3	0	0
Being exposed to different cultural elements, I developed a negative attitude	0	2	1	4	4	14	4	15	7	9

Table 8: Learners' attitudes of Learning English as a Second Foreign Language.

To analyse the data in the table above, it is better to combine answers of “strongly agree” and “agree” together to demonstrate the learners’ positive attitudes towards the statements addressed, and the “disagree and strongly disagree” answers together to indicate the students’ negative attitude towards the issue.

Question 10 is composed of nine statements. Learners were asked to rank these statements using the five Likert scale. A very large number of learners from the East (89%) and West (100%) universities strongly agreed with the idea that learning language skills in connection with learning about the target culture helps to develop linguistic and communicative competence. The amalgamation of language and culture teaching is very important as it is discussed in the literature review because learning about culture makes the learners able to use English successfully in real-life settings, and makes them aware of the sociocultural rules of language use in a society.

This can be confirmed in the fourth statement which, constitutes the second next majority of learners from both settings, who agreed that learning the ways foreigners behave, think, and communicate encourages their willingness to improve their communicative skills. This agreement though does not infer that all of them are exposed to the ICC notion and its dimensions. By contrast, there is a very small number of learners (2%) from the East who disagreed with the teaching combination of language and culture.

10 (63%) learners from the West shared the idea that learning language skills alone eases the learning process of the English language. However, another 8 (50%) responses from the same setting indicated their agreement with the second statement that learning about the target culture makes the English learning process easier and expedited.

On the other hand, most of the learners (86%) from the East agreed on the idea that learning the four skills alone makes the learning of English much easier for EFL students. By the same token, 30 (68%) learners from the East strongly agreed that learning about the target culture facilitates teaching English to students, who are not familiar with foreign cultures. Very small responses from both universities, as shown in the above table, are allocated to the other three options neutral, disagree and strongly disagree.

In addition, 13 (81%) learners from the West held positive attitudes when they were exposed to different cultural elements. By contrast, only one learner (6%) from the same setting confirmed that he developed a negative attitude towards the other.

32 (73%) learners from the East developed a positive attitude when they were exposed to several cultural elements. Other nine (20%) participants from the same university neither supported nor denied that learning about the cultural elements helped them to develop a positive attitude, so they stated a neutral answer.

Question 11: How important are the following goals for you as an English Master learner?

Statements	A		A		N		D		SA	
	W	E	W	E	W	E	W	E	We	E
To get a degree	1	7	10	23	4	1	1	3	0	0
Developing competence in daily communication	13	24	3	18	0	0	0	1	0	1
Reflection upon cultural diversity in English classroom	8	1	8	26	0	15	0	2	0	0
Develop the intellectual thinking side	10	16	6	21	0	6	0	1	0	0
Enlighten your mind and broaden your knowledge about other foreign or international cultures	5	27	11	15	0	0	0	1	0	1
Improve your personal knowledge and develop your lifelong learning abilities	10	1	6	21	0	21	0	1	0	0
To develop your global communication skills	13	18	3	19	0	4	0	3	0	0

Table 9: Learners' goals of learning English.

This closed-ended item examines the participants' main goal of learning English in Algeria. Six objectives were provided. The aim of developing attitudes and different competencies in daily communication occupied a great space in the learners' perceptions (16 (100%) from the West/ 42 (95%) from the East). Learners from both settings robustly agreed that their goal is to improve their daily communication skills with their colleagues and with others from different cultural backgrounds.

Furthermore, 16 (100%) responses from the West revealed that the second-ranked goal is to be able to reflect upon several cultural diversity practices in the classroom. A smaller percentage of respondents from the East showed their agreement about reflecting upon cultural differences. This idea is recognised in Byram's (1997) theoretical framework, where he referred to reflection upon cultural similarities/differences as the skill of interpreting/ relating and discovery/interacting.

The last four statements showed that the whole number of learners from the West (100%) significantly agreed about developing intellectual thinking, enlightening the students' knowledge about other cultures and developing personal and global communication skills as important goals to achieve as Master learners of English. However, a small number of participants from the East marked their disagreement about these four goals. The respondents (11 (68%) out of 16 from the West/ 30 (68%) out of 44 from the East) showed that the primary goal of learning English is to get a degree.

Question 12: What is Culture?

Statements (Culture is to know about?)	SA		A		N		D		SD	
	W	E	W	E	W	E	W	E	W	E
Information which tackles history, geography and political issues of cultures of English-speaking countries.	1	11	11	10	2	6	2	3	0	2
knowledge about daily life and routine of people who have different cultures.	7	9	7	22	1	3	0	3	1	1
Shared beliefs, values and moral that are different from your own values.	8	0	5	22	2	16	0	6	1	0
Is about films, mass media, poems, drama and short stories, theatre and music.	6	13	8	19	2	9	0	3	0	0
About developing empathy, tolerance towards peoples living in other cultures.	8	10	8	15	0	14	0	5	0	0
About boosting reflection and critical thinking on cultural differences.	6	7	10	21	1	7	0	5	0	4
About promoting your understanding towards your own culture.	6	8	7	19	3	6	0	4	0	7
About developing the ability to handle intercultural contact situations.	6	15	10	22	0	2	0	1	0	4

Table 10: Learners' definitions of culture.

The complexity of agreeing on one definition of the term culture is explained in the literature review and it was looked at from myriad different perspectives, where many scholars were reluctant to give a constant comprehensive definition (Seelye, 1974).

This is a closed-ended question that was set out mainly to examine the learners' perceptions and understandings of the concept of culture, they were required to rate their answers using the five Likert scale to yield useful straightforward data that addresses the research question. The answers to these questions relate in one way or another to the answers revealed in the preceded question. The above table revealed that the behavioural patterns of people such as their beliefs, values, identities, and daily life patterns occupied the first rank of agreement among the majority of learners as a valid succinct definition of the term culture with a total of 14 (88%) answers from the West and 31 (70%) from the East.

Next, the total number of learners who agreed that the term culture refers to knowledge that tackles history, civilization and geographical issues of cultures of English-speaking countries was 12 (75%) learners from the West. In contrast, 21(48%) from the East agreed about the

above definition. The participants' choice refers back to the fact that they are exposed to the aspects of capital "C" culture in the classroom. This can be confirmed in the teachers' interviews especially those from the East, where they revealed that culture subject is being addressed theoretically.

The four last statements were mainly mentioned to see how learners can understand the linked relationship between the term culture and the ICC. It also aimed to investigate the learners' perceptions towards the shift to ICC when it comes to defining culture. Therefore, I made sure to mention many different dimensions of the ICC as empathy, tolerance, critical reflection, and handling several intercultural issues. It can be noted that the majority of participants from both universities ticked the agree box where the aforementioned components are strongly significant to be included whenever we define culture. These perceptions will be deeply explored in the analysis of the focus group discussions.

Question 13: What is Intercultural Communicative Competence?

Statements	SA		A		N		D		SD	
	W	E	W	E	W	E	W	E	W	E
How to interact successfully with people who are culturally different.	11	19	4	23	1	1	0	0	1	1
Field of research that addresses how people grasp and understand the cultural boundaries.	6	8	10	25	0	7	0	1	0	3
The commonalities and differences between different cultures.	4	8	11	15	1	12	0	8	0	1
Analysing and adopting one's behaviours while interacting with others from different cultures.	4	7	7	16	1	9	2	9	2	3
Making judgments and stereotypes while communicating with others.	0	3	0	10	2	6	3	15	11	10

Table 11: Learners' Definitions of the Notion ICC

This question was raised to examine the students' definitions of the notion of ICC. I gave the participants five definitions and asked them to rate from strongly agree to strongly disagree. Again, the strongly agree/agree and strongly disagree/disagree answers are combined.

The first, second and third statements captured the highest number of participants' attitudes. Fifteen (94%) EFL students from the West strongly agreed that interacting properly with people, who are culturally different, can be considered a crucial definition of the term ICC. However, only one participant showed his disagreement about the use of this definition. In this case, it seems that most of the participants except one shared a prevalent understanding

of what ICC is. Similarly, 42(95%) participants out of 44 who were enrolled at the East University robustly agreed about the use of this definition.

Understanding cultural boundaries was ranked as the second significant suggested definition. All participants from the West held an attitude of understanding cultural boundaries because the ICC subject is introduced in their university, and 7 (44%) participants who took part in the questionnaires have had intercultural encounters. In contrast, there were 33 (75%) responses out of 44 from the East who agreed that bridging and understanding cultural boundaries is a convenient definition for the ICC. However, 7 participants preferred to stay neutral and 4 disagreed. Furthermore, the third high-ranked definition had 14 (88%) out of 16 responses from the West agreeing that ICC can be defined as exploring and understanding the commonalities and differences between several cultures. 23 (52%) answers allocated to the university in the East agreed about the use of the above definition. 12 participants from the same setting preferred not to share their understanding of this statement, they stated neutral answers. The fourth statement was about the ability to analyse and adopt other cultural behaviours while interacting with others. Only 4(25%) participants from the West disagreed with this aforementioned definition. Similarly, a small proportion of 12 (27%) students from the East disagreed with the use of this definition. In the same vein, the last statement can be deemed to be the opposite of the one that preceded it. 13 (30%) participants from the East robustly agreed that the act of constructing stereotypes and making judgments about others can be considered as a definition of the ICC. However, no student from the West University used it as a definition.

Learners were later provided with an open space to freely express their views and perspectives about their attitudes about intercultural competent speakers (ICS). The reason behind incorporating this type of question was to highlight in-depth their awareness or unfamiliarity with intercultural communication.

The majority of learners defined ICS as an individual who can understand and interact properly with people who share neither the same language nor the same culture. Others, specifically from the West, referred to ICS as an individual who has skills of appreciation, acceptance, and openness towards his own culture and others' cultures.

Another participant from the West, WLB defined the concept as a language learner who possesses the five Savoirs of attitudes, knowledge, skills and critical cultural awareness referenced by Byram, (1997). She also explained that an individual, who can understand,

analyse, adapt his/her attitudes and behaviours accordingly to intercultural situations can be called an intercultural competent speaker. Another interesting definition of ICS was provided by learner WLH from West University. WLH stated:

Understanding that if we do not share the same points of view, no one is right or wrong, my way of doing things is not necessarily the right way and the best way is always our way (WLH).

Other respondents from the West University defined an intercultural competent speaker as referring to the ICC dimensions of openness, tolerance, empathy, and flexibility towards all cultures. This demonstrates that the respondent has a well-developed awareness and familiarity with the ICC concept and its components.

On the other end of the spectrum, there were some respondents from East University, whose understanding of an ICS was bound and limited to someone who can fluently communicate in English. None of the learners from East University referred to the ICC dimensions". Some participants from the East University revealed that learners were not familiar with interculturality and ICS. Instead, they stated, "I have no idea" EL14, and others preferred to leave the writing space empty.

Question 14: Have you ever been abroad?

Travelling abroad	Percentage	
	W	E
Yes	7	5
No	9	39
Total	60	

Table 12: Learners' distributions according to their travelling experiences.

This question is close-ended followed by three sub open-ended questions about learners' travelling experiences.

First, I was interested to know whether the learners, who took part in the questionnaires, have had the opportunity to travel abroad or not. This question was mainly raised to shed light on learners' intercultural experiences as it is shown in the table. Investigating their perspectives towards the cultural differences they experienced was vital. Raising this question assisted me as a researcher to invite some of the participants to take part in the focus group discussions from both settings.

Seven learners (44%) from the West have had international experiences by travelling to foreign countries including three Malian learners who mentioned that their intercultural lived experience was in Algeria. Five learners (11%) from the East had travelling experiences but mainly to Arab countries such as Dubai and Tunisia, in addition to two Malian learners, who travelled to Algeria to pursue their postgraduate studies at the University of the East.

The following sub-questions were raised if the learners' answers were yes.

- a) Which countries?
- b) For how long?
- c) For what purpose?

The participants were provided an open space to share their thoughts about the countries they have been to, the length of staying, and the purposes of the trip.

Twelve out of the whole population (20%) answered yes, they had the chance to travel abroad. One of the learners from the West stated that she had been to South Korea and stayed there for few months. Her main purpose was to attend university summer school. The same learner reported her second travel experience, which lasted longer which was in Portugal. Again, it was for academic purposes to attend an Erasmus program that was provided with limited places at the University of the West.

Another learner from the West University listed different places such as France, Germany, Belgium, Netherlands, and Switzerland. The purpose of travelling was tourism. This learner indicated that all her travelling experiences were for a short period, where she had to travel from one place to another to discover the commonalities and differences that exist among cultures. This learner indicated her fondness and passion for traveling to discover the different attitudes and beliefs of people from diverse cultural backgrounds. This is illustrated in the following quotation:

I have been to some European countries like France, Germany, Netherlands, Belgium, and Switzerland. In all these countries I stayed only a few days...not that much because I had to move on to discover different places and different cultures. I went there actually for vacation, besides my love towards discovering places and people and the way these people function in those places (WLH).

Five Malian participants (3 from the West/ 2 from the East) indicated that the foreign country they had been to was Algeria and the purpose was to pursue their postgraduate studies. Their lived experience in Algeria is extensively addressed in the focus group discussions.

On the other hand, learners from the East University stated that their travelling experiences were mainly to Arab countries, where language is similar to some extent. Their traveling experiences were for a short period. Furthermore, learners from the same site reported that they travelled to Tunisia and Turkey for two purposes tourism and work.

In brief, what can be noticed here is that a very small number of the Algerian learners had the experience of stepping out of their comfort zone “Algeria”. In fact, 48 (80%) learners have not had any intercultural traveling experiences.

Question 15: Do you think intercultural communicative competence should be given more/less emphasis in foreign language learning? What are the potential benefits?

Another open-ended question invited learners to identify freely their perspectives towards ICC learning in a foreign language context. The answers provided by students were expanded in the focus group analysis. The majority of learners from both settings reported that the integration of ICC should be robustly emphasised in the EFL (Foreign Language Learning) context.

In their answers, some learners referred to the interwoven relationship between language and culture such as EL5 who stated that “Culture and language are interrelated entities” (Risager,2006). Others described it as one coin with two sides, as stated in the literature review, language and culture cannot be dealt with as separate entities (Byram, 2014, Newton et al., 2010). In the same line of this view, learners’ beliefs from the West revolved particularly around acquiring cultural knowledge, understanding and appreciating cultural differences, overcoming misunderstandings and tensions, and promoting a sense of tolerance and empathy towards other cultures. These perspectives were found in one focus group discussion that took place at the West campus of Algeria.

This perspective can be illustrated in the following quotation:

Through incorporating the ICC in EFL learning, we will have an opportunity to learn more about our and other people's cultures, as well as the ability to avoid cultural shocks, stereotypes and misunderstandings that can lead to huge problems between the communicators (WLB).

On the other hand, learners from the East campus expressed their disappointment about the fact that the ICC is not introduced in the curriculum.

In our university, teachers can introduce new modules to teach students about the ICC or at least they can change parts of the curriculum. Teachers should stop teaching theories about old British and American civilisations and nations' history (EL12).

Some learners' perceptions from the East were limited, they indicated that the ICC should be emphasised and that is all. Their answers were very short, maybe this goes back to the little knowledge they had about the ICC. EL17 stated, "I am actually unable to answer this question as I have no idea". However, learners from the West explicitly expressed their perceptions and understandings of the ICC. Most of them tended to mention the ICC and IC dimensions whenever they answered an open-ended question. WLK stated that "Students who learn intercultural competence will be more aware of others' culture so they can be more critical not only about others' culture but about their own culture".

Question 16: In your opinion, what are the appropriate methods/approaches to use to develop the individual's cross-cultural competence towards foreign and international cultures?

This question endeavoured to explore learners' viewpoints about the appropriate approach or method that promotes learners' intercultural communication and enhances their understanding of intercultural awareness. Learners from West University believed that classrooms should be an intercultural setting where direct intercultural dialogues can take place. They also reported that learners' intercultural attitudes can be developed through integrating ICC dimensions (attitudes, knowledge, skills and critical cultural awareness) in English language teaching practices. Learners from West University shed light on the importance of providing classrooms and laboratories with network access, where learners can properly use social media platforms to interact with people from different cultures.

On the other hand, learners from East University demonstrated that the effective model of promoting ICC is to be taught by native speakers of English. EL1 reported, "Personally, I would prefer to be taught and have direct interaction with native speakers of English to be able to develop my intercultural and cross-cultural competence". As demonstrated by the views provided by learners from both universities, it can be stated that learners from West University are aware of intercultural communicative competence in contrast with learners from East University, who believed in the existence of one single culture (native speakers of English).

Learners' understandings of the notion of ICC and their intercultural experiences could be understood further by qualitative methodologies. Therefore, two focus group discussions were conducted on two different campuses in Algeria with Master students. One focus group was in the East and the other in the West to provide students (participants) with enough space to freely express their views and perceptions about ICC. The focus group discussions also outlined some of the participants' intercultural encounters and what their attitudes were.

6.3 Focus Group Discussions Analysis

In this section, I present and discuss the perceptions and conceptions of Master learners of English from both universities (East and West of Algeria) about their English language learning experience and the place of culture in the learning process. This study also aimed to explore learners' definitions and understandings of intercultural communicative competence (ICC) and how it is embedded in the classroom. Two focus group sessions took place in two different locations (East and West universities). I couldn't gather both groups in one session to gather more insightful and in-depth perceptions due to the geographical distance between the two settings of the study. I had to travel 838km to arrive at the second setting to gather the required data to answer the third research question of this study.

Both sessions were conducted and organised in meeting rooms at both universities with twelve (n12) learners in total (6 from each university). It is worth mentioning that learners who participated in the focus group discussions were of Algerian and Malian nationalities. There were four (n4) Malian students, two (n2) from each university, who participated in this study. They obtained a scholarship from their country to pursue their postgraduate studies in the East and West Universities in Algeria. Learners from the East University were identified with numbers while learners from the West University were indicated by alphabets. The same codes were used to analyse the open-ended questions in the questionnaires.

As a researcher, I was curious first to explore learners' perceptions of majoring in English in Algeria before diving into the discussion about their understanding of culture and ICC.

6.3.1 Learners' Perceptions of Their English Learning Experience in Algeria

It was significant to shed light on learners' experiences and perceptions of majoring in English at the university in Algeria and to explore their primary objectives. Remarkably, it was stated that most of the learners from the East University expressed their dissatisfaction about the methods employed in teaching English as a Foreign Language at their university. More

importantly, the majority demonstrated that the subjects provided by the Department of Didactics of Language and Foreign Cultures are outdated and deficient. In other words, these subjects do not stimulate the learners' curiosity and fail to promote their critical thinking skills. Therefore, learners believe that they are exposed repeatedly to the same modules and the same outdated content, which is not compatible with learners' needs and interests. EL1 expressed:

I am not satisfied because it is like repeating itself, each year we study the same things at university, and you specialise in unnecessary modules, which have nothing to do with critical thinking skills. For example, this year we studied the "Study Skills" Module. How can you teach the "study skills" module to a master student while he has already developed these skills? (EL1).

This perception thus concurs with some researchers' findings, Ashraf and Yousefi (2019) stated that Iranian EFL teachers tend to avoid critical cultural awareness because of the "uncritical nature" of the educational system and the predominance of conventional, non-reflective teaching methods they use in their teaching practices (Ashraf and Yousefi, 2019, p. 332).

As previously stated, the participants who took part in the focus group discussions were learners from Algeria and Mali. Similarly, to Algerians, learners from Mali interestingly conveyed their frustration about their English learning experience in Algeria in general and in the East University in particular. The aim of majoring in English as elucidated by EL3, from Mali, was to speak English fluently and to be able to effectively communicate with native speakers of English. She believed that her main aim was not fulfilled because Algerian teachers of English at East University lacked the appropriate ways and techniques to help them develop their language skills. This is exemplified as:

When we came here, we were told that they teach us how to speak in English, but we see it's the opposite because we do not have enough knowledge. Here we use French more than English, this is our big problem (EL3).

It can be stated that EL3 had high expectations of achieving fluency in English before arriving in Algeria. However, she was disappointed to discover that French is the predominant language and most commonly used in Algeria, following Arabic. The learner's primary objective was to improve her communication skills. She believed that being able to communicate in English would enable her to effectively interact with individuals from diverse

cultural backgrounds. It is also noteworthy that developing intercultural communicative competence (ICC) has not been stated as an objective among EL3 and other students enrolled in the East University. This may be attributed to a lack of familiarity or awareness regarding the notion of ICC. Conversely, learners from the West University described their first encounter with the English language as a non-academic experience, and reported that English was instructed through informal methods:

For me, at first, it was not the academic field that taught me the English language, I basically learned English from movies and TV shows. So, before the academic English learning was mainly focused on grammar. It was not the communicative approach or ICC (WLA).

It was through exposure to authentic materials such as movies, songs, and TV programmes. WLA demonstrated that he had a pre-existing knowledge of English before it was introduced in a formal setting (school). Additionally, this learner highlighted that the pedagogical approach of teaching English in Algerian Primary Education predominantly focuses on the acquisition of vocabulary and grammar, and neither the CC nor the ICC was incorporated. This finding is in line with the study conducted by Rabehi (2021). Her study investigated the status of culture and ICC in Algerian middle school textbooks. The study's findings revealed that foreign cultures are not a prominent feature in teaching English in Algeria. Instead, it is viewed as a secondary component in teachers' teaching practices. In other words, it is not substantial as they aim to develop learners' communicative competence.

WLB, similarly, noted that the curriculum in Primary Education was insufficient and inadequate to improve learners' knowledge and to acquire language proficiency. She reported that she relied on watching several English series and listening to English songs to learn to speak the language and explore the culture during her first learning experience. She addressed:

The curriculum we had in Middle school and High school was not adequate, I guess, because we all have learned the English language through the series, through the songs, as I said it was Hannah Montana, through that we learned vocabulary, we also loved and learned about the culture (WLB).

This finding can be linked to what Sercu (2005) and Ait-Aissa and Said (2012) highlighted. They demonstrated that textbooks are strongly guided by conventional teaching methods where grammar and language structure is the primary objective of learning a foreign language.

It is noteworthy to state that one learner from the West University has drawn attention to the inadequacy of the university curriculum in fulfilling learners' needs. Specifically, the curriculum failed to equip learners with intercultural skills and attitudes. This might be because intercultural communication is incorporated at a late stage of learning English, Master level.

6.3.1.1 English and French Status in Algeria

EL2 articulated her dissatisfaction regarding the low status of English in Algeria compared to the French Language. She blamed the Algerian Educational System which gives great importance and prioritises French over English thereby, diminishing the latter's significance. EL2 proclaimed that "They completely eliminated the English language, but compared to French, each year they give it much importance. The changes they make in the syllabus are very beneficial to the students who major in French language". She expressed:

Due to their neglect of this language (English), the students learn not to give attention to the English language, they give more attention to the French language because they find it more useful in their education and their daily life (EL2).

I can state that EL2 had anger in her tone when she was articulating her views about the dominant status of the French language in Algeria. She reported that English learning is not highly prioritised by Algerian learners due to its perceived limited relevance in their daily lives, academic institutions, and employment prospects. French has a fundamental and powerful status in Algeria because it was colonised by France for 132 years (Benrabah,2004). During the colonial phase, France sought to dominate and control Algerians through the implementation of the assimilation policy in education and other facets of society (Heggo,1973). The French language and culture were imposed at the expense of the Algerian mother languages (Tamazight and Arabic) and cultures (Benrabah, 2005). Therefore, the French language was classified as the official language (Murphy, 1977), and Tamazight and Standard Arabic as foreign languages (Maamri, 2009). Another learner from Mali (WLD) attending the West University reported that the English language is not given significant attention in his country because it is regarded as a second foreign language. However, he reported that the French language was given more importance when he travelled to Algeria to pursue his postgraduate in the West of Algeria.

6.3.1.2 Expectations Versus Reality

Malian Learners from the East University had high expectations regarding the improvement of their language skills. They believed that their communicative skills were not enhanced as expected. Speaking native-like was their primary aim in choosing to study English in a different country. Conversely, some learners from Mali (WLC) who attended the West University elucidated the importance of English as a global language and its consequential role in facilitating international travel and job opportunities. However, WLC interestingly expressed that his primary aim of majoring in English, at the West University, is to enhance his abilities to comprehend and effectively communicate with individuals from diverse cultural backgrounds, rather than striving to attain native speakers' proficiency. This is exemplified in the following quotation:

English is the only spoken language in the world, and we cannot travel or work in the world without English. Because English is the key to the world. For me I don't need to be a native speaker of English, what I need is to express myself to converse with other people of different cultures and understand them (WLC)

It was a remarkable discussion when Algerian learners demonstrated a notable level of curiosity to explore the English learning experience of their fellow Malian learners in Algeria. When EL3 conveyed her significant dissatisfaction about her experience of majoring in English at the East University. An Algerian learner asked her if she met with other Malian students, who pursued their studies in other universities in Algeria, and whether their learning experience differed from hers. According to her perception, Malian students who have pursued their studies in other Algerian Universities developed a commendable proficiency in the English language, which is not the case for her and her peers in eastern regions of Algeria. She expressed:

"They speak well English more than us, but we left our countries to come here to study English and to say that we speak well English, and we are Master specialised in English, and we cannot express ourselves very well in English" (EL3).

Therefore, Malian learners' experiences in the East and West Universities were different. The expectations of Malian learners from the East University were not accomplished as opposed to the experience of Malian learners from the West University, which was manifested during the focus group discussion where they were able to communicate openly in English.

6.4 Learners' Perspectives of Culture

As it was stated previously culture and ICC are the main concepts on which this research revolves; thus, exploring and understanding how learners of English perceive and view the concepts of culture and ICC was crucial.

6.4.1 Learners' Definitions of Culture

Two succinct interesting definitions of the concept of culture were shared by learners from the East University. According to their perceptions, the concept of culture can be understood in two distinguished ways, as a means of identifying an individual's background and heritage, and as a set of customs and practices that are collectively shared by a particular society. The formation of identity is attributed to a set of values, beliefs, traditions, history, and religion. They perceived culture as a collective phenomenon that is shared by an entire society, in other words, they believed in the existence of a monoculture approach in a society. For example, EL2 believed that culture is singular, static, unchangeable, and shared by individuals, who live in the same country. She stated, "It is a way of living in a particular country, it describes your identity and who you are". According to Holliday (2010) and Baker (2015), the concept of culture can be delineated in accordance with the geographical and national boundaries of a particular country, both of which are aligned with the essentialist perspective (Holliday, 2010; Baker, 2015). In this regard, cultures are confined within geographical boundaries and perceived as singular, unchanging entities, and often categorised according to national affiliations and languages (Liddicoat and Scarino, 2013; Baker, 2015).

On the other hand, some learners tend to list features of culture. WLC defined culture as something related to him, "culture is the way I live, the manner I live". This indicates that culture is not limited to a singular shared culture within a given society, rather, there might be multiple cultures in the same society. The rationale for this interpretation could be attributed to the fact that Mali is a nation characterised by diverse ethnic groups and different cultural traditions that exist in a state of coexistence (Yattara, 2018). Thus, WLC's reference to culture was not of a universal, collective, and homogenous sense, but as something that is individually relative to him. The non-essentialist perspective posits that culture should be perceived as a fluid, dynamic, and diverse phenomenon, rather than being constrained to a particular geographical context to which people belong. This perspective recognises the

complex and dynamic characteristics of culture, which serve to both unite and separate individuals (Holliday, 2005; Holliday, 2010; Hoff, 2020).

- *Culture as behaviour*

Learners from the West University defined culture as the behaviour of people. One common shared definition is “the way of behaving and living, culture is everything even religion is included” (WLF). They believe that culture is the primary factor that determines peoples’ behaviour and their reactions to everything.

6.4.2 Learners’ Experience of Learning Culture

During the interview, I asked the learners about the modules that address cultural awareness (CA) in the classroom. It turned out that most of learners from the East University were resentful and dissatisfied with the selection of subjects by the Department of English, where the teaching of English is culture-free. EL2 remarked that her CA was not developed through the courses she attended in the classroom, “Absolutely not at all”. Another learner EL5 further commented, “Look the content of our courses here has no idea about the foreign culture or even the target language culture”. This explains that learners from the East University were not exposed to cultural content, and it was not considered as a substantial objective in the curriculum. According to EL2, the reason that teaching about cultures is not common in the East University is because EFL teachers themselves lack knowledge when it comes to other cultures. She blamed teachers for not having a pre-planned syllabus to use in their teaching practices. She expounded:

Each teacher comes here and teaches randomly whatever suits them. Their knowledge is already limited about other cultures. We end up with a whole generation of Algerian students who study English and have no idea about the English language or other cultures. it was completely useless (EL2).

This perspective aligns with Byram and Risager's (1999) findings where they showed that teachers' comprehension of the term culture appeared to be lacking and insufficient. They were not aware of the depth and complexity of the term. This demonstrates the need for further training about the teaching of culture and its dimensions. In addition, it can be stated that it's challenging for teachers to teach language as culture instead of language and culture (Byram,2008).

6.4.2.1 Culture vs Language Skills

It is interesting to state that one of the learners believed that mastering the four language skills was enough and adequate for him to effectively interact with people from different backgrounds. He expressed, “If I master the four skills, what I need more?” (EL6). EL5 interestingly responded, “You need to know about their culture”. EL2 added, “You may have good pronunciation and a good accent, but if you don’t know how to use idioms and phrasal verbs, your speaking skills will be useless because you will have communication breakdown with others”. Despite their limited knowledge about culture and ICC, it was intriguing that some learners’ views reflected some of the ICC dimensions, they articulated and discussed the significance of learning about other cultures because developing linguistic competence is insufficient in intercultural interactions. It is also interesting to note that learners from the West University’s perceptions contradict some learners’ views in the East University. Most of them expressed their disagreement about the idea that developing linguistic and communicative competence is adequate for effective communication with other people from diverse cultural backgrounds. This is exemplified by WLC:

No, they are the basic elements to learn the language, but they are not enough because what defines the CC is the socio-context even if you know how to speak and read, if you don’t have the knowledge about the context, it is not possible for you to communicate properly (WLC).

Another learner WLD from Mali stated, “The productive skills and receptive skills are plus, and they are related to each other, but just focusing on those four skills, for me, is not sufficient to have good and great communicative skills”.

Despite the significant changes in the world, teachers from the East University’s primary focus of teaching English remained to develop learners’ communication skills. Learners from the East University reported that they are aiming to become “citizens who could communicate in English”. However, Learning English at the West University is no longer reduced to the development of the linguistic and communicative approach. Sarangi (2011) stated that integrating culture and language enables us to shift from merely identifying miscommunication at the linguistic level to also understanding and explaining it through cultural factors. Therefore, analytical and critical stances were promoted to encourage learners to be intercultural citizens, who are critically aware of the context of learning and using the language (Bandura, 2011; Byram, 2000; Guilherme, 2002; Liddicoat and Scarino,

2010). This is confirmed in their perceptions when they defined intercultural competent speaker and their conceptions about the significance of the inclusion of the ICC in Algerian Primary Education. Learners from the West University reported that teachers from that university tend to put equal focus to develop both linguistic and intercultural competence (Liddicoat and Scarino, 2013; Risager, 2007, Sercu *et al.*, 2005).

6.4.2.2 Why learning about other cultures is important?

During the interview, I asked the learners about how important it was for them to widen their knowledge about other cultures. They all stated that it was fundamentally important because it is a key to “better communication” (EL2). It was also interesting that EL5 stated another significant objective of the inclusion of other cultures in the EFL classrooms, which promotes certainty and avoids confusion during interactions. She expressed, “You won’t have the sense of confusion”. This learner’s perspective reflects one of the most important aims of ICC, which is developing curiosity and openness in communication, which helps in navigating cultural misunderstandings in intercultural interactions. Although exploring other cultures is not considered a prominent aim to be developed at the East University, all learners expressed their interest and curiosity to know about other peoples’ cultures.

Learners from the West University viewed that acquiring the language solely is not adequate for successful intercultural interactions. They perceived English as a medium of communication, which requires learners to learn about others’ cultures because learning the language solely might lead to several cultural misunderstandings. WLB reported:

For me, language is mainly a medium of communication, we must know about other cultures, and we must only use the language to communicate. So, we must know how they view things in their culture to communicate with them effectively (WLB).

It is good to know about them before you speak with them. We have to respect other cultures. There is no, my way is the only way, or your way is the right one. So, when you know about their own way, their own attitude you can deal with them properly. Also, you can teach them about your way and your culture (WLE).

Most of the learners from the West University expressed their satisfaction with the cultural content taught in the West University. They further demonstrated how this helped them to appreciate and understand their own culture. A learner from Mali (WLC) affirmed that his learning about other peoples’ cultures increased his understanding and appreciation of his

own culture. He remarkably elucidated that there were some features and aspects of his own culture that he was not proud of. However, after his exposure to the ICC dimensions at the West University, he could improve his knowledge and understanding of other cultures. WLC started to appreciate and embrace his own culture. He exemplifies this in the following:

Even knowing about others' cultures has an impact on our culture because, personally speaking, knowing about other cultures allows me to love my own culture. I began to appreciate many aspects of it, maybe in the past this aspect of my culture I was not proud of it, but I'm now proud of having this because it does exist in my culture, and this hidden different part is part of my identity (WLC).

As stated in the above quote, learning about other cultures can indeed enhance the learners' skills to learn about themselves and their own culture. Also, a sense of openness and appreciation is developed if the goal of teaching is to promote the learner's awareness about the cultural differences.

Another learner, WLD, from Mali, added:

It is challenging to deal with other cultures because it takes into consideration many things. you have to know about other people, how they live, how they speak, how they think, the way they consider things and their cultural aspects, this sometimes creates the cultural shocks, and how to deal with these new differences and new changes, especially for us when we came to Algeria it was difficult for the first time, the first experience is really difficult (WLD).

Another intriguing point that was revealed by one of the learners from Mali (WLD) was that it was challenging for him to adapt to the new context he travelled to, as he did not have much knowledge about Algeria. His intercultural experience taught him not take things for granted and to learn about other people's ways of thinking, ways of living, and other cultural aspects. He asserted that if the individual is not aware that cultural differences exist, he would encounter several cultural shocks.

6.5 Learners' Conceptions and Understanding of ICC

It is worth stating that most of learners from the East University were not able to make a distinction between communicative competence (CC) and intercultural communicative competence (ICC). Therefore, they used both concepts interchangeably, and they provided the same definitions for both terms. This indicates their little knowledge or unfamiliarity with ICC. EL2 used the same definition for CC and ICC as "the ability to communicate well towards

other people who have different cultures than yours". EL2 defined it as "to communicate with someone with a different cultural background the same way you communicate with someone with the same cultural background".

EL5 believed in the existence of one proper/right way of communication, which can be used with people of the same culture as well as with people of different cultural backgrounds. This perception indicates that this learner assumed that her own way is the only possible and correct way, which can be used in several intercultural settings. Therefore, I can state that this learner lacks one fundamental ICC component attitude (*savoir être*). Attitudes are the foundation of ICC (Byram,1997), where the learner has to develop a sense of curiosity, openness, and readiness to eliminate all disbeliefs about other cultures, and believe that one's own culture is the best and correct one. Also, to have the ability and competence to view their culture from an outsider perspective who has different beliefs and values (Byram, 1997, 2000).

EL5's perception of disregarding cultural differences, and assuming that she can successfully communicate with others indicates her unfamiliarity and unawareness of the concept of ICC. Other responses were composed of answers that were either vague or too broad as "ability" or "communication". Furthermore, some learners preferred not to share their understanding of the notion of ICC, this implied that they were not familiar with the concept. Most of the learners from the East University lacked the confidence to express their conceptions of ICC. On the other hand, learners from West University were aware of the difference between CC and ICC. In defining CC, most of them recalled Chomsky and Dell Hymes's theories of linguistic competence and communicative competence respectively, for example, WLB defined CC as the ability to communicate in a socially appropriate and effective manner. She stated:

I guess CC was a reaction to what Chomsky said about linguistic competence. Dell Hymes has brought a new thing, which is the appropriateness and effectiveness of that linguistic competence. So, when to say this and when not to say it, that's the communicative competence, we have to bear in mind what is formal and what is informal (WLB).

WLC from Mali defined it as:

Dell Hymes defined CC as when and how to say and to whom, the setting, the manner, the subject, because maybe it's formal or informal, the way I speak with my teacher and my colleague might not be the same, and the common concern is not just the linguistic aspects of the language, we can include the socio-linguistic context strategies (WLC).

Other respondents from the same university shared the same perceptions of CC as their fellows, they were aware to use both concepts differently. They viewed ICC as the ability/desire to effectively understand and communicate with other people from different backgrounds. Others assured to include in their definitions intercultural competence components such as acceptance, openness, and tolerance. The most recurrent definitions of ICC provided by learners (WLE and WLC) from the West are: “ICC is here to facilitate the communication between cultures” and “I think that the term intercultural communicative competence is the desire to know about other cultures and to accept them, to learn and to communicate the differences effectively without any harm from both sides”.

The West University learners’ conceptions of ICC demonstrate their awareness and knowledge of the intercultural field in general and the ICC in particular. All of them invoked the key terms of ICC as attitudes, knowledge, acceptance, understanding, and tolerance among cultures. WLB stated, “If you have the knowledge, you are going to be tolerant and accept other people’s ways and behaviours”.

6.5.1 Passive Learning and Its Impact on Cultural Understanding

Learners from East University expressed their disappointment with the absence of ICC instruction in the Department of English. Interestingly, many of them mentioned that the teachers themselves lack knowledge about ICC and are unfamiliar with the concept. EL1 believed that native English speakers are better equipped to teach both the language and the target culture, as opposed to Algerian teachers who may lack knowledge of ICC. The same learner added that their learning about other cultures was passive as he expressed:

We didn’t learn ICC, to be honest, we just look at the teacher who looks at the paper and reads, and at the end of the course, the only thing we focus on is to ask her for that paper to make copies and read it ourselves. It was a passive learning (EL1).

Referring to the target culture as other cultures each time by learners from the East University is a reflection of native speakerism, which gives a narrowed space to learners to know or learn about other cultures that are not related to English-speaking countries (inner circle countries). Another learner talked about the challenges that might encounter the learners when learning about ICC. EL4 related the ICC with the target culture and the notion of native speakers. She viewed the idea of the inclusion of ICC in the EFL classroom as not applicable. When I asked her to elaborate on her perception, she stated that teaching about the target culture can be

only done through real-life or virtual communication with native speakers of English. She expressed:

I think about an idea about teaching the ICC, but I think it's not applicable here in Algeria, which is making an online real conversation between an Algerian learner and a native speaker of the target language, but maybe it is not going to be acceptable (EL4).

I asked EL4 to clarify her perspective about "not acceptable". EL1 expressed, "Because of religious reasons". EL4 agreed and added, "Because their way might be the wrong way, each culture has its negative side. I think especially for young learners. This may affect them negatively". Most of the learners from the East University advocate for communicative language learning (CLL), which prioritises the communication of messages and meanings between people and fulfilling functions of the language within native speakerism. This perspective is recurrent among English learners from the East University because teachers from that University have not yet made a shift towards ICC, rather they still following CC approaches as revealed in the teachers' interviews analysis section. Another point that is worth discussing is how EL4 pictured that others' cultures might be wrong or negative because it is different from her own culture and religion. In ICC, this is called stereotype, which is deemed to be a barrier to successful intercultural interactions because it refers to holding beliefs and attitudes about other individuals or groups based on pre-existing formed knowledge.

6.5.2 Learners' Exposure to ICC at the West University

Learners from the West University reported that ICC has been introduced as a separate module where the learners' own culture and other cultures are involved. It is important to note that all learners from the Language and Communication Stream expressed their contentment about the inclusion of ICC. They expressed that this subject helped them to deconstruct stereotypes and fostered their curiosity to learn, understand, and tolerate the differences between cultures. WLA stated that the ICC subject helped him to develop several intercultural skills and attitudes to navigate cultural differences.

I can say that the ICC module opened my eyes to the skills and the ways we should treat foreigners. I might have had them before, but I didn't know that there was something special

about these techniques; so, when I learned ICC, I knew it opened my eyes towards other cultures (WLA).

Additionally, WLB elucidated that ICC helped her personally and academically. She stated that the ICC boosted and reinforced her critical thinking to learn how to be an intercultural competent speaker. She also stated that the skills she acquired helped her to effectively communicate with her fellows, who were from different cultural backgrounds. The same learner outlined that teachers need to prepare learners to respect the differences that exist within their culture and other cultures. An important point WLB shed light on is that Algeria is a multicultural country, where several sub-cultures exist and differ; however, not many people tolerate the differences. WLB demonstrated that Algerian people from the East do not tolerate the cultural differences of the West, and vice versa. Therefore, ICC should be applied in the Algerian context to deconstruct such discrimination and prejudice between sub-cultures, and then then extended to an international context by fostering tolerance and respect. This is exemplified in the following quotation:

We were studying ICC to include it in our daily lives, how to be interculturally competent, and how to act towards a class that has many students coming from different cultural backgrounds. So, for me, it seems really interesting and effective because this is the thing that we are lacking in Algeria. We are from Algeria, and we have a cultural diversity, but we cannot tolerate it. We have this original discrimination, we don't accept people from the East and East from the West, the South from the North. So, what about meeting people from different cultures, and from other countries? (WLB).

It was also interesting to explore learners from Mali learning exposure to ICC in the West University. WLC emphasised the usefulness of ICC. He recalled the ICC models of Byram (1997) and Deardoff's model of IC (2006). He demonstrated that learning these models boosted his confidence to overcome his fears and frustration and helped him to effectively communicate with people of different cultures. Additionally, WLC reported that although ICC was primarily taught through theories and models at West University, it successfully developed their cultural and intercultural awareness. The inclusion of ICC in the West University also helped them develop essential skills to act as mediators between different cultures, enabling them to bridge cultural gaps more effectively. WLC expressed:

Some people say, if the culture doesn't fit, it is regarded as a bad culture and my culture is the best one. In our university, we got the ICC module, and it is among the best modules in our department because it allows us to overcome our fears and to openly understand others through applying the ICC components of Byram (1997;2020) and the IC dimensions of Deardoff (2006). Even though we are studying more on the theoretical aspect of the ICC, awareness of these skills can help us mediate the bridge between different cultures (WLC).

Deardoff's (2006) perspective can be aligned with the findings of the study, she stated that intercultural competence can be developed and fostered through several means, such as the curriculum, and constructive intercultural interactions among students on campus.

6.5.3 The Impact of ICC Education on Shaping Intercultural Attitudes and Deconstructing Stereotypes

The findings revealed that learners from the East University hold several stereotypes about other people's cultures. They tend to judge others' views, attitudes, and beliefs because these people are different. EL6 stated, "We find ourselves judging people, judging their opinions, their attitudes, and their way of thinking". EL2 continued, "Sometimes even without doing it on purpose, sometimes we have this pre-assumption of judging". Most learners from the East acknowledged having prior assumptions and beliefs about other people's attitudes and beliefs. None of them evoked the ICC components as a remedy for this issue, which may harm other individuals and impede intercultural communication.

In contrast, Learners from West University's exposure to the ICC had an impact on their attitudes towards other cultures. Most of them stated that they developed a sense of flexibility, tolerance, and openness in their attitudes. They reported that they used to judge people of different cultures before the introduction of the ICC module in West University.

One of the learners, who is from the East of Algeria but she was pursuing her studies at the West University demonstrated that she went through the denial stage (Beennett's,1993; 2004) when she travelled to the West side of Algeria. She reported that she denied the cultural differences she encountered in the West of Algeria. She considered that her way of perceiving things is the only correct one, "I always applied it on myself when I was in my hometown, I thought that my way is the only and the best way. When I travelled to the West, I went through the denial stage" (WLB). WLC supported this perception and added, "It is not only you. We all used to think this way" (WLC).

WLB narrated her experience of living in a new context (West) yet still in Algeria., she stated that the culture in the West is slightly different from that of the East. She reported that she reflected on her culture and questioned why that difference exists and how to find a common ground to interact with people. Attending the ICC course, according to her, was the key to reaching tolerance and understanding.

When I came here and I met with different people and cultures, I started questioning why they do that, and I thought that there must be a common way why they are doing things, and I started somehow tolerating others' attitudes, behaviours, and ways of thinking. The ICC module really helped me a lot and made things crystal clear. I was put on the spot to understand how to be interculturally tolerant through attitudes, knowledge, and skills, and learn how to celebrate and embrace differences (WLB).

6.5.4 The Role of Knowledge in Enhancing Intercultural Understanding and Tolerance

WLC and WLD highlighted the central role of knowledge in intercultural communication competence (ICC). WLC emphasised that the development of knowledge is crucial for understanding and appreciating cultural differences. According to WLC, when learners acquire this knowledge, they become more aware of why cultures vary and consequently, more tolerant and flexible in their interactions with people from different backgrounds. WLD shared a similar perspective, reflecting on their prior lack of knowledge before attending the ICC course at the West University. WLD noted that before acquiring knowledge about other cultures, they previously had stereotypes about others' values and beliefs. He stated that he viewed his culture as superior and the right one (Defence stage) (Bennett,1993; 2004). However, exposure to the ICC module at West University provided them with insights into why people act and view things differently. He reported that this helped him develop a more nuanced and empathetic understanding of other cultures.

Both WLC and WLD expressed their satisfaction with the ICC education received at West University, which was absent in their previous educational context in Mali. Their experiences underscore the importance of ICC knowledge in fostering cultural awareness and improving interpersonal interactions across diverse cultural contexts. They expressed:

Before, sometimes, I used to judge other cultures unconsciously. It is all about intercultural knowledge. If learners develop such knowledge, they are going to be aware of why cultures are different. They will be also tolerant and flexible towards ways other people live and think (WLC).

For me, before coming here we didn't have the knowledge of ICC. I used to neglect others and only focus on myself, but being exposed to the ICC module helped me to understand why people are acting and viewing things that way (WLD).

6.6 Learners' Intercultural Lived Experience

As it has been stated before, the ICC is the core of this research project. It was necessary to shed light on the participants' intercultural encounters. EL3 and EL4 were students from Mali who pursued their studies at the University of the East. It was interesting to ask them about their intercultural experience in Algeria. EL3 demonstrated that before travelling, she had basic knowledge about Algeria, she knew that Algeria is a Muslim Country. She has been informed in Mali that she needs to change her way of dressing and she should put the headscarf on as all Algerian girls do. EL3 had several stereotypes about Algeria before travelling. She believed that she should be veiled when she travels to Algeria because all Algerian women wear the Hijab, which is not the case.

It is also interesting to state that EL4 took some time to reflect and talk about her experience in Algeria. This may refer to indicating and choosing careful thoughts or because she was trying to translate and then express her thoughts in a second foreign language (English) despite that she was encouraged to use her first language (French). EL4, interestingly stated that everything was different for her in Algeria, the educational system, the Algerian culture, and religion. She did not explain much about her intercultural experience, she preferred to list only major differences.

However, the rest of the Algerian learners except EL5 have never had any intercultural traveling experience. Although EL5 had travelled to a different country that has a different culture but shares the same religion and language, this learner has not considered it as an intercultural encounter. When I asked her, she responded as she has never travelled to a different country, "I have never been in a different culture or a different country" (EL5). In another question the same learner contradicted herself, when she stated that she has been to Tunisia. She did not consider it as an intercultural experience maybe because Algeria and Tunisia share the same religion (Islam), and the same official language (Standard Arabic), but

not the same culture, “Tunisia for vacation and I think we have similar culture”. EL5 viewed an intercultural experience as an experience with people who have different language, different religion, and different culture. She gave an example of Europe.

Traveling abroad was a dream that was shared by EL1, and this was the reason he chose to major in English. He demonstrated that travelling overseas is the only way for him to improve his English and to develop his understanding of other cultures through real-life experiences. This perspective was shared by teachers from the same university.

Like learners from the East University, learners from the West University, who participated in the focus group, had no experience abroad except those from Mali.

WLD stated that his intercultural lived experience in Algeria was not heavily challenging because he had an idea about Algeria. He elucidated that he used his cousins’ experience of studying in Algeria as a source to learn about the culture, the attitudes, and the religion of people in Algeria. He was able to identify the sub-cultures in Algeria, and spot the differences exist between his own culture and the Algerian cultures. In addition, he elucidated that he heard some negative comments about Algeria in his hometown such as, “They consider Algeria as a racist country”.

It is also interesting to shed lights on WLC intercultural experience. He stated that he had little knowledge about Algeria. He was aware that Algeria is a Muslim country where people’ beliefs, attitudes, and their appearances are different from his own, “I knew that Algeria is part of Africa and most of people religion here is Islam, also the way they dress is different”.

WLD and WLC also pointed out that he has been told that “in my country, people used to say that most Algerian people are terrorists, and they are racist because they say that the Algerian people do not accept Black people”.

What is more interesting is that WLC had a different image of Algeria when he experienced it, “But when I came here, I see that things are not exactly as they said, and it is different from what they said because there are people in Algeria who are good and open as there are people who are not, and this is everywhere”. In the end, he highlighted that he had several cultural shocks about the cultural differences there, but after the inclusion of ICC, he has been prepared to learn and understand others’ attitudes and beliefs.

6.7 The Creation of Intercultural Clubs

Although all learners shared an agreement about the importance of the creation of an intercultural club at the level of the university, learners from the East University stated that they never had a club where they could discuss their views about different cultures and enhance their intercultural awareness. EL1 proposed the idea of opening a book club where students could engage in reading and discussing ideas collaboratively. However, this initiative never took place due to the lack of motivation and commitment. On the other hand, learners from the West University were aware of the existence of the intercultural club known as the GRC (The Global Representative of Cultures), which advocates for cultural diversity.

As outlined by WLA:

There was an intercultural club in Language and Communication Speciality. I remember they presented a ceremony or a festival about Japanese culture, and they even invited some Japanese Aikido and Karate Masters. They did some demonstrations to introduce the Japanese culture to Algerians, and we had a great day. The club is called the GRC (the Global Representative of Cultures).

All respondents were asked to state the benefits of creating such clubs. They highlighted that intercultural clubs can significantly promote the learners' intercultural attitudes. The key advantages of these educational intercultural clubs, as identified by the learners from the West University, include:

- Intercultural skills, respect, and appreciation are fostered through engaging in intercultural clubs.
- Intercultural clubs as an educational approach to develop intercultural dimensions (attitudes, skills, knowledge and critical cultural awareness)
- The enhancement of learners' leadership abilities.
- The promotion of tolerance and understanding among learners from different cultural backgrounds.

This learning approach is discussed in depth in the following section. It was crucial to explore the members' perceptions of the intercultural club, which was established at the West University. A brief description of the relevant data is presented to provide an authentic description of the GRC members' perceptions. The interviews were carried out online with two members of the GRC due to the difficulty of travelling from one place to another.

Participants will be identified as GRC1 and GRC2 to preserve their anonymity as promised in the consent forms (Thomas, 2009). The data were coded to answer the last research question of this study. *RQ4*: How does the model of intercultural speaking clubs contribute to the development of ICC?

General Overview of the GRC

GRC1 and GRC2 (female and male), both former students of West University in Algeria, earned their bachelor's and master's degrees in Language and Communication, where culture and intercultural communicative competence (ICC) are key concepts. Notably, both participants graduated with distinction and high averages. Thus, they were granted a fully funded scholarship to pursue their doctoral studies in the United Kingdom (Algerian Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research, 2014).

6.8 The GRC Members' Perspectives of the Intercultural Club

6.8.1 Motivations for Joining the GRC

The GRC was established at the West University in Algeria. GRC2, who was one of the co-founders. According to him, the idea of creating an intercultural club at this university was raised by one of his friends, who was unhappy and bored with the learning routine. Therefore, she suggested establishing a club that tackles engaging and interesting topics such as exploring one's own culture and others' cultures and fostering empathy, respect, and openness among learners (Feng, 2009). Furthermore, promoting tolerance towards diverse cultures (Alred et al., 2003). These qualities lead to successful intercultural dialogues (Crosbie, 2014; Holmes, 2014). GRC2 stated,

That is an interesting idea but what do you mean by culture? It is very broad! She said we can tackle it in this intercultural club with others' cultures, attitudes, principles, and values. We will be able to develop our cultural awareness and intercultural awareness. If we acquire knowledge about different cultures and we explore others' attitudes and perceptions, we can be intercultural citizens, who can successfully communicate in intercultural dialogues. I was like, I want to do that, then the club started to welcome members until we reached fifteen students (GRC2)

6.8.2 Impact of the GRC on Personal Development

After joining the GRC, GRC2 revealed that all members became autonomous and independent learners and gained cultural and intercultural awareness. They developed leadership skills, they were able to organise various conferences, workshops, presentations, and other cultural activities to promote learning about different cultures. GRC2 believed that the GRC played a crucial role in developing their communicative skills and intercultural attitudes. He also demonstrated that their involvement in the club helped them reflect on and appreciate their own culture while embracing and respecting cultural differences.

The GRC is an intercultural club where we were able to share knowledge about cultures, we had the space where we could learn about the attitudes and values of other people, and we developed an open mindset towards others' principles and views. We acquired intercultural skills and intercultural awareness. the GRC started small, it welcomed more than fifteen students (GRC2).

GRC2 and GRC1 also demonstrated the benefits of the creation of intercultural clubs at universities. She described her experience of being an effective member of the GRC as an interesting and enriching experience, allowing her to develop not only her understanding of her own culture but also her knowledge of other cultures. Participating in the GRC provided numerous opportunities for personal growth. For example, she engaged in presentations and seminars on topics such as challenging stereotypes and assumptions, deconstructing prejudice, and fostering intercultural diversity and inclusion. These experiences contributed to her personal development by enhancing her openness skills, improving her ability to interact across cultures, and overcoming her own fears and anxieties related to intercultural interactions. Additionally, being involved in these activities helped her build confidence, develop leadership skills, and cultivate empathy, all of which are valuable for both personal and professional growth.

6.8.3 Challenges of the Creation of Intercultural Clubs in Algeria

When GRC1 tried to illustrate the necessity and the importance of the existence of intercultural clubs in Algeria, she shed light on several obstacles which hinder the creation of such clubs. The lack of inclusivity and the unawareness of diversity in Algeria is one of the main challenges. This sub-theme is discussed and presented below.

- Lack of inclusivity in the Algerian Educational System

GRC1 expressed frustration about the fact that internationalisation and globalisation in education is not promoted in Algeria. It was interesting how this participant made a comparison between the UK and the Algerian Educational System (based on her own experience). She stated that the UK universities welcome international students who come from different parts of the world. All international students in the UK are entitled to attend induction week, where students from different cultural backgrounds meet and exchange talks. This approach fosters intercultural inclusion, empathy, and the development of intercultural identities. In contrast, in Algeria, the educational system lacks inclusivity, and it also lacks awareness of diversity in dealing with international students, who come from Mali, Nigeria, Syria, and other parts of the world. GRC1 expressed her disappointment about how international students are marginalised and do not experience an environment that promotes openness and inclusivity. Therefore, promoting cultural diversity and inclusivity in Algeria is crucial. This can be achieved by integrating intercultural competence curricula (ICC) into the educational system and establishing intercultural clubs that involve both Algerian and international learners.

The Algerian university system is really frustrating, it does not take care of international students like Nigerian students, students from Mali and Ghana, and students from Syria. These nationalities are denied. They are considered a minority, and nothing is provided for embracing cultural diversity. They come from completely different educational systems and from different cultural backgrounds. However, there is a huge gap when it comes to inclusion (lack of events, and socialisation). This is so frustrating! I can say that an induction week is very crucial to be included in all Algerian universities. Furthermore, the integration of ICC in the curriculum is significant as well as the creation of intercultural clubs where all students are included; they can exchange perceptions about cultures, and they also can develop cultural openness and empathy towards each other (GRC1).

Interestingly, GRC2 shared a similar perception, he considered the lack of intercultural inclusivity and openness in Algerian Universities as a factor that hinders cultural club existence. He stated that the focus of learning is to obtain a degree rather than gaining knowledge. He also talked about the lack of inductions, which Algerian and international students should attend before they start their learning journey. He expressed:

The creation of intercultural clubs is 100% crucial, but what makes me sick is that the Algerian universities back home focus on the degree. There is a huge lack of research, a lack of external

activities (clubs), a lack of intercultural inclusivity among international students, and a lack of open mindsets. Teachers have a huge role because they do not aim for globalisation, they do not aim to develop learners' cultural empathy or intercultural skills (GRC2).

The aforementioned perspectives indicate that the establishment of intercultural clubs is considered as an intercultural learning approach which promotes the understanding of diverse cultures and fosters the development of intercultural competencies among learners.

6.8.4 Mutual Intercultural Awareness and Sensitivity

It was intriguing to explore members of the GRC's perceptions and conceptions about their intercultural lived experience in a different sociocultural environment (The UK). Shedding light on how far the ICC learning exposure in Algeria assisted them in engaging within the host culture, interacting with people of different cultures, and understanding and dealing with unfamiliar attitudes.

Throughout several intercultural interactions and exposures, participants' ways of thinking and performing were opposed to the new life they confronted with people from different cultures. For example, GRC1 talked about her first exposure to the drinking culture. She showed a continuous effort to understand the reason behind the significance of drinking in any type of gathering and to comprehend the process of socialization in the new environment. GRC1 expressed her appreciation for the inclusion of the ICC as a subject in the Language and Communication Department at the West University. She outlined that the modules and the GRC were of great assistance. She developed intercultural awareness and sensitivity towards different attitudes. She demonstrated that she was able to apply the ICC dimensions in intercultural dialogue and negotiation of meanings.

GRC1 shared her intercultural experience with her friends, who shared a different culture than hers. Her friends shared the drinking culture, and they liked to drink at all social gatherings. At first, GRC1 and her friends had several cultural misunderstandings because she did not drink. She displayed that she frequently got questions from her friends and others about why she does not drink with them. GRC1's awareness of the ICC assisted her in explaining her reasons for not sharing the culture of drinking, which was based on religious beliefs. She demonstrated that she is Muslim and drinking alcohol is not allowed in Islam.

It was interesting to mention that GRC1 expressed that people, like herself, who do not share the drinking culture are more likely to feel less welcomed and less appreciated than people, who drink while gathering because socialisation culture in the UK is mostly done around the consumption of alcoholic drinks. In this line of thought, she asserted that tolerance and empathy towards cultures should be mutual among interlocutors. This perspective is in line with Ruben (1989) who demonstrated that most of the definitions of intercultural competence and ICC are relatively monological and individualistic since they leave the interlocutor out. In other words, most definitions focus on the user of the competence and leave out the impact of the other person and the surrounding circumstances in interaction (Dervin, 2010). Any person can be an intercultural competent speaker (Byram, 1997, 2006), yet s/he may be easily troubled by the other's lack of motivation and lack of intercultural attitudes and language skills. Therefore, these acts of co-construction of speech and interaction should be vital to be included in the definitions and dimensions of IC and ICC.

Another interesting intercultural experience that GRC1 recalled is her contact with her neighbours, who were Chinese students. She stated that she lived in a single flat studio, where her neighbours were from China. She indicated that they were friendly, but they were living in a community where all of them were from the same culture. She further noted that it was easy to talk to them, but it was not easy to be one of them, in other words, to be a member of their community. The participant's intercultural immersion led her to compare/contrast her own culture with others. Initially, she perceived her PhD journey as isolating due to the perceived lack of close relationships in the host culture, which she found to be more individualistic and reserved. This contrasted with the Algerian culture, where people are sociable and forming new friendships is effortless.

Furthermore, GRC2 viewed the significance of intercultural awareness and sensitivity in fostering meaningful connections. He stated that he gained intercultural awareness and knowledge about people of different cultural backgrounds. He recalled one of his interesting intercultural experiences when he invited his French friend to breakfast with him during Ramadan.

Ramadan is one of the five pillars of Islam. It is a sacred month where Muslims must fast from dawn to sunset. In this sacred month Muslims devote themselves to their faith and to get close to Allah. The participant shared a religious cultural experience with his French friend, who never knew about Ramadan. This shared experience not only introduced his friend to a

significant cultural tradition but also demonstrated their mutual respect and appreciation for each other's cultural practices. Such interactions highlight the importance of mutual understanding and sensitivity in building meaningful intercultural relationships.

6.8.5 Developing Cross-Cultural Awareness Through Immersive Intercultural Experiences

GRC1 revealed that her ICC learning experience in Algeria and her exposure to different cultures in the host culture assisted her in developing her cultural awareness towards other people of different cultures. She talked about several incidents, where she was the only person who had a different cultural background. She expressed that there were unusual situations, misunderstandings, and tensions, but she was able to preserve and present her own culture properly and respect and tolerate the differences that exist within her friends' cultures. She demonstrated that she was going through continuous self-development with every intercultural incident she encountered. She developed critical cultural awareness, where she deconstructed stereotypes and judgments about other peoples' values and different worldviews.

GRC1 highlighted that the ICC courses she attended at the West University in Algeria had been of great help. She stated that the course fostered her critical thinking and promoted her understanding of cultural differences. Although the course was more based on theories of the ICC, it helped her to use the knowledge she gained during the course to overcome several misunderstandings. According to her, the ICC course was an educational intercultural approach to prepare learners for intercultural encounters.

Self-development was a theme that was shared by **GRC2**, where he outlined that he started to construct knowledge and understand attitudes about diversities through engaging in different intercultural interactions with people who hold different attitudes and values. As the UK was his first intercultural lived experience, the participant had one reference to refer to and compare to Algeria. He revealed that through observing and comparing both experiences, his intercultural experience enlightened his thinking and opened his eyes to novelties he had never experienced before.

I believe I developed very much because coming from a background which is an Algerian background, my reality about the world was very narrow and limited. Why was it limited? I think because we (Algerians) do not travel that much because of visa restrictions. But since I had the opportunity to travel here and across the UK, I believe I became more mature, more critical,

and more reflective. I learned that there is no right or wrong culture. I learned to question everything around me and not to take cultural differences for granted (GRC2).

Unlike GRC1, GRC2 displayed that self-development and intercultural awareness were promoted through intercultural immersion and not through the course he attended in Algeria. Overall, members of the GRC confirmed the usefulness and necessity of the creation of intercultural clubs at Algerian educational institutions. They both viewed their experience of being members of the GRC as valuable and enlightening experiences where they created an intercultural space to openly engage in different cultural aspects such as transcending stereotypes and prejudice and developing cultural openness and acceptance.

The establishment of the GRC at West University was a successful intercultural initiative that enhanced participants' intercultural communicative competence and deepened their understanding of diverse attitudes and values. It effectively fostered their ability to tolerate and appreciate different cultural norms.

6.9 Unanticipated Findings

An unanticipated result of the study was the different perspectives on intercultural communicative competence (ICC) among participants from the East and West universities. While it was anticipated that there would be some variation in experiences and perceptions, the extent of the differences was unexpected. Participants from the East and West universities expressed contrasting viewpoints on various aspects of ICC including their understanding of ICC, their cultural awareness, their intercultural attitudes and critical cultural awareness. Participants from the East University tended to focus more on language proficiency as the primary driver of successful interactions. They believed that mastering the four language skills was key to navigate and bridge cultural differences and develop learners' national and target culture. On the other hand, participants from the West University highlighted how intercultural awareness went beyond language skills and involved understanding cultural diversities. Most of them emphasised the importance of developing intercultural attitudes in the classroom or through deep cultural immersion. That would foster effective intercultural interactions.

Additionally, the unexpected participation of Malian students in the study and the insights they shared about their intercultural lived experiences in Algeria emerged as one of the most intriguing findings. Initially, the focus of the study was on exploring Algerian English language

teachers and learners' perspectives of ICC. However, the inclusion of Malian students added a valuable dimension to the study. Their perspectives provided unique insights into the dynamics of intercultural interactions within the Algerian context, particularly from the standpoint of individuals who are both foreign students and part of a different cultural and linguistic background. The Malian students discussed their challenges in adapting to Algerian cultural norms and educational practices. Malian participants from the West University demonstrated how ICC course helped them to understand cultural diversities and navigate intercultural interactions. Their stories revealed a rich and vibrant process of intercultural learning and adaptation, it highlighted the complex interplay between language, culture, and identity. Malian students' participation in this study highlighted the often-overlooked experiences of international students in Algeria, it also offered a deeper understanding of how intercultural competence is negotiated in everyday academic and social interactions.

6.10 Concluding the Chapter

This chapter sought to investigate English language learners' perspectives of their English learning experience in the East and West universities. It also attempted to explore their understandings and assumptions of the notions of culture and interculturality and how these concepts are addressed in English language classrooms in Algerian higher education. Overall, the findings revealed that all learners from the East University expressed their dissatisfaction with their English learning experience because of the outdated teaching methods. Additionally, their understandings of culture and interculturality were limited and bounded to communicative competence. The majority of learners from the East University were not familiar with the concepts of interculturality but tended to use intercultural communicative competence and communicative competence interchangeably. As far as these participants are considered, it can be stated that the ICC is neither promoted nor prioritised at the East University. Instead, conventional teaching approaches are followed in which the focus of learning is on transmitting factual knowledge about the history of old civilisations. On the other end of the spectrum, learners from the West University were familiar with and aware of the concept of ICC. They all, without exception, outlined some of the ICC dimensions (tolerance, open-mindedness, flexibility, empathy, and appreciation) in their definitions. Furthermore, they highlighted that there is a whole module of ICC that they were exposed to

in the Department of Language and Communication. Most of the learners from this university shared their positive attitudes towards the inclusion of the ICC in ELT and FL because of the utmost importance of the ICC attitudes in today's globalised world. They believed that integrating the ICC into EFL education fosters learners' intercultural awareness, understanding, and respect for cultural differences. It also prepares learners to navigate the complexities of intercultural dialogues. Furthermore, some of them posited that acquiring grammar or linguistic competence is not adequate, rather learners should be exposed to diverse cultural contexts where they can gain insights about other cultural perspectives such as values, behaviours, and norms of other people. Therefore, learners can develop a deeper and richer sense of appreciation for cultural diversity.

This chapter also presented the GRC member's perspectives about the intercultural knowledge club they established at the West University. They demonstrated that their awareness and understanding of ICC in the classroom motivated them to create the GRC. According to the participants, the creation of GRC (Global Representatives of Cultures) is considered a valuable approach for promoting intercultural communicative competence among learners from diverse cultural backgrounds. This platform's utmost aim is to foster cultural understandings, facilitate intercultural meaningful interactions, and celebrate diversity. Exposure to the ICC and such intercultural clubs broadens learners' perspectives, deconstructs stereotypes, promotes empathy and tolerance, negotiates meanings, and overcomes misunderstandings in intercultural interactions. Last but not least, the club contributes to building a more interconnected, diverse, and inclusive environment for learners where curiosity, openness, and appreciation are promoted. More importantly, it paves the way for more successful navigation of international experience.

Chapter Seven

General Conclusion

7.1 Introduction

In this chapter I present and discuss the key findings which answer the four research questions of the study, linking these to the literature review, and to the theoretical framework. This research study sought to explore the Algerian English language teachers and English Master learners' understandings of the concept of culture and how they view and perceive its place in their English language teaching and learning practices. It also endeavours to gain more comprehensive insights into participants' (from the East and West Universities in Algeria) understandings and viewpoints of intercultural communicative competence. Additionally, it is enriching to explore teachers' and learners' intercultural lived experiences and to understand how these experiences assisted them in fostering their ICC attitudes and skills. It is significant to highlight that there was an intercultural knowledge club which was established at the West University. The primary aim of this club was to promote the ICC learning practices and to foster learners' tolerance and empathy towards peoples' behaviours and values of different cultures. This intercultural club is called "The Global Representatives of Culture". Therefore, investigating the founders of the GRC's attitudes and understandings of this intercultural initiative was crucial and significant.

The findings attained from the semi-structured interviews, online survey, and focus group discussions complemented each other and aided the researcher in having comprehensive insights and a clear understanding of participants' views, perspectives, and practices. It is also crucial to demonstrate that the quantitative results from the online survey encompass different areas that were explored in great depth during the focus group discussions where learners were more reflective and open to discussing their knowledge and awareness of culture and the ICC. Finally, implications and recommendations for Algerian policymakers, institutions, and teachers are presented in addition to the limitations of and contributions to the study.

7.2 Summary of the Study

The primary aim of this explorative interpretive study was to investigate the teachers' and learners' views and perspectives on the notions of culture and intercultural communication. It also endeavoured to explore the participant's teaching and learning practices in the EFL classrooms in accordance with the development of the ICC. An exploratory inquiry strategy from a social constructivist viewpoint was conducted, where semi-structured interviews, questionnaires, and focus group discussions were used as the main methods for data collection. Participants in this study were ten (n10) Algerian language teachers of English from two different sites in Algeria which are the East University and the West University. Semi-structured interviews were used as the main instrument to collect teachers of English perceptions of the ICC. Interviews were also conducted with two GRC members to get insights and investigate the attitudes of the intercultural club at the West University. Furthermore, Master learners of English (Algerians and Malians) took part in answering the questionnaires and some of them participated in the two focus group discussions, that were separately conducted in the East and the West universities. Eventually, all participants' perspectives and viewpoints provided rich data for thematic analysis. In order to answer the research questions, I attempted to gain an understanding of the Algerian EFL teachers' and learners' current views and perspectives on the teaching of culture and its relationship with English Language Teaching. I also sought to explore their attitudes towards interculturality and intercultural communication, and how it is introduced in ELT practices in Algeria. The participants' intercultural lived experiences are also presented to understand how real-life experiences fostered their ICC attitudes. It is paramount to highlight the importance of promoting the ICC in ELT because it leads teachers and learners to successfully engage in different intercultural dialogues, (Ganesh and Holmes, 2011; Holmes, 2014) fosters their critical thinking skills, and prepares them to communicate as global and intercultural citizens (Guilherme, 2002; Byram, 2006; Porto and Byram, 2015).

7.3 Answering the research questions of the study

The main findings that answer the four research questions can be summarised and addressed as follows:

7.3.1 Research Question 1

1. *RQ1: How do Algerian English Language teachers perceive and understand the concept of culture and how it is placed in their English language teaching practices?*

It is important to answer the first research question because intercultural communication addresses communication between different cultures. Findings from the semi-structured interviews, that were carried out with ten (n10) Algerian English Language teachers from two different Algerian universities (East and West), revealed that most teachers from both universities were satisfied with their experiences of teaching English as a Foreign language. They all described it as an interesting, enriching, yet challenging experience where they endeavoured to prepare learners to properly communicate in English.

It was even more interesting that all participants from both universities indicated their willingness to teach culture and highlighted the interwoven relationship between language and culture. They all agreed that language and culture cannot be taught separately, they are linked and connected to each other (Kramersch, 2008; Risager, 2007).

These findings are in line with Jiang's (2000) perception, where he believed that language cannot be possible without culture. They reflect and influence each other. He further elucidates his view by using a metaphor that language is the mirror of culture, in a way that people view and perceive culture through its language. It is crucial to demonstrate that participants' perspectives and conceptions of defining the notion of culture were different and variant among teachers of English at the East and the West Universities. Teachers' (from the East University) views of culture revolved around concrete and tangible aspects of culture. Teachers from the East University demonstrated the importance of teaching culture and its linked relationship with the target language; however, there was a contradiction between how they perceived and thought of the notion of culture, and how they tackled it in their classroom. In other words, they perceived culture as something important, that underpins and fosters the teaching of English as a Foreign Language (Luk, 2012; Nguyen, et al., 2016). However, their teaching of culture was reported to be implicit and separate, in modules such as literature, history, and civilisation (Bouhidel, 2018). It cannot be denied that literature and civilisation are significant aspects of the culture of any nation; however, they do not define the other components of culture. Teachers from the East University believed that culture is introduced in courses of literature and history of the target culture, which tend to narrate the

old history of the target civilisation, either British or American, by studying works in the literature and analysing them.

This finding is compatible with the study of Bouhidel (2018), where she demonstrated that culture is superficially taught in Algeria through narrating old history and analysing literature. She further elaborates that learners who learn foreign languages should be taught to explore, comprehend, and tolerate the cultural differences of other people.

Furthermore, some other teachers from the same university elucidated that the cultural content predominantly focuses on developing students' linguistic competence, enhancing their knowledge of language structure and vocabulary, and fostering the students' communicative competence. These findings are in line with the study conducted by Bouhidel (2018). Her study revealed that English language students tend to give significant importance to courses in grammar, writing, oral expression, and linguistics while they give little value to courses in culture such as literature and old civilisations. Such courses (literature and old civilisations) are not of much interest to the students because according to many, the ultimate teaching goal is to teach the language.

According to Hymes (1986) and Kramsch (1993; 2008), CC emphasises the sociolinguistic aspects of the language. Learners should have the ability to employ these competencies to be aware of what to say, to whom, how, when and where. This supersedes Chomsky's (1957) use of linguistics competence, which involves only the grammatical aspects of the language. All teachers from the East University shared similar teaching objectives except one who demonstrated that the focus of his teaching at the beginning was to enable learners to properly write in English and effectively communicate; however, his aim shifted to prepare learners to be critical thinkers and function as global citizens. Although this teacher's perception demonstrates that his teaching is shifting to an intercultural English language teaching approach (IELT), this was not really displayed in his perspectives when he was asked to define ICC. Furthermore, most of the teachers from the former university believed that developing the four language skills (listening, speaking, reading and writing) is a fundamental and the utmost aim of teaching English as a foreign language. It was interesting how these teachers also underlined and viewed the aspects of culture through particular places and products, which are socially constructed within a particular nation. The study outlined that the teaching of culture at the East University is based on the conventional, traditional, and essentialist perspectives of culture and the accumulation of knowledge about old civilisations.

To summarise teachers attitudes from the East University, I can say that culture is merely content. The deep aspects of culture are taken for granted and they are not tackled in any way in the classroom, in other words, culture is not seen as a fundamental goal in EFL teaching in the East University.

However, some teachers from the West University were aware of the linked relationship between language, culture and intercultural communication. Therefore, most of them viewed culture as something fluid, dynamic and complex to define, they all agreed that culture cannot be reduced only to the traditions, customs, food, weather, and lifestyle of a particular nation. It cannot also be limited to the surface culture (big C), and it cannot be considered as a separate skill added to the four receptive and productive skills (Kramsch, 1993; 2008; Risager, 2007). This is opposed to Chomsky's (2006) perspectives whose main focus is the development of linguistic competence, which assumes that culture is not relevant or an ultimate aim of language teaching.

Teachers from the West linked the concept of culture with intercultural communication. They viewed it as understanding and appreciating oneself culture and perceiving and respecting others' behaviours and values. The perspectives of teachers from West University were shifted to an intercultural English language teaching approach where ICC awareness, attitudes, knowledge and skills are promoted at West University. The findings highlighted that teachers from West University seek to frequently foster students' cultural awareness and intercultural awareness. To summarise, the findings indicate that deep aspects of culture were introduced and taught in West University unlike at East University where only superficial aspects of culture were tackled.

7.3.2. Research Question 2

RQ2: What are Algerian English Language teachers' understandings and conceptions of intercultural communicative competence? How does their intercultural lived experience foster their ICC teaching practices?

The findings revealed that teachers from both sites viewed intercultural communication in teaching English as a Foreign Language as interesting, enriching and complex. Teachers from the East University perceived ICC as a distant and separate notion in the department of English, speciality of Didactics of Languages and Foreign Cultures. Their conceptions and understandings of interculturality were limited.

Participants' unfamiliarity with the concept of ICC was noted as they were using general definitions and terms such as culture, communicative competence, multiculturalism and intercultural communicative competence interchangeably (Boyé, 2016). Findings reported that some participants from East University did not have an idea about the notion of ICC. Therefore, they preferred to ask the researcher to provide a clear explanation of the term. They also believed in the existence of one right/ correct definition of the notion ICC.

The participants from East University were irresolute and reluctant about sharing how they perceive ICC and its dimensions because they had very little knowledge about the term, and their teaching predominantly focused on a communicative language teaching approach. This aligns with Ryan and Sercu's findings (2003) where they stated that teachers' main objective is language learning (acquisition) and the least important objective is culture learning. Furthermore, ICC was not, at all, introduced in their courses. Although the participants from East University believed that culture has various facets, they tended to focus in their teaching on its structural elements such as the linguistic competence and the macro-skills of the target language. In other words, this conceptualising of culture was mainly on identifying the relationships between language and culture, as well as the importance of addressing theoretical definitions of different concepts such as culture, cultural awareness, and cultural assimilation. Although these participants held a shared awareness of language-culture links, they tended to teach the English language free of culture, and the content focus was language structure. Moreover, I have provided the participants with the theoretical framework of this study (Byram's model of ICC) and asked them to share their thoughts.

Most of the teachers were able to understand and explain the linguistic and sociolinguistic aspects of the language solely. However, they did not have a clear understanding of ICC dimensions. Only one teacher demonstrated that it is difficult to implement or promote the ICC elements in an EFL context because the model encompasses theoretical aspects that are not applicable in an artificial setting (the classroom). They can see light only when they are applied in real-life contexts (foreign country).

It was also reported that the huge size of the classroom, the passive learning, the conventional and outdated teaching methods, the lack of technology devices and the absence of a network hinder the inclusion of ICC in East University and make it challenging in the West University. Although there are some laboratories assigned to the faculty of Didactics and Foreign Languages at East University, but teachers still follow traditional and outdated teaching

methods because of the limited number of computers and the absence of collaborative learning between students. Moreover, internet connectivity in Algerian universities is very low and far from satisfying teachers' and learners' demands and needs (Bouzidi, 2005; Aoumeur, 2017). Teachers highlighted that internet access in Algerian Higher Education is considered a substantial limitation that hinders the teaching of ICC. These considerable issues are articulated in many studies (Tong and Trinidad, 2005; Harris and Rea, 2009), where they demonstrated that innovative well-equipped classrooms and the use of technology facilitate communication between learners and the worldwide community, giving them the opportunity to share their cultures and understand the differences.

It was outlined in the data that some teachers conveyed that EFL teachers should require the Byram's (1997) ICC dimensions in the first place (*savoir être, savoir faire, savoir comprendre/savoir apprendre et savoir s'engager*) to be able to transmit and promote them in their students' attitudes (Byram,1997).

At the other end of the spectrum, all five participants from West University indicated that they were familiar with the concept of ICC and its dimensions, and that they have been teaching it as a subject in Language and Communication major in the Department of English. Most of them defined it as the art of welcoming differences and the ability to mediate and bridge between different cultures and understandings. While defining it, they sometimes referred to it as intercultural sensitivity, intercultural skills, and intercultural awareness. These different terms used by participants hinted that they viewed interculturality in different ways. Therefore, the participants' interpretations of the term ICC tended to address communication between cultures, flexibility, tolerance, acceptance, understanding and openness of oneself culture and others' cultures. In the same vein other participants from the same university referred to intercultural communicative competence as the ability to perform and behave adequately and properly in different intercultural contexts, where multiple cultures co-exist. Most of them did not use intercultural competence to equate intercultural communicative competence. They viewed IC as the knowledge acquired while ICC as the action of using the acquired knowledge in intercultural encounters. However, one participant, who revealed that his field of teaching is ICC, believed that IC and ICC cannot be viewed as separate notions. He reported that they are connected and compiled in one phrase 'intercultural communicative competence' where culture, language, and communication are bounded and needed in language education (Baker, 2009b). The informant demonstrated his

understanding to ICC concept as the art of fostering cultural empathy and welcoming differences through cultural comparisons.

All participants from the West University provided more elaborate perspectives and understandings of interculturality. They all recalled works of Byram, Fantini, Deardorff and Bennet and included the ICC dimensions in their definitions. Moreover, a closer and deeper examination of the data revealed that all participants from the West University shared positive attitudes towards the inclusion of interculturality in English Language Teaching. This can be explained as a positive tendency to shift forward towards more critical approach of teaching language and culture regardless of the intensity and depth of English language courses. Findings indicated that all teachers from the West University were able to identify and explain the five *savoirs* of ICC, and they agreed about the importance of promoting intercultural dimensions in their teaching practices. Moreover, they all expressed their dissatisfaction about the fact that ICC module was assigned to Master learners of English. In other words, ICC according to them is introduced at a late stage of learning. Participants indicated that students should be exposed to ICC dimensions from the very beginning of their learning journey. According to Byram (1997; 2006) and Fantini (2005), meeting the students' requirements and needs when teaching the language in a globalised world, should not revolve only around developing learners' communicative competence, but also should encompass intercultural communicative competence (ICC). The latter predominantly focuses on the amalgamation of language, culture and cultural facets of attitudes, knowledge, skills and critical cultural awareness (Byram, 1997; 2006). The aforementioned dimensions should be considered as the primary aim of teaching English as a global language and as a *lingua franca* (ELF).

According to the participants, students will be able to openly perceive different cultural worldviews and tolerate the differences if they are introduced to ICC dimensions at an early learning stage. They believed that conventional methods of teaching theories about old literature and definitions of culture have become of very little charm and interest to many students because this essentialist teaching approach is devoted to piling up knowledge-based facts about culture.

Findings reported that most of the teachers from both Algerian universities stated that they had never been offered training in Algeria to include or teach intercultural communication in their teaching practices. This question was raised for the sake of investigating the participants'

willingness to develop their knowledge about interculturality and its inclusion in teaching English as a FL. Most of them demonstrated the importance and usefulness of intercultural training. However, some teachers from East University believed that teachers should be trained by native instructors of English (NS) in order to promote the target culture. Teachers' lack of awareness of ICC made them believe that the target culture is the ICC. Although the teachers from West University never attended any training which promoted intercultural communication, they highlighted that they developed their ICC through their intercultural encounters and that is the reason for introducing it (ICC) at the West University. Therefore, they had to prepare and widen their knowledge about the term and its application in the classroom. This can be in line with Guilherme (2002), who concluded that intercultural training is not visible in the teaching of foreign languages and cultures. Therefore, she advocated the significance of introducing IC and ICC in pre-service and in-service English language teachers.

Although teachers from West University did not attend any intercultural training, some of them demonstrated that they were provided with several opportunities to attend international conferences abroad where interculturality and cross-cultures were the major themes of the conference. They highlighted that ICC was not tackled in any training they attended. This seems to contradict the Algerian Ministry of Higher Education assertion that teachers were provided with several cultural trainings. There was no consensus which confirms the effectiveness of these trainings and whether they tackled ICC or not. In line with this, Bellalem (2008) highlighted that training proposed by the AMHE mostly tackles theories and traditional methods; therefore, teachers claimed that these trainings do not go with the interest of a globalised world.

However, Teachers from the West were aware of the importance of tackling intercultural communication skills in their lessons because cultural differences can cause problems and several misunderstandings in communication. They also believed that the inclusion of ICC in English language lessons has a significant potential to foster learners' cultural and intercultural awareness. It can also reinforce their curiosity and openness to explore the differences that exist withing other cultures (Byram, 1997). In this line of thought, teachers from the West University agreed on the significance of the inclusion of ICC in all educational levels. They also highlighted that it is substantial for EFL teachers to enhance their own teaching qualities and constantly update their knowledge, and they should strive to expand

their knowledge and make their understanding of education updated and oriented towards intercultural teaching perspective (Ying and Ying's, 2012, p. 28). In other words, updated methods and techniques should be employed to promote and foster the acquisition of the five *savoirs* (attitudes, knowledge, skills and more importantly critical cultural awareness) (Byram, 1997; 2006). However, training offered by the Algerian Ministry of Higher Education focuses on theories that do not adequately prepare teachers for promoting their ICC teaching skills (Sercu *et al.*, p. 177-178; 2007).

Findings revealed that most of the participants agreed about the significance of intercultural training abroad for teachers and exchange programs for learners. This would develop their intercultural attitudes to understand the differences and foster their intercultural awareness in real-life contexts. This perception is in line with Tang and Choi's (2004) study, where they investigated the development of intercultural competence through pre-service training among four Mandarin primary English teachers. The findings of the study highlighted that teachers' personal and academic experiences were developed, and intercultural competence in cross-cultural settings was promoted (Tang and Choi, 2004, p.50).

2.1 How Teachers' intercultural lived experience foster their ICC teaching practices?

All participants had succinct and interesting intercultural lived experiences. They were asked to describe any of their intercultural encounters. Teachers from the East University did not really understand the question; therefore, I had to reformulate the question to 'have you had direct contact with people of different cultures?'. This illustrates that there is a lack of awareness in relation to interculturality concepts among interviewees from East University as most of them were not familiar with terms such as intercultural encounters, intercultural lived experience and interculturality in general. The findings revealed that all teachers from the East had enriching intercultural short-lived experiences in foreign countries where language, religion, and culture are different. Most of them indicated that they encountered challenges in communication with people of different cultural backgrounds, in other words, they viewed the English language they use in their teaching in Algeria is nothing like the English language spoken in real-life settings. Most of them highlighted that it took them a while to familiarise themselves with the language and accent of native speakers of English. Another challenge which hindered the teachers' interactions with other cultures was the fact that most of them

fell into the trap of misunderstanding other cultures. They faced unfamiliar and unusual situations where they could not communicate.

Some teachers stated that experiencing confusion and stress in countries where English is spoken as the first language assisted them to reflect upon their use of English in their teaching in Algeria. The data also reported that all participant teachers had positive attitudes towards their intercultural lived experience. They all expressed their satisfaction about how these experiences taught them to improve their communicative competence as well as intercultural awareness about different beliefs and values of people from different cultural backgrounds. Moreover, some teachers talked about intercultural adaptation they developed through travelling. They went through a lot of stress, confusion, and cultural shocks because of their unfamiliarity with the cultural differences and the absence of intercultural attitudes, knowledge, and skills. Based on the findings, other teachers from the East University highlighted that they had several online intercultural interactions with people of different cultures through social media platforms, which aided them to develop empathetic intelligence, openness, and tolerance towards others' values and behaviours. Through these experiences, teachers from East University learnt to put aside judgmental thoughts and negative attitudes and develop self-discipline towards understanding and respecting others' emotions and thoughts. They also indicated that it assisted them in deconstructing and avoiding stereotypes (Holliday et al., 2004) and eliminating the ethnocentric attitudes they had before. They used to view and evaluate others' values and behaviours according to the preconceptions originated in their traditions and cultures; however, their exposure to cultural differences helped them to cope and respect the differences. Although most of the participant teachers believed that their cultural and intercultural awareness was fostered and developed through their intercultural lived experience, they did not highlight the significance of the inclusion of intercultural communication in their teaching practices

One teacher from East University expressed that his intercultural exposure to people from different parts of the world changed his attitudes and fostered his intercultural knowledge towards cultures. People of other cultures interest and eagerness to explore the teachers' Algerian culture made him thrilled to share a glimpse of the Algerian lifestyle, traditions, and history. However, he demonstrated that he also experienced unusual and uncomfortable scenarios with some people who do not share the same culture. They were neither tolerant nor open towards the teacher's culture because it did not go hand in hand with their culture.

Therefore, this teacher urged for promoting a mutual tolerance and empathy between all cultures.

Similar to the participants' perceptions from the East University, teachers from the West University expressed their satisfaction and positive attitudes towards their intercultural lived experiences in different parts of the world. They indicated that they had several enriching and useful experiences. For instance, some of them narrated their first experience as international students in England where they aimed to improve their communicative skills, they also outlined that they were provided with the opportunity to be in an intercultural classroom, which encompasses students from different cultural backgrounds. Some teachers from the West University also had interesting intercultural experiences. Some had been teaching English in a multi-cultural setting in England, they highlighted that these experiences raised their awareness and widened their knowledge about how countless cultures can co-exist together under the umbrella of humanity. Most of them expressed that experiencing different cultures helped them to appreciate their culture and openly respect others' cultures. Unlike teachers from the East University, some teachers from the West University did not face challenges in communication because, according to them, they were aware of what, when, and how to interact and respect cultural differences. One of the teachers demonstrated that she was trained in England to deal with her students, who were from different cultural backgrounds. She was aware of what is acceptable and what is offensive in other cultures.

Results showed that intercultural teaching approach is used to teach English as a Foreign Language in West University. All teachers revealed that they tackled some of their interesting intercultural lived experiences as a course in intercultural communication subject which is taught at West University. They sought to develop their students' intercultural attitudes and skills. For example, one of the teachers tackled the Indian culture as an ICC course, sharing the knowledge he gained from his Indian friend. He stated that students at first had stereotypes and prejudice about the Indian culture. They viewed it as a dull culture where Indians are only good at dancing. They viewed the Algerian culture as superior.

This teacher used the intercultural knowledge he acquired from his Indian friend to break down students' presumptions. His intercultural experience with his Indian friend was fruitful and intellectual because they both could develop flexibility and tolerance towards the differences between Algerian and Indian cultures. They both had the ability to mediate and bridge between cultures, this illustrates that they are intercultural competent speakers (IS).

Findings reported that most of the teachers' (from West University) familiarity and awareness of interculturality, in general, and intercultural dimensions, in particular, assisted them in properly dealing with unfamiliar situations and effectively communicating with people who share different cultures. They claimed that their intercultural encounters reinforced tolerance and empathy in their attitudes. On the other hand, some other teachers from the same site articulated that they had little knowledge about ICC before travelling. Therefore, they had several misunderstandings and conflicts because of inadequate behaviour or inappropriate comprehension of cultures. In the same vein, teachers confirmed that these intercultural misunderstandings raised her intercultural awareness developed their skills to understand the differences, and fostered her tolerance and empathy.

To summarise all participants' perspectives from the two contexts expressed their positive attitudes towards their intercultural lived experiences. They all acknowledged that these intercultural encounters developed them on a personal and academic level. From a personal angle, teachers developed cultural appreciation of their own culture and tolerance and respect towards others cultures. From an academic level, teachers from East University believed that their communication skills were improved. Therefore, they considered enhancing the learners' speaking skills as a primary aim of teaching. They did not consider intercultural attitudes (curiosity, openness, flexibility, and tolerance) as aimed to be promoted in EFL classrooms. They believed this dimension could be developed only through travelling and experiencing other cultures. However, teachers' (from West University) viewpoints demonstrated the significance of fostering learners' intercultural awareness and attitudes and enriching their intercultural knowledge about other cultural differences. In other words, teachers used their intercultural lived experiences as an approach to teaching ICC.

It is also interesting to state that all teachers from the West recalled Byram (1997) ICC model when they were asked to define ICC. Teachers from West University were aware of the cruciality of moving forward towards intercultural teaching approach in teaching English as a Foreign Language in Algeria. This can help prepare learners for critical intercultural encounters as well as construct third spaces identities in intercultural dialogues (Kramsch, 1993; Lo Bianco *et al.*, 1999; Sercu, 2005; Feng, 2009).

To summarise, the exposure to diverse cultures brought teachers and learners into direct contact with people of different cultures. These intercultural encounters exposed them to

diverse perspectives of beliefs, values, and attitudes. It also challenged them to deconstruct preconceived thoughts and foster their understandings about different cultures. Therefore, these intercultural exposures assisted teachers to recognise the significance of the inclusion of diverse perspectives into their teaching practices to promote learners' intercultural awareness.

7.3.3 Research Question 3

RQ3: What are Master English language learners' perceptions and conceptions of culture and ICC?

The findings from the questionnaire and focus group discussions examined English Master learners' perspectives of learning English in Algeria. It also addressed their conceptions of the notions of culture and ICC. Most of the learners from the East University expressed their discontentment and frustration about the outdated approaches of teaching English and culture in Algeria. In line with this finding, the concept of cultural competence in FL education is generally perceived as the mastery of old literature (Allen, 1985; Crozet *et al.*, 1999). They considered the acquisition of knowledge about old civilisation that is linked to the target culture through reading as significant (Flewelling, 1993; cited in Lessard-Clouston, 1997).

Findings revealed that learners from Mali were not satisfied with their learning experience because their communicative language skills were not improved. All learners from the East University reported that the primary aim of learning a foreign language is to be able to communicate effectively with native speakers of English. In line with this thought, English teaching and learning in East University is predominantly based on traditional approaches, which focus on transferring factual and basic knowledge about peoples of the target culture (Kramsch, 1993; Byram, 1997; Fenner, 2008) through tackling subjects of old civilisations and works of literature (Bouhidel, 2018). This perception confirms the data generated from teachers' findings from the same university. Teachers from the East University appeared to have little awareness or interest in the actual use of the English language in different intercultural interactions (Baker, 2015). They neglect the fact that English acts as a lingua franca in the majority of intercultural encounters (Baker, 2015). Preparing learners to speak like natives is an ill, inadequate and impractical approach which hinders successful intercultural interactions (Baker, 2009a). According to Baker (2015), the fact that L2 users of

English currently exceed L1 users has significant consequences for our understanding of English as a language and a medium for international communication.

It was also interesting that most of the participants from the East University outlined that the mastery of the four skills (receptive and productive skills) are adequate for successful communication with people of different cultural backgrounds. Therefore, they believed that learners' linguistic and communicative competence should be a substantial aim to be fostered to become citizens, who could successfully communicate in English. Similarly, learners from West University affirmed that language structure, grammar, and vocabulary acquisition are the fundamental goal of teaching English in Primary Education (Middle and High School). Thus, language and culture are taught separately. They highlighted that culture is generally viewed as a skill that reinforces and promotes the teaching of English (Luk, 2012; Nguyen et al., 2016). This finding is in line with the study of Rabehi (2021), who stated that the notion of culture has generally been approached in Algerian middle school textbooks from an essentialist structural standpoint, where the diversity of cultures is restricted to geographical boundaries (Rabehi, 2021).

Findings indicated that most of learners from the West University shared positive attitudes about their learning journey of English at the university, where intercultural communication is promoted. ICC module was introduced in Language and Communication speciality in the West University to learners of Masters level. All learners (Algerians and Malians) from the West University highlighted the significance of the inclusion of intercultural communication in EFL contexts. Learners believed that promoting ICC in English language classrooms leads to the development of teachers' and learners' intercultural awareness and communication. It also promotes effective and successful intercultural interactions with people of different cultural backgrounds. Furthermore, ICC dimensions prepare teachers and learners to construct global intercultural citizenship (Byram, 1997; 2012; Porto and Byram, 2015).

Results revealed that although culture and intercultural communication are not promoted in the East University, the majority of learners expressed their willingness and interest of exploring and understanding cultures. Some of them considered learning about cultures as very enriching and enlightening because it helps to develop their communication skills with others and eliminates cultural tensions and confusion. In the same vein, all learners from West University indicated that tackling other cultures in English language teaching and learning from a deeper and critical standpoint is crucial in today's world. In other words, this

approach endeavours to make both teachers and learners perceive themselves as critical global citizens rather than cohabitants of a particular community, who share the same understanding (Byram, 2008).

Findings from the questionnaires and the focus group discussions reported that learners from the East University's perspectives of ICC were limited. In other words, learners' unawareness of the concept made them conceive it as challenging and inapplicable in the Algerian Educational System. Most of them used CC and ICC interchangeably. Some of them claimed that their cultural knowledge and attitudes can be applied in a similar manner when engaging with both individuals from diverse cultures and from their own culture. In other words, learners from the East believed in the existence of one correct and established way of culture (their own way), which is opposed to what Liddicoat and Scarino (2013) advocated. Liddicoat and Scarino (2013) believed that culture is relative and heterogeneous. That is, there is no correct or wrong culture, and there is no particular universal established way of doing things, instead, all behaviours and attitudes are culturally different and malleable (Liddicoat and Scarini, 2013).

Kramersch (2015) demonstrated that the concept of culture has constantly been associated with notions of right and wrong. However, the use of these references may lead to the formation of several negative stereotypes because they share different religious beliefs. Therefore, it can be stated that learners from East University lack intercultural attitudes, which refer to attitudes of curiosity and openness to dispel disbelief about other cultures and belief that one's culture is the correct one (Byram, 1997).

On the other hand, learners from West University demonstrated that intercultural communication has been introduced as a subject where learners are prepared for intercultural interactions. They all expressed their satisfaction about the inclusion of ICC in teaching English at West University. Learners stated that their cultural and intercultural awareness was promoted through developing the five *savoirs* (Byram, 1997). In other words, they highlighted that they developed attitudes of curiosity and openness, which assisted them in deconstructing several negative stereotypes. It is intriguing to state that some learners experienced cultural differences within Algeria and held negative stereotypes towards other sub-cultures. However, their exposure to ICC taught them to know and understand what and why this difference exists.

Based on the findings that were generated from the interviews and questionnaires, some learners experienced some intercultural encounters with people who share different languages, cultures, and religions. Learners from the East University (Malian learners) had negative attitudes about their intercultural lived experience because they held several negative stereotypes about others' values before travelling to Algeria. Since ICC was not introduced at East University, learners were not aware of the seriousness of such stereotypes and how they may lead to intercultural tensions and misunderstandings. However, Malian learners from the West University revealed the assumptions they held towards Algeria were deconstructed through their exposure to ICC. **WLC** expressed, "Through the module of ICC, I have been prepared to understand and appreciate other cultures". This perception was confirmed in the questionnaires, where learners from the West (Malian and Algerian) outlined the significance of the inclusion of intercultural communication in the EFL context, and how this approach assisted them in their intercultural encounters with people of different values and beliefs.

The inclusion of ICC education in language teaching and learning in Algeria is crucial to promote teachers' and learners' awareness to handle intercultural tensions and ambiguities in a constructive and creative way during intercultural encounters (Hoff, 2016). In other words, it will assist them to decentre and perceive "the stranger familiar and the familiar strange" (Byram et al., 2002, p.19).

7.3.4 Research Question 4

RQ4: How does the model of intercultural speaking clubs contribute to the development of ICC?

It was crucial to investigate the members of the intercultural club perspectives and attitudes about the creation of the GRC (Global Representatives of Culture). The co-founder of the club demonstrated that the aim of this initiative was to promote understanding, exchange knowledge, and foster intercultural awareness. This open platform was provided for learners to share their knowledge, experiences, and their attitudes on various cultural topics. Results showed that the GRC members were introduced to intercultural communication module when they used to study in the West University. Their awareness and understandings of ICC fostered their intercultural attitudes and skills, and prepared them for intercultural dialogues (Ganesh and Holmes, 2011). Therefore, they were motivated and eager to create an open

platform where cultural diversity and intercultural tolerance are promoted. The GRC also fostered learners' responsibility, management skills, intercultural leadership, and intercultural awareness. Furthermore, members of the club highlighted the primary focus of the GRC is to prepare learners to act as critical citizens in intercultural interactions (Byram, 2006).

Findings from the interviews revealed that members of club organised several discussions, presentations, seminars, and events about how to be interculturally competent and how to be tolerant and how to be open towards others' cultural differences because learners are living in a world which needs intercultural dialogue and communication (Byram, 2006). The GRC created an inclusive, diverse, and supportive environment where learners can engage in open intercultural interactions and aim to deconstruct stereotypes and misconceptions. The members believed that being a member in intercultural club can expand learners' horizons, promote tolerance and empathy, and construct meaningful connections with people from different cultural backgrounds.

Results reported that members of the GRC demonstrated that their awareness of intercultural communication assisted them in several intercultural encounters they had in the UK. In other words, they posited that intercultural familiarity, and awareness assisted them to understand the cultural differences that exist between themselves and individuals from diverse cultures. It also enabled them to overcome intercultural tensions and barriers during conversations.

Findings also revealed that members of the club highlighted some challenges which hinder the creation of such intercultural clubs in the Algerian context. One major obstacle is that the Algerian educational system lacks inclusivity and cultural diversity. Participants demonstrated that learners from other cultural backgrounds are considered a minority in Algeria. These learners left their homes to pursue their postgraduate studies in Algeria, yet they do not feel accepted or included in the university's events and conferences. According to the GRC members, the Algerian Educational System does not promote internationalisation and globalisation because international students are not provided with an inclusive and intercultural environment where all cultures are promoted. Therefore, it is crucial to promote cultural diversity and intercultural awareness in Algeria through the inclusion of intercultural communication in the teaching of English, as well as, through the creation of intercultural clubs which make learners intercultural competent speakers.

Overall, members of the GRC affirmed the usefulness of the creation of intercultural clubs in Algerian institutions where learners from different cultural backgrounds are included. An intercultural club fosters learners' intercultural understandings and promotes mutual respect and appreciation between different cultures. It can be stated that the GRC club at West University was a successful approach which developed learners' intercultural knowledge and skills to adapt and accommodate to cultural variations and overcome several misunderstandings and stereotypes in intercultural dialogues.

7.4 Implications for Policy-Makers and Teachers

As a sponsored PhD student by the Algerian Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research, my research focuses on identifying and addressing the weaknesses or the absence of teaching intercultural communicative competence (ICC) in higher education. The findings of my thesis will be submitted to the Algerian Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research, where they will be accessible to stakeholders and policy-makers. By highlighting these issues, my role as a sponsored researcher is to raise awareness among policymakers and educators about the critical gaps in ICC instruction. The increased awareness can prompt policymakers to initiate changes and reforms needed to address these weaknesses. While my influence on policy will be indirect, it is significant in triggering the necessary actions by those in positions of authority to improve the educational system. Therefore, my contribution by conducting this research is to demonstrate the necessity of moving forward towards an intercultural language teaching approach. The following are implications for policymakers and teachers to integrate ICC in education:

- Classes should not be limited to teaching information regarding the diverse literary epochs and ideological frameworks within British and American literature. Currently, the Algerian educational programme does not incorporate the significant aspects of interculturality which are substantial enough to be included in language classrooms.
- Educators should establish a culture of collaboration with their colleagues, policymakers, and educationalists from other universities and students to enhance their teaching methodologies and foster the development of creative, innovative and critical thinking skills among students.
- Policymakers should prioritise the integration of intercultural communication as a mandatory subject in Algerian Higher Education and Primary Education.

- Policymakers should offer Algerian English language teachers professional development programs which prioritise intercultural communicative competence through providing workshops, conferences and events. This would assist educators in understanding ICC dynamics and boost their abilities to implement effective intercultural teaching approaches.
- Classroom teaching in both schools and universities should integrate authentic materials where international cultures are included and promoted. This would help learners to reflect and understand their own culture in relation to other cultures and foster their intercultural attitudes and skills. This can be accomplished through developing collaborations with universities from different parts of the world and creating online platforms where Algerians and international learners can engage in intercultural dialogues (see chapter 3).
- Promote collaboration between the Ministry of National Education, Higher Education and the Ministry of ICT to equip classrooms with reliable Wi-Fi and appropriate digital resources. Allocate funds for essential IT materials to support the effective integration of technology in classrooms. This would facilitate the development of intercultural communicative competence (see chapter 3).
- Educators should be supported to change textbooks, which promote communicative competence, and design inclusive curricula that integrate diverse perspectives, beliefs and experiences, instead, of focusing on an idealised native speaker that is now outdated in globalised formations of a range of Englishes (see chapter 3).
- Stakeholders should provide resources and support to teachers and learners to address language barriers in intercultural interactions. This could entail offering them exchange programs (virtual), hiring bilingual educators and intensive intercultural training (see chapter 3).
- I recommend providing open spaces or platforms for learners to create intercultural clubs where learners from different sociocultural backgrounds could meet and engage in intercultural interactions (see chapter 3).
- The development of ICC requires time, as the immediate development of learners' intercultural attitudes and skills from one course should not be expected. Therefore, I recommend raising awareness about ICC at an early stage of learning. This can be

achieved by integrating the development of intercultural dimensions as the main objective within textbooks (see chapter 3).

7.5 Limitations and Recommendations for Future Research

Like any other research, this study has its own limitations. This section highlights the limitations that the study encountered, despite my conscientious attempts to restrict them. These limitations should be considered for future research.

The first limitation of this study is related to the data collection stage, where the selection of participants was the most challenging and time-consuming especially those from the West University. I aimed for a sample of 20 participants (10 teachers from each university). However, only five participants from each university accepted to take part in this research study.

Due to the limited scope and the interpretive nature of this study, which only involved two out of forty-eight directorates in Algeria, it is not possible to overgeneralise the findings to the whole population across Algeria. Therefore, the present study was limited and further research, which investigates educators' perspectives from other universities about the status of intercultural communicative competence in their teaching practices is important. This will provide a wider and more accurate understanding of the educational landscape in Algeria. Transferability does not require generalisations but rather encourages readers of the research to draw connections between the findings of the study and their own experiences (Savin-Baden and Major, 2010). Therefore, my aim was not to generalise, but to better explore the uniqueness and the contrasting contexts chosen in more depth.

This research was conducted in English, which was chosen by the participants as their favoured and convenient language to share their thoughts and experiences about ICC. However, on some occasions, their meaning and understanding of ICC were not clear. This is illustrated when some learners from East University had challenges communicating in English during the focus group discussions. Therefore, I encouraged them to use their first language to share their thoughts. If the research had been conducted in Arabic or French, it could have eliminated these challenges, and some participants may have expressed themselves freely in their native language.

The practical phase of this research study demanded difficult travel across Algeria from the East to the West. The present study was limited by time constraints and the availability of the selected participants. Allocating more time for data collection would have been advantageous and convenient in gathering more data with a larger sample.

As a final limitation, I would like to shed light on the absence of classroom observation in this study. Conducting more studies including classroom observations may provide insightful data on ICC teaching practices, where researchers could observe the teaching methods, teachers' and students' interaction in real life, and students' engagement level related to subjects of cultural diversity and interculturality.

7.6 Contribution to the Study

The findings of this study add several significant contributions to the existing literature as presented below:

The study aimed to explore and understand Algerian English language teachers' and learners' perspectives of intercultural communicative competence in the Algerian context. It also sought to highlight the participants' intercultural lived experiences and how they affected the promotion of the ICC in their teaching and learning practices. Due to the fact that Algeria gathers multiple cultures, it was interesting and enriching to investigate Malian learners' conceptions of ICC, and how the development of intercultural dimensions assisted them in their lived experience in Algeria. Furthermore, exploring the members' perspectives of the intercultural knowledge club (The GRC) was crucial. All the findings of this study filled a gap in the existing literature on intercultural education in the Algerian context.

The present study extends upon the pre-existing literature about the significance of promoting ICC in education in general and in the Algerian context in particular. It also demonstrates the need to re-evaluate the outdated English language teaching approaches and methods in Algeria. The present study affirmed that it is important for teachers to enable learners to acquire intercultural communicative dimensions to be efficient global citizens.

The present research study provided a significant and valuable contribution to the domain of English language education in Algerian Higher Education institutions. It highlighted the

importance of the inclusion of students' national cultures and other diverse cultures into the English learning process. It was suggested by several scholars that it is essential for teachers to integrate learners' native cultures. This would enable them to foster cultural and intercultural awareness, ultimately promoting their intercultural attitudes and perspectives towards people from diverse sociocultural backgrounds (Kramersch, 1993). Kramersch (1993) and Mahmoud (2019) argue that exposing learners to their familiar context (first culture) can ease the process of learning about a foreign culture where they can identify similarities and differences between both cultures.

Findings also indicated the development of ICC of learners from Mali, who were pursuing their studies at West University. They demonstrated that they had several stereotypes about Algeria, but through exposure to ICC, they developed intercultural awareness and sensitivity towards the differences that exist in the Algerian culture. Conversely, teachers and learners from East University viewed culture as static and frequently linked it to the target culture because their primary aim is to develop communicative competence. They were not familiar with the ICC terminology. Therefore, this research adds to the literature by illustrating the significant difference of perspectives of teachers, Algerian learners, Malian learners, GRC members about ICC and their intercultural lived experiences.

This study contributes to the literature by shedding light on the significance of intercultural clubs as an approach to promoting intercultural communicative competence in education in general and in the Algerian context in particular. Investigating the GRC (The Global Representatives of Cultures) members' perspectives confirms the development of the interculturality sphere in West University. The aim of the club is to gain a deeper understanding and appreciation of different cultures.

Due to the fact that people have different beliefs and norms, several misunderstandings and miscommunications in communication are likely to occur due to cultural differences. Therefore, conducting this research which explains the ICC knowledge and perspectives from the Algerian context is essential in order to assist people from other cultural backgrounds to understand how Algerians could communicate across cultures. Thus, it could help to deconstruct stereotypes and minimise misunderstandings during intercultural interactions.

7.7 Reflections

Leaving behind the familiar comforts of Algeria, I found myself navigating a foreign culture, a foreign currency and a completely foreign lifestyle. The transition was far from smooth. Adapting to these new cultural diversities proved to be a challenge that required more resilience than I had anticipated.

As I reflect upon my Ph.D. journey, as an international student in the UK, I am saturated with a range of emotions of gratitude and a sense of accomplishment. Throughout my academic and personal growth, I have encountered numerous intercultural experiences that have significantly impacted my development. This journey has been both challenging and rewarding. It encouraged me to explore new cultures and confront various challenges along the way. The decision to pursue a PhD in the field of interculturality was made with a strong sense of enthusiasm and curiosity, it has driven my passion for understanding and exploring the diverse cultures I encountered.

In the very first days, I felt safe to stick to the Algerian community as every aspect of life in the UK was different from my own culture. Based on the challenges I encountered, I chose to carry PhD research on the significance of integrating intercultural communicative competence in Algerian Higher education to raise Algerian teachers' and learners' awareness of the significance of developing intercultural attitudes and openness towards people of different cultural backgrounds. However, when I delved into the field of interculturality, I found that most of the perspectives and definitions that were provided to define this notion emphasised an individualistic-centred approach, where the user of the competence has to develop intercultural attitudes and skills towards other cultures. However, they neglect the crucial influence of the interlocutor and the context of the interaction. This perspective fails to acknowledge how the dynamics between interlocutors and the context of their interactions can significantly impact the process of interactions. From my personal experience, I have developed an intercultural attitude and openness towards diverse cultures. However, communicating with people from different cultural backgrounds was not always successful because the other interlocutor lacked intercultural communication skills. Therefore, mutual understanding and tolerance should be promoted in both parties. Decolonising education involves confronting the historical biases, Eurocentrism, and power dynamics that have

shaped the pedagogical approaches. It necessitates a deliberate effort to centre the marginalised and silenced voices that have been side-lined for far too long.

This international experience provided me with the opportunity to learn how to conduct qualitative interpretivist research. In Algeria, the emphasis on research tends to lean more towards quantitative approaches influenced by positivist paradigms that prioritise measurable data and statistical analysis. However, conducting a mixed research method in this study with a focus on qualitative methods was a challenging experience for me as I was new to the field. The journey of learning, from how to decide about the interview and focus group questions, how to deal with participants, how to gather and analyse the data, how to present and categorise the themes, and how to relate them to the existing literature was challenging and a time-consuming process. Despite all the difficulties, I firmly believe that this experience was invaluable because of the knowledge and skills I gained throughout the process.

Looking ahead, I am enthusiastic to apply the knowledge and skills I have acquired during my doctoral program. My dedication is to foster the teaching of intercultural communicative competence to promote cultural and intercultural awareness.

7.8 Concluding the study

The primary aim of this study was to explore the Algerian language teachers' and learners' perspectives and attitudes towards the status of intercultural communicative competence in their teaching and learning practices. In addition to that, this research attempted to explore the participants' intercultural lived experiences and how these experiences helped them to promote ICC. It is worth stating that it was significant to investigate the intercultural club members' attitudes towards the creation of this initiative as an intercultural approach which promotes the understanding of ICC among learners from West University. Through the analysis of participants' perceptions, valuable insights have been obtained regarding their understanding of ICC.

The findings of this study displayed several themes related to teachers' and learners' conceptions of ICC. Although teachers' and learners from the East and West Universities perceptions of ICC were varied, they highlighted the significance of developing learners' intercultural communication and recognising its relevance in today's globalised world.

Teachers and learners from the West University emphasised the need for incorporating intercultural dimensions (five *savoirs*) and interactive activities in the Algerian classrooms at Primary and Higher education.

This study also called for the necessity of providing training and professional development programs that focus on intercultural teaching pedagogies, which lead to developing teachers' intercultural attitudes. Teachers play a major role in fostering and developing learners' intercultural communication skills.

Participant learners, on the other hand, expressed positive attitudes towards the learning of ICC because they want to effectively engage in diverse cultures to enhance their intercultural communication skills, and construct a broader perspective about diversity.

The foundation of an intercultural knowledge club (The GRC) can be considered as a valuable and interesting approach to promoting intercultural communicative competence in English as a Foreign Language context. This initiative serves as an open platform, where learners can engage in significant intercultural interactions with their fellows, who are from different cultural backgrounds. This helps promoting the development of a deeper understanding and appreciation of diverse cultures. Furthermore, the intercultural club can be considered an effective approach as it provides students with the opportunity to go beyond language proficiency and develop their intercultural attitudes and critical thinking skills.

Successful intercultural communication is a two-way process that involves active engagement, understanding, and effective exchange of information between individuals or groups from different cultural backgrounds. Both parties are required to listen and to respect each other's perspectives and values. If only the user of the competence (foreign learner) developed ICC, effective communication would be unattainable.

Last but not least, the inclusion of ICC in the Algerian Education and the creation of intercultural clubs provide teachers and learners with a supportive and inclusive environment where they can understand and embrace their culture and appreciate and tolerate cultural differences.

References

- Abdelhai, B. (2001) *L'école algérienne version Ennahda*. *El Watan*, 8 April, 7.
- Aguilar, M. J. (2009) 'Intercultural communicative competence in the context of the European higher education area'. *Language and Intercultural Communication*, 9(4), 242-255. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14708470902785642>
- Aikenhead, G. S. (1997) 'A framework for reflecting on assessment and evaluation' (from Paper presented at the Korean Education Development Institute international conference, Seoul, Korea), *Globalisation of Science Education*, pp. 195–199.
- Ait-Aissa, M. and Keskes, S. (2012) 'Evaluation of intercultural communicative competence in the English language textbook "New Prospects" for the third level secondary school in Algeria', *Journal of Social Sciences*, 1(20), pp.19-35.
- Allen, W. W. (1985) 'Toward cultural proficiency'. In A. C. Omaggio, A. O. Hadley & S. L. Levy (eds.), *Proficiency, Curriculum, Articulation: The Ties that Bind: Northeast Conference on the Teaching of Foreign Languages*. 137-166
- Al-Mawoda, K. R. A. (2011) *Exploring Secondary Teachers' Perceptions towards Teaching Intercultural Competence in Bahrain in English Language Classroom*. PhD Thesis, University of Exeter. Available at: <https://ore.exeter.ac.uk/repository/handle/10036/3688> (Accessed 15 April 2018).
- Al-Omari, J. (2015) *Understanding the Arab culture: a practical cross-cultural guide to working in the Arab world*. London: Robinson.
- Alred, G., Byram, M., & Fleming, M. (2003) *Intercultural experience and education*. Clevedon. England: Multilingual Matters.
- Aoumeur, H. (2017) 'The Impact of class size on teaching and learning English as a foreign Language: The case of the department of English at Abdelhamid Ibn Badis University', *Arab World English Journal*, 8(2). pp. 349-361. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3005591
- Alptekin, C. (2002) 'Towards intercultural communicative competence in ELT', *ELT journal*, 56(1), 57-64. <https://academic.oup.com/eltj/article-abstract/56/1/57/414608?login=false>

- Assous, O. (1985) *Arabization and Cultural Conflicts in Algeria*. PhD thesis. Northeastern University. <https://www.proquest.com/openview/5c9e2163c7f3225c07e946d494be661e/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=18750&diss=y>
- Attride-Stirling, J. (2001) 'Thematic networks: an analytic tool for qualitative research', *Qualitative research*, 1(3), 385-405. [file:///Users/nawelouchene/Downloads/Attride-Stirling01ThematicAnalysisNets%20\(1\).pdf](file:///Users/nawelouchene/Downloads/Attride-Stirling01ThematicAnalysisNets%20(1).pdf)
- Baker, W. (2009a) *Intercultural awareness and intercultural communication through English: An investigation of Thai English language users in higher education*. PhD Thesis. University of Southampton, Southampton, England. Available at: <https://eprints.soton.ac.uk/66542/>
- Baker, W. (2009b) 'The cultures of English as a lingua franca', *TESOL Quarterly*, 43(4), pp. 567-592. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/j.1545-7249.2009.tb00187.x>
- Baker, W. (2011) 'Intercultural awareness: modelling an understanding of cultures in intercultural communication through English as a lingua franca', *Language and Intercultural Communication*, 11 (3), 197-214. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/14708477.2011.577779>
- Baker, W. (2012) 'From cultural awareness to intercultural awareness: culture in ELT', *ELT journal*, 66(1). pp. 62-70. <https://academic.oup.com/eltj/article-abstract/66/1/62/391947>
- Baker, W. (2015) *Culture and Identity Through English as a Lingua Franca: Rethinking Concepts and Goals in Intercultural Communication*. Berlin, Germany: De Gruyter Mouton.
- Baldwin, J. R., Faulkner, S. L., Hecht M. L., & Lindsley S. L. (Eds.) (2006) *Redefining culture: Perspectives across the disciplines*. Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates Publishers.
- Bandura, E. (2011) 'Developing Cultural Self-Awareness and Knowledge to Enhance Intercultural Competence of Foreign Language Students'. In A. Nizegorodcew, Y. Bystrov & M. Kleban (Eds.), *Developing intercultural competence through English:*

Focus on Ukrainian and Polish cultures, Jagiellonian: Wydawnictwo University Press, pp. 45-57

- Banks, J. A. (2002) *Cultural diversity and education: Foundations, curriculum, and teaching* 4th edn. New York, NY: John Wiley & Sons.
- Barany, L. K. (2016) 'Language awareness, intercultural awareness and communicative language teaching: Towards language education', *International Journal of Humanities and Cultural Studies*, 2(4), 257-282. <https://www.ijhcs.com>
- Barili, A., & Byram, M. (2021) 'Teaching intercultural citizenship through intercultural service learning in world language education', *Foreign Language Annals*, 54(3), 776-799. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/flan.12526>
- Barron, P. and Dasli, M. (2010) 'Towards an understanding of integration amongst hospitality and tourism students using Bennett's developmental model of intercultural sensitivity', *Journal of Hospitality, Leisure, Sport and Tourism Education*, 9(2), pp. https://www.pure.ed.ac.uk/ws/portalfiles/portal/18690702/Towards_and_understanding.pdf
- Bellalem, F. (2008) *An Exploration of Foreign Language Teachers' Beliefs about Curriculum Innovation in Algeria: A Socio-Political Perspective*, PhD Thesis. University of King's College, London. PhD Thesis. Available at: <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED537247.pdf> (Accessed: 02 August 2020).
- Bellalem, F. (2012) 'Political history of foreign language teaching in Algeria', Working Papers. (pp. 1-12). https://www.academia.edu/7268046/Political_History_of_Foreign_Language_Teaching_in_Algeria
- Belmihoub, K. (2012) *A framework for the study of the spread of English in Algeria: a peaceful transition to a better linguistic environment*. Master Thesis. University of Toledo. Available at: https://etd.ohiolink.edu/pg_10?0::NO:10:P10_ETD_SUBID:78462 (Accessed: 20 January 2019).
- Belmihoub, K. (2015) 'English for peach in Algeria', *Reconsidering Development*. 4(1), pp. 35-50. <file:///Users/nawelouchene/Downloads/importeditor,+Journal+editor,+fulltext.pdf>

- Belmihoub, K. (2018) 'English in a multilingual Algeria', *World Englishes*, 37(2), pp. 207-227. <https://doi.org/10.1111/weng.12294>
- Benadla, L. (2013) 'The Competency Based Language Teaching in the Algerian Middle School: From EFL Acquisition Planning to its Practical Teaching/Learning', *Arab World English Journal*, 4(1), pp. 144-151. <https://www.awej.org/images/AllIssues/Volume4/Volume4Number1March2013/13.pdf>
- Bennett, M.J. (1986) 'A developmental approach to training for intercultural sensitivity', *International journal of intercultural relations*, 10(2), pp.179-196. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/0147176786900052>
- Bennett, M. (1993) 'Towards Ethnorelativism: A developmental model of intercultural sensitivity', In: M. Paige (ed.), *Education for the intercultural experience*. Yarmouth, ME: Intercultural Press, pp.21-71.
- Bennett, M.J. (1997) 'How not to be a fluent fool: Understanding the cultural dimension of language', *New ways in teaching culture*. pp.16-21. file:///Users/nawelouchene/Downloads/feil_appendix_k.pdf
- Bennett, M.J. (2004) 'Becoming interculturally competent'. *Toward multiculturalism: A reader in multicultural education*, 2(1), pp.62-77.
- Bennett, J. (2011) 'Developing intercultural competence for international education faculty and staff' (Paper presented at the Association of International Education Administrators (AIEA) Conference, San Francisco, 20th-23rd February). *Leaders in international higher education* (22 February 2011), pp.2-14.
- Bennett, J., Bennett, M., & Allen, W. (2003) 'Developing intercultural competence in the language classroom', In D. Lange & R. Paige (Eds.), *Culture as the core: Perspectives on culture in second language learning*. Greenwich, CT: Information Age, pp. 237-270.
- Bennett, M.J. and Hammer, M. (2017) 'Developmental model of intercultural sensitivity', *The international encyclopedia of intercultural communication*, 1(10), pp. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Milton-Bennett-2/publication/318430742_Developmental_Model_of_Intercultural_Sensitivity/links/5c49d6c6299bf12be3e05f91/Developmental-Model-of-Intercultural-Sensitivity.pdf

- Bennoune, M. (2000) *Education, Culture et Developpement en Algerie: Bilan et Perspectives du Systeme Educatif [Education, Culture and Development in Algeria: Assessment and Perspectives for the Educational System]*. Algiers: Marinoor-ENAG.
- Benouar, D. (2013) 'Algerian Experience in Education', *Research and Practice. Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, (102), pp. 361-367. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/270848377> Algerian Experience in Education Research and Practice
- Benrabah, M. (1999). *Langue et pouvoir en Algérie: Histoire d'un traumatisme linguistique*, Paris: Edition Segueie.
- Benrabah, M. (2004) 'Language and politics in Algeria', *Nationalism and ethnic politics*, 10(1), pp. 59-78. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/13537110490450773>
- Benrabah, M. (2005) 'The language planning situation in Algeria', *Current Issues in Language Planning*, 6(4), pp. 379-502. doi: 10.1080/14664208.2005.10807312.
- Benrabah, M. (2007a) 'Language-in-Education Planning in Algeria: Historical Development and Current Issues'. *Language Policy*. 6(2), Grenoble: Springer, pp. 225-252. (Accessed: 02 August 2023). DOI 10.1007/s10993-007-9046-7
- Benrabah, M., (2007b) 'Language maintenance and spread: French in Algeria', *International Journal of Francophone Studies*, 10 (1-2), pp.193-215. https://www.ingentaconnect.com/content/intellect/ijfs/2007/00000010/F0020001/art0001_2 (Accessed: 02 August 2023).
- Benrabah, M. (2013) *Language conflict in Algeria: from colonialism to post-independence*. Grenoble, France: Multilingual matters.
- Benrabah, M. (2014) 'Competition between four "world" languages in Algeria', *Journal of World Languages*, 1(1), pp. 38-59, doi: 10.1080/21698252.2014.893676.
- Berger, A.E. (2002) *Introduction. Algeria in Others' Languages* (Ed). Ithaca and London: Cornell University Press, pp. 1-16
- Bishop, R. (2005) 'Pathologizing the lived experiences of the indigenous Maori people of Aotearoa/New Zealand'. In C. Shields, R. Bishop, & A.E. Mazawi (Eds.), *Pathologizing practices: The impact of deficit thinking on education*. New York: Peter Lang, pp. 56-84

- Blaikie, N. (2010) *Designing Social Research*. Cambridge: Polity Press.
- Bouhadiba, F. (2006) 'The CBLT in Algeria: facts and findings', *Revue Maghrébine des Langues*, 4 (1), pp.165-182. <https://www.asjp.cerist.dz/en/downArticle/163/4/1/129781>.
- Bloomberg, L.D. and Volpe, M. (2012) *Completing your qualitative dissertation: A road map from beginning to end*. Sage Publications.
- Bloor, M., Frankland, J., Thomas, M., Robson, K. (2001) *Focus groups in social research*. London: Sage Publications.
- Bouhadiba, Z. (2013) *The LMD System in Algeria: The case of English* (from the international conference, 7th International Technology, Education and Development Conference Valencia, Spain, 4-5 March, 2013), IATED digital Library, pp. 1826-1829. <https://library.iated.org/download/BOUHADIBA2013LMD>
- Bouhidel, H. (2018) *Developing Students' Intercultural Competence through the Use of Literary Culture-Based Texts: An Experimental Approach: The Case of Second Year Students at the Department of English, Batna University*. PhD Thesis. Batna University, Algeria. <http://eprints.univ-batna2.dz/1663/1/After%20Viva.pdf>
- Bouzidi, L. (2005) *Formation des Enseignants Universitaires à la Pédagogie et à L'usage des TIC pour L'enseignement*, (in Colloque Former des Enseignants-Professionnels, Savoirs et Compétences, Nantes, Février 2005). <file:///Users/nawelouchene/Downloads/2005-bouzidiColloqueNantes.pdf>
- Boyé, S. (2016) *Intercultural communicative competence and short stays abroad: Perceptions and developments*. München, Germany: Waxmann.
- Breeze, R. (2017). 'Promoting Critical Cultural Awareness in the International University'. In R. Breeze & C. Sancho Guinda (eds.), *Essential Competencies for English-medium University Teaching*, Educational Linguistics, Switzerland: Springer International. Publishing.
- Brinkmann, S. (2014) 'Interview'. In: Teo, T. (eds) *Encyclopaedia of Critical Psychology*, New York: Springer.
- Brinkmann, S., & Kvale, S. (2018) *Doing interviews*. London and Thousand Oaks: Sage Publications.
- British Psychological Society. (2009) *Code of Ethics and Conduct*. United Kingdom: British Psychological Society.

- Brown, H. D. (1986) 'Learning a second culture', In J. M. Valdes (ed.) *Culture bound*. New York, NY: Cambridge University Press, pp. 33-48
- Brown, H. D. (2007) *Principles of language learning and teaching* 5th edn. White Plains: Pearson Education.
- Brown, H. D. (2014). *Principles of language learning and teaching*. 6th edn. White Plains, NY: Pearson Education.
- Bruner, J. (1997) *The culture of education*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press.
- Bryman, A. (2012) *Social research methods*. 4th (edn). Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Bryman, A., (2015) *Social research methods*. 5th edn. Oxford: Oxford university press.
- Bryman, A. (2016) *Social research methods*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Burrell, G. and Morgan, G. (1979) *Sociological paradigms and organisational analysis*. Aldershot, UK: Heinemann Educational Books.
- Byram, M. (1988) 'Foreign language education and cultural studies', *Language, Culture and Curriculum*, 1(1), 15-31. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07908318809525025>
- Byram, M. (1991) 'Teaching Culture and Language: Towards an Integrated Model', In D. Buttjes & M. Byram (eds.), *Mediating languages and cultures: Towards an intercultural theory of foreign language education*. Clevedon: Multilingual Matters.
- Byram, M. (1997) *Teaching and assessing intercultural communicative competence*, Clevedon, England: Multilingual Matters.
- Byram, M. (2000) 'Assessing intercultural competence in language teaching'. 18(6), *Sprogforum*, pp.8–13.
- Byram, M. (2003) 'On being 'bicultural' and 'intercultural''. In: G. Alred, M. Byram & M. Fleming (eds.) *Intercultural experience and education*. Clevedon: Multilingual Matters, pp.50-66.
- Byram, M. (2006) 'Developing a concept of intercultural citizenship'. In A. Geo, M. Byram and M. Fleming (eds), *Education for intercultural citizenship: Concepts and comparisons*. Clevedon: Multilingual Matters LTD, pp. 109-129
- Byram, M. (2008) *From foreign language education to education for intercultural citizenship*. Clevedon, England: Multilingual Matters.

- Byram, M. (2009) 'Intercultural competences in foreign languages. The intercultural speaker and the pedagogy of foreign language education', In D. K. Deardorff (Ed.), *The SAGE Handbook of Intercultural Competence*. London: SAGE Publications, pp. 321-332.
- Byram, M. (2011) 'From foreign language education to education for intercultural citizenship', *Intercultural Communication Review*, 9, pp.17-35.
- Byram, M. (2012) 'Language awareness and (critical) cultural awareness - relationships, comparisons and contrasts'. *Language Awareness*, 21(1-2), pp. 5-13. doi:10.1080/09658416.2011.639887
- Byram, M. (2013) 'Foreign language teaching and intercultural citizenship', *Iranian Journal of Language Teaching Research*, 1(3), UK and Luxemburg: Urmia University Press, pp. 53-62.
- Byram, M. (2014) 'Twenty-five years on –from cultural studies to intercultural citizenship', *Language, culture and curriculum*, 27(3), pp. 209-225. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07908318.2014.974329>
- Byram, M., 2020. *Teaching and assessing intercultural communicative competence: Revisited. 2nd edn*. Multilingual matters
- Byram, M., & Fleming, M. P. (1998) *Language learning in intercultural perspective: Approaches through drama and ethnography*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Byram, M., Gribkova, B., & Starkey, H. (2002) *Developing the intercultural dimension in language teaching: A practical introduction for teachers*. Strasbourg, France: Council of Europe.
- Byram, M., Holmes, P., & Savvides, N. (2013) Intercultural communicative competence in foreign language education: Questions of theory, practice and research. *The Language Learning Journal*, 41(3), 251-253.
- Byram, M. and Kramsch, C. (2008) 'Why is it so difficult to teach language as culture?' *The German Quarterly*, University of California, Berkeley: American Association of Teachers of German, pp.20-34. <https://faculty.weber.edu/cbergeson/516/byram.2008.pdf>
- Byram, M. and Masuhara, H. (2013) 'Intercultural competence', In Tomlinson, *Applied linguistics and materials development*. London: Bloomsbury Academic, pp. 142-158.

- Byram, M., Nichols, A., & Stevens, D. (2001) *Developing intercultural competence in practice*. Clevedon, England: Multilingual Matters.
- Byram, M., Porto, M. and Yulita, L. (2023) 'Beyond teaching languages for communication—Humanistic perspectives and practices'. *Languages*, 8(3), pp.1-13. <file:///Users/nawelouchene/Downloads/languages-08-00166-v2.pdf>
- Byram, M., & Risager, K. (1999) *Language teachers, politics and cultures*. Clevedon, Sydney: Multilingual matters.
- Canale, M. and Swain, M. (1980) 'Theoretical bases of communicative approaches to second language teaching and testing'. *Applied Linguistics*, 1(1), pp. 1- 47.
- Canale, G. (2016) '(Re)Searching culture in foreign language textbooks, or the politics of hide and seek', *Language, Culture and Curriculum*, 29(2), pp. 225–243.
- Charmaz, K. (1996) 'Grounded theory'. In J. Smith, R. Harre, and L. Langenhove, *Rethinking methods in psychology* (pp. 27-49). London: Sage Publications.
- Chastain, K. (1976) *Developing second-language skills: Theory to practice*. Boston: University of Virginia Press.
- Chomsky, N. (1957) *Syntactic Structures*. The Hague/Paris: Mouton.
- Chomsky, N. (1965) *Aspects of the Theory of Syntax*. Massachusetts: MIT Press.
- Chomsky, N. (2006) *Language and mind*. 3rd ed. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Christians, C.G. (2005). 'Ethics and politics in qualitative research'. In N.K. Denzin & Y.S. Lincoln (eds.), *The Sage handbook of qualitative research 3rd* (edn), pp. 139-164). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- Clancy-Smith, J. (1997) '13 *The Maghrib and the Mediterranean World in the Nineteenth Century: Illicit Exchanges, Migrants, and Social Marginals*', *In the Maghrib in Question: Essays in History and Historiography*. University of Texas Press, pp. 222-24
- Cohen, L., Manion, L. and Morrison, K. (2000) *Research Methods in Education*. 5th Edition, London: Routledge Falmer.
- Cohen, L., Manion, L. and Morrison, K. (2011) *Research Methods in Education*. 7th edn. London and New York: Routledge Falmer.

- Corbett, J. (2003) *An intercultural approach to English language teaching (7)*: Intercultural Approach to English Language Teaching. Clevedon: Multilingual Matters.
- Cortazzi, M., & Jin, L. (1999) 'Cultural mirrors: Materials and methods in the EFL classroom', In: E. Hinkel (Ed.), *Culture in second language teaching*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, pp. 196-219.
- Creswell, J. (2009) *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approach*. London: Sage Publications, Incorporated.
- Creswell, J. W. (2014) *A concise introduction to mixed methods research*, United States: Sage Publications.
- Creswell, J. W. and Miller, D. L. (2000) 'Determining validity in qualitative inquiry'. *Theory into Practice*, 39(3), pp. 124-130. https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1207/s15430421tip3903_2?journalCode=htip20
- Creswell, J.W., Plano Clark, V.L., Gutmann, M.L. and Hanson, W.E., (2003) *Advanced mixed methods research designs. Handbook of mixed methods in social and behavioral research*. London: Sage Publications, pp. 209-240.
- Creswell, J.W. and Plano Clark, V.L. (2007) *Designing and Conducting Mixed Methods Research*. Thousand Oaks.CA: Sage Publications.
- Creswell, J.W. and Clark, V.L.P. (2011) *Mixed methods research*, London: Sage Publications.
- Crotty, M.J. (1998) *The foundations of social research: Meaning and perspective in the research process*. London: Sage Publications, pp.1-256.
- Croucher, S. (2017) *Global perspectives on intercultural communication*. New York: Routledge.
- Crozet, C., Liddicoat, A. J., & Lo Bianco. J. (1999) 'Intercultural competence: from language policy to language education', In J. E. Lo Bianco., C. E. Crozet & A. J. E. Liddicoat, *Striving for the Third Place: Intercultural Competence Through Language Education*. Melbourne: Language Australia, pp.1-18
- Cuzzort, R. P. (1969) *Humanity and modern sociological thought*. New York, NY: Holt, Rinehart and Winston.

- Daniels, D. (2008) 'Exploring Ethical Issues When Using Visual Tools in Educational Research'. In P. Liamputtong (ed.), *Doing Cross-Cultural Research: Ethical and Methodological Perspectives*. Netherlands: Springer Link, pp. 119-133
- Denzin, N.K. and Lincoln, Y.S. (eds) (2011). *The Sage handbook of qualitative research*. London: Sage Publications.
- Deardorff, D.K. (2006) 'Assessing intercultural competence in study abroad students', *Languages for intercultural communication and education*, 12, p.232.
- Djité, P.G. (1992) 'The Arabization of Algeria: Linguistic and sociopolitical motivations', *international journal of the sociology of language*, 98(1), pp.15-28. <https://www.deepdyve.com/lp/de-gruyter/the-arabization-of-algeria-linguistic-and-sociopolitical-motivations-4aSKwUsx8t>
- Diener, E. and Crandall, R., (1978) *Ethics in social and behavioral research*. Washington: U Chicago Press.
- Daoudi, A. (2018) 'Multilingualism in Algeria: between 'soft-power', 'Arabisation', 'Islamisation', and 'globalisation', *The Journal of North African Studies*, 23 (3), pp.460-481. [http://pure-oai.bham.ac.uk/ws/portalfiles/portal/46442265/Daoudi Multilingualism in Algeria Journal of North African Studies.pdf](http://pure-oai.bham.ac.uk/ws/portalfiles/portal/46442265/Daoudi%20Multilingualism%20in%20Algeria%20Journal%20of%20North%20African%20Studies.pdf)
- Dervin, F. (2009) 'Transcending the culturalist impasse in stays abroad: helping mobile students to appreciate diverse diversities', *Frontiers the interdisciplinary journal of study abroad*. 18(1), pp.119-141. <https://doi.org/10.36366/frontiers.v18i1.257>
- Dervin, F. (2010) 'Assessing intercultural competence in language learning and teaching: A critical review of current efforts', *New approaches to assessment in higher education*, 5, pp.155-172. [https://edisciplinas.usp.br/pluginfile.php/4399335/mod_resource/content/1/Dervin %20on%20ICC.pdf](https://edisciplinas.usp.br/pluginfile.php/4399335/mod_resource/content/1/Dervin%20on%20ICC.pdf)
- Dervin, F., & Gross, Z. (eds.) (2016) *Intercultural competence in education: Alternative approaches for different times*. London, England: Palgrave.
- Dervin, F. (2017) 'I find it odd that people have to highlight other people's differences – even when there are none: Experiential learning and interculturality in teacher

- education'. *International Review of Education*, 63(1), pp.87–102. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11159-017-9620-y>
- Dignen, B., Chamberlain, J. (2009) *Fifty ways to improve your intercultural skill*. London: Summertown Publishing Ltd.
 - Djamel, B. (2001) 'Re'forme de l'e'cole, les islamo-conservateurs accusent', *Le Matin*, (March).
 - Djebbari, Z. (2016) 'Language policy in Algeria: An Outlook into Reforms', *Institute of Education Sciences*, pp.1-24. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED582670.pdf>
 - Dodd, C. H. (1998) *Dynamics of intercultural communication*. Boston: McGraw-Hill.
 - Dörnyei, Z. (2007) *Research methods in applied linguistics: Quantitative, qualitative, and mixed methodologies*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
 - Doyé, P. (1999) *The intercultural dimension: Foreign language education in the primary school*. Berlin: Cornelsen Verlag.
 - Eagleton, T. (2016) *Culture*. London: Yale University Press.
 - Elsen, A., & St. John, O. (2007) 'Learning autonomy and intercultural competence', In M. Jiménez Raya & L. Sercu (Eds.), *Challenges in Teacher Development: Learner Autonomy and Intercultural Competence. Foreign Language Teaching in Europe*. Frankfurt: Peter Lang Publishing Group, pp. 15-38.
 - Ennaji, M. (1991) 'Aspects of multilingualism in the Maghreb'. *International Journal of the Sociology of Language*, 87 (1), pp.7-26. <https://doi.org/10.1515/ijsl.1991.87.7>
 - Ezzaki, A. and Wagner, D.A. (1991) 'Language and Literacy in the Maghreb'. *In Annual Review of Applied Linguistics*, 12, pp. 216-229. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0267190500002233>
 - Fanon, F. (1967) *Black skin, white masks*. New York: Grove.
 - Fantini, A. E. (2000) 'A central concern: Developing intercultural competence', *SIT Occasional Paper Series*, 1(1), pp. 25-42. <https://digitalcollections.sit.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?referer=&httpsredir=1&article=1000&context=sop&s#page=33>
 - Fantini, A. (2005) 'About intercultural communicative competence: A construct', *SIT Occasional Papers Series*, pp. 1-4.

- Fantini, A. (2012) 'Language: an essential component of intercultural communicative competence', In J. Jackson (ed.), *The Routledge handbook of language and intercultural communication*. London: Routledge, pp. 263-278.
- Fantini, A. (2018) *Intercultural communicative competence in educational exchange: a multinational perspective*. Milton: Routledge.
- Feng, A. (2009) 'Becoming interculturally competent in a third space', In A. Feng, M. Byram, & M. Fleming (Eds.), *Becoming interculturally competent through education and training*. Bristol, England: Multilingual Matters pp. 71-91.
- Finch, J. (1985) 'Social policy and education: problems and possibilities of using qualitative research.' *Issues in educational research: Qualitative methods*, pp.109-128.
- Fisher, C and Buglear, J. (2010) *Researching and Writing a Dissertation: An Essential Guide for Business Students*. 3th edn. Harlow, England: Pearson Education
- Flewelling, J. (1993) 'Teaching culture in the' 90s: implementing the National Core French Study syllabus', *Canadian modern language review*, 49(2), 338-344.
<https://www.utpjournals.press/doi/epdf/10.3138/cmlr.49.2.338?role=tab>
- Fenner, A. B. (2008) 'Cultural awareness in the foreign language classroom', In Hornberger, N. H. (ed.), *Encyclopaedia of language and education*, 6, Springer, pp.273-285.
- Flick, U. (2007) *An introduction to qualitative research*. London: Sage Publications.
- Frank, J. (2013) 'Raising Cultural Awareness in the English Language Classroom', In *English teaching forum*, 51(4), pp. 2.
https://americanenglish.state.gov/files/ae/resource_files/51_4_2_frank.pdf
- Ganesh, S. & Holmes, P. (2011) 'Positioning intercultural dialogue', *Theories, pragmatics, and an agenda, Journal of international and intercultural communication*, 4 (2). pp. 81-86.
<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/17513057.2011.557482>
- Garcia, M. I. F., & Biscu, M. G. (2005) 'Theatre in the acquisition of intercultural communicative competence', *International Journal of Learning*, 12(10), pp. 327-335. DOI: 10.18848/1447-9494/CGP/v12i10/48217.
- Glaser, B., & Strauss, A. (1967) *The discovery of grounded theory: Strategies for qualitative research*, London and New York: Routledge

- Gonen, S.I. K. & Saglam, S. (2012) 'Teaching Culture in the FL Classroom: Teachers' Perspectives International'. *Journal of Global Education*, 1(3), pp. 26-46. <http://www.ijge.net/index.php/ijge/article/view/60/61>
- Goodman, L. A. (2011) 'Comment: respondent-driven sampling and snowball sampling in hard-to-reach populations.' *Sociological Methodology*, 41(1), 347-353. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1111/j.1467-9531.2011.01242.x>
- Gordon, D.C. (1966) *The Passing of French Algeria*. London, New York: Oxford University Press.
- Gordon, D.C. (1978) *The French Language and National Identity*. France: The Hague Mouton.
- Graddol, D. (2006) *English next: Why global English may mean the end of "English as a foreign language"*. London: British Council.
- Grandguillaume, G. (2004) 'Arabisation au Maghreb', *Revue d'Aménagement Linguistique*, 107, pp. 15–39, Winter. Available: https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=frandas_sdt=0%2C5andq=Grandguillaume%2C+G.+%282004%29.+L%E2%80%99Arabisation+au+Maghreb.+andbtnG= [Accessed: 18 April 2018].
- Crosbie, V. (2014) 'Capabilities for intercultural dialogue', *Language and Intercultural Communication*, 14(1), pp. 91-107. doi: 10.1080/14708477.2013.866126.
- Guba, E.G. and Lincoln, Y.S., (1988) 'Do inquiry paradigms imply inquiry methodologies?' *Qualitative approaches to evaluation in education*, pp.89-115.
- Guba, E. G. (1990) *The Paradigm dialog*. Newbury Park, CA: Sage Publications.
- Guba, E.G. and Lincoln, Y.S., (1994) 'Competing paradigms in qualitative research'. In: Denzin, N.K. and Lincoln, Y.S., (eds), *Handbook of qualitative research*. Thousand Oaks: Sage Publications, Inc, pp.105-117. https://miguelangelmartinez.net/IMG/pdf/1994_Guba_Lincoln_Paradigms_Quali_Research_chapter.pdf
- Guilherme, M. (2000) 'Intercultural Competence', In: M. Byram (ed.), *Routledge Encyclopaedia of Language Teaching and Learning*. London: Routledge, pp. 297-300.
- Guilherme, M. (2002) *Critical citizens for an intercultural world: foreign language education as cultural politics*, Blue Ridge Summit, PA: Multilingual Matters.

- Guirdham, M. (2005) *Communicating across cultures at work*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillian.
- Gustin, S. (2007-2008) *La Formation Professionnelle, en Algerie: De la Colonisation a nos Jours*. Master Dissertation. Université Lumiere Lyon 2. Available at <https://docplayer.fr/29409519-La-formation-professionnelle-en-algerie-de-la-colonisation-a-nos-jours-memoire.html> (Accessed 16 August 2023).
- Hammond, M., and Wellington, J. (2013) *Research methods: the key concepts*. London: Routledge.
- Hall, E. T. (1976) *Beyond culture*. New York: Doubleday Anchor.
- Hall, J.K. (2012) *Teaching and researching: Language and culture*. 2nd edn. Harlow: Longman.
- Hamdan, J.M. and Kessar, S. (2023) 'Language Policy and Planning in Algeria: case study of Berber language planning', *Theory and Practice in Language Studies*, 13(1), pp.59-68. <https://tpls.academypublication.com/index.php/tpls/article/view/5317>
- Hatch, J.A., (2002) *Doing qualitative research in education settings*. 2nd edn. Albany: University of New York Press.
- Hismanoglu, M. (2011) 'An investigation of ELT students' intercultural communicative competence in relation to linguistic proficiency, overseas experience and formal instruction', *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 35(6), 805-817. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0147176711000903>.
- Hoff, H. E. (2014) 'A critical discussion of Byram's model of intercultural communicative competence in the light of bildung theories', *Intercultural Education*, 25(6), pp. 508-517. doi: 10.1080/14675986.2014.992112
- Hoff, H. E. (2016) 'From 'intercultural speaker' to 'intercultural reader': A proposal to reconceptualize intercultural communicative competence through a focus on literary reading.', In F. Dervin, & Z. Gross (Eds.), *Intercultural competence in education: Alternative approaches for different times*. London, England: Palgrave, pp. 51-73.
- Hoff, H. E. (2020) 'The evolution of intercultural communicative competence: Conceptualisations, critiques and consequences for 21st century classroom practice', *Intercultural Communication Education*, 3 (2), pp. 55-74. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1284796>

- Hofstede, G., Hofstede, G. J., & Minkov, M. (2010) *Cultures and Organizations: Software of the Mind*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Holliday, A., Hyde, M. and Kullman, J. (2004) *Intercultural communication: An advanced resource book*. London: Routledge, Taylor and Francis.
- Holliday, A. R. (2005) *The struggle to teach English as an international language*. Oxford: Oxford University.
- Holliday, A. (2009) 'The role of culture in English language education: Key challenges', *Language and Intercultural Communication*, 9, pp. 144-155. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14708470902748814>
- Holliday, A. (2010) 'Complexity in cultural identity', *Language and Intercultural Communication*, 10(2), pp. 165-177. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14708470903267384>
- Holliday, A. (2019) *Understanding intercultural communication: negotiating a grammar of culture*. 2nd edn. London: Routledge.
- Holmes, P. (2014) 'Intercultural dialogue: challenges to theory, practice and research', *Language and Intercultural Communication*, 14(1), pp.1-6. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/14708477.2013.866120>
- Holtzman, L., & Sharpe, L. (2014) *Media messages: What film, television, and popular music teach us about race, class, gender, and sexual orientation*. 2nd edn. London and New York: Routledge.
- Horton, P. B., & Hunt, C. L. (1984) *Sociology* (6th ed.). New York, NY: McGraw-Hill.
- Horwitz, E. K., Horwitz, M. B., & Cope, J. (1986) 'Foreign language classroom anxiety', *The Modern Language Journal*, 70(2), pp. 125-132. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/327317>
- Huang, Y., & Kou, Y. (2012) 'Empirical study on intercultural communication teaching for English majors in Chinese universities', *Cross-Cultural Communication*, 8(6), pp. 21-29. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.3968/j.ccc.1923670020120806.1101>
- Huang, Y. (2014) 'Constructing intercultural communicative competence framework for English learners', *Cross-Cultural Communication*, 10(1), pp. 97- 101. DOI: 10.3968/j.ccc.1923670020141001.3970

- Hudson, L.A. and Ozanne, J.L. (1988) 'Alternative ways of seeking knowledge in consumer research'. *Journal of consumer research*, 14(4), pp.508-521. <https://academic.oup.com/jcr/article-abstract/14/4/508/1811971?login=false>.
- Huebenere, T. (1965) *How to teach foreign language effectively*. New York: New York University Press.
- Hymes, D.H. (1972) 'On Communicative Competence', In: J.B. Pride and J. Holmes (eds.) *Sociolinguistics. Selected Readings*. Harmondsworth: Penguin, pp. 269-293.
- Hymes, D. (1986) 'Discourse: scope without depth', *International Journal of the Sociology of Language*, 57, pp. 49-89. <https://doi.org/10.1515/ijsl.1986.57.49>
- Jandt, F. E. (2013) *An introduction to intercultural communication. Identities in a global community*. 7th edn. Thousand Oaks: Sage.
- Hydén, L. C., & Bülow, P. H. (2003) 'Who's talking: drawing conclusions from focus groups—some methodological considerations.' *Int. J. Social Research Methodology*, 6(4), 305-321. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/13645570210124865>
- Jiang, W. (2000) 'The relationship between culture and language' *ELT journal*, 54(4), pp. 328-334. <https://doi.org/10.1093/elt/54.4.328>
- Johnson, R.B. and Onwuegbuzie, A.J. (2004) 'Mixed methods research: A research paradigm whose time has come'. *Educational researcher*, 33(7), pp.14-26. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.3102/0013189x033007014>
- Kahlouche, R. (2004) 'Le berbère dans la politique linguistique algérienne', *Revue d'Aménagement Linguistique*, 107, Winter, pp.103–132.
- Kayman, M. A. (2004) 'The state of English as a global language: Communicating culture', *Textual Practice*, 18(1), pp.1-22. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0950236032000140131>
- Kemper, E.A., Stringfield, S. and Teddlie, C. (2003) 'Mixed Methods Sampling Strategies in Social Science Research', in: A. Tashakkori and C, Teddlie (eds) *Handbook of Mixed Methods in Social and Behavioral Research*. Thousand Oaks: Sage Publications, pp. 273-296.

- Kerlinger, F.N., (1970) 'A social attitude scale: Evidence on reliability and validity' *Sage Journal, Psychological Reports, 26(2)*, pp.379-383. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.2466/pr0.1970.26.2.379>
- Killam, L. (2013) *Research terminology simplified: Paradigms, axiology, ontology, epistemology and methodology*. Sudbury.
- Kiss, T. (2018) 'Developing Intercultural Communicative Competence: An example of the New College English textbook series' *Indonesian Journal of English Language Teaching, 1(12)*, pp. 79-99. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.25170/ijelt.v12i1.1470>
- Kramersch, C. (1993) *Context and culture in language teaching*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Kramersch, C. (2003) 'Teaching language along the cultural faultline', In Lange, D., Paige, R, *Culture as the core: Perspectives on culture in second language learning*(eds). University of Minnesota: Information Age Publishing, pp.19-35.
- Kramersch, C. (2008) 'Ecological perspectives on foreign language education', *Language Teaching, 41(3)*, pp.389-408. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0261444808005065>
- Kramersch, C. J. (2009) *The multilingual subject: What foreign language learners say about their experience and why it matters*. Oxford, England: Oxford University Press.
- Kramersch, C. (2011) 'The symbolic dimensions of the intercultural', *Language Teaching, 44(3)*, pp. 354–367. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0261444810000431>
- Kramersch, C. (2012) 'Authenticity and legitimacy in multilingual SLA'. *Critical Multilingualism Studies, 1(1)*, pp.107-128. <file:///Users/nawelouchene/Downloads/dgl,+Journal+manager,+9-1-53-1-10-20121119.pdf>
- Kramersch, C. (2013) 'Culture in Foreign Language Teaching', *Iranian Journal of Language Teaching Research, 1(1)*, pp.57-78. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ej1127430>
- Kramersch, C. (2015) 'The Cultural Component of Language Teaching', *Zeitschrift für Interkulturellen Fremdsprachenunterricht, 1(2)*, pp. 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07908319509525192>
- Krasner, I. (1999) 'The role of culture in language teaching'. *Dialog on Language Instruction, 13(1-2)*, pp.79-88. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ589727>

- Krueger, R.A. and Casey, M.A. (2000). *Focus groups*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- Kun, L. (2013) 'The Culture Study in Foreign Language Education', *International Review of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 6 (1), pp. 196-204. www.irssh.com
- Kvale, S. (1996) *Interviews: an introduction to qualitative research interviewing*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Kvale, S., & Brinkmann, S. (2009) *InterViews: Learning the craft of qualitative research interviewing*. Los Angeles, CA: Sage Publications.
- Laib, M. (1993) 'L'anglais en 4ème année', *La langue alibi El Watan*, 27 May.
- Lakehal-Ayat-Benmati, (2008). *Is the Algerian Educational System Weakening? An Investigation of the High School Curricula and their Adequacy with the University Curricula*. PhD Thesis. <https://bu.umc.edu.dz/theses/anglais/LAK1017.pdf>
- Landis, D., Bennett, J. and Bennett, M. (2004) *Handbook of intercultural training*. 3rd edn. London: Sage Publications.
- Larzén-Östermark, E. (2009) 'Language teacher education in Finland and the cultural dimension of foreign language teaching—a student teacher perspective', *European Journal of Teacher Education*, 32(4), 401-421. DOI: 10.1080/02619760903012688
- LeCompte, M. D., Preissle, J., & Tesch, R. (1993) *Ethnography and qualitative design in educational research*. Academic Press.
- Lee, Y. J. (2009) 'Treating Culture: What 11 High School EFL Conversation Textbooks in South Korea Do'. *English Teaching: Practice and Critique*. 8(1), pp.76-96. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ847287>
- Le Roux, C. S (2017) 'Language in education in Algeria: a historical vignette of a 'most severe' socio linguistic problem', *Language & History*, 60(2), pp. 112-128. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/17597536.2017.1319103>
- Lewis, J.E. (2004) 'Freedom of Speech-in Any Language'. *Middle East Quarterly*. 11(3), pp 37-46. <https://www.meforum.org/635/freedom-of-speech-in-any-language>
- Lewis, J. and Ritchie, J., (2003) 'Generalising from qualitative research'. *Qualitative research practice: A guide for social science students and researchers*, 2, pp.347-362. <https://books.google.co.uk/books?hl=en&lr=&id=hANdBAAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PA26>

[3&dq=%E2%80%A2%09Lewis,+J.+and+Ritchie,+J.,+\(2003\)+%E2%80%98Generalising+from+qualitative+research.+Qualitative+research+practice%E2%80%99:A+guide+for+social+science+students+and+researchers,+2,+pp.347-362.&ots=QjmYP4EdAl&sig=D7EBn8H-MP21q88T1UJ2Dk4AyXc#v=onepage&q&f=false](#)

- Liddicoat, A. J., & Kollner, M. (2012) 'Teaching Asian languages from an intercultural perspective', In X, Song & K, Cadman (eds.) *Bridging Transcultural Divides: Asian Languages and Cultures in Global Higher Education*. Adelaide: University of Adelaide Press. pp.73-100.
- Liddicoat, A., & Scarino, A. (2010) 'Eliciting the intercultural in foreign language education at school', In L. Sercu, & A. Paran (eds.) *Testing the untestable in language and education*. Clevedon, England: Multilingual Matters, pp. 52-73.
- Liddicoat, A. J. and Scarino, A. (2013) *Intercultural language teaching and learning*. Chichester, U.K.: Wiley-Blackwell.
- Lincoln, Y.S. and Guba, E. G. (1985) *Naturalistic inquiry*, Beverly Hills: Sage Publications.
- Lo Bianco, J. L., Liddicoat, A., & Crozet, C. (1999) 'Intercultural competence: From language policy to language education', In J. L. Bianco, A. Liddicoat & C. Crozet (eds.) *Striving for the Third Place: Intercultural Competence Through Language Education*. Australia and France: Language Australia. pp. 1- 20.
- Luk, J. (2012) 'Teachers' Ambivalence in integrating culture with EFL teaching in Hong Kong', *Language, Culture and Curriculum*, 25(3), pp.249–264. doi:10.1080/07908318.2012.716849.
- Lunsford Mears, C. (2009) *Interviewing for education and social science research: The gateway approach*. New York, NY: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Maamri, M. (2009) 'The syndrome of the French Language in Algeria', *International Journal of Arts and Sciences*, 3(3), pp. 77-89. Available at: <https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/document?repid=rep1&type=pdf&doi=50823f5c939ee1d42a56c8d7a8cf6d9cb70ef6fe>
- Mack, N., Woodsong, C., MacQueen, K. M., & Guest, G. (2005) *Qualitative research methods*. North Carolina: Family Health International.

- Mahmud, Y.S. (2019) 'The representation of local culture in Indonesian EFL textbooks: rationales and implications', *Indonesian EFL Journal*, 5(2), pp.61–72. <https://journal.uniku.ac.id/index.php/IEFLJ/article/view/1727/1361>
- Mami, N. A. (2013) 'Teaching English under the LMD reform: the Algerian experience', *World Academy of Science, Engineering and Technology, International Journal of Social, Behavioral, Educational, Economic, Business and Industrial Engineering*, 7(4), pp. 910-913. [https://www.academia.edu/3635199/Teaching_English_under_the_LMD_Reform_t he Algerian Experience World Academy of Science Engineering and Technology WASET Issue 76 April 2013 Venice pISSN 2010 376X Eissn 2010 3778 pp 10 5 108](https://www.academia.edu/3635199/Teaching_English_under_the_LMD_Reform_t_he_Algerian_Experience_World_Academy_of_Science_Engineering_and_Technology_WASET_Issue_76_April_2013_Venice_pISSN_2010_376X_Eissn_2010_3778_pp_10_5_108)
- Mansouri, N. (2019) *Bloggng and EFL writing: teachers and students attitudes towards weblogs-storytelling in one university in Algeria*. PhD thesis. University of the West of Scotland
- Marshall, M.N., (1996) 'Sampling for qualitative research'. *Family practice*, 13(6), pp.522-526. <https://academic.oup.com/fampra/article/13/6/522/496701?login=false>
- Maxwell, J. A. A. (2012) *Qualitative research design: An interactive approach*. 3 rd edn. London: Sage Publications.
- Metatla, O. (2016) Higher education reform in Algeria: reading between the lines, *Open Democracy*. <https://www.opendemocracy.net/en/north-africa-west-asia/higher-education-in-algeria-reading-between-lines-of-lmd-reform/>
- Merriam, S.B. (2009) *Qualitative research: a guide to design and implementation*. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
- Merriam, S. (1998) *Qualitative research and case study applications in education*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass Publishers.
- Messekher, H. (2014) 'Cultural representations in Algerian English textbooks', In: S , Garton & K, Graves, (ed.) *International Perspectives on Materials in ELT*. London: Palgrave Macmillan UK, pp. 69-86.
- Miles, M. B., & Huberman, A. M. (1994). *Qualitative data analysis: An expanded sourcebook* 2nd (edn.). London: Sage Publications, Inc.

- Miliiani, M. (2001) 'Teaching English in a multilingual context: The Algerian Case', *Mediterranean Journal of Educational Studies*, 6(1), pp. 13-29. <https://core.ac.uk/reader/83022650>
- Miller, P. (2008). 'Validity'. In L. M. Given (ed.), *The Sage encyclopaedia of qualitative research methods* (pp. 909-910). Los Angeles, CA: Sage Publications.
- Mize, D. W. (1978) *Algeria: A Study of the Educational System of Algeria and a Guide to the Academic Placement of Students in Educational Institutions of the United States*. University of California: American Association of Collegiate Registrars and Admissions Officers.
- Mohamed, M. and Brahim, M., (2010) 'The LMD higher education system in the Maghreb countries: The example of Algeria. *Towards an Arab higher education space*': *International challenges and societal responsibilities*, pp.267-280. <https://search.shamaa.org/PDF/41452/MohammedEn41485.pdf>
- Moore, Z.T. (1996) 'Teaching and testing culture: Old questions, new dimensions', *International Journal of Educational Research*, 23(7), pp. 595-606. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0883-0355\(96\)80439-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0883-0355(96)80439-3)
- Morgan, D., (1997) *The focus group guidebook*. Thousand Oaks: Sage publications.
- Murphy, D. (1977) 'Colonial and Post-Colonial Language Policy in the Maghreb'. *In The Maghreb Review*, 2(2), pp.1-9.
- Murphy-Lejeune, E. (2003) 'An experience of interculturality: Student travellers abroad', In G. Alred., M. Byram., & M. Fleming (eds), *Intercultural experience and education*. Clevedon, England: Multilingual Matters, pp.101-113.
- Nachmias, F and C. and Nachmias, D. and (1992) *Research Methods in the Social Sciences*. 4th (edn). New York: St. Martin's Press.
- Nadia, R. (2011) 'Teaching English in Algeria and educational reforms: An overview on the factors entailing students' failure in learning foreign languages at university', *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 29, pp. 1327-1333. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2011.11.370>.
- Nault, D. (2006) 'Going global: Rethinking culture teaching in ELT contexts', *Language, Culture and Curriculum*, 19(3), 314-328. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07908310608668770>

- Newton, J., Yates, E., Shern, S., & Nowitzki, W. (2010) *Intercultural communicative language teaching: Implications for effective teaching and learning - A literature review and an evidence-based framework for effective teaching*. Wellington, NZ: Ministry of Education.
- Nguyen, L., Harvey, S., & Grant, L. (2016) 'What teachers say about addressing culture in their EFL teaching practices: The Vietnamese context', *Intercultural Education*, 27(2), 165-178. doi: 10.1080/14675986.2016.1144921
- Nieto, S. (2002) *Language, culture, and teaching: Critical perspectives for a new century*. Mahwah, NJ: L. Erlbaum.
- Ntuli, C. D. (2012) 'Intercultural misunderstandings in South Africa: An analysis of nonverbal communication behaviour in context', *Intercultural Communication Studies*, XXI(2), pp.20-31. <https://www-s3-live.kent.edu/s3fs-root/s3fs-public/file/02CynthiaDanisileNtuli.pdf>
- Nugent, K., & Catalano, T. (2015) Critical cultural awareness in the foreign language classroom. *Faculty publications: Department of teaching, learning and teacher education*. 75, pp.16-30. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1193&context=teachlearnfacpub>
- Ogay, T. (2000) *De la compétence à la dynamique interculturelles*. Berlin: Peter Lang.
- Patel, F., Li, M., & Sooknanan, P. (2011) *Intercultural Communication*. India : SAGE Publications.
- Onwuegbuzie, A. J., & Leech, N. L. (2007). 'A call for qualitative power analysis'. *Quality & quantity*, 41(1), pp.105-121. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11135-005-1098-1>.
- Patton, M.Q. (2002) *Qualitative research and evaluation methods. 3 rd edn*. Thousand Oaks, California: Sage Publications.
- Pena-Dix, B. M. (2018) *Developing Intercultural Competence in English Language Teachers: Towards Building Intercultural Language Education in Colombia*. PhD thesis, Durham University. Available at: <http://etheses.dur.ac.uk/12619/>

- Peterson, B. (2004) *Cultural intelligence: A guide to working with people from other cultures*. Yarmouth, ME: Intercultural Press.
- Paige, R.M., Jacobs-Cassuto, M., Yershova, Y.A. and DeJaeghere, J. (2003) 'Assessing intercultural sensitivity: An empirical analysis of the Hammer and Bennett Intercultural Development Inventory', *International journal of intercultural relations*, 27(4), pp.467-486. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0147176703000348>
- Piper, H., & Simons, H. (2005) 'Ethical responsibility in social research', in B. Somekh & C. Lewin (Eds.), *Research methods in the social sciences*. London, England: Sage Publications, pp. 56-63.
- Porto, M., & Byram, M. (2015) 'Developing intercultural citizenship education in the language classroom and beyond', *Argentinian Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 3(2), pp.9-29. <http://www.faapi.org.ar/ajal/home.html>
- Pulverness, A. (2000) 'Distinctions & dichotomies: Culture-free, culture-bound', *English Teaching Professional*, (14), pp.1-2. https://www.academia.edu/268755/Distinctions_and_Dichotomies_Culture_Free_Culture_Bound
- Rabehi, A. (2021) *Investigating the Status of Intercultural Communicative Competence in Algerian Middle Schools: The Case of the New Curriculum of EFL*. Lancaster University. Available at: <https://eprints.lancs.ac.uk/id/eprint/159388/1/2021rabehiphd.pdf>
- Reid, E. (2014) *Intercultural Aspects in teaching English at primary schools*. Stevenage: Nielsen Bookdata.
- Reid, E. (2015) 'Techniques developing intercultural communicative competences in English language lessons', *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 186, pp. 939-943. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.04.011>.
- Richards, K., (2003) *Qualitative inquiry in TESOL*. Birmingham: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Risager, K. (1998) 'Language teaching and the process of European integration', In M. Byram & M. Fleming (eds.) *Language Learning in Intercultural Perspective: Approaches Through Drama and Ethnography*: Cambridge University Press, pp. 242-254.

- Risager, K., Byram, M. (1999) *Language Teachers Politics and Cultures*. Clevedon: Multilingual Matters LTD.
- Risager, K. (2004) 'Cultural awareness', In M. Byram (ed.) *Routledge Encyclopaedia of Language Teaching and Learning*. London: Routledge, pp. 159-162.
- Risager, K. (2005) 'Foreword', in L. Sercu (ed.), *Foreign language teachers and intercultural competence: An international investigation*. Clevedon: Multilingual Matters.
- Risager, K. (2006) *Language and culture: global flows and local complexity*. Clevedon: Multilingual Matters, LTD.
- Risager, K. (2007). *Language and culture pedagogy: From a national to a transnational paradigm*. Clevedon: Multilingual Matters.
- Rouabah, S. (2022) 'Multilingualism in Algeria: educational policies, language practices, and challenges', *Journal of the British Academy*, 10(s4), pp. 21–40. <https://www.thebritishacademy.ac.uk/documents/4216/10s4-00-FULL.pdf#page=23>
- Roberts, H. (2003) *the battlefield: Algeria 1988-2002: Studies in a broken polity*. London: Verso.
- Roberts, C., Byram, M., Barro, A., Jordan, S. and Street, B. (2001) *Language Learners as Ethnographers*. Clevedon: Multilingual Matters.
- Robinson, O. C. (2014) 'Sampling in Interview-Based Qualitative Research: A Theoretical and Practical Guide'. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 11(1), pp.25-41. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/14780887.2013.801543>
- Robson, C. (2002) *Real world research: A resource for social scientists and practitioner-researchers*. 2 nd edn. Oxford, UK: Blackwell Publishing.
- Robson, C. (2011) *Real world research: A resource for users of social research methods in applied settings*. 3 rd edn. United Kingdom: Wiley-Blackwell.
- Ruben, B.D. (1989) 'The study of cross-cultural competences: traditions and contemporary issues', *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 13(3), pp. 229-240. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/0147176789900114>
- Ryan, P., and Sercu, L. (2003) 'Foreign language teachers and their roles as mediators of language-and-culture: a study in Mexico', *Estudios de Lingüística Aplicada*, 37, pp. 99-118. <file:///Users/nawelouchene/Downloads/760-3547-1-PB.pdf>

- Saad, Z. (1992) *Language planning and policy attitudes: A case study of arabization in Algeria*. PhD Thesis, Columbia University Teachers College. https://books.google.co.uk/books/about/Language_Planning_and_Policy_Attitudes.html?id=hvWLuAAACAAJ&redir_esc=y
- Sakuragi, T. (2008) 'Attitudes toward language study and cross-cultural attitudes in Japan', *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 32(1), pp. 81-90. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0147176707000818>
- Salem, L. R. (2013). *Incorporating intercultural competence in English language teaching in a Lebanese university intensive English program context: An action research project*. PhD Thesis, University of Leicester. [file:///Users/nawelouchene/Downloads/2012salemlrEdD%20\(1\).pdf](file:///Users/nawelouchene/Downloads/2012salemlrEdD%20(1).pdf)
- Sapir, E. (1921). *Language: an introduction to the study of speech*. New York: Brace.
- Seale, C. (1999). *Quality in qualitative research. Qualitative Inquiry*, London: Sage Publications LTD. 5(4), 465-478.
- Serai, S. (2022) *Translanguaging in Algerian University EFL Classrooms: Practices and Attitudes*. PhD thesis. University of Portsmouth. Available at: [https://pure.port.ac.uk/ws/portalfiles/portal/65602152/Translanguaging in Algerian University EFL Classroom Practices and attitudes Safia Serai .pdf](https://pure.port.ac.uk/ws/portalfiles/portal/65602152/Translanguaging_in_Algerian_University_EFL_Classroom_Practices_and_attitudes_Safia_Serai_.pdf)
- Sharifian, F. (2010) Globalization of English in World Englishes: An emerging variety among Persian speakers of English, in: M. Saxena, & T. Omoniyi (eds.) *Contending with globalization in World Englishes*. Clevedon: Multilingual Matters, pp.155- 170.
- Sharifian, F. (2012) World Englishes, Intercultural Communication and Requisite Competences, in: Jackson, J (ed) *The Routledge handbook of language and intercultural communication*. Abingdon: Routledge.
- Shenton, A.K. (2004) 'Strategies for Ensuring Trustworthiness in Qualitative Research Projects'. *Education for Information*, 22(2). pp. 63-75. <https://content.iospress.com/articles/education-for-information/efi00778>.
- Sarangi, S. (2011) 'Intercultural or not? Beyond celebration of cultural differences in miscommunication analysis', in Zhu, Hua (ed.) *The language and intercultural communication reader*. London and New York: Routledge, pp. 409-427.

- Sarter, H. and Sefta, K. (1992) 'La glottopolitique algerienne. Faits et discours. *Französisch Heute*, (2), pp.109.
- Sasani, S. (2018) *The place of culture in English language teaching: an exploration of non-native ESOL teachers' attitudes towards intercultural competence*. PhD Thesis. University of Sheffield. <https://etheses.whiterose.ac.uk/20958/>
- Savin-Baden, M., & Major, C. H. (2010) *New approaches to qualitative research, Wisdom and uncertainty*. London, England: Routledge.
- Savignon, S. J. (2009) EIL, native-speakerism and the failure of European ELT, in: S. J. Savignon (ed.). *Interpreting communicative language teaching: Contexts and concerns in teacher education*. New Haven: Yale University, pp.1-28.
- Scarino, A. (2010) Assessing intercultural capability in learning languages: A renewed understanding of language, culture, learning, and the nature of assessment, *The Modern Language Journal*, 94(2), pp.324-329. doi: 10.1111/j.1540-4781.2010.01026.x
- Sebti, N. (2001) 'Rapport de la Commission'. *Des propositions et des échecs Liberte'*, 20 March. On www at <http://www.liberte-algerie.com>.
- Sharkey, H.J. (2012) 'Language and Conflict: The Political History of Arabisation in Sudan and Algeria', *Studies in Ethnicity and Nationalism*, 12 (3), pp.427-449. <https://doi.org/10.1111/sena.12009>
- Sercu, L. (2005). Foreign language teachers and the implementation of intercultural education: a comparative investigation of the professional self-concepts and teaching practices of Belgian teachers of English, French and German. *European Journal of Teacher Education*, 28(1), 87-105. doi: 10.1080/02619760500040389.
- Sercu, L. (2006) 'The foreign language and intercultural competence teacher: The acquisition of a new professional identity'. *Intercultural education*, 17(1), pp.55-72. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14675980500502321>
- Sercu, L., Bandura, E., Castro, P., Davcheva, L., Laskaridou, C., Lundgren, U., Mendez Garcia, M.C., & Ryan, P. (2005) *Foreign language teachers and intercultural competence: An international investigation*. Clevedon: Multilingual Matters.
- Sercu, L., & St. John, O. (2007) 'Teacher beliefs and their impact on teaching practice: a literature review', in M. Jiménez Raya & L. Sercu (eds.), *Challenges in Teacher*

Development: Learner Autonomy and Intercultural Competence. Foreign Language Teaching in Europe, pp.41-64.

- Seelye, H. N. (1974) *Teaching culture: strategies for foreign language educators*. University of Texas: National Textbook Co.
- Seelye, H. N. (1988) *Teaching culture*. Lincolnwood, IL: National Textbook Company.
- Shin, J., Eslami, Z. R., & Chen, W. C. (2011) 'Presentation of local and international culture in current international English language teaching textbooks', *Language, Culture and Curriculum*, 24(3), 253-268.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/07908318.2011.614694>
- Smith, Andrea L. (2006) *Colonial Memory and Postcolonial Europe: Maltese Settlers in Algeria and France*. Bloomington, IN: Indiana University Press.
- Smith, L. E. (1987) *Discourse across cultures. Strategies in world Englishes*. New York: Prentice-Hall.
- Smithson, J. (2000) 'Using and analysing focus groups: limitations and possibilities. *International journal of social research methodology*, 3(2), 103-119.
<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/136455700405172>
- Soiferman, L.K. (2010) 'Compare and Contrast Inductive and Deductive Research Approaches', *ERIC, Institute of Education Sciences*, pp.1-23.
<https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED542066.pdf>
- Spencer-Oatey, H., & Franklin, P. (2009) *Intercultural interaction. A multidisciplinary Approach to Intercultural Communication*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Spisak, S. (2009) 'The Evolution of a Cosmopolitan Identity: Transforming Culture', *Current Issues in Comparative Education*, 12(1), pp. 86-91.
<https://journals.library.columbia.edu/index.php/cice/article/view/11444>
- Stewart, D and Shamdasi, P. (1990) *Focus Groups: Theory and Practice*. 3rd edn. Los Angeles: Sage Publications.
- Strauss, A., & Corbin, J. (1998) *Basics of qualitative research: Techniques and procedures for developing grounded theory*. London: Sage Publications.
- Sybing, R. L. (2011) 'Assessing perspectives on culture in EFL education', *ELT Journal*, 65(4), pp. 467-469. <https://doi.org/10.1093/elt/ccr025>

- Tang, S. Y. F., & Choi, P. L. (2004) 'The development of personal, intercultural and professional competence in international field experience in initial teacher education', *Asia Pacific Education Review*, 5(1), pp.50-63. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF03026279>
- Tashakkori, A., & Teddlie, C. (2003) 'Issues and dilemmas in teaching research methods courses in social and behavioural sciences: US perspective'. *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*, 6(1), pp. 61-77. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/13645570305055>
- Teddlie, C. and Tashakkori, A., (2009) *Foundations of mixed methods research: Integrating quantitative and qualitative approaches in the social and behavioral sciences*. London: Sage Publications.
- Teddlie, C. and Yu, F. (2007) 'Mixed methods sampling: A typology with examples', *Journal of mixed methods research*, 1(1), pp.77-100. <https://www.dedoose.com/publications/mixed%20methods%20sampling%20-%20a%20typology%20with%20examples.pdf>
- Tefiani, M. (1984) 'Arabisation et fonctions linguistiques en Algérie. *Französisch Heute*, 15 (2), pp. 118–128.
- Tong, K. P., & Trinidad, S. G. (2005) 'Conditions and constraints of sustainable innovative pedagogical practices using technology', *International Electronic Journal for Leadership in Learning*, 9(3), pp.1-24. <https://journals.library.ualberta.ca/iejll/index.php/iejll/article/view/403/65>
- Triandis, H. C. (1989) 'Intercultural education and training', in P. Funke (ed.). *Understanding the USA*. Tübingen: Gunter Narr Verlag, pp. 305-322
- Trochim, W., & Donnelly, J. (2006) *The research methods knowledge base*. Boston: Cengage Learning.
- Tulga, A.Y. (2020). Multiculturalism, Nation-State and Berber Movement in Algeria. *International Journal of Social and Humanities Sciences (IJSHS)*, 4(3), 93-106. <https://dergipark.org.tr/en/download/article-file/1486764>
- Van Ek, J.A. (1986) *Objectives for foreign language learning*. Strasbourg: Council of Europe.
- Wagner, M., Cardetti, F., & Byram, M. (2019) 'Teaching intercultural citizenship across the curriculum', *American Council on the Teaching of Foreign Languages*.

- Walliman, N. (2005) *Your research project: A step-by-step guide for the first-time researcher*. 2 nd edn. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- Walliman, N. S. R. (2011). *Research Methods*. London: Routledge.
- Wardhaugh, R., (1987) *Languages in Competition: Dominance, Diversity, and Decline*. Oxford: Basil Blackwell.
- Weaver, G., R. (1986) 'Understanding and coping with cross-cultural adjustment stress', in R. M. Paige (ed.), *Cross-Cultural orientation, new conceptualizations and applications*. Lanham, MD: University Press of America.
- Webster, S., Lewis, J. and Brown, A. (2014) 'Ethical Considerations in Qualitative Research', in: J. Ritchie and J. Lewis, (eds). *Qualitative Research Practice: A Guide for Social Science Students and Researchers*. London: Sage, pp. 78-110.
- Wellington, J. (2015) *Educational Research: contemporary issues and practical approaches*. 2 nd ed. London: Bloomsbury.
- Wiles, R. (2013) *What are qualitative research ethics?*. London: Bloomsbury Publishing PLC.
- Wilmot, A. (2005) 'Designing sampling strategies for qualitative social research: with particular reference to the Office for National Statistics' Qualitative Respondent Register', *Survey methodology bulletin-office for national statistics*, pp.219-231 <https://wwwn.cdc.gov/qbank/Quest/2005/Paper23.pdf>
- Williams, R. (1983) *Keywords: a vocabulary of culture and society*. London: Fontana Paperbacks.
- Witte, A. (2011) On the Teachability and Learnability of Intercultural Competences: Developing Facets of the "Inter", in A. Witte & T. Harden (eds.), *Intercultural Competence: Concepts, Challenges, Evaluations*. Oxford: Peter Lang Ltd, pp. 89-107
- Witte, A., & Harden, T. (2011) *Intercultural Competence: Concepts, Challenges, Evaluations*. Oxford: Peter Lang Ltd.
- Yuen, K. M. (2011) 'The representation of foreign cultures in English textbooks', *ELT journal*, 65(4), pp. 458–466. <https://doi.org/10.1093/elt/ccq08>

APPENDICES

Appendix 1: Participants Consent Form

School of Education
Paisley Campus

Consent Form-Interviews, Questionnaire and Focus group discussions-:

Title of the research project: An Exploration of Algerian English Language Teachers' and Learners' Perspectives and Conceptions of Intercultural Communicative Competence: A Case Study of Two Universities in Algeria.

Name of the researcher: Nawal Ouchene

- 1- I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet for the above project and the researcher has the opportunity to ask any question
- 2- I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw from the project at any time, without providing any reason
- 3- I understand that I am going:
 - To participate in an interview of 30 minutes to an hour (for teachers and the GRC members).
 - To participant in an online survey (Learners)
 - To participant in focus group discussions (Learners)
- 4- I understand that, while being interviewed, everything will be audio-recorded
- 5- I understand that any information recorded during the research will remain confidential and no information that identifies me will be made publicly available
- 6- I understand that my name will be replaced by a pseudonym to keep my identity confidential

By signing below, you confirm that you have understood the information provided in the consent form.

I consent to participate in this research project:

Name of the participant: _____

Date: _____

Signature: _____

Name of the Researcher: _____

Date: _____ Signature: _____

Thank you very much for accepting to take part in this study and to share your experience.

Appendix 2: Teachers Information Sheet

School of Education
Paisley Campus

Participant Information Sheet – Interview-:

Title of the study: An Exploration of Algerian English Language Teachers’ and Learners’ Perspectives and Conceptions of Intercultural Communicative Competence: A Case Study of Two Universities in Algeria.

Introduction:

This research project is conducted by the researcher Nawal Ouchene, a Ph.D. student at the school of Education and Social Sciences, The University of the West of Scotland.

Background of the study:

This study aims at exploring the Algerian teachers and learners’ perceptions and attitudes towards the importance of teaching intercultural communicative competence in EFL classroom. It also attempts to investigate the participants’ intercultural lived experiences and to what extent these experiences influenced their English language teaching and learning practices. Furthermore, it sought to understand to what extent ICC is promoted in the Algerian education.

What will you be required to do?

Taking part in the research project is completely voluntary, it is up to you to decide. Your name will be anonymous unless you decide to be identified. If you ever changed your mind, I will make sure to replace it with a pseudo name. You will have the chance to withdraw at any point of time during the interview and you have the right to refuse to answer any questions that you do not like. No risks or penalties of any form will apply.

What will you do in this research project?

You will be required to take part in a face-to-face interview or over a Skype interview that will take a minimum 30 minutes to an hour maximum. The researcher will ask questions about different concepts of interculturality such as culture, intercultural awareness, cultural awareness, intercultural communicative competence and how these concepts are addressed in the classroom. During the interview, it is advised that you think of any intercultural exposure or interaction you encountered with people from diverse socio-cultural backgrounds. The data collected will be used to raise educators' and policy-makers' awareness concerning the integration of intercultural English language teaching approaches which promote the teaching of intercultural communicative competence in Algeria.

The criteria for participation in this research are as follows:

- You must be an Algerian English language teacher at the East or West University in Algeria
- You have considerable experience teaching cultures in the Department of English speciality Didactics of Languages and Foreign Cultures at East University/ OR speciality of Language and Communication at West University.
- You taught/ teach English to learners of Master level

What are the potential risks to you in taking part?

There will be no harm or risks of your participation in this research study except the interview may take some of your time for the completion of the interview.

What are the possible benefits to you in taking part?

We cannot guarantee the study will help you, but you may find the project interesting while having a chance to reflect upon your teaching experiences and it may raise your awareness about the significance of intercultural communicative competence.

What will happen to the information in this research project?

The data collected will be stored and reported confidentially. Your participation will be anonymous while coding and reporting the data. Only the researcher and the director of studies will have access to the data, which will be securely and strictly stored on password-protected at university computers and storage devices. Your identity will be altered by a pseudonym in the publication of the findings.

What will happen next?

If you decide to take part in the present research study, you will be kindly asked to sign and date a consent form that I will send you with the participant information sheet through email to confirm your willingness to be involved in my study and return it back to me. Once the consent form is signed and returned to the researcher, the convenient date, time and space will be arranged according to your choice. If you decided not to participate there is no need to return the consent form.

Who has reviewed the project?

The School of Education Ethics Committee at the University of the West of Scotland.

If you have any questions concerning the research project, during or after the investigation, and wish to contact an independent person to whom any questions may be directed or further information may be sought, please contact:

Ph.D. Researcher	Director of Studies
Nawal Ouchene School of Education University of the West of Scotland Paisley Campus Room: E339 Email: [REDACTED]	Dr. Beth Cross University of the West of Scotland School of Education Hamilton Campus E-mail: [REDACTED]

Thank you for reading this information – please feel free to ask any further questions concerning the research project

Appendix 3: Interview Protocol

Dear Teachers,

Hello, my name is Nawal Ouchene, a PhD student in the school of Education at West of Scotland University. I would like to thank you very much for accepting my invitation to participate in this research study. The focus of the interview will be on the strategies and ways culture and intercultural communicative competence are addressed in your courses by you as an EFL teacher and mentor. This interview will take 30 to 60 minutes, thereby let me know if you want to take break or withdraw at any point of time you want.

Background and General Information:

- How long have you been engaged in teaching the English language?
- Do you use syllabus in your teaching?
- What languages do you use while interacting with your learners?
- How would you describe your academic teaching experience in Algeria?

Culture

- How would you define culture?
- What do you understand from 'culture teaching' in the English language teaching context?
- In what ways culture is part of the course?
- To what extent is the target culture embedded in your course?
- How important is it for you as an EFL teacher to expose your students to cultural diversity?
- Do you think learning about foreign cultures might change a student's attitude towards his/her own national culture? How?

Teaching Objectives

- What are the important objectives and goals you wish to accomplish in your teaching practices?
- What are the skills you focus on while teaching EFL.

Intercultural Communicative Competence

- Are you familiar with the concept of Intercultural communicative competence? How would you define it?
- Do you teach intercultural communicative competence in your course?
- Do you think that students are ready and mature enough for cultural learning in language classrooms?
- What ways, let's say, strategies do you have for educating students about cultural diversity?
- Do you usually provide your students with the chance to compare and contrast cultural differences in the course?
- What topics do you think are important to enhance the students' cross-cultural understanding?
- What does it mean to hold critical stances towards other foreign or international cultures?
- Do you have the chance to create a multicultural environment in your classroom through the materials you use?

Intercultural lived Experiences:

- What kind of intercultural experience have you encountered?
- Do you have any friends or colleagues from different cultures? What do you think of the way they interact with you?
- Have you faced any challenges in communicating with people who have different cultural backgrounds?
- How have these intercultural exposures influenced your teaching practices?
- Have you ever experienced a clash of your values while interacting with people from different cultures?
- Did these intercultural exposures raise your cultural awareness and intercultural awareness? How?

Teachers' Training and Development:

- Have you ever attended any training that tackles ICC or other related topics? If yes, what was it like?

- How useful do you find pre-service training for EFL teachers to teach Intercultural communicative competence?
- What kind of training or drill do you think English language teachers should have in future concerning the teaching of Intercultural communicative competence?

I provided Byram's model of ICC and asked the participants about their perceptions

Byram's Intercultural Communicative Competence Model

- Are you familiar with this model?
- How would you implement it?
- What kind of attitudes, knowledge, and skills are needed to develop the students' intercultural competence?
- What challenges or difficulties might you meet when it comes to implementing or teaching cultural subjects and intercultural competence?

Thank you very much for accepting to take part in this study and to share your experience

Appendix 4: Learners Information Sheet – Questionnaire and focus group interviews –

School of Education
Paisley Campus

Learners Information Sheet – Questionnaire and focus group interviews –

Title of the study: An Exploration of Algerian English Language Teachers' and Learners' Perspectives and Conceptions of Intercultural Communicative Competence: A Case Study of Two Universities in Algeria.

Introduction

This research project is conducted by the researcher Nawal Ouchene, a PhD student at the School of Education, University of the West of Scotland.

What is the purpose of the study?

This study endeavours to explore and understand Master learners' English language learning experience in Algeria, and how it is related to cultural learning. It also aims to investigate the participants' perceptions and perspectives of intercultural communicative competence in EFL context and how essential it is considered as a goal to be promoted in the classroom.

What will you be required to do?

Taking part in the research project is completely voluntary, it is up to you to decide. Your name will be anonymous unless you decide to be identified. If you ever change your mind, I will make sure to replace it with a pseudo name. You will have the chance to withdraw at any point of time you want during the interview, and you have the right to refuse to answer any question that you do not feel comfortable answering. No risks or penalties of any form will be applied.

What will you do in this research project?

You will be required to take part in an online web-based questionnaire that will take 10 to 15 minutes maximum. The questionnaire includes a demographic section where you state the university you are studying and other general questions. The other two sections comprise several statements that describe your abilities, competencies and skills in learning the language in coordination with the cultures. You will be kindly asked to sincerely select the answers that describe your viewpoint towards Intercultural communicative competence.

Concerning the focus group discussions, you will be asked to take part in a group discussion with six other learners from the same university you are studying at, and this will take around 30 minutes minimum to 45 minutes maximum. The discussion will be moderated and organised by the researcher and everything will be audio taped. The researcher may feel the need to take notes during the discussion for the data analysis section.

The criteria for participation in this research are as follows:

- You are a Master's student of English
- You are majoring in Didactics of Languages and Foreign Cultures at the East University OR Language and Communication at the West University
- You have been exposed to modules which address national, foreign or international cultures

What are the potential risks to you in taking part?

There will be no harm or risks to your participation in this research study except the questionnaire and focus group discussions may take some of your time to complete.

What are the possible benefits to you in taking part?

We cannot guarantee the study will help you, but you may find the project interesting while having a chance to reflect on your learning experiences and it may raise your awareness towards intercultural communicative competence and intercultural interactions.

What will happen to the information in this research project?

The data collected will be stored and reported confidentially. Your participation will be anonymous or disguised while coding and reporting the data. Only the researcher and the director of studies will have access to the data, which will be securely and strictly stored on password-protected university computers and storage devices.

What will happen next?

If you decide to take part in the present research project you will be kindly asked to sign a consent form that I will send with the participant information sheet through email to confirm your willingness to be involved in my study and return it. Once the consent form is signed and returned to the researcher, the convenient date, time and space will be arranged according to your choice. If you decide not to participate, there is no need to return the consent form.

Who has reviewed the project?

The school of Education Ethics Committee at the University of the West of Scotland.

If you have any questions concerning the research project, during or after the investigation, and wish to contact an independent person to whom any questions may be directed or further information may be sought from, please contact.

Researcher	Director of Studies
Nawal Ouchene School of Education University of the West of Scotland Paisley Campus Room:E339 Email: [REDACTED]	Dr. Beth Cross University of the West of Scotland School of Education Hamilton Campus E-mail: [REDACTED]

Thank you for reading this information – please feel free to ask any further questions concerning the research project.

Appendix 5: Students' Questionnaire

Students' Questionnaire

Dear students,

This questionnaire is part of my doctoral research programme which aims to investigate your perceptions regarding your English language learning experience. It also endeavours to explore your understandings of the notions culture and intercultural communicative competence (ICC). There are no wrong or right answers. Your answers will remain anonymous and confidential and the results will be analysed and interpreted solely for the purpose of this research study. You can skip questions you do not want to answer, and end your participation at any time you prefer.

It is crucial to be honest as possible as you can in your answers in order to reach an in-depth understanding of the findings of this research study.

Section 1: Demographic information

1- Fill the below table with your own information

University	Department	Nationality	Gender	Age

2- Years of studying English (since your middle school):

1-4

5-8

9-12

13+

3- Please rate the three most important primary reason for choosing to learn English at university as (1 very important) (2 second most important) (3rd most important):

- University requirement
- Personal interest
- To study in foreign countries
- English is a lingua franca
- For passing English language tests: IELTS, TOFEL
- To know more about foreign cultures
- To teach EFL in Algeria
- To teach EFL abroad

4- Languages that you are studying other than English:

5-

To what extent do you agree/disagree that the following methods are good to increase the practical use of English?	SA	A	N	S	SD
Attending practical courses such as how to make successful English conversations					
Memorising vocabulary and well-formed utterances to use during interactions					
Learning more about grammatical rules					
Joining language study groups					
Reading English newspapers and magazines					
Reading short stories and novels					
Listening to English songs					
Watching English series or movies					
Reading articles, essays that deals with socio-cultural issues like gender, race					

Section 2: Language and Culture

6. Please indicate the extent of your agreement or disagreement by ticking the appropriate box:

SE (Strongly Emphasized), SLE (Slightly Emphasised), OE (Occasionally Emphasised), NE (Note Emphasised).

To what extent these competences are taught in the classroom??	SE	SLE	OE	NE
Linguistic competence (listening, speaking, reading and writing)				
Academic English resources relevant to your speciality				
Communicative competence/ Fluency				
Understanding of range of foreign cultural practices				
Gaining awareness about cultural differences				
Differences and similarities between the Algerian cultures and other foreign cultures.				
Learning how to interact with others who are culturally different from you.				

7.

Please indicate to what extend do you agree/disagree with the following statements.	SA	A	N	D	SD
Learning language skills solely (listening, speaking, reading and writing) facilitate the learning of English language.					
Learning the target culture solely facilitates the learning					
Learning the language skills in conjunction with the target culture facilitates the learning of the English language.					
Learning about different cultural subjects makes learning English more interesting.					
Learning about how people from foreign countries behave in various circumstances enables you to have a better successful communication with them.					

Addressing other foreign cultures in English language classes teaches you to be a respectful and tolerant individual.					
Keeping an open mind is an important aspect of learning about unfamiliar cultures.					
Learning English doesn't necessitate learning the target culture.					
Being exposed to different cultural elements in English language classes, I have developed a positive attitude					
Being exposed to different cultures elements in English language classes, I have developed a negative attitude.					
Language and culture are two intertwined concepts					
Language and culture are two separate entities.					
Culture is not important to be included in the English curriculum at university					

8.

How important are the following goals for you as an English master students?	SA	A	N	D	SD
To develop your competences of listening, speaking, reading and writing					
To get distinction diplomat					
To get knowledge for exams					
To know more about other cultures when learning English					
Developing competence in daily communication					
Gaining cultural knowledge					
Acceptance of cultural differences in language classroom					
Reflection upon cultural diversity in English classroom					
Develop the intellectual thinking side					
To develop you global communication skills.					
To develop an independent critical thinking capacities					
To enlighten your mind and broaden your knowledge about other foreign or international cultures					
To improve your personal knowledge and develop your lifelong learning abilities.					

9:

What do you understand by 'culture learning' in English language learning context?	SA	A	N	D	SD
Information which tackles history, geography and political issues of cultures of English speaking countries.					
knowledge about daily life and routine of people who have different cultures					
Various beliefs, values and moral that are different from your own values					
Materials such as films, mass media, poems, drama and short stories, theatre and music.					

Developing empathy, tolerance towards people living in other cultures					
Boosting reflection and critical thinking on cultural differences.					
Promoting your understanding towards your own culture.					
Developing the ability to handle intercultural contact situations.					

Section 3: Intercultural Communicative Copmetence

10

Intercultural Competence is:	SA	A	N	D	SD
How to interact successfully with people who are culturally different.					
Field of research that addresses how people grasp and understand the cultural boundaries.					
The commonalities and differences between different cultures.					
Analysing and adopting one’s behaviours while interacting with others from different cultures.					
Making judgments and stereotypes while communicating with others					

11. How do you define an intercultural competent speaker (ICS)?

.....

12- Have you ever been abroad?

Yes No

If your answer is yes, please answer the following questions:

a. What country/ies?

.....

b. For how long?

.....

c. For what purpose?

.....

13. Do you think intercultural communicative competence should be given more/less emphasis in foreign language learning? What are the potential benefits?

.....

14. In your opinion, what are the appropriate methods/approaches to use in order to develop the individual’s cross-cultural competence towards foreign and international cultures?

.....
.....
.....

Thank you for your cooperation.

Appendix 6: Focus Group Protocol

Opening Questions

The researcher and students will introduce themselves to each other.

English Language Learning and Culture:

- How long have you been studying French?
- How long have you been studying English?
- How do you describe your English language learning experience in Algeria?
- What are the skills you consider important to develop?
- How do you define culture?
- Do you think that the courses you had in the classroom helped you to develop your cultural awareness? How?
- Have you been exposed to other cultures in the classroom? How?

Intercultural Communicative Competence and Intercultural Exposure:

- Are you familiar with the concept of communicative competence? How would you define it?
- How do you define intercultural ICC?
- Are you interested to know and explore others cultures?
- How far is it important for you to develop intercultural attitudes?
- How important for you as an individual to be an intercultural competent speakers?
- Have you been abroad? If yes, how was it like? and how did you find interacting with people from different cultures?
- Do you find the creation of intercultural model clubs an approach that promote ICC
- Do you think that creating knowledge club is significant? Why?

Thank you for your cooperation.

Interview Questions with the Members of the Intercultural Knowledge Club in the West University:

- Could you please tell me a bit about how the intercultural club (the Global Representatives of Culture) was created in the West University (motivation)?
- What activities do you usually organise?
- What languages do you use inside the club?
- How did being a GRC member develop your intercultural skills and attitudes?
- Do you think that creating an intercultural club is significant? Why?
- What are the challenges that may face educators to integrate ICC in Algeria?
- According to you, what are the challenges that hinder the creation of intercultural clubs in Algerian Higher Education?
- How did your exposure to ICC and being part in the GRC in the West University help you to navigate intercultural interactions with people from different cultural backgrounds?
- Have you ever experienced miscommunication or disconnection while interacting with people from different cultures? If yes, how?

Thank you for your cooperation.

Appendix 7: Learners' Educational Background

Appendix 8: Teachers' Profile

Appendix 9: Data Analysis Process

Appendix 10: Thematic Analysis of the Study

Thematic Network of the Study

Appendix 11: Learners' Thematic Network

Learners' Thematic Network